

D3.3 Report on data collection campaigns

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Executive Summary

The following document is ‘Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’ in the framework of the project titled ‘Revealing fair and actionable knowledge from data to support women’s inclusion in transport systems’ (Acronym: DIAMOND; Grant Agreement No 824326).

The document describes the data collection campaigns executed within ‘Work Package 3 –Data collection’ (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020), focusing on each Use Case:

- Use Case I: Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways);
- Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car;
- Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management;
- Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.

Data collection campaigns have been based on the methodological approach of the DIAMOND project already presented in Deliverable 3.1 and Deliverable 3.2¹. This relies on the Fairness Characteristics identified through Thematic Analysis and on a series of interdisciplinary tools.

A series of heterogeneous and disaggregated information have been gathered through the executed data collection campaigns and classified in three main categories:

- Thematic Analysis:
 - Literature review (all Use Cases);
 - Focus group discussions (all Use Cases)
 - Semi-structured interviews (all Use Cases).
- Service and Employers’ Provision Data:
 - Structured data (Use Cases I, III and IV);
 - Observations (Use Cases I, II and III);
 - Users and Employees’ Satisfaction Index questionnaires (all Use Cases);
 - Social media data (Use Cases I, II and III).
- Users and Employees’ Perception Data:
 - Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (all Use Cases).

Deliverable 3.3 is aimed at planning data collection and reporting the executed data collection campaigns with reference to timing and means deployed, results on user engagement level, surveys obtained and data from Web and other sources.

Within the objectives of ‘Work Package 4 – Interdisciplinary model creation’, the collected Service and Employers’ Database will be analysed through Factor and Regression Analysis and Bayesian Network techniques, while the Users and Employees Perception Database is going to be analysed using Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) approach.

¹ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’ and ‘Deliverable 3.2 User engagement strategy’.

Deliverable 3.3 is especially useful for:

- WP4 Interdisciplinary Model Creation;
- WP5 DIAMOND Toolbox Development;
- WP6 DIAMOND Testing and Validation;
- WP8 Ethical, Legal and Data Management.

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Terminology and Acronyms

ADAS	Advanced Driving Assistance System
ADS	Automated Driving System
AITEC	Aitec Asesores Internacionales srl
AHP	Analytic Hierarchy Process
API	Application Programming Interface
AV	Automated Vehicles
BN	Bayesian Network
CBI-R	Career Barriers Inventory-Revised
CCTV	Closed-circuit Television
CF	Concept of Fairness
CFCs	Cluster of Fairness Characteristics
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
DAD	Dynamic Argumentative Delphi
DDT	Dynamic Driving Tasks
ENU	Edinburgh Napier University
EU	European Union
EURECAT	Eurecat - Centro Tecnológico de Cataluña
FCs	Fairness Characteristics
FGC	Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya
FTTE	University of Belgrade
G&V	Genre et Ville
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GIS	Geographic Information System
GPS	Global Positioning System
HAV	Highly Automated Vehicles
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HR	Human Resources
IBV	Instituto de Biomecánica
ID	Inclusion Diamond
IPs	Influencing Parameters
M	Month
OAPs	Old Age Pensioners
OSM	Open Street Map
PI	Polyhedral Individual
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
RINA	Rina Services spa
SD	Standard Deviation
STIR	University of Stirling
SYS	Systematica srl
TU Dublin	Technological University Dublin

UESI	<i>Users and Employees' Satisfaction Index questionnaires</i>
UC1	<i>Use Case I</i>
UC2	<i>Use Case II</i>
UC3	<i>Use Case III</i>
UC4	<i>Use Case IV</i>
VELIB	<i>Syndicat Mixte Autolib et Velib Métropole</i>
WAVE	<i>Wave Women and Vehicles in Europe</i>
WP	<i>Work Package</i>
ZTM	<i>Miasto Stołeczne Warszawa</i>

I. Introduction

The current document ‘Deliverable 3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’ describes the **data collection activities** executed within ‘Work Package 3 – Data collection’ of the DIAMOND project (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020). In this regard, the document includes information regarding the identification of dataset sources, data collection tools, data collection timeline and partners responsible for each data collection activity.

The main objective of the DIAMOND project is to turn data into reliable and actionable knowledge for supporting the inclusion of women in transport systems as both users and employees. The document is focused on **four Use Cases**²:

- Use Case I: Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways);
- Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car;
- Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management;
- Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.

Within the objectives of ‘Work Package 2 – Conceptual Framework’ and ‘Work Package 3 – Data collection’, data collection campaigns were executed on the basis of: the Inclusion Diamond representation³, the concept of Polyhedral individual⁴, the Concept of Fairness⁵ and the **methodological approach**⁶ of the DIAMOND Project.

This was aimed at collecting **heterogeneous and disaggregated data** about women’s needs in the transport sector, as users and employees. The gathered data sets are divided into three main categories:

- **Thematic Analysis:**
 - Literature review (Use Case I, II, III and IV);
 - Focus group discussions (Use Case I, II, III and IV)
 - Semi-structured interviews (Use Cases I, II, III and IV).
- **Service and Employers’ Provision Data:**
 - Structured data regarding the operation of transport services (Use Cases I and III) and job holders of the sector (Use Case IV);
 - Observations regarding relevant features of transportation settings (Use Cases I and III) and emotional responses to autonomous vehicles (Use Case II);
 - Users and Employees’ Satisfaction Index questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III) and job conditions and employability (Use Case IV);

² See ‘Deliverable 2.1 Use case definition’.

³ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

⁴ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

⁵ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

⁶ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’ and ‘Deliverable 3.2 User engagement strategy’.

- Social media data from Twitter regarding geospatial/time-based information and the opinion of the end-users of the services (Use Cases I, II and III).
- **Users and Employees' Perception Data:**
 - DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires regarding the Fairness Characteristics (Use Cases I, II, III and IV).

As a preliminary step towards data collection, the methodological approach of DIAMOND was based on the identification of a series of Fairness Characteristics (FCs) related to the inclusion of women in the transport sector.

FCs were defined and validated through **Thematic Analysis**⁷, which was based on a review of the most relevant scientific literature and on the execution of a series of focus groups and semi-structured interviews.

All data collection activities have been conducted once ethical approval has been granted locally and by **following a rigid ethical framework of conducting social research**⁸.

Within the objectives of Work Package 4 – 'Interdisciplinary model creation', the Service and Employers' Database will be analysed through **Factor and Regression Analysis** and **Bayesian Network**, while the Users and Employees Perception Database will be analysed using **Analytic Hierarchy Process** (AHP).

Deliverable 3.3 is aimed at planning the execution of Thematic Analysis actions and at reporting data collection campaigns through a series of interdisciplinary tools.

The results of the data collection campaigns are presented in the following Sections, with reference to Thematic Analysis (Section 2), Use Case I (Section 3), Use Case II (Section 4), Use Case III (Section 5) and Use Case IV (Section 6).

A series of detailed information regarding the developed and used data collection tools, are described in Annex 1 (Thematic Analysis), Annex 2 (Use Case I), Annex 3 (Use Case II), Annex 4 (Use Case III) and Annex 5 (Use Case IV).

Annex 6 focuses on the clustering analysis executed to validate the Fairness Characteristics identified through Literature Reviews. Annex 7 focuses on the piloting analysis to validate the DAD questionnaires.

⁷ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁸ See 'Deliverable 8.1 Data Management Plan' and 'Deliverable 8.2 Guide to interview and ethics'.

2. Thematic Analysis

Thematic Analysis was aimed at identifying and validating a series of **Fairness Characteristics** (FCs) through the review of the most relevant scientific literature and the execution of several Focus Groups and Semi-structured Interviews related to ‘Inclusiveness for Women Users and Employees in Transport Sector’.

In order to achieve the stated aims and objectives of the DIAMOND project as set out in the project proposal (i.e. identify the needs, expectations, and requirements of women as users and employees in the transport sector at a granular level), both **quantitative and qualitative data** have been collected to provide a more comprehensive view of the barriers and facilitators faced by women.

The rationale behind the decision to include qualitative data and analysis through Thematic Analysis was twofold, firstly it provides validation and triangulation of the overall data and secondly it allows us to probe deeper and explore more fully the recurring concepts raised in the quantitative data.

2.1 Literature review

The **literature review**⁹ was aimed at identifying a series of FCs for each Use Case (FCs – Level 2), which were later grouped into several Clusters of Fairness Characteristics (CFCs – Level 1). Then, a series of Influencing Parameters (IPs – Level 3) were identified for each FC. The literature review was conducted through several academic databases by multiple international consortium partners and organized in a tabular structure (see Annex 1).

This thematic analysis action was executed only in the **first iteration** of the DIAMOND’s methodological approach (see Figure 1 and Deliverable 2.2¹⁰).

The identified FCs were clustered into the three mentioned levels (i.e. CFCs, FCs, Ips) by performing two different statistical tests for each of the four Use Cases in order to highlight significant relationships between the identified categorical variables (see Annex 1): (i) Cramer’s V test, to determine the strength of the relationship between variables; (ii) Chi squared test - χ^2 , determine the level of significance of the relationship between variables¹¹ (see Annex 6).

2.2 Focus Groups

On the basis of a preliminary focus group performed by TU Dublin and STIR¹² in Dublin (Ireland) (June 2019-M8), a series of **Focus Group Discussions** were executed (from March 2020-M17

⁹ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

¹⁰ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

¹¹ See García-Jiménez, E., Poveda-Reyes, S., Molero, G.D., Santarremigia, F.E., Gorrini, A., Hail, Y., Ababio-Donkor, A., Leva, M.C., Mauriello, F. (2020). Methodology for gender analysis in transport: factors with influence in women’s inclusion as professionals and users of transport infrastructures, *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3656 doi: 10.3390/su12093656

¹² See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

to November 2020-M25). This was aimed at better investigating the concept of ‘Inclusiveness for Women Users and Employees in Transport Sector’ and at revising the FCs identified through the Literature Review (see Annex I).

The outline of Focus Groups (see Annex I) were developed on the basis of the Inclusion Diamond representation¹³, the concept of Polyhedral individual¹⁴ and the FCs identified through the Literature Review.

This thematic analysis action was done in the **first and second iteration** of the DIAMOND’s methodological approach (see Figure I and Deliverable 2.2¹⁵).

Data was collected on each Use Case and from across partner countries in order to provide more robust cross-cultural findings to validate the identified FCs:

- Use Case I: France (G&V), Poland (ZTM), Spain (EURECAT and FGC);
- Use Case II: Spain (IBV);
- Use Case III: France (G&V);
- Use Case IV: France (G&V), Poland (ZTM), Spain (EURECAT and FGC).

2.3 Semi-structured Interviews

The objective of **Semi-structured Interviews** was to review the Fairness Characteristics (FCs) identified through the Literature Review and Focus Groups (focusing on specific profiles of target users), considering also the difficulty to join people in the same place (i.e. Focus Groups) caused by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Semi-structured Interviews have also the following objectives: (i) generate useful FCs for the maturity self-assessment model carried out by the interdisciplinary panel; (ii) gather qualitative information to be considered during the data analysis (e.g. establish forced connections between nodes in the Bayesian Networks); (iii) feed the toolkit and provide the self-diagnosis maturity tables with robust recommendations and guidelines.

The question set and discussion points of Semi-structured Interviews were developed on the basis of the outlines of the Focus Groups, the scoping review of literature carried out in Deliverable 4.2¹⁶ and the initial Bayesian Network analysis of Service and Employers’ Provision Data collected (i.e. Structured Data, Observations, UESI questionnaires).

This thematic analysis action was done only in the **second iteration** of the DIAMOND’s methodological approach (see Figure I and Deliverable 2.2¹⁷).

¹³ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

¹⁴ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

¹⁵ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

¹⁶ See ‘Deliverable 4.2 Socio-economic, demographic and psychological analysis’

¹⁷ See ‘Deliverable 2.2 Methodology and conceptual framework’.

The interview schedules were firstly written in English and then translated into several other languages in order to collect comparative data from different Countries and provide robust cross-cultural findings. All interviews were recorded, transcribed, and then translated into English for upload to NVivo software programme for analysis¹⁸.

Semi-structured Interviews began in July 2020-M21 and are still ongoing. Supporting partners for this data collection activity were (in alphabetic order): EURECAT (Spain), FGC (Spain), STIR (Scotland), TU Dublin (Ireland) and ZTM (Poland).

¹⁸ See: NVivo (Release 1.0) – QSR International

Figure 1 The methodological approach for data collection of the DIAMOND Project.

3. Use Case I: Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways)

3.1 Introduction

The objective of the Use Case I ‘Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways)’ is to **investigate women’s needs as users of metro and urban railway infrastructures**. This is aimed at supporting the development of gender-equitable transport planning and design policies. The final goal of the Use Case I is to increase the percentage of women using metro and commuter railway public transports.

The **Inclusion Diamond**¹⁹ representation for Use Case I is based on: Vertex VI – Transport infrastructure and business model today (Layer L3 – Public transport) and Vertex V4 – Transport infrastructure and business models tomorrow (Layer LI – New technologies, Layer L2 – New business models).

The **Polyhedral Individual**²⁰ representation for the Use Case I addresses a variety of female profiles included in the gender definition of women (e.g., single women, women with children, disabled women, a variety of ages, economic profiles, ethnicities and levels of education).

The **Concept of Fairness**²¹ for the Use Case I is linked to the accessibility of public transport services to take full part in civil and social life.

The **Clusters of Fairness Characteristics**²² (CFCs) defined for the Use Case I are the following: (i) Accessibility of the Service; (ii) Design of the Infrastructure; (iii) Safety and Security.

The **methodology for data collection**²³ for the Use Case I consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers’ Provision Data:
 - Structured data regarding the transport settings and the operation of the service;
 - Observations regarding universal design indicators of the infrastructures;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users;
 - Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users;
- Users and Employees’ Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers’ Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were collected focusing on the metro and commuter urban railway stations managed by **FGC-Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya** (Province of Barcelona, Spain) and by **ZTM-Miasto Stołeczne Warszawa** (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland). Users and Employees’ Perception Data (only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several **European Countries** (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain, Ireland and UK).

¹⁹ See ‘Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition’.

²⁰ See ‘Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition’.

²¹ See ‘Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition’.

²² See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

²³ See ‘Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection’.

3.2 Service and Employers' Provision Data (Use Case I)

3.2.1 Structured Data (Use Case I)

Structured data collection (from M9-July 2019 to M17-March 2020) was aimed at selecting and characterizing a sample of suitable 10 stations managed by **FGC** (82 stations in total) and 10 stations managed by **ZTM** (96 stations in total).

The shortlisted stations were investigated through: (i) onsite observations about universal design indicators; (ii) UESI questionnaires focused on women's needs and expectations; (iii) social media data from Twitter regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Structured Open Data were retrieved, sorted and filtered from open data repositories, national geoportals and census databases (see Annex 2). Preliminary structured open data analysis was based on Geographic Information Systems (GIS). A series of thematic maps (see Annex 2) related to the localization and density distribution of datasets were designed to assess the level of accessibility of the railway network managed by FGC and ZTM, focusing on:

- **Territorial data:** density distribution of urban fabric on land use (including continuous urban fabric, discontinuous dense urban fabric and isolated structures) and points of interest (e.g. commercial activities, schools, facilities, public services, attractions, etc.);
- **Socio-demographic data:** density distribution of the total population, female population, elderly population and foreigner population²⁴ per census section;
- **Mobility data:** density distribution of public transport services (e.g. metro and commuter railway stations, bus stops, tram stops, etc), road infrastructures and parking assets;
- **Railway network data:** metro and railway lines localization, tariff zones, characteristics of the railway infrastructures (under-ground or above-ground stations), characteristics of the territory surrounding the stations (city, town, village, countryside).

In order to further characterize the shortlisted stations, structured open data were merged with **Structured Proprietary Data** provided by FGC and ZTM (see in Annex 2), focusing on:

- **Travel demand data:** number of passengers per station per year related to the entire metro and urban railway network;
- **Reliability of the service:** minutes of service delay per station, number of service disruption episodes, operational hours, frequency of the service;
- **Accessibility of the service:** discounted and flexible fares, pay-per-use payment options, subscription or monthly payment options;
- **Security of the transport infrastructures:** number and typology of incidents, presence and visibility of CCTV system, presence and visibility of SOS emergency phone, presence of police and security personnel.

²⁴ Not available data for the Warsaw Metropolitan Area.

The proposed approach for structured open data collection allowed the identification of a **short list of 10 heterogeneous and non-adjacent stations** (see Annex 2), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to the objectives of the Use Case I²⁵.

Structured proprietary data and data coming from observations, UESI questionnaires and social media will be exploited to further characterize the selected stations managed by FGC and ZTM.

3.2.2 Observations (Use Case I)

Onsite observations were aimed at further characterizing the metro and commuter urban railway stations previously selected through structured open data. Observations were based on an *ad hoc* developed checklist defined by SYS with the support of FGC and ZTM for the evaluation of relevant **infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics** related to the women's needs in public transport infrastructure.

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis²⁶, the **assessment checklist** was based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case I and it was composed of four main parts (see Annex 2 for a detailed description of the data collection instrument): (i) area surrounding the station; (ii) concourse level of the station; (iii) platform level of the station; (iv) carriage.

Data collection campaigns were executed in M15-January 2020 by the staff of FGC and ZTM at different time periods of the day (day and night) in order to capture any variations across commuting times. Onsite observations took the form of researchers visually observing the public and recording their finding on paper. In addition, some still photo survey of the metro and urban railway stations was carried out.

3.2.3 UESI Questionnaires (Use Case I)

UESI questionnaires were aimed at further characterizing the metro and commuter urban railway stations previously selected through structured open data. UESI questionnaires were based on an *ad hoc* developed **questionnaire focused on women's needs and expectation** about the railway transport service and infrastructures.

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis²⁷, the outline of the UESI questionnaires were designed by TU Dublin based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case I and it was composed of two main parts (see Annex 2): (i) **users' satisfaction** of the service and infrastructure design; (ii) **socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns** of the end-users.

UESI questionnaires were administrated face to face by external specialized companies enrolled by FGC and ZTM in the selected stations at different time periods of the day, including peak and off-peak hours, from M16-February 2020 to M24-October 2020. The outline of the UESI questionnaire was translated in the local language by specialized subcontractors.

²⁵ Further information about Structure Open Data analysis are provided in 'Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description'.

²⁶ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

²⁷ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

Considering the yearly travel ridership data of FGC and ZTM, the sample size of respondents to UESI questionnaires was designed as composed of No. 800 participants²⁸ (No. 40 for each selected station). According to **intersectional analysis approach**, the sample was composed of a variety of female profiles²⁹.

Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected online from general public from across partner countries in order to provide more robust **cross-cultural findings** to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs.

3.2.4 Social Media Data (Use Case I)

The selected 10 stations were further characterized through the analysis of disaggregated social media data collected from **Twitter Social Network**, focusing on: (i) geospatial data; (ii) time-based metadata; (iii) content (hashtags). The KALIUM tool³⁰ was used to retrieve data from the Twitter streaming API in real time (from M14-December 2019 to M24-October 2020) focusing on the Province of Barcelona (Spain) and the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

This was aimed at monitoring the areas surrounding the selected relevant stations and **cluster geospatial data**. Then, the dataset was disaggregated considering the gender of the users through the open source tool M3Inference³¹. This tool relies on a deep learning model trained on multilingual data to infer gender of users based on the username, short bio text and profile picture. This allowed to investigate gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing **content analysis** through hashtags and relevant keywords.

3.3 Users Perception Data (Use Case I)

3.3.1 DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (Use Case I)

The goal of data collection through the DAD survey questionnaires was to define a **hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs** (level 1 and level 2 respectively) identified through Thematic Analysis (see Annex 2). We should highlight that the DAD was delivered online.

The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires was defined by AITEC, considering the CFCs and FCs identified through Thematic Analysis. RINA, as a certification body, carried out a test about the consistency of the DAD survey in two phases as an Ex-ante analysis about the quality of the questionnaires: Phase I) by analysing the validity in a qualitative way and phase II) by analysing the reliability in a quantitative way through a CATANOVA test. This analysis was conducted on a sample with 30 respondents which demonstrated to be a representative sample size for the significance of the results and the power of the test. Details and results of this analysis can be found in the Annex 7.

²⁸ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

²⁹ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

³⁰ Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: *Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*, pp. 392–399.

³¹ Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In *Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference* (pp. 2056-2067).

The initial phase of data collection through DAD survey questionnaires was performed from January 2020 (M15) to October 2020 (M24). The questionnaires was designed to be completed by a large sample of respondents³² (a minimum of 300 participants and 500 ideally per each Use Case in total) gathered from general public using several techniques under the **public engagement strategy**: an innovative snowball approach designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing, newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires was translated into several languages (English, French, Spanish, Polish, Italian and Serbian) and data were collected from across partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. Supporting partners for this activity are presented in alphabetic order: AITEC (Spain), EURECAT (Spain), FTTE (Serbia), G&V (France), IBV (Spain), STIR (Scotland), SYS (Italy), TU Dublin (Ireland), WAVE (France), ZTM (Poland).

³² See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Time Period	Leading Partner	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector	Supporting Partners
Structured Data	To identify and characterise a short list of relevant metro and urban railway stations managed by FGC (Province of Barcelona, Spain) and ZTM (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland), where to perform further data collection activities.	Open data (territorial, socio-demographic, mobility data, etc.) and proprietary data (travel ridership, etc.).	M9-M17	SYS.	SYS.	FGC, SYS, ZTM.	-
Observations	To further characterize the selected metro and urban railway stations and to compare data with UESI questionnaires.	Assessment checklist: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M15	SYS.	SYS, FGC, ZTM.	FGC, ZTM.	-
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to investigate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the selected stations.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M16-M24	TU Dublin.	G&V, SYS, STIR, TU Dublin.	FGC, ZTM.	All Partners
Social Media Data	To characterize the selected stations through the opinion of the end-users by clustering Twitter data among space and time and by analysing hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: geospatial data, time-based meta data, hashtags and textual contents.	M14-M24	EURECAT.	EURECAT, SYS.	EURECAT.	-
DAD survey questionnaires	Define a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis for the Use Case I.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (initial phase)	AITEC.	AITEC, STIR.	AITEC, EURECAT, FTTE, G&V, IBV, TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.	-

Table 1 Description of the data collection approach for the Use Case I.

4. Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car

4.1 Introduction

The objective of the Use Case II is to investigate the **women's emotional needs as passengers of autonomous vehicles**. This is aimed at supporting the design of women-friendlier fully automated cars. The goal of the Use Case II is to increase the level of acceptance of women towards autonomous driving technology.

The **Inclusion Diamond**³³ representation of the Use Case II is based on: Vertex V2 – Vehicle of today; Layer L4 – Vehicles; Vertex V5 – Vehicle tomorrow; Layer L1 – Road Transport;

The **Polyhedral Individual**³⁴ representation for the Use Case II addresses different female profiles that are included in the gender definition of women (e.g. women with and without children under 12-year-old), disabled women, a variety of ages, economic profile, ethnicities and levels of education). Observations will be focused on gender for the emotional aspects, elicitors and physiological response.

The **Concept of Fairness**³⁵ for the Use Case II is linked to the development of fair and accessible autonomous driving technology.

The **Clusters of Fairness Characteristics**³⁶ (CFCs) defined for the Use Case II are the following: (i) Safety and Security; (ii) Comfort; (iii) Mobility; (iv) Economy; (v) Environment; (vi) Design Options.

The **methodology for data collection**³⁷ for the Use Case II consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers' Provision Data:
 - Observations based on an experimental investigation of women's emotional reactions to autonomous driving performance;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users;
 - Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users;
- Users and Employees' Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers' Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were focused on a sample of subjects participating in an experimental study managed by IBV-Instituto de Biomecánica (Valencia, Spain) (Observations and UESI questionnaires) and on the opinion of the end-users across several European Countries (social media data). Users and Employees'

³³ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

³⁴ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

³⁵ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

³⁶ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

³⁷ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

Perception Data (only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several European Countries (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain, Ireland and UK).

3.2 Service and Employers' Provision Data (Use Case II)

3.2.1 Observations (Use Case II)

A series of experiments in a simulator laboratory setting were executed to collect data about **gender differences in passengers' emotional appraisal while driving autonomous vehicles** characterized by Level 4 of automation.

Previous research has found gender differences in the willingness to use automated cars, but did not provide any examination of variables potentially explaining this difference (Hohenberger et al., 2016)³⁸. The goal of the proposed experimental campaign is to empirically investigate emotional differences between men and women in automated driving scenarios, considering other relevant variables (e.g. age, care responsibilities³⁹, driving scenarios).

A sample of about 40 participants (with an age between 25-55 years old) was balanced according to the modalities of the independent variables gender and family composition involving care responsibilities (10 men and 10 women with children under 12 years old, and 10 men and 10 women without children under 12 years old). Age and technology affinity level of participants are controlled within groups to explore the effect on emotional response and to avoid biases in results between groups.

The procedure was based on the use of sensors to empirically monitor participants' physiological reactions (i.e. *dependent variables*). The emotional state of the participant monitored through the recordings of the physiological signals is represented with the *Arousal* (emotion activation level)

³⁸ Hohenberger et al. (2016) provided evidenced by means a questionnaire-based study that affective responses towards automotive cars (i.e. anxiety and pleasure) mediate the effect of gender on willingness to use them. In particular, they concluded that men in comparison to women will show a higher level of willingness to use automated cars and men are more likely to associate positive emotions towards automated cars than women while women are more likely to associate negative emotions towards automated cars than men. They, additionally, validated that the effect of gender on the willingness to use automated cars is mediated through positive and negative emotions. Also, the variable age together with gender were explored and they concluded that with increasing age people showed low levels of pleasure but not anxiety, and with increasing age men compared to women, exhibit lower levels of negative emotional (anxiety) intensity towards automated cars and the indirect effect of gender on willingness to use through negative emotions is greater for low levels of chronological age. These results suggest that addressing anxiety-related responses towards automated cars (e.g. by providing safety-related information) and accentuating especially the pleasurable effects of automated cars could reduce differences between men and women acceptance. See: Hohenberger, C., Spörrle, M., & Welpel, I. M. (2016). How and why do men and women differ in their willingness to use automated cars? The influence of emotions across different age groups. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 94, 374-385.

³⁹ The presence of kids in the family represents a relevant factor linked to care responsibilities. In Spain, also, 12 years old, represents the end of primary school, and contrary to other countries, because of extended cultural issues, is usually the end age for kids walking accompanied by an adult to school. Thus, the sample of men and women will be equilibrated according to this factor.

and *Valence* (qualitative connotation of the emotion) model⁴⁰. Additionally, participant’s facial expression was recorded during the experimental procedure through video footages, in order to enable automatic emotion identification.

Table 2 The physiological signals monitored in experiments and their relations with Arousal and Valence model.

Physiological signals	Physiological reaction related with emotional state
Electrocardiogram (ECG) sensor for obtaining the heart rate (HR) and the heart rate variability (HRV) ⁴¹ .	Corrugator supercilia increases the activity when the valence of the person is low. Zygomaticus major increases the activity when the valence of the person is high.
A skin conductance sensor to record the Electro Dermal Activity (EDA) ^{42, 43} .	EDA produces fast changes associated to emotional events. These changes are higher for higher arousals
Two facial EMG sensors recording the muscle activity of zygomaticus major and corrugator supercilia ³³ .	HR increases with arousal. The low frequency component of HRV decreases with higher arousals. The high frequency component of HRV increases with higher valences.

The scenarios for the autonomous driving simulator were designed through the execution of a Focus Group which was held in November 2019 (MI3) in IBV facilities (see Annex 3). Six autonomous driving scenarios were designed considering different environmental, traffic and driving conditions (i.e. *independent variables*), as presented below:

Scenario	Main goal	Justification
S1. Trust in autonomous driving in different weather conditions	Simulate an autonomous driving with favourable and unfavourable weather. Relate the emotional state with user trust in AV and the influence of weather condition due to a change in danger perception.	FC2. Comfort\Trust in the technology Trust in technology means in all possible and different conditions. Weather condition was identified a relevant factor related with safety and trust in focus group.

⁴⁰ Lang, Peter J., Margaret M. Bradley, and Bruce N. Cuthbert. 1999. ‘International Affective Picture System (IAPS): Instruction Manual and Affective Ratings’. The Center for Research in Psychophysiology, University of Florida.

⁴¹ Nardelli, M., G. Valenza, A. Greco, A. Lanata, and E. P. Scilingo. 2015. ‘Recognizing Emotions Induced by Affective Sounds through Heart Rate Variability’. *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 6 (4): 385–94. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TAFFC.2015.2432810>.

⁴² Laparra-Hernández, J., J. M. Belda-Lois, E. Medina, N. Campos, and R. Poveda. 2009. ‘EMG and GSR Signals for Evaluating User’s Perception of Different Types of Ceramic Flooring’. *International Journal of Industrial Ergonomics* 39 (2): 326–332.

⁴³ Zhou, Shou-Han, D. Oetomo, Ying Tan, E. Burdet, and I. Mareels. 2012. ‘Modeling Individual Human Motor Behavior Through Model Reference Iterative Learning Control’. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering* 59 (7): 1892–1901. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TBME.2012.2192437>.

<p>S2. Sportive driving mode in time constrain scenario</p>	<p>Simulate a sportive/aggressive driving to reach the goal trip with time constrain. Measure the emotional impact and preference of this situation.</p>	<p>FC6. Design options\Vehicle behaviour</p> <p>FC3. Mobility\Travel time</p> <p>Accordingly, to bibliography men tend to be more aggressive than women when driving. We want to assess if this difference can be assessed in terms of emotions when the car behaves in different modes, sportive vs comfort conduction. Travel time is another important consideration when talking about AVs in comparison with non-AVs.</p>
<p>S3. Comfort driving mode in time constrain scenario</p>	<p>Simulate a comfort/smooth driving to reach the goal trip with time constrain. Measure the emotional impact and preference of this situation.</p>	
<p>S4. Simultaneity</p>	<p>In this case we ask the participant to perform task while traveling in the car in two different environments, an enriched one with more external inputs and a calmer one.</p> <p>Measure of the emotional impact of performing a secondary task and the influence of different levels the mental workload due to external driving events.</p>	<p>FC2. Comfort\Simultaneity.</p> <p>One identified main values of AV is the fact of not being responsible of the driving allows and using the time inside the car in other purposes such as relaxing or performing simultaneous tasks. This fact has to do also with the possible perception of joy or boredom.</p> <p>The Focus Group identified possible differences in the way men and women value the opportunity. Women were more motivated to multitasking and men to relax. Men were more likely to identify themselves as bored in an AV than women.</p>
<p>S5. AV Failure while driving</p>	<p>Simulate a system failure and the AV performs an emergency stop in a minimal risk condition. Measure the emotional impact and the relation with user trust.</p>	<p>FC2. Comfort\Trust in the technology This represents the trust in technology from the point of view of tech liability, identified in the Focus Group and bibliographic review.</p>
<p>S6. Dangerous driving event</p>	<p>Simulate a critical situation that another car falls to stop at a red traffic light and the user AV must do a sudden braking to avoid the collision. Measure the emotional impact when there is an event that affect personal safety perception.</p>	<p>FC2. Comfort\Trust in the technology This represents the trust in technology from the point of view of safety, identified in the Focus Group. Is going the AVs to be able to prevent or detect critical situations better than humans?</p>

The experimental protocol was defined by IBV (see Annex 3), with support from AITEC, SYS and TU Dublin. Data were collected by the staff of IBV through experimental campaign execution from September 2020-M23 to October 2020-M24.

The main goal of observation was the identification of **gender-driven stressors related to autonomous driving emotional experience**, focusing on the FCs identified through Thematic Analysis⁴⁴.

3.2.2 UESI Questionnaires (Use Case II)

UESI questionnaires are focused on the acceptance of the end-users related to autonomous vehicles. The outline of UESI questionnaires is composed of two main parts. The first is focused on profiling the **socio-demographic characteristics** and **mobility patterns** of the end-users and it is administrated before the execution of the experiments. The second part is focused on evaluating the **users' satisfaction regarding the autonomous driving performance** experienced through the simulator and gathering information related with acceptance factors.

The outline of UESI questionnaires was defined by IBV (see Annex 3), considering the CFCs, FCs and influencing parameters identified through the Thematic Analysis⁴⁵.

UESI questionnaires were administrated by the staff of IBV (from M23-September 2020 to M24-October 2020) to the participants of the experimental study⁴⁶.

Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected from general public from across partner countries in order to provide more robust **cross-cultural findings** to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs.

3.2.3 Social Media Data (Use Case II)

A series of disaggregated social media data were collected from **Twitter Social Network**, focusing on their content (hashtags). The KALIUM tool⁴⁷ was used to retrieve data from the Twitter streaming API in real time (from M12-December 2019 to M24-October 2020) across partner countries in order to provide more robust **cross-cultural findings**.

The dataset was disaggregated considering the gender of the users through the open source tool M3Inference⁴⁸. This tool relies on a deep learning model trained on multilingual data to infer gender of users based on the username, short bio text and profile picture. This allowed us to investigate gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing **content analysis** through hashtags and relevant keywords.

⁴⁴ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁴⁵ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁴⁶ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

⁴⁷ Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: *Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*, pp. 392–399.

⁴⁸ Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In *Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference* (pp. 2056-2067).

3.3 Users and Employees' Perception Data (Use Case II)

3.3.1 DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (Use Case II)

The goal of data collection through DAD survey questionnaires is to define a **hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs** (Level 1 and Level 2 respectively) identified through Thematic Analysis (see Annex 3). We should highlight that the DAD was delivered online.

The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires was defined by AITEC, considering the CFCs and FCs identified through Thematic Analysis. RINA, as a certification body, carried out a test about the consistency of the DAD survey in two phases as an Ex-ante analysis about the quality of the questionnaires: Phase I) by analysing the validity in a qualitative way and phase II) by analysing the reliability in a quantitative way through a CATANOVA test. This analysis was conducted on a sample with 30 respondents which demonstrated to be a representative sample size for the significance of the results and the power of the test. Details and results of this analysis can be found in the Annex 7.

The initial phase of data collection through DAD survey questionnaires was performed from January 2020 (M15) to October 2020 (M24). The questionnaires was designed to be completed by a large sample of respondents⁴⁹ (a minimum of 300 participants and ideally 500) gathered from general public using several techniques under the **public engagement strategy**: an innovative snowball approach designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing, Newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media⁵⁰.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires was translated in several the individual native languages of partner countries and data were collected from across partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. Supporting partners for this activity are presented in alphabetic order: AITEC (Spain), EURECAT (Spain), FTTE (Serbia), G&V (France), IBV (Spain), SYS (Italy), TU Dublin (Ireland), WAVE (France), ZTM (Poland).

⁴⁹ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

⁵⁰ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Time Period	Leading Partner	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector	Supporting Partners
Observations	To identify stress triggers related to autonomous driving performance, focusing on gender.	Experiments in a driving simulator laboratory setting.	M23-M24	IBV.	IBV.	IBV.	AITEC, SYS, TU Dublin.
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the autonomous driving performance experienced through the simulator.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M17-M24	TU Dublin.	IBV	IBV (in experimental study)	All Partner.
Social Media Data	To analyse hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: hashtags and textual contents.	M14-M24	EURECAT.	EURECAT.	EURECAT.	IBV
DAD survey questionnaires	Define a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis for the Use Case II.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (initial phase)	AITEC.	AITEC, STIR.	AITEC, EURECAT, FTTE, G&V, IBV, TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.	-

Table 3 Description of the data collection approach for the Use Case II.

5. Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management

5.1 Introduction

The objective of the Use Case III is to investigate the **women's needs as users of bike-sharing services**. This is aimed at supporting the development of policies for gender-equitable bike sharing fleet management. The goal of the Use Case III is to increase the percentage of women using bike sharing services.

The **Inclusion Diamond**⁵¹ representation of the Use Case III is based on: Vertex VI – Transport infrastructure and business model today (Layer L3 – Public transport); Vertex V4 – Transport infrastructure and business models tomorrow (Layer L1 – New technologies, Layer L2 – New business models).

The **Polyhedral Individual**⁵² representation for the Use Case III addresses a variety of female profiles that are included in the gender definition of women (e.g., single women, women with children, disabled women, a variety of ages, economic profile, ethnicities and levels of education).

The **Concept of Fairness**⁵³ for the Use Case III is linked the possibility to access bike-sharing services in order to take full part in civil and social life.

The **Clusters of Fairness Characteristics**⁵⁴ (CFCs) defined for the Use Case III are the following: (i) Accessibility and Spontaneity; (ii) Safety and Security; (iii) Social Constraints; (iv) Weather and Topography.

The methodology for **data collection**⁵⁵ for the Use Case III consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers' Provision Data:
 - Structured data regarding the bike-sharing docking stations and the operation of the service;
 - Observations regarding universal design indicators of bike-sharing docking stations and their surrounding urban context;
 - UESI questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users;
 - Social media data regarding the opinion of the end-users.
- Users and Employees' Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Service and Employers' Provision Data (only Service Provision Data in this case) were collected focusing on the bike-sharing docking stations managed by **VELIB-Syndicat Mixte Autolib et Vélib Métropole** (Metropolitan Area of Paris, France). Users and Employees' Perception Data

⁵¹ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

⁵² See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

⁵³ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

⁵⁴ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁵⁵ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

(only Users Perception Data in this case) were collected focusing on the opinion of the end-users across several **European Countries** (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain, Ireland and UK).

5.2 Service and Employers' Provision Data (Use Case III)

5.2.1 Structured Data (Use Case III)

Structured data collection (from M9-July 2019 to M19-May 2020) was aimed at selecting and characterizing a sample of suitable 20 bike-sharing docking stations managed by **VELIB** (1377 docking stations in total). The shortlisted docking stations were further investigated through: (i) onsite observations about universal design indicators; (ii) UESI questionnaires focused on women's needs and expectations; (iii) social media data from Twitter regarding the opinion of the end-users.

Structured Open Data were retrieved, sorted and filtered from open data repositories, national geoportals and census databases (see Annex 4). Preliminary structured open data analysis was based on Geographic Information Systems (GIS). A series of thematic maps (see Annex 4) related to the localization and density distribution of datasets were designed to assess the level of accessibility of the bike sharing docking stations managed by VELIB, focusing on:

- **Territorial data:** density distribution of urban fabric on land use (including continuous urban fabric, discontinuous dense urban fabric and isolated structures) and points of interest (e.g. commercial activities, schools, facilities, public services, attractions, etc.);
- **Socio-demographic data:** density distribution of total population, female population, elderly population and foreigner population per census section;
- **Mobility data:** density distribution of public transport services (e.g. metro and commuter railway stations, bus stops, tram stops, etc) and cycleway infrastructures;
- **Bike-sharing docking stations network data:** docking stations capacity (number of bikes available for each docking station).

In order to further characterize the shortlisted stations, structured open data were merged with **Structured Proprietary Data** provided by VELIB (see Annex 4), focusing on:

- **Travel demand data:** number of users per docking station per year, number of users per docking station per month, origin/destination matrix of the users, average length of trips, average time duration of trips;
- **Accessibility and Spontaneity:** number of public campaigns on cycling in the past year, number of adverts on bike-sharing services in the past year, type of requirement for signing-up for membership, number and percentage of cash payment members, the entry cost of bike-sharing scheme (upfront cost), rental charges above one hour, annual membership cost of the scheme, types of safety equipment supplied by the operator, nature and type of insurance cover for bikes and users (i.e. damages, theft, accidents etc.) if available, number and percentage of docking stations at transport hubs, number and percentage of bikes with a child seat, trailers and carriages for carrying children and goods, number of practical cycling programs/training held in the past year, number and percentage of docking stations with shelter, number and percentage of docking stations with toilet facilities;

- **Safety and Security:** percentage of bike network segregated from vehicular traffic, number of cycling training programmes organised in a year to educate cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road, number of public campaigns held to address harassment of cyclist in the past one year, number of public campaigns held to boost cyclists' confidence in the past one year, number and percentage of docking stations with security devices, number and percentage of docking stations with CCTV, number and percentage of bikes with well-functioning brakes, lights and reflectors etc, number and percentage of docking stations with information centres for users, speed limits on roads with cycle lanes, percentage of roads with physically separated bike lanes from vehicular traffic;
- **Social Constraints:** number of campaigns targeted at low-income and minority groups/neighbourhoods to promote cycling as an acceptable form of transport, number of practical cycling training programmes;
- **Weather and Topography:** percentage of cycle network that is all-weather cycle friendly, number and percentage of electric bikes among bike fleet and at each docking station.

The proposed approach for structured open data collection allowed the identification of a **short list of 20 heterogeneous and non-adjacent docking stations** (see Annex 4), characterized by positively and negatively relevant characteristics related to the objectives of the Use Case III⁵⁶. Structured proprietary data and data coming from observations, UESI questionnaires and social media will be exploited to further characterize the selected docking stations managed by VELIB.

5.2.2 Observations (Use Case III)

Onsite observations were aimed at further characterizing the bike sharing docking stations previously selected through structured open data. Observations were based on the development of an assessment checklist defined by ENU with the support of SYS for the evaluation of relevant **infrastructure design and surrounding context characteristics** related to the all users' needs as users of bike-sharing docking stations.

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis⁵⁷, the **assessment checklist** was based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case III and it was composed of five main parts (see Annex 4): (i) Accessibility and Spontaneity; (ii) Safety and Security; (iii) Social Constraints; (iv) Weather and Topography; (v) Other.

Data collection campaigns were executed from M17-March 2020 to M23-September 2020 by the staff of G&V at different time periods of the day (day and night). Onsite observations took the form of researchers visually observing the public and recording their finding on paper. In addition, some still photography of the bike sharing docking stations was carried out.

⁵⁶ Further information about Structure Open Data analysis are provided in 'Deliverable 4.1 Datasets description'.

⁵⁷ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

5.2.3 UESI Questionnaires (Use Case III)

UESI questionnaires were aimed at further characterizing the bike sharing docking stations previously selected through structured open data. UESI questionnaires were based on the development of **questionnaire focused on women's needs and expectation** about the bike sharing service and infrastructures.

Considering the findings of Thematic Analysis⁵⁸, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was designed by TU Dublin based on the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified for the Use Case III and it was composed of two main parts (see Annex 4): (i) **users' satisfaction** of the service and infrastructure design; (ii) **socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns** of the end-users.

UESI questionnaires were administrated face to face by VELIB at the selected docking stations at different time periods of the day, including peak and off-peak hours, from M17-March 2020 to M24-October 2020. The outline of the UESI questionnaire was translated from English to French by VELIB.

Considering the yearly travel ridership data of VELIB, the sample size of respondents to UESI questionnaires was design to be composed of 400 participants⁵⁹ (20 for each selected station). According to the framework of an **intersectional analysis approach**, the sample composed of by a variety of female profiles⁶⁰.

Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected from general public from across partner countries in order to provide more robust **cross-cultural findings** to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs.

5.2.4 Social Media Data (Use Case III)

The selected docking stations were further characterized through the analysis of disaggregated social media data collected from **Twitter Social Network**, focusing on: (i) geospatial data; (ii) time-based metadata; (iii) and content (hashtags). The KALIUM tool⁶¹ was used to retrieve data from the Twitter streaming API in real time (from M14-December 2019 to M24-October 2020) focusing on the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

This was aimed at monitoring the areas surrounding the selected relevant docking stations and **cluster geospatial data**. Then, the dataset was disaggregated considering the gender of the users through the open source tool M3Inference⁶². This tool relies on a deep learning model trained on multilingual data to infer gender of users based on the username, short bio text and

⁵⁸ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁵⁹ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

⁶⁰ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

⁶¹ Napalkova, L., Aragón, P., Robles, J.C.C. (2018). Big data-driven platform for cross-media monitoring. In: *Proceedings of IEEE 5th International Conference on Data Science and Advanced Analytics (DSAA)*, pp. 392–399.

⁶² Wang, Z., Hale, S., Adelani, D. I., Grabowicz, P., Hartman, T., & Jurgens, D. (2019). Demographic Inference and Representative Population Estimates from Multilingual Social Media Data. In *Proceedings of World Wide Web Conference* (pp. 2056-2067).

profile picture. This allowed to investigate gender difference in the activity of Twitter users, by performing **content analysis** through hashtags and relevant keywords.

5.3 Users and Employees' Perception Data (Use Case III)

5.3.1 DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (Use Case III)

The goal of data collection through DAD survey questionnaires is to define a **hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs** (Level 1 and Level 2 respectively) identified through Thematic Analysis (see Annex 4). We should highlight that the DAD was delivered online

The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires was defined by AITEC, considering the CFCs and FCs identified through Thematic Analysis. RINA, as a certification body, carried out a test about the consistency of the DAD survey in two phases as an Ex-ante analysis about the quality of the questionnaires: Phase I) by analysing the validity in a qualitative way and phase II) by analysing the reliability in a quantitative way through a CATANOVA test. This analysis was conducted on a sample with 30 respondents which demonstrated to be a representative sample size for the significance of the results and the power of the test. Details and results of this analysis can be found in the (Annex 7) analysing its validity and ii) analysing its reliability.

The initial phase of data collection through DAD survey questionnaires was performed from January 2020 (M15) to October 2020 (M24). The questionnaires was designed to be completed filled by a large sample of respondents⁶³ (a minimum of 300 participants and 500 ideally per each Use Case in total) gathered from general public using several techniques under the **public engagement strategy**: an innovative snowball approach designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing. Newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media⁶⁴.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected from across partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. Supporting partners for this activity are presented in alphabetic order: AITEC (Spain), EURECAT (Spain), FTTE (Serbia), G&V (France), IBV (Spain), SYS (Italy), TU Dublin (Ireland), WAVE (France), ZTM (Poland).

⁶³ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'..

⁶⁴ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Time Period	Leading Partner	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector	Supporting Partners
Structured Data	To identify a short list of relevant bike-haring pickup/return points managed by VELIB within the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France), where to perform future data collection activities.	Open data (territorial, socio-demographic, mobility data, travel demand data) and proprietary data (e.g. travel ridership).	M9-M17	SYS.	SYS.	SYS, VELIB.	-
Observations	To further characterize the selected bike-sharing pickup/return points and to compare data with UESI questionnaires.	Assessment checklist: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M17-M23	SYS.	ENU, SYS.	G&V	-
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and mobility patterns of the end-users and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the bike-sharing pickup/return points.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, mobility patterns, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M17-M24	TU Dublin.	G&V, TU Dublin.	VELIB.	All Partners.
Social Media Data	To characterize the selected pickup/return points through the opinion of the end-users by clustering Twitter data among space and time and by analysing hashtags and textual contents.	Twitter (disaggregated) data: geospatial data, time-based meta data, hashtag and text content.	M14-M24	EURECAT.	EURECAT, SYS.	EURECAT.	-
DAD survey questionnaires	Define a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis for the Use Case III.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (initial phase)	AITEC.	AITEC.	AITEC, EURECAT, FTTE, G&V, IBV, TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.	-

Table 4 Description of the data collection approach for the Use Case III.

6. Use Case IV: Women Recruitment in Railways and Freight / CSR Protocols

6.1 Introduction

The objective of the Use Case IV is to investigate women's **needs as employees in the transport sector**. The goal of the Use Case IV is to assess the key factors regarding fairness and inclusiveness of employment for women across different positions in transport and help to increase the percentage of women working on-site and off-site in specific male dominated roles in railway, freight transport and the logistics sectors.

The **Inclusion Diamond**⁶⁵ representation for the Use Case IV is based on: Vertex V3 - Jobholder today (Layer L4 – On-site professional jobs, Layer L5 – Off-site professional jobs); Vertex V6 - Jobholder tomorrow (Layer L4 – On-site professional jobs, Layer L5 – Off-site professional jobs).

The **Polyhedral Individual**⁶⁶ representation for the Use Case IV addresses a variety of female profiles that are included in the gender definition of women (e.g., single women, women with children, disabled women, a variety of ages, economic profiles, ethnicities and levels of education).

The **Concept of Fairness**⁶⁷ for the Use Case IV is linked to the development of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) protocols preventing contrasting the discrimination of women as workers in the public transport sector (e.g., discriminatory hiring, unequal payment, etc.).

The **Clusters of Fairness Characteristics**⁶⁸ (CFCs) defined for the Use Case IV are the following: (i) Socio-economic conditions; (ii) Job Characteristics; (iii) Personal Circumstances; (iv) Individual Characteristics.

The **methodology for data collection**⁶⁹ for the Use Case IV consisted of the following:

- Service and Employers' Provision Data:
 - Structured data: regarding the percentage of women currently involved in professional jobs related to the transport sector in several (which countries) EU Countries. With a focus on differing job roles, women's career progression, job opportunities and training and conditions of employment etc.
 - UESI questionnaires: regarding the opinion of employees.
- Users and Employees' Perception Data:
 - DAD survey questionnaires regarding the opinion of the end-users.

⁶⁵ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

⁶⁶ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

⁶⁷ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use cases definition'.

⁶⁸ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁶⁹ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

Service and Employers' Provision Data (only Employers Provision Data in this case) were provided by the Human Resources Department of **FGC-Ferrocarrils de la Generalitat de Catalunya** (Province of Barcelona, Spain) and **ZTM-Miasto Stoleczne Warszawa** (Warsaw Metropolitan Area, Poland). Users and Employees' Perception Data (only Employees Perception Data in this case) was collected focusing on the opinion of women involved in professional jobs related to the transport sector across several **European Countries** (France, Italy, Poland, Serbia, Spain, Ireland and UK).

6.2 Service and Employers' Provision Data (Use Case IV)

6.2.1 Structured Data (Use Case IV)

Structured data collection (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020) is aimed at characterizing the level of participation of women to on-site and off-site professional jobs related to the transport sector (railway, freight transport and logistics sectors). On-site professional jobs including administrative and office management in transport departments, operators for warehouses, rail maintenance technicians. Off-site professional jobs include drivers of short and long distances.

Structured Open Data collection was performed by STIR and TU Dublin using historical series of open data focused on several European Countries which countries (see Annex 5) and through **Structured Proprietary Data provided by FGC and ZTM**.

The goal of structured data collection was to highlight depict the level of participation of women into professional jobs related to the wider transport sector across the in EU. The data that were collected considering the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified through Thematic Analysis⁷⁰.

6.2.2 UESI Questionnaires (Use Case IV)

UESI questionnaires were focused on job conditions and employability to identify barriers and needs related to the level of **participation of women in professional jobs related to the transport sector** in EU, focusing on the Human Resources Department of FGC and ZTM.

The outline of UESI questionnaires was composed in two main parts. The first is focused on profiling the **socio-demographic characteristics** and **career profiles** of women employees in the transport sector. The second part was focused on evaluating the **employees' satisfaction** regarding job conditions and employability.

The outline of UESI questionnaires (see Annex 5 for a detailed description of the data collection instrument) was defined by G&V, STIR and TU Dublin (in alphabetic order) considering the CFCs, FCs and IPs identified through Thematic Analysis⁷¹. UESI questionnaires were administrated from M17-March 2020 to M24-October 2020.

⁷⁰ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

⁷¹ See 'Deliverable 3.1 Methodology and requirements for data collection'.

Then, the outline of the UESI questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected from general public from across partner countries in order to provide robust **cross-cultural findings** to further investigate the identified CFCs, FCs and IPs⁷².

6.3 Users and Employees' Perception Data (Use Case IV)

6.3.1 DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires (Use Case IV)

The goal of data collection through the online DAD survey questionnaires is to define a **hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs** (level 1 and level 2 respectively) identified through Thematic Analysis (see Annex 5).

The outline of the DAD-Dynamic Argumentative Delphi survey questionnaires was defined by AITEC, considering the CFCs and FCs identified through Thematic Analysis. RINA, as a certification body, carried out a test about the consistency of the DAD survey in two phases as an Ex-ante analysis about the quality of the questionnaires: Phase I) by analysing the validity in a qualitative way and phase II) by analysing the reliability in a quantitative way through a CATANOVA test. This analysis was conducted on a sample with 30 respondents which demonstrated to be a representative sample size for the significance of the results and the power of the test. Details and results of this analysis can be found in the Annex 7. The initial phase of data collection through DAD survey questionnaires was performed from January 2020 (M15) to October 2020 (M24). The questionnaires was designed to be completed by a large sample of respondents⁷³ (a minimum of 300 participants and ideally 500) gathered from general public using several techniques under the **public engagement strategy**: an innovative snowball approach designed for complex questionnaires, e-mailing. Newsletters and spreading the online surveys in the social media⁷⁴.

The outline of the DAD survey questionnaires was translated in several languages and data were collected from across partner countries (France, Spain, Italy, United Kingdom, Ireland, Poland and Poland) in order to provide more robust **cross-cultural findings** to hierarchize the identified CFCs and FCs. Supporting partners for this activity are presented in alphabetic order: AITEC (Spain), EURECAT (Spain), FTTE (Serbia), G&V (France), IBV (Spain), SYS (Italy), TU Dublin (Ireland), WAVE (France), ZTM (Poland).

⁷² See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

⁷³ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

⁷⁴ See 'Deliverable 2.1 Use-cases definition'.

Data Typology	Objective	Sources	Time Period	Leading Partner	Data Set Designer	Data Set Collector	Supporting Partners
Structured Data	To define the level of participation of women on-site and off-site professional jobs related to transport sector in several European Countries.	Open data and proprietary data.	M9-M25	TU Dublin.	STIR, TU Dublin.	FGC, STIR, TU Dublin ZTM.	AITEC, EURECAT.
UESI questionnaires	To profile the socio-demographic characteristics and career profiles of the employees and to correlate their level of satisfaction with the characteristics of the job conditions.	Questionnaires: Socio-demographic data, career profiles, CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2), Influencing Parameters (Level 3).	M17-M24	TU Dublin.	G&V, STIR, TU Dublin.	FGC, ZTM.	All Partners
DAD survey questionnaires	Define a hierarchical model of the CFCs and FCs identified through the Thematic Analysis for the Use Case IV.	DAD questionnaires: CFCs (Level 1), FCs (Level 2).	M15-M24 (initial phase)	AITEC.	AITEC.	AITEC, EURECAT, FTTE, G&V, IBV, TU Dublin, SYS, WAVE, ZTM.	-

Table 5 Description of the data collection approach for the Use Case IV.

Conclusion

The current document ‘Deliverable D3.3 Report on data collection campaigns’ describes the **data collection activities** executed within the ‘Work Package 3 – Data collection’ of DIAMOND project (from M9-July 2019 to M25-November 2020). In this regard, the document includes information regarding the identification of **dataset sources, data collection tools, data collection timeline and responsible partners of the Consortium for each data collection activity**.

The main objective of DIAMOND project is to turn data into reliable and actionable knowledge for supporting the inclusion of women in transport systems as both users and employees. The document is focused on **Use Cases of the DIAMOND project** (see Table 6 for the summary and timeline):

- Use Case I - Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways);
- Use Case II: (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car;
- Use Case III: Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management;
- Use Case IV: Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.

Use Case	Data Typology	Data collection timeline
Use Case I	Structured Data, Observations, UESI questionnaires, Social Media, DAD survey.	M9-M24
Use Case II	Observations, UESI questionnaires, Social Media, DAD survey.	M10-M24
Use Case III	Structured Data, Observations, UESI questionnaires, Social Media, DAD survey.	M14-M24
Use Case IV	Structured Data, UESI questionnaires, DAD survey.	M9-M25

Table 6 Data collection campaigns summary.

Annex I – Thematic Analysis

Literature Review Results

Table 7: Results of literature review for the Use Case I.

Literature Review Use Case I	ID			CFCs			FCs									
	V1 - L3 Public transport	V4 - L1 New technologies	V4 - L2 New business models	Accessibility of the Service	Design of the Infrastructure	Safety & Security	Service Availability & Efficiency	Travel & Wayfinding Information	Ticketing Options & Fares	Travel Purpose	Universal Design	Cleanliness & Maintenance	Furniture & Facilities	Harassment & Pickpocketing	Overcrowding & Emergency Situations	
(Albeniz & Alonso, 2009)	•			•	•	•	•				•	•	•	•		
(APTA, 2013)	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		
(Asian Development Bank, 2013)	•			•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	
(Duchène, 2011)	•			•	•	•	•		•	•	•		•	•		
(European Commission, 1994)	•			•	•	•	•		•		•		•	•		
(FIA Foundation, 2017)	•			•	•	•	•	•		•			•	•	•	
(Gheorghiu et al., 2017)		•	•	•		•		•	•					•		
(Madriaza et al., 2016)	•				•	•					•		•	•	•	
(ITF, 2018)	•				•	•					•		•	•	•	
(Loukaitou-Sideris, 2014)	•				•	•					•	•	•	•		
(MacLeod et al., 2006)	•		•	•			•	•	•		•					
(Network Rail, 2011)	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	
(Peters, 2013)	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	
(Shrestha et al., 2017)	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•		
(Soltani, Sham, Awang, & Yaman, 2012)	•			•				•	•		•		•			
(Suman & Bolia, 2019)	•			•	•	•	•		•		•	•	•	•	•	
(Thompson et al., 2012)	•			•	•	•	•	•			•	•	•	•	•	
(Transport for London, 2012)	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	
(Transport for London, 2015)	•			•	•	•		•	•		•	•		•	•	
(Turner, 2012)	•			•	•	•	•		•		•		•	•	•	

Table 8: Results of literature review for the Use Case II.

Literature review Use Case II	ID		CFCs							FCs																		
	V2 - L2 Vehicle today	V5 - L1 Vehicle tomorrow	Safety & Security	Comfort	Mobility	Economy	Environment	Design options	Accident rate	Human errors	Training	Traffic management	Trust in technology	Simultaneity	Traffic efficiency	Travel time	Congestion	Accessibility	Monetary costs	Non-monetary costs	Vehicle efficiency	Noise	Emissions	Public health	Infrastructure adaptation	Vehicle shape	Vehicle behaviour	Human Machine Interface (HMI)
(Barnard et al., 2018)	•	•	•		•	•	•								•				•	•				•				
(Blokpoel & Lu, 2018)		•	•		•	•									•						•							
(Böhm et al., 2017)	•	•		•									•															
(Brell, Philipsen, & Ziefle, 2019)	•		•	•	•	•	•						•	•			•				•		•					
(Collet & Musicant, 2019)	•	•	•																									
(Diels et al., 2017)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•		•					•								
(Duy Son et al., 2018)	•		•		•	•		•									•			•								•
(Hand & Lee, 2018)	•	•		•									•															
(Hohenberger, Spörrle & Welppe, 2016)	•	•	•	•	•		•				•		•					•					•	•				
(Jugade et al. 2018)	•	•	•					•	•																•		•	•
(Kuhn et al., 2018)	•	•	•		•			•				•			•										•			•
(Kyriakidis, Happee & De Winter, 2015)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			•	•		•		•			•				•	•	•		
(Meschtscherjakov et al., 2018)	•		•	•				•	•	•	•		•															•
(Nielsen & Christiansen, 2018)	•		•	•	•								•	•				•										
(Olsen & Sweet, 2019)	•	•	•	•	•				•				•	•	•													
(Patz, 2018)	•	•	•		•		•								•								•					
(Pereira, Costa, Costa, & Arezes, 2019)	•		•	•				•		•			•															•
(Peter & Pernilla, 2018)	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•							•	•		•	•		•			•			
(Pettigrew et al., 2019)	•	•	•	•	•				•		•		•					•										
(Raposo et al., 2018)	•	•	•			•	•		•			•							•				•	•				
(Rogic et al., 2018)	•							•															•	•				•
(Schieben et al., 2019)	•							•																				
(Schwarz, Gaspar, & Brown, 2019)	•			•									•															
(Shergold, Wilson & Parkhurst, 2016)	•	•	•	•	•				•				•					•										

Table 9: Results of literature review for the Use Case III.

Literature review Use Case III	ID			CFCs				FCs																						
	V1 - L3 Public transport.	V4 - L1 New technologies	V4 - L2 New business models	Accessibility & spontaneity	Safety & Security	Social constraints	Weather & Topography	Public awareness	Sign-up & booking process	Membership cost	Spontaneity of accessing bike/dock	Proximity of docking station	Helmet issues	Travelling with children/Carrying things	Travel distance	Insufficient Infrastructure	Driver behaviour	Separate Infrastructure	Personal safety	Harassment	Safe environment	Confidence/ experience	Traffic safety	Subjective norm	Socio-cultural constrain	Family responsibilities	Weather	Topography		
(Berger, Reback, & Palmatier, 2018)	•		•	•	•	•		•	•	•		•				•								•		•				
(Bikeplus, 2017)		•		•			•		•		•				•									•						•
(Bonham & Wilson, 2012)	•		•	•	•	•	•							•	•	•	•							•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Bopp, Child, & Campbell, 2014)	•			•	•	•	•		•					•	•	•			•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Campbell et al., 2016)	•	•	•	•	•		•					•			•	•								•						•
(Clark & Curl, 2016)		•	•	•	•			•		•		•								•										
(Cornish Jones, 2015)	•		•	•	•	•						•		•		•					•		•			•	•			
(Duncan et al., 2016)	•	•		•	•	•			•							•			•			•		•						
(Faghih-Imani et al., 2014)	•		•	•	•		•							•	•														•	
(Fishman et al., 2014)	•		•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•				•								•						
(Fishman et al., 2015)	•		•	•	•	•						•	•			•			•											
(Fishman, Washington, & Haworth, 2012)	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•			•	•		•					•				•	•	
(Howland et al., 2017)	•		•	•	•	•		•		•		•				•				•				•			•			
(Jin, Kong, Wu, & Sui, 2018)	•			•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•								•										
(Mateo-Babiano et al., 2017)	•		•	•	•	•		•			•	•			•	•			•			•		•			•			
(McNeil et al., 2017)	•	•	•	•	•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(McNeil et al., 2017a)	•	•	•	•	•	•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(McNeil et al., 2017b)	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(McNeil, Broach, & Dill, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Médard de Chardon, Caruso, & Thomas, 2017)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Murphy & Usher, 2015)	•			•	•	•	•	•					•	•	•	•	•						•	•						
(Stredwick, 2017)	•			•	•	•	•	•					•			•			•	•	•	•	•	•					•	
(Transport for London, 2011)				•	•	•	•	•		•						•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Zanotto, 2014)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•			•			•			•			•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•

Table 10: Results of literature review for the Use Case IV.

Literature review Use Case IV	ID		CFCs					FCs																		
	V3 Job Holders Today	V6 Job Holders Tomorrow	Socio-economic Conditions	Job Characteristics	Personal Circumstances	Individual Characteristics	Job Segregation	Policy/Legal	Demand Factors	Female facilities	Terms and Conditions	HR Policies	Negative attitude of male colleagues	Safety and security	Training Provision	Flexible Working	Caring/Parenting responsibilities	Economic Deprivation	Residential Location/Distance from Employment	Access to/ownership off resources	Health Status and Wellbeing	Adaptability, attitudes to work and travel to work	Demographic	Skills	Educational level/attainment	
(Anciaes, 2014)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•									
(Azad Foundation & University of Western Ontario, 2014)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•	•	•	•	•
(Batac et al., 2012)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•									
(Colgan, Johnstone, & Shaw, 1996)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•		•	•	•
(Corral & Isusi, 2007)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•								•	•
(Duchêne, 2011)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•									
(European Commission, 2011)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•				•
(European Commission, 2017)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•							•	•	•
(European Commission, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•								•	•
(French & Strachan, 2009)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•			•	•
(Giannelos et al., 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•				
(Hanlon, 1996)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•								•	•
(ILO International Labour Office, 2010)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•		•	•	•	•	•
(International Transport Workers, 2008)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•	•	•	•	•
(Keinert-Kisin, 2016)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Kurshitashvili & Isik, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•	•	•	•	•
(Kurshitashvili, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•	•	•	•	•
(McQuaid & Lindsay, 2005)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•
(Sicard, 2012)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•			•	•
(Tanis, 2018)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•	•	•	•	•
(Turnbull, 2013)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•		•	•		•	•		•	•
(Women in Rail, 2015)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•				•	•	•	•	•	•
International Transport Workers Federation (2014)	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•	•					•	•	•	•	•

Focus groups methodology

Table 11 The methodological requirements regarding the Focus Groups.

Information	Focus	Note
Location	4 Countries	France (offline), Ireland (offline), Poland (online), Spain (online).
Time	From M17-March 2020 to M25-November 2020.	Executed offline and online.
Documentation Method and Requirements	Audio recording, questionnaires in local language, final report in English.	<p>The entire focus group should be audio recorded with the permission of each participant and in accordance with local and national ethical research guidelines; the recorded material will be accessible only to the members of consortium.</p> <p>The topic guides for each focus group will be translated in each local language of the country of focus group.</p> <p>A report (in English) of main findings of each set of focus groups should be provided for the members of the consortium.</p>
Moderators	Maximum 2 per each focus group.	<p>Moderators should be familiar with the topics and technical aspects of DIAMOND project, and the context of focus group location.</p> <p>Having two moderators per session is to ensure the smooth progression and coverage of all the topics. Participation of at least one woman as moderator is suggested to ensure the comfort of participants to speak their mind.</p>
Topic	Use Cases I, II, III and IV.	Public Transport Infrastructures (Railways); (Emotion in) Autonomous Passenger Car; Vehicle (Bike) Sharing Fleet Management; Employment of Women in Rail Industry and Freight/CSR Protocols.
Participants	6 to Maximum 8 Women.	<p>For the Use Case I, II and III: different profiles of age, ethnic groups, income level, physical ability, employment status, care givers to children and/or to elderly, etc. Participants should be ordinary users of transport services and should not have any traumatic experience with transport service. It is preferred to randomly select the participants so they will not know each other and will feel free to speak their mind.</p> <p>For the Use Case IV: different profiles of age, ethnic groups, income level, physical ability, employment status, care givers to children, elderly, etc. and preferably different ranking positions (e.g., managers, seniors, juniors and administrative staff). The participants should be ordinary employees of transport sector and should not have any traumatic experience or history of legal dispute with their current or previous employer in the transport sector. It is preferred to randomly select the participants so they will not know each other and will feel free to speak their mind.</p>
Duration	2 Hours and 15 minutes.	<p>15 mins introduction of DIAMOND Project & Ethical Requirement Documents to be signed by the participants.</p> <p>30 min to complete the questionnaires. Questionnaires start with general profile questions, followed by their opinion regarding different fairness characteristics for each Use Case</p>

		<p>including but not limited to the ones identified through literature review. Responses will be ranked between 0 and 7, being 0 when users entirely disagree and 7 when users entirely agree.</p> <p>1:45 to 2 hours of free discussion with the participants on the topic of related Use Cases.</p> <p>In order to keep the coherency, the focus groups time should not take longer than 2 hours and 15 minutes.</p>
Total Number	8 Focus Groups.	Use Case I: France (G&V), Poland (ZTM), Spain (EURECAT and FGC); Use Case II: Spain (IBV); Use Case III: France (G&V); Use Case IV: France (G&V), Poland (ZTM), Spain (EURECAT and FGC).
Responsible Partner	TU Dublin.	<p>EURECAT, FGC and IBV (Barcelona, Spain);</p> <p>G&V (Paris, France);</p> <p>STIR and TU Dublin (Dublin, Ireland);</p> <p>ZTM (Warsaw, Poland).</p> <p>TU Dublin is the leading partner responsible for the design of the focus groups protocol and questionnaires.</p>

Question Set for Focus groups and Semi-structured Interviews

INITIAL SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC QUESTIONNAIRE

1. Where do you currently live?

- a. Spain
- b. France
- c. Italy
- d. United Kingdom
- e. Ireland
- f. Poland
- g. Serbia
- h. Other

Please specify if you wish _____

2. Do you consider yourself to live in a:

- a. Rural environment
- b. An urban environment
- c. Suburban environment

3. What age bracket are you?

- a. 18-24 years
- b. 25-34 years
- c. 35-44 years
- d. 45-54 years
- e. 55-64 years
- f. 65-74 years
- g. 75 years or more
- h. Prefer not to answer

4. What is the highest level of education you have achieved?

- a. Not formal education
- b. Primary education
- c. Lower secondary education
- d. Upper secondary education
- e. Post-secondary education
- f. Short-cycle tertiary education
- g. Degree
- h. Master
- i. Doctorate
- j. Prefer not to answer

5. What is your average yearly income?

- a. No income
- b. Less than 10,999 €
- c. 11,000-20,999 €
- d. 21,000-30,999 €
- e. 31,000-40,999 €
- f. 41,000-50,999 €
- g. 51,000-70,999 €
- h. More than 71,000 €
- i. Prefer not to answer

6. What is your household type?

- a. Married/Civil partnership-Heterosexual
- b. Married/Civil partnership-Same sex
- c. Cohabiting
- d. Lone parent
- e. Single
- f. Prefer not to say

7. In your family unit, do you live with any dependent person? (e.g. children, elderly, caring for disabled person).

- a. No
- b. Preschool age children (under 5 years)
- c. School age children (5-16 years)
- d. Elderly relative
- e. Disabled person

8. Do you travel on a weekly basis with a dependent person? (children, elderly, caring for disabled person).

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Prefer not to answer

9. What is your professional status?

- a. Paid employment
- b. Self-employed
- c. Non-paid work
- d. Student
- e. Keeping house/house maker Home maker
- f. Retired
- g. Unemployed (health reason)
- h. Unemployed (other reason)
- i. Other
- j. Prefer not to answer

10. If in employment do you

- a. Work full time (30 hours per week or more)
- b. Work part time (less than 30 hours per week)
- c. Other

11. Do you currently have an illness, impairment or disability which affects how you work or travel that has an expected duration of 12 months or more?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Prefer not to answer

11a. Does this health problem affect the kind of paid work that you might do?

- a. Yes
- b. No

11b. Does this health problem affect the amount of paid work that you might do?

- a. Yes
- b. No

11c. Does your health problem limit your use of transport?

- a. Yes
- b. No

12. What is your (main) citizenship?

13. With which ethnic group do you mostly identify with?

- a. White
- b. Mixed
- c. Asian
Please specify if you wish _____
- d. Chinese
- e. Black
- f. Other
Please specify if you wish-----
- g. Prefer not to answer

14. Which religious group do you most identify with?

- a. No religion
- b. Christian (all denominations)
- c. Muslim
- d. Hindu
- e. Buddhist
- f. Folk Religion
- g. Jewish
- h. Other
Please specify if you wish -----
- i. Prefer not to answer

15. Do you identify as:

- a. Male: A person observed male at birth who feels as a man
- b. Female: A person observed female at birth who feels as a woman
- c. Transsexual woman: A person observed as male at birth but feels as a woman
- d. Transsexual man: A person observed as female at birth but feels as a man
- e. Non-binary: A male or female person who does not define as a man or woman

f. Prefer not to answer

16. Do you consider yourself to be

- a. Heterosexual
- b. Homosexual
- c. Bisexual
- d. Other
Please specify if you wish-----
- e. Prefer not to answer

17. Have you ever been discriminated against using/working in transport for your appearance (aesthetics/the way you look)?

- a. Yes
- b. No

18. Are you currently working in transport?

- a. Yes
 - b. No
- Please answer Q18a to 18d
 Please go to Q19

18a. If yes, which transport sector do you work in?

- a. Policy making and public authority
- b. Education
- c. Research, innovation and technology
- d. On-site job in the city private transport
- e. Off-site job in the city private transport (driver)
- f. On-site job in the regional or international private transport
- g. Off-site job in the regional or international private transport (driver)
- h. On-site job in the public transport (planner, maintenance, administration...)
- i. Off-site job in the public transport (driver)
- j. Other

18b. What mode of transport do you work with?

- a. Car
- b. Truck
- c. Bus
- d. Bike
- e. Taxi
- f. Train
- g. Tram
- h. Maritime
- i. Aviation
- j. Multimodal
- k. Other (Logistics forwarder)

18c. What is your job title, please specify:

18d. What level is your role?

- a. Operator
- b. Supervisor/Foreman
- c. Manager
- d. Director
- e. Other

19. What is your usual method of travel to work

- a. Car, van, minibus, works van
- b. Motorbike, moped, scooter
- c. Bicycle
- d. Bus, coach, private bus
- e. Taxi
- f. Railway – train
- g. Underground train/light railway/tram
- h. Walk
- i. Other way of travelling

20. How long does it usually take you to travel from home to work (enter time in minutes).

QUESTION SET - USE CASE I

- Q1: Can you tell me briefly about yourself and how you use public transport?
- Q2. In general, why do you travel? What are your daily mobility needs?
- Q3. Can you tell me some of the reason why you choose to use/ not use public transport?
- Q4. In general, how easy is it for you to access public transport that meets your needs? For example price and cost?
- Q5. Do you have any suggestions to improve the current accessibility for you as a user?
- Q6. Can you tell me about the facilities provided at the local station you use and if they are suitable for all travellers, including those traveling with small children or toddlers, elderly and disabled travellers?
- Q7. In what ways could the current facilities be improved to enhance the experience of women users?
- Q8. As a woman travelling on public transport can you tell me about some of the specific concerns you have regarding safety and security whilst traveling on public transport?
- Q9. How would you improve personal safety and security for you as a user? Suggestions.
- Q10. What about the station you use, can you tell us about any specific safety concerns you have there
- Q11. Do you have any suggestions to improve safety concerns for women travelers?
- Q12. Are there any other issues related to women accessing and using public transport that you would like to discuss?

Additional Pandemic questions

- Can you tell me about any concerns you have using public transport during the pandemic?
- How satisfied have you been in general with protective measures put in place for users of public transport during the COVID-19 situation?
- How satisfied are you that the measures implemented were also effective in protecting transport staff working, i.e. train drivers, conductors etc.?
- In your opinion, how important is it that users of public transport are all required to wear a mask and use hand sanitizer on public transport?
- During the COVID-19 how satisfied have you been with the level and service of public transport in your area?

QUESTION SET - USE CASE II

- Q1 Presentation of the session and introduction of the group
 - Introduction of participants and objective of the session. (10 min.)
- Q2 Participants general experience linked with driving
 - Global discussion focused on personal experience regarding driving:
 - Aspects such as: enjoyment-stress, type of rides, travelling alone or with company, with whom?
- Q3 Analysis of current knowledge of autonomous car in an open way
 - Open discussion to leverage participants knowledge on autonomous cars (what they think cars can or cannot do? Already in the market? Have you tried any kind of automated car?)
- Q4 CAV Presentation with short video
 - What is and what an autonomous car can do and immersion on the session focusing in this type of car.
- Q5 Scenarios for different possible experiences lived inside the autonomous car that could generate rejection/acceptance
 - Participants will work individually and tell 2 positive and 2 negative scenarios that they imagine inside the CAV. Describe the scene and emotion that these generate in them (pos/neg).

- All post-it will be organized in two groups (positive and negative) and shared with all participants being read by the moderator.
- All situations will be ranked and if some of them have high frequency, they will be the ones discussed and considered for next block. (In the case there are so many different situations and it is not possible to make groups; each participant will vote for 1 and the three most voted situation (pos and neg) will be the ones used in the next stage to discuss more in-depth about CAV characteristics.
- Q6 CAV characteristics that can improve negative situations/scenarios and how to use it to enable/enhance the positive ones
 - Focusing in elected scenarios from positive and negative experiences in the CAV, participants debate globally among CAV characteristics they demand, and how they imagine the CAV should act in order to help them in these situations.
- Q7 CAV use description
 - Participants work individually (can be text, supported with sketching drawings or painting) to describe one typical use of CAV that they could do in their daily life.
 - The description should include details of aspects that could happen or be present in the ride.
- Q8 Assessment of CAV acceptance. (5 min)
 - To wrap up up, ask in a quantitative way (Likert 1-7): acceptance of CAV, likeliness to accept CAV in the near future (5 or 10 years)
 - Likes and Dislikes in general terms

QUESTION SET - USE CASE III

Scope of exercise 1: Introduction and bike sharing experience

- Q1. Can you briefly tell me about yourself and how you use Bike sharing services?
- Q1.1. General cycling and bike sharing experience
- Q1.2. Have you experienced any problems or difficulties using the services?

Scope of exercise 2: characteristics of Bike sharing services

Elicit key variables to determine actionable fairness characteristics for female users of bike sharing services and cycling.

- Q2.1. In your opinion what should be the characteristics of bikes sharing services for females?
- Q2.2. In your opinion what are the key factors/characteristics that would indicate that a shared bike service is providing fair access to female users?
- Q2.3. What are the key indicators you would recommend to verify the characteristics in Q2.2?
- Q2.4 Please rank the indicators in Q2.3 in order of importance

Scope of exercise 3: NEEDS

Elicit Key needs for female users of shared bike services

- Q3.1. In your opinion what are the key needs in respect to fairness for female users of shared bike services?

Scope of exercise 4: BARRIERS

Elicit key barriers for female users of shared bike services

- Q4.1 In your opinion what are the key barriers to real Inclusiveness for women users of shared bike services?
- Q4.2 What are the key verifiable observable indicators or data you would associate to the barriers in Q4.1?

Scope of exercise 5: grouping key characteristics of Inclusiveness with female bike sharing needs, and barriers

Link each key *characteristic* of Fairness and Inclusiveness with key needs and *barriers* for female users of shared bike services

- Q5.1. Link the characteristics identified for Inclusiveness with a representative need and related barriers for women users of shared bike services?
- Q5.2. If useful refer the links created to concrete scenarios.
- Q5.3 In your experience, are current bike sharing services successful in respect to inclusiveness for female users?

Scope of exercise 6: validation of the hierarchical tree

Validate, add or delete the different fairness characteristics gathered from the literature review analysis

- Q6.1 Do you consider there is any characteristic missing or any that should not be included in the next list to make a fairness bike sharing transport system?
- Q6.2 Taking into consideration next picture, do you consider these are the most appropriate groups of characteristics to increase the percentage of women sharing vehicle (bike) fleets?
- Q6.3 In case you have changed or added any new characteristic, where should it be grouped?
- Q6.4 By 2030, which factors do you consider could have influence in the future bike sharing?

QUESTION SET - USE CASE IV

- Q1. Which transport sector do you work in?
- Q2. Can you tell me about your role, what this involves and what level this is?

Capacity to meet required needs

- Q3. Can you tell me about the ways in which your company ensure equal access to job vacancies for men and women?
- Q4. Can you tell me about any social and/or local cultural barriers that you face being a woman working in the transport industry?
- Q5. Can you tell us about the main factors that have influenced your experience of fairness in working in the sector?
- Q6. Can you tell me how your company actively looks to retain women employees in the organization?
- Q7. In your opinion what would fairness for female employees in the transport services look like?

Safety and Security

- Q8. In what ways does your company promote a safe and secure working environment for women? Is this in any way different from what they do for male employees?

Accessibility

- Q9. Can you tell us about any specific barriers you have faced in relation to your employment as a woman in the transport sector?

(If participant is a male, please adjust question to suit ie employment for women)

- Q10. Can you tell us about any specific support you have received in relation to being a woman employed in the transport sector?

(If participant is a male, please adjust question to suit ie for women)

- Q11. In your experience are current employment practices successful in respect to fairness for women employees in the/your transport sector?
- Q12. Is there anything else you would like to highlight that we have not already discussed regarding women as employees in the transport sector?

Additional COVID Questions

- During COVID did you work remotely or continue to work in your usual location?
- Can you tell us about the key challenges you faced by working in your usual location?
- Can you tell us about the key challenges you faced working from home?
- How did your organisation support you either working from home or your usual location?
- What could your organisation have done to support you more/better?

Annex 2 – Data collection tools (Use Case I)

Structured data related to FGC stations (Use Case I)

Table 12 The list of retrieved structured open data and structured proprietary data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant metro and urban railway infrastructures managed by FGC.

Data	Data typology	Indicators	Data Source	Year
Structured Open Data	Preliminary Data	Boundaries of the Province of Barcelona	Cartographic Institute of Catalunya	2019
		Boundaries of the census section of the region of Catalunya	National Statistics Institute	2019
		Localization of the FGC metro and commuter railway stations	Barcelona's City Hall Data Service	2019
	Territorial Data	Localization of urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
		Localization of points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Socio-demographic Data	Total population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Age of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Gender of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Nationality of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
	Mobility Data	Localization of public transport services	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of road infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of parking facilities	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Railway Network Data	Localization of FGC lines	FGC	2019

		Localization of FGC tariff zones	FGC	2019
		Infrastructure characteristics of the stations (i.e. underground or above ground)	FGC	2019
		Characteristics of the territory surrounding the stations (city, town, village, countryside)	FGC	2019
Structured Proprietary Data	Travel Demand Data	Number of passengers per stations per year	FGC	2017-2018
		Number of passengers per stations per month	FGC	2017-2018
	Reliability of the service	Percentage of trains on time (no delays or delays of less than 3 minutes)	FGC	2019
		Operational hours and frequency of the service	FGC	2019
	Accessibility of the service	Discounted and flexible fares,	FGC	2019
		Pay-per-use payment options	FGC	2019
		Subscription or monthly payment options	FGC	2019
	Security of the transport infrastructures	Number and typology of incidents	FGC	2019
		Presence and visibility of CCTV system	FGC	2019
		Presence and visibility of SOS emergency phone	FGC	2019
		Presence of police and security personnel	FGC	2019

Thematic maps related to the FGC stations (Use Case I)

Figure 2 Localization of the stations managed by FGC within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 3 Localization of urban fabric on land use within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 4 Localization and density distribution of points of interest within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 5 Density distribution of total population per census section within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 6 Density distribution of female population per census section within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 7 Density distribution of elderly population per census section within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 8 Density distribution of foreigner population per census section within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 9 Localization and density distribution of public transport services within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 10 Localization of road infrastructures within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 11 Localization and density distribution of parking facilities within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Figure 12 Localization of the 10 selected stations managed by FGC within the territory of the Province of Barcelona (Spain).

Structured data related to ZTM stations (Use Case I)

Table 13 The list of retrieved structured open data and structured proprietary data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant metro and urban railway infrastructures managed by ZTM.

Data	Data typology	Indicators	Data Source	Year
Structured Open Data	Preliminary Data	Boundaries of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area	Website Warsaw Metropolis	2018
		Boundaries of the census section of the Mazowieckie Region	GIS Support Sp. z o.o.	2011
		Localization of the ZTM metro and commuter railway stations	GTFS Data Exchange	2019
	Territorial Data	Localization of urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
		Localization of points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Socio-demographic Data	Total population per census section	National Statistical Office	2011
		Age of population per census section	National Statistical Office	2011
		Gender of population per census section	National Statistical Office	2011
	Mobility Data	Localization of public transport services	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of road infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of parking facilities	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Railway Network Data	Localization of ZTM lines	ZTM	2019
		Localization of ZTM tariff zones	ZTM	2019
		Infrastructure characteristics of the	ZTM	2019

		stations (i.e. underground or above ground)		
		Characteristics of the territory surrounding the stations (city, town, village, countryside)	ZTM	2019
Structured Proprietary Data	Travel Demand Data	Number of passengers per stations per year	ZTM	2019
		Number of passengers per stations per month	ZTM	2019
	Reliability of the service	Percentage of trains on time (no delays or delays of less than 3 minutes)	ZTM	2019
		Operational hours and frequency of the service	ZTM	2019
	Accessibility of the service	Discounted and flexible fares,	ZTM	2019
		Pay-per-use payment options	ZTM	2019
		Subscription or monthly payment options	ZTM	2019
	Security of the transport infrastructures	Number and typology of incidents	ZTM	2019
		Presence and visibility of CCTV system	ZTM	2019
		Presence and visibility of SOS emergency phone	ZTM	2019
		Presence of police and security personnel	ZTM	2019

Thematic maps related to the ZTM stations (Use Case I)

Figure 13 Localization of the stations managed by ZTM within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 14 Localization of urban fabric on land use within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 15 Localization and density distribution of points of interest within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 16 Localization and density distribution of total population within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 17 Localization and density distribution of female population within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 18 Localization and density distribution of elderly population within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 19 Localization and density distribution of foreign population within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 20 Localization and density distribution of road infrastructures within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 21 Localization and density distribution of parking facilities within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Figure 22 Localization of the 10 selected stations managed by ZTM within the territory of the Warsaw Metropolitan Area (Poland).

Results of Structured Open Data analysis (Use Case 1)

Short List FGC stations	Metro Line	Urban Railway Line	Tariff Zone	Network Branch	Station Characteristics	Territory Characteristics	HQ		LQ	
							TDI	SDDI	TDI	SDDI
Sarrià	L6/L12	S1/S2/S5/S6/S7	I	Línia Barcelona-Vallès	Underground	City	•	•		
Pàdua	L7		I	Línia Barcelona-Vallès	Underground	City	•	•		
Pl. Espanya	L8	S3/S4/S8/S9/R5/R6/R60	I	Línia Llobregat-Anoia	Underground	City	•	•		
Sant Cugat		S1/S2/S5/S6/S7	2C	Línia Barcelona-Vallès	Above-ground	Town	•	•		
Can Ros		S3/S4/S8/S9/R5/R6	2B	Línia Llobregat-Anoia	Above-ground	Town	•	•		
Sant Joan		S2/S6	2C	Línia Barcelona-Vallès	Above-ground	Village			•	•
Igualada		R6/R60	6B	Línia Llobregat-Anoia	Above-ground	Town			•	•
El Palau		S4/S8/R5/R6	2B	Línia Llobregat-Anoia	Above-ground	Village			•	•
Martorell Enllac		S4/S8/R5/R6	3B	Línia Llobregat-Anoia	Above-ground	Town			•	•
Castellbell i el Vilar		R5	5E	Línia Llobregat-Anoia	Above-ground	Village			•	•

Short List ZTM stations	Metro Lines	Urban Railway Lines	Tariff Zone	Station Characteristics	Territory Characteristics	HQ TDI	HQ SDDI	HQ MDI	LQ TDI	LQ SDDI	LQ MDI
Ratusz Arsenal	M1		1	Underground	City	•	•	•			
Zabki		R60	2	Above-ground	Town	•	•	•			
Stoklosy	M1		1	Underground	Town	•	•	•			
Plac Wilsona	M1		1	Underground	City	•	•	•			
Warszawa Pludy		S3/S9/R9/R90/RL	1	Above-ground	Town				•	•	
Warszawa Zacisze - Wilno		R60	1	Above-ground	City				•	•	
Zalesie Górne		R8/RE8	2	Above-ground	Countryside				•	•	
Plochocin		R3/RE3	2	Above-ground	Village				•	•	
Warszawa Wesola		S2/R2/RE2	1	Above-ground	Village				•	•	

Figure 23 Results of Structured Open Data analysis for selecting 20 relevant stations (in total) managed by FGC and ZTM.

Observations checklist (Use Case 1)

SURROUNDING AREA (400 m)								
CFCs	FCs	IPs		SURROUNDING AREA			COMMENTS	
Accessibility of the Service	Service Availability & Efficiency	1	Are there alternative shared mobility services for last mile connections (e.g. bike, scooter and car sharing)?	Yes	No	N/A		
		2	Are there on-demand transport services including taxi and paratransit?	Yes	No	N/A		
Design of the Infrastructure	Universal Design	3	Are the drop-off and pick-up points safe and easily accessible?	Yes	No	N/A		
		4	Are the pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations safe and step free?	Yes	No	N/A		
		5a	How adequate is the lighting in the surrounding area of stations? (AM, natural lighting)	4	3	2	1	N/A
		5b	How adequate is the lighting in the surrounding area of stations? (PM, artificial lighting)	4	3	2	1	N/A
	Furniture & Facilities	6	Are there car and moto public parking places?	Yes	No	N/A		
		7	Are there bicycles storage facilities and bicycles racks?	Yes	No	N/A		
		8	Are the pedestrian routes between transit modes weather protected? (where applicable)	Yes	No	N/A		
		9	Are the waiting areas for buses, taxis, etc sheltered?	Yes	No	N/A		
Safety and Security	Harassment and Pickpocketing	10	Are there police and security personnel including women police? (to be a deterrent for perpetrators)	Yes	No	N/A		
		11a	How is the level of visibility of the surrounding area of the station? (AM, natural lighting)	4	3	2	1	N/A
		11b	How is the level of visibility of the surrounding area of the station? (PM, artificial lighting)	4	3	2	1	N/A

STATION - CONCOURSE LEVEL							
CFCs	FCs	IPs	CONCOURSE LEVEL			COMMENTS	
Accessibility of the Service	Service Availability & Efficiency	12	Are there services available within the transport infrastructure (e.g. shop, pharmacy, newsstand)?	Yes	No	N/A	
	Travel and Way finding Information Provision	13a	Are the travel updates through video announcements clear and timely?	Yes	No	N/A	
		13b	Are the travel updates through video announcements provided in multiple languages?	Yes	No	N/A	
		14a	Are the travel updates through audible announcements clear and timely?	Yes	No	N/A	
		14b	Are the travel updates through audible announcements provided in multiple languages?	Yes	No	N/A	
		15	Are the timetable and network map user friendly, intuitive and easily understandable?	Yes	No	N/A	
		16	Are there information points, enquiry desks, help desks, security desks?	Yes	No	N/A	
		17	Are there vertical and horizontal signposting for easy wayfinding?	Yes	No	N/A	
		18	Are there information regarding positive environmental contribution?	Yes	No	N/A	
	Ticketing Options & Fares	19	Are there electronic ticket and flexible payment methods using cash, card, smartphones and mobile apps?	Yes	No	N/A	
		20	Are there ATMs, ticket machines, ticket office and alternative sale points?	Yes	No	N/A	
		21	Are there lift with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair?	Yes	No	N/A	
		22	Are there ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, strollers, luggage and wheelchair?	Yes	No	N/A	

Design of the Infrastructure	Universal Design	23	Are there tactile surfaces to provide wayfinding information to people with reduced visual capabilities?	Yes	No	N/A		
		24	Are there signposting with bright colour contrasting and large font to help people with visual impairment?	Yes	No	N/A		
		25a	Are the ticket machines positioned at convenient height for a wide variety of users?	Yes	No	N/A		
		25b	Are the wayfinding info positioned at convenient height for a wide variety of users?	Yes	No	N/A		
		26	Are there fare gates to accommodate a wide variety of users?	Yes	No	N/A		
		27a	How adequate is the lighting in the stations? (AM, natural lighting)	4	3	2	1	N/A
		27b	How adequate is the lighting in the stations? (PM, artificial lighting)	4	3	2	1	N/A
	Cleanliness & Maintenance	28	Is the environment clean and hygienic?	Yes	No	N/A		
		29a	Are there waste baskets?	Yes	No	N/A		
		29b	Are there waste recycling baskets?	Yes	No	N/A		
		30	Are there deterioration, graffiti and vandalism?	Yes	No	N/A		
	Furniture & Facilities	31	Are there separated toilets for women?	Yes	No	N/A		
		32	Are there waiting areas with seating arrangements?	Yes	No	N/A		
		33	Are there baby changing facilities in both men and women toilets?	Yes	No	N/A		
		34	Are there breastfeeding facilities?	Yes	No	N/A		
35		Are there vending machines?	Yes	No	N/A			

		36	Are there left luggage and lost property offices?	Yes	No	N/A	
		37	Is there Wi-Fi or 3G/4G connection?	Yes	No	N/A	
Safety and Security	Harassment and Pickpocketing	38	Is the CCTV system available and visible?	Yes	No	N/A	
		39	Are there SOS emergency phones?	Yes	No	N/A	
		40	Are there police and security personnel including women police? (to be a deterrent for perpetrators)	Yes	No	N/A	
		41	Are there complaint Information in case of violations to personal safety?	Yes	No	N/A	
		42	Are there hospitality rooms where to ask for help in case of aggression or need?	Yes	No	N/A	
		43	Are there advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicising helpline numbers?	Yes	No	N/A	

STATION - PLATFORM LEVEL								
CFCs	FCs	IPs		PLATFORM LEVEL		COMMENTS		
	Travel and Way finding Information Provision	44a	Are the travel updates through video announcements clear and timely?	Yes	No	N/A		
		44b	Are the travel updates through video announcements provided in multiple languages?	Yes	No	N/A		
		45a	Are the travel updates through audible announcements clear and timely?	Yes	No	N/A		
		45b	Are the travel updates through audible announcements provided in multiple languages?	Yes	No	N/A		
		46	Are the timetable and network map user friendly, intuitive and easily understandable?	Yes	No	N/A		
		47	Are there vertical and horizontal signposting for easy wayfinding?	Yes	No	N/A		
Design of the	Universal Design	48	Are there lift with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair?	Yes	No	N/A		
		49	Are there ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, strollers, luggage and wheelchair?	Yes	No	N/A		
		50	Are there tactile surfaces to provide wayfinding information to people with reduced visual capabilities?	Yes	No	N/A		
		51	Are there signposting with bright colour contrasting and large font to help people with visual impairment?	Yes	No	N/A		
		52b	Are the wayfinding info positioned at convenient height for a wide variety of users?	Yes	No	N/A		
		53a	How adequate is the lighting in the stations? (AM, natural lighting)	4	3	2	1	N/A
		53b	How adequate is the lighting in the stations? (PM, artificial lighting)	4	3	2	1	N/A

Infrastructure	Cleanliness & Maintenance	54	Is the environment clean and hygienic?	Yes	No	N/A	
		55a	Are there waste baskets?	Yes	No	N/A	
		55b	Are there waste recycling baskets?	Yes	No	N/A	
		56	Are there deterioration, graffiti and vandalism?	Yes	No	N/A	
		57	Are there waiting areas with seating arrangements?	Yes	No	N/A	
		58	Are there vending machines?	Yes	No	N/A	
		59	Is there Wi-Fi or 3G/4G connection?	Yes	No	N/A	
Safety and Security	Harassment and Pickpocketing	60	Is the CCTV system available and visible?	Yes	No	N/A	
		61	Are there SOS emergency phones?	Yes	No	N/A	
		62	Are there police and security personnel including women police? (to be a deterrent for perpetrators)	Yes	No	N/A	

CARRIAGE							
CFCs	FCs	IPs		CARRIAGE			COMMENTS
Accessibility of the Service	Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision	63a	Are the travel updates through video announcements clear and timely?	Yes	No	N/A	
		63b	Are the travel updates through video announcements provided in multiple languages?	Yes	No	N/A	
		64a	Are the travel updates through audible announcements clear and timely?	Yes	No	N/A	
		64b	Are the travel updates through audible announcements provided in multiple languages?	Yes	No	N/A	
		65	Are the timetable and network map user friendly, intuitive and easily understandable?	Yes	No	N/A	
Design of the Infrastructure	Universal Design	66	Are there bright colour handrail to help people with visual impairment to identify support quickly?	Yes	No	N/A	
		67	Is access to trains with appropriate height steps or step-free?	Yes	No	N/A	
		68	Are handles suited at convenient height for all users or vertical grab bars?	Yes	No	N/A	
	Cleanliness & Maintenance	69	Is the environment clean and hygienic?	Yes	No	N/A	
		70	Are there deterioration, graffiti and vandalism?	Yes	No	N/A	
	Furniture & Facilities	71	Are there allocated seats to pregnant women, parents with young children and elderly?	Yes	No	N/A	
72		Is there Wi-Fi or 3G/4G connection?	Yes	No	N/A		
Safety and Security	Harassment and Pickpocketing	73	Is the CCTV system available and visible?	Yes	No	N/A	
		74	Are there SOS emergency phones?	Yes	No	N/A	
		75	Are there police and security personnel including women police? (to be a deterrent for perpetrators)	Yes	No	N/A	

Overcrowding and Emergency Situations	76	Is there improved ventilation and air-conditioning?	Yes	No	N/A	
	77	Is there improved layout of seating? (longitudinal seating allows more privacy)	Yes	No	N/A	

Figure 24 Observation checklist for the Use Case 1.

UESI Questionnaires (Use Case I)

The aim of this survey is to evaluate fairness criteria of the railway system. The purpose is to compare and evaluate fairness criteria to increase railway usage. Your data will not be passed on to any third-party companies unless there is a legal obligation to do so. Participation in this study is entirely voluntary and your replies will remain anonymous. As a participant, you can stop your participation at any time or refuse the use of your data without giving reason.

By filling out this survey you are giving us permission to use your replies. For more information on the ethical permissions for this study please see (insert web address for long description of ethics information).

This questionnaire is asking about one specific station.

Please select a station from the following list and answer our questions thinking about this station:

For the questions below, select the responds that you feel best suits/agree with statement

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither nor Disagree	Agree	Somewhat Agree	Strongly Agree
It is easy to get to where I want to go using this public transport service	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The frequency (number of trains) and service efficiency (being on time) at this station is adequate for my needs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Operational hours (starting and ending hours) are sufficient to meet my travel needs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am pleased with the provided travel information at the railway station	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The availability of travel information and directions (e.g. maps, announcements and video messages in and around stations.) at this station meet my travel needs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am satisfied with travel ticketing, timetabling and route planning services available on a smartphone app or online	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am satisfied that all services, exits, and platforms are clearly signposted	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of work commute and other trips	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Public transport fulfils my daily travel requirements in terms of time, price, security	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I can easily travel to my workplace using public transport, if this applies to you	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Fare discounts and ticket options are more affordable and better value for money than traveling by private car	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Do you have a chronic illness (including mental illness) or physical, learning or sensory disability which affects your capacity to use PUBLIC TRANSPORT?

- Yes
 No

If Yes, please specify or describe

How often do you travel on public transport with?

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Very Often
A pram or pushchair	1	2	3	4	5
Children under 5	1	2	3	4	5
School age children	1	2	3	4	5
With your own wheelchair or mobility aid	1	2	3	4	5
With someone who uses a wheelchair or mobility aid	1	2	3	4	5
Many shopping bags, equipment or luggage	1	2	3	4	5

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Disagree/agree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Access within and around the station suit the needs of people with varying abilities (stairs, lifts, rail etc)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
There is adequate lighting in the station and the area around the station.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The cleanliness and maintenance of the environment (station and the train) are adequate.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Facilities such as seating, backrests and restrooms are adequate and convenient for all genders and abilities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
The facility and service availability within the station is appropriate (seating area, bar, pharmacy, ATMs)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
There are quiet or private facilities available to parents for infant feeding if they wish to avail of them.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I feel comfortable with the air-conditioning (temperature, ventilation, humidity) at stations and in carriages.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I feel comfortable with the personal space available to me at stations and in carriages.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I can easily get to my destination from the station by walking or using other means of transport.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
At all times of the day, there are safe and easily accessible parking, drop-off and pick-up points nearby for all private vehicles.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
When arriving at or leaving the station I feel safe at any time of the day.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Within the station I feel that my belongings and I are safe at any time of the day.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
There are enough CCTV systems and other security measures visible to make me feel safe.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
If needed, I am satisfied that I could get help or make a complaint straight away (e.g. security staff, emergency phone number).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I am confident that I would be able to evacuate the station/train in an emergency situation (with help if necessary).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

The purpose of this study is to look at equity and fairness between different user groups.
To do this, we need to ask you questions about yourself and your household.

Your honest answers are very important to us. Everything that you tell us will be kept strictly confidential (secret).

<p>1. Where do you currently live?</p> <p>Spain <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>France <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Italy <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>United Kingdom <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Ireland <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Poland <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Serbia <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>2. Do you consider yourself to live in a:</p> <p>Rural environment <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>An urban environment <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Suburban environment <input type="checkbox"/></p>
Please specify if you wish-----	
<p>3. What age bracket are you?</p> <p>18-24 years <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>25-34 years <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>35-44 years <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>45-54 years <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>55-64 years <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>65-74 years <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>75 years or more <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>4. What is the highest level of education you have achieved?</p> <p>Not formal education <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Primary education <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Lower secondary education <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Upper secondary education <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Post-secondary education <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Short-cycle tertiary education <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Degree <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Master <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Doctorate <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>5. What is your average yearly income?</p> <p>No income <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Less than 10,999 € <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>11,000-20,999 € <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>21,000-30,999 € <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>31,000-40,999 € <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>41,000-50,999 € <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>51,000-70,999 € <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>More than 71,000 € <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>6. What is your household type?</p> <p>Married/Civil partnership-Heterosexual <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Married/Civil partnership-Same sex <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Cohabiting <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Lone parent <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Single <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to say <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>7. In your family unit, do you live with any dependent person? (e.g. children, elderly, caring for disabled person).</p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Preschool age children (under 5 years) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>School age children (5-16 years) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Elderly relative <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Disabled person <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>8. Do you travel on a weekly basis with a dependent person? (children, elderly, caring for disabled person).</p> <p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/> Prefer not to answer</p>
<p>9. What is your professional status?</p> <p>Paid employment <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Self-employed <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Non-paid work <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Student <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Keeping house/house maker Home maker <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Retired <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Unemployed (health reason) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Unemployed (other reason) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>10. If in employment do you</p> <p>Work full time (30 hours per week or more) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Work part time (less than 30 hours per week) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other <input type="checkbox"/></p>

If the answer in this question is unemployed, skip next question

<p>11. Do you currently have an illness, impairment or disability which affects how you work or travel that has an expected duration of 12 months or more?</p> <p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>11a. Does this health problem affect the kind of paid work that you might do?</p> <p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p><input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>11b. Does this health problem affect the amount of paid work that you might do?</p> <p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>11c. Does your health problem limit your use of transport?</p> <p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>12. What is your (main) citizenship?</p> <div style="border: 1px solid black; height: 30px; width: 100%;"></div>	<p>13. With which ethnic group do you mostly identify with?</p> <p>White <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Mixed <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Asian <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Chinese <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Black <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Please specify if you wish----- <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>14. Which religious group do you most identify with?</p> <p>No religion <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Christian (all denominations) <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Muslim <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Hindu <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Buddhist <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Folk Religion <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Jewish <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Please specify if you wish ----- <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>15. Do you identify as:</p> <p>Male: <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>A person assigned male at birth who feels as a man</p> <p>Female: <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>A person assigned female at birth who feels as a woman</p> <p>Transsexual woman: <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>A person assigned as male at birth but feels as a woman</p> <p>Transsexual man: <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>A person assigned as female at birth but feels as a man</p> <p>Non-binary: <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>A person who does not define oneself as a man or woman</p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>
<p>16. Do you consider yourself to be</p> <p>Heterosexual <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Homosexual <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Bisexual <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Please specify if you wish----- <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Prefer not to answer <input type="checkbox"/></p>	<p>17. Have you ever been discriminated against using/working in transport for your appearance (aesthetics/the way you look)?</p> <p>Yes <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>No <input type="checkbox"/></p>

18. Are you currently working in transport? Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Please answer Q18a to 18d No <input type="checkbox"/> Please go to Q19		18a. If yes, which transport sector do you work in? Policy making and public authority <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Research, innovation and technology <input type="checkbox"/> On-site job in the city private transport (planner, maintenance, administration...) <input type="checkbox"/> Off-site job in the city private transport (driver) <input type="checkbox"/> On-site job in the regional or international private transport (planner, maintenance, administration...) <input type="checkbox"/> Off-site job in the regional or international private transport (driver) <input type="checkbox"/> On-site job in the public transport (planner, maintenance, administration...) <input type="checkbox"/> Off-site job in the public transport (driver) <input type="checkbox"/> Other <input type="checkbox"/>	
18b. What mode of transport do you work with? Car <input type="checkbox"/> Truck <input type="checkbox"/> Bus <input type="checkbox"/> Bike <input type="checkbox"/> Taxi <input type="checkbox"/> Train <input type="checkbox"/> Tram <input type="checkbox"/> Maritime <input type="checkbox"/> Aviation <input type="checkbox"/> Multimodal <input type="checkbox"/> Other (Logistics forwarder) <input type="checkbox"/>		18c. What is your job title, please specify? <div style="border: 1px solid black; height: 40px; width: 100%;"></div>	
18d. What level is your role? Operator <input type="checkbox"/> Supervisor/Foreman <input type="checkbox"/> Manager <input type="checkbox"/> Director <input type="checkbox"/> Other, _____		19. What is your usual method of travel to work? Car, van, minibus, works van <input type="checkbox"/> Motorbike, moped, scooter <input type="checkbox"/> Bicycle <input type="checkbox"/> Bus, coach, private bus <input type="checkbox"/> Taxi <input type="checkbox"/> Railway – train <input type="checkbox"/> Underground train/light railway/tram <input type="checkbox"/> Walk <input type="checkbox"/> Other way of travelling <input type="checkbox"/>	
20. How long does it usually take you to travel from home to work (enter time in minutes 3hours = 180 minutes etc.) <div style="border: 1px solid black; height: 20px; width: 100%;"></div>			

Figure 25 Outline of the UESI questionnaires for the Use Case 1.

DAD Survey Questionnaires (Use Case I)

UC-I - PUBLIC TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE. RAILWAYS SURVEY

GOAL: TO INCREASE THE NUMBER OF PEOPLE USING RAILWAYS

(PUBLIC TRANSPORT)

Current situation (present):

The following questions are focused on the comparison of different aspects of railways currently; including issues related to accessibility of the service, the design of the infrastructure and safety and security. We are therefore asking you to help us identify what you believe to be the most important characteristics in relation to people's use of public transport and tell us briefly why they are important.

1. ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE RAILWAYS INFRASTRUCTURE.

A: 1.1. SERVICE AVAILABILITY AND EFFICIENCY - Metro and commuter rail infrastructure should be connected with other modes of transport, particularly in suburbs and during off-peak hours, in order to reach places of residence, work, childcare facilities and shops.

B: 1.2. INFORMATION PROVISION - Travel and route information provision includes the possibility to receive real-time information regarding the operation of the service and information for easy wayfinding.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 1.1. SERVICE AVAILABILITY AND EFFICIENCY - Metro and commuter rail infrastructure should be connected with other modes of transport, particularly in suburbs and during off-peak hours, in order to reach places of residence, work, childcare facilities and shops.

B: 1.3. TICKETING OPTIONS AND FARES - Public transport service provision should be based on cost recovery through taxation, flexible tickets and discounted fares.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 1.1. SERVICE AVAILABILITY AND EFFICIENCY - Metro and commuter rail infrastructure should be connected with other modes of transport (e.g. buses, trams, etc.), particularly in suburbs and during off-peak hours, in order to reach places of residence, work, childcare facilities and shops.

B: 1.4. TRAVEL PURPOSE - Different travel purposes (such as work, shopping, personal business, leisure, education, etc.) influences the public transport chosen.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. INFORMATION PROVISION - Travel and wayfinding information provision includes the possibility to receive real-time information regarding the operation of the service and information for easy route planning.

B: 1.3. TICKETING OPTIONS AND FARES - Public transport service provision should be based on cost recovery through taxation, flexible tickets and discounted fares.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. INFORMATION PROVISION - Travel and route information provision includes the possibility to receive real-time information regarding the operation of the service and information for easy route planning.

B: 1.4. TRAVEL PURPOSE - Different travel purposes (such as work, shopping, personal business, leisure, education, etc.) influences the choice for using public transport.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.3. TICKETING OPTIONS AND FARES - Public transport service provision should be based on cost recovery through taxation, flexible tickets and discounted fares.

B: 1.4. TRAVEL PURPOSE - Different travel purposes (such as work, shopping, personal business, leisure, education, etc.) influences the choice for using public transport.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

2. DESIGN OF THE INFRASTRUCTURE

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT DESIGN OF THE INFRASTRUCTURE CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE RAILWAYS INFRASTRUCTURE.

A: 2.1. UNIVERSAL DESIGN - Public transport infrastructures should be designed so that they can be accessed, understood and used to the greatest extent possible by all people regardless of their age, ability or disability.

B: 2.2. CLEANLINESS AND MAINTENANCE - Public transport infrastructures should be clean and characterised by routine monitoring and an atmosphere of order and lawfulness.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.1. UNIVERSAL DESIGN - Public transport infrastructures should be designed so that they can be accessed, understood and used to the greatest extent possible by all people regardless of their age, ability or disability.

B: 2.3. FURNITURE AND FACILITIES - Public transport infrastructures should provide furniture and facilities to accommodate the needs of all users and of the persons they accompany, notably children and elderly people.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.2. CLEANLINESS AND MAINTENANCE - Public transport infrastructures should be clean and characterised by routine monitoring and an atmosphere of order and lawfulness.

B: 2.3. FURNITURE AND FACILITIES - Public transport infrastructures should provide furniture and facilities to accommodate the needs of all users and of the persons they accompany, notably children and elderly people.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

3. SAFETY AND SECURITY

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT **SAFETY AND SECURITY** CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE RAILWAYS INFRASTRUCTURE.

A: 3.1. HARASSMENT AND PICKPOCKETING - Public transport operators should ensure that its passengers and employees are protected from criminal or antisocial acts, to protect equipment and belongings, and to ensure other violations do not occur.

B: 3.2. OVERCROWDING AND EMERGENCY SITUATIONS - Public transport operators should avoid overcrowding situations to ensure the comfort, safety and security of passengers considering also emergency situations.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

Future scenarios:

HYPERLOOP

Fuente: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/File:Hyperloop_all_cutaway.png

How do you rate your knowledge on the hyperloop?

- High
- Medium
- Low
- None

The hyperloop is one of the possible scenarios of the future. It has been said that by 2040 the first Hyperloop will connect two capital cities in the EU (Gheorghiu et al., 2017).

In your opinion what are the most important concepts which will support the future use of the hyperloop?

A: 1. ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE - Operational details and quality of service provided by the operators.

B: 2. DESIGN OF THE INFRASTRUCTURE - Architectural and design characteristics, facilities provided and maintenance of the infrastructure.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)				

A: 1. ACCESSIBILITY OF THE SERVICE - Operational details and quality of service provided by the operators.

B: 3. SAFETY AND SECURITY - Factors influencing the users' perception of personal safety and security while using railway infrastructures.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)				

A: 2. DESIGN OF THE INFRASTRUCTURE - Architectural and design characteristics, facilities provided and maintenance of the infrastructure.

B: 3. SAFETY AND SECURITY - Factors influencing the users' perception of personal safety and security while using railway infrastructures.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

Figure 26 Outline of the DAD survey questionnaires for the Use Case 1.

Annex 3 – Data collection tools (Use Case II)

Observations – experimental protocol (Use Case II)

DESCRIPTION OF THE SCENARIOS OF EVALUATION DURING THE SIMULATION

A total number of six scenarios have been implemented for the simulation evaluation of emotions. The following points contain the description of these scenarios. Some changes, in the detail of the scenarios, may occur as the detailed programming goes on for each of the scenarios due to the real and strict possibilities given by the simulation tool.

Scenario 1: Emotion in autonomous driving in favourable and unfavourable (weather) conditions

- **Main goal:** Measure the emotional state in autonomous driving in favorable and unfavorable (weather) conditions.
- **Automation mode:** L4+ without taking the control.
- **Goal of the trip:** No special purpose.
- **Experimental hypothesis:** There is a relation of the emotional state in autonomous driving with trust in this technology (and it would be influence if the situation is perceived more dangerous)
- **Type of road:** Highway.
- **Weather:** At the beginning is sunny and the rainy (or foggy).
- **Speed:** Adequate.
- **Relevant events:** When raining the road is wet and another car skids.

EMOTIONAL STATE MEASURES RELATED WITH FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS
FC2- Trust in technology: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Valence during AV driving in favourable weather conditions. - Arousal during AV driving in favourable weather conditions. - Valence during AV driving in unfavourable weather conditions. - Arousal during AV driving in unfavourable weather conditions.

Scenario 2: Sportive driving mode in time constrain scenario

- **Main goal:** Measure the emotional impact of sportive/aggressive driving to reach the goal trip with time constrain.
- **Automation mode:** L4+ without taking the control.
- **Goal of the trip:** Arrive on time to pick up the children for school.
- **Experimental hypothesis:** Impact of aggressive driving vs Smooth driving in time constrain scenario.
- **Type of road:** Intercity.
- **Weather:** Sunny.
- **Speed:** High.
- **Relevant events:** Aggressive take over and aggressive braking when another car suddenly brakes.

EMOTIONAL STATE MEASURES RELATED WITH FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS

FC6-Vehicle behaviour:

- Valence during AV sportive driving mode.
- Arousal during AV sportive driving mode.

Scenario 3: Comfort driving mode in time constrain scenario

- **Main goal:** Measure the emotional impact of comfort/smooth driving to reach the goal trip with time constrain.
- **Automation mode:** L4+ without taking the control.
- **Experimental hypothesis:** Impact of aggressive driving vs Smooth driving in time constrain scenario.
- **Goal of the trip:** arrive on time to pick up the children for school.
- **Type of road:** Intercity
- **Weather:** Sunny.
- **Speed:** Adequate.
- **Relevant events:** Overtaking of a car and braking when another car brakes (with enough distance).

EMOTIONAL STATE MEASURES RELATED WITH FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS

FC6-Vehicle behaviour:

- Valence during AV comfort driving mode.
- Arousal during AV comfort driving mode.

Scenario 4: Simultaneity

- **Main goal:** Measure the time doing secondary tasks and its emotional impact in different levels the mental workload due to external events.
- **Automation mode:** L4+ without taking the control.
- **Experimental hypothesis:** Impact of simultaneity in emotional state
- **Tipo of road:** Highway.
- **Weather:** Sunny.
- **Speed:** Adequate.
- **Relevant events:** Firstly, the traffic is fluid and later on there is a traffic jam with intermittent circulation.

EMOTIONAL STATE MEASURES RELATED WITH FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS

FC2-simultaneity:

- Valence during AV driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment.
- Arousal during AV driving when performing simultaneous tasks in comfortable external environment.

- Valence during AV driving when performing simultaneous tasks in enriched external environment.
- Arousal during AV driving when performing simultaneous tasks in enriched external environment.

<p>EFFICIENCY OF THE SIMULTANEOUS TASK</p>
--

<p>FC2-simultaneity:</p>

- | |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Time to perform the simultaneous task in comfortable external environment. - Time to perform the simultaneous task in comfortable enriched environment. |
|--|

Scenario 5: Failure

- **Main goal:** Measure the emotional impact when there is a system failure and the AV performs an emergency stop in a minimal risk condition.
- **Automation mode:** L4+ without taking the control.
- **Experimental hypothesis:** Impact of failure and emergency stop in emotional state.
- **Type of road:** Highway/intercity.
- **Weather:** Sunny.
- **Speed:** Adequate.
- **Relevant events:** The car informs of a failure. Performs an emergency stop in a minimal risk condition. In a few seconds the failure is solved and the car returns to automated driving.

<p>EMOTIONAL STATE MEASURES RELATED WITH FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS</p>

<p>FC2-trust:</p>

- | |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Valence when the AV car indicate a failure and must to stop. - Arousal when the AV car indicate a failure and must to stop.
 - Valence during the period the AV car is solving the failure - Arousal during the period the AV car is solving the failure |
|--|

Scenario 6: Dangerous driving situation

- **Main goal:** Measure the emotional impact when there is an event that affect personal safety perception.
- **Automation mode:** L4+ without taking the control.
- **Experimental hypothesis:** Impact of a dangerous situation for personal safety in emotional state.
- **Tipo of road:** Highway/intercity.
- **Weather:** Sunny.
- **Speed:** Adequate.
- **Relevant events:** Another car falls to stop at a red traffic light and the AV car has to do a sudden braking to avoid the collision.

<p>EMOTIONAL STATE MEASURES RELATED WITH FAIRNESS CHARACTERISTICS</p>

<p>FC2-trust:</p>

- | |
|--|
| <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Valence an event affects personal safety perception. - Arousal an event affects personal safety perception. |
|--|

Figure 27 Experimental design for the Use Case II.

UESI Questionnaires (Use Case II)

PROFILING QUESTIONNAIRE

The automobile industry is one of the industries that has evolved more in the last decades. If until a few years ago the effort was on safety related issues in the car, protecting driver and passengers in the event of an accident, the last decade has come with the introduction of driving assistance systems (maintain cruising speed, rear view camera for parking ...). The future in the next 10-20 years heads towards the autonomous car, a car in which there may be no steering wheel and passengers / drivers could forget about the driving task, as we know now.

This questionnaire focusses on three main aspects: personal demographics, driving experience and technology interest. Please answer it accurately as your answer, together with the answers of the others participants in the study, will be used to produce recommendations for the car industry in order to improve their products by answering to the needs and preferences of men and women.

This is a first step of the validation process in which you are taking place previous to the simulation of AVs driving. At the end of the simulation in our lab you will have to answer another questionnaire.

DRIVING AND CARS

1. Which one of the below is most applicable to you?

Tick the option corresponding to your answer

- I own a car
- I share a car with a family member
- I have a subscription to a car-sharing scheme

2. How many years of driving experience do you have?

Fill-in-the-blank with the number of years you have been driving. If you just obtained your driver's licence please indicate "0".

3. How frequently do you drive a car?

Tick the option corresponding to your answer

- Everyday
- Almost everyday
- A couple of times a week
- A couple of times a month
- Almost never
- Never

4. With which of the following sentences do you identify the most as a driver?

Tick the option corresponding to your answer

- In general, I drive, not out of choice but necessity (work, family displacements, etc.). It is something I don't like and I don't enjoy.
- To drive is something I do, not pleasure not pain.
- I like driving, but if another person offers to drive I prefer not driving myself.
- I love driving and I offer myself as a driver in situations with several potential drivers.

5. For which purpose(s) do you mostly use a car?

Tick as many options as fitting.

- Commuting to work / study
- Bringing my kids to school
- Accompanying to family relatives (children or older persons) to no leisure activities (doctor, to renew ID)
- Accompanying family relatives (children or older persons) to their social/leisure activities Shopping/doing the groceries
- Going to my social/leisure activities
- Going on holidays/vacations (distance less than 150 km)
- Going on holidays/vacations (distance more than 150 km)
- Other (please indicate): _____

6. My knowledge of AVs and autonomous driving is?

I don't know anything			I know everything			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

NOTE. This question will be asked also at the end of the validation

7. Which one of the following in-vehicle technologies do you have in your car and how frequently do you use them?

Tick as many options as fitting and indicate next to it how frequently you are using it.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
<input type="checkbox"/> In-car navigation (such as GPS units)	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Automatic parking	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Lane keep assistance	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Automatic emergency braking	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Adaptive Cruise Control	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Backup cameras and parking sensors	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Blind spot monitoring	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Speed monitoring and warning signals	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	1	2	3	4	5

8. Technology Interest

Please, indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the statements in the table below. Read each statement carefully, and using the rating scale (1-7) opposite each phrase, tick the appropriate number to describe how accurately each statement fits your judgement (e.g. 1 = Strongly disagree)

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
1- I try new products before my friends and neighbours	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2- I know more than others on latest new products	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3- I often purchase new technology products, even though they are expensive	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
4- I am excited by the possibilities offered by new technologies	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
5- I have little to no interest in new technology	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
6- I am excited by the possibility to drive in an AV	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7- I have little to no interest to use an AV	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
8- I would like to purchase an AV even though they might be expensive	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

NOTE. The last three questions in blue will be asked after the validation

9. Punctual and edgy

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
1- I consider myself as a punctual person	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
2- I consider myself as an edgy person	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

10. When I go to my work I make intermediate stops (leave the recycled rubbish in the bin, leave the kids in the school, visit a family relative who requires specific care, do the shopping...)

- Yes. Go to question 13 and 14.
- No. You have finished

11. Please select the frequency of these intermediate stops

- Everyday
- More than three times a week
- At least once a week
- Twice or three times a month
- At least once a month
- Almost never

12. Distribute in % the different tasks you perform during a complete day implying displacements

Activity	%
<input type="checkbox"/> Taking care or accompanying relative family to no leisure activities (school, doctor, bank..., could refer to children, older persons or people with disability).	
<input type="checkbox"/> Home purchase and supplies	
<input type="checkbox"/> Own leisure activities (I go to the gym)	
<input type="checkbox"/> I accompany my family relative to their leisure activities (gerontogymnasia, music lessons, games library...)	
<input type="checkbox"/> Go to my workplace or to study	
<input type="checkbox"/> Others	

UESI QUESTIONNAIRE

SCENARIO 1: Driving in favourable and unfavourable (weather) conditions

INTRODUCTION NOTE. After having travelled in an AV in different weather conditions value the following affirmations

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1. I am comfortable to travel by AV under favourable meteorological conditions. (FC2 - Trust in technology). 01.01.01							
2. I am comfortable to travel by AV under unfavourable meteorological conditions. (FC2 - Trust in technology). 01.01.02							

SCENARIO 2: Sportive driving in time constrain scenario

At the end of Scenario 2.

INTRODUCTION NOTE. Please assess the following sentences according to your feelings after this simulation session.

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
3. I feel "sportive conduction" is appropriate for AVs in most circumstances. (FC6 - Vehicle Behaviour).							
4. I feel "sportive conduction" is appropriate when I need to arrive on time. (FC6 - Vehicle Behaviour).							
5. I feel "sportive conduction" is exciting (FC6 - Vehicle Behaviour)							
6. I feel "sportive conduction" is safe (FC6 - Vehicle Behaviour)							

SCENARIO 3: Comfort driving in time constrain scenario

At the end of Scenario 3.

INTRODUCTION NOTE. Please assess the following sentences according to your feelings after this simulation session.

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
7. I feel "comfort conduction" is appropriate for AVs in most circumstances (FC6 - Vehicle Behaviour)							
8. I feel "comfort conduction" is boring (FC6 - Vehicle Behaviour)							
9. I feel "comfort conduction" is safe. (FC6 - Vehicle Behaviour)							

SCENARIO 4: Simultaneity

At the end of Scenario 4.

INTRODUCTION NOTE. Please assess the following sentence according to your feelings after this simulation session.

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree		
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
10. I value doing other tasks in my displacements in AV (FC2 - simultaneity).							

SCENARIO 5: Failure

At the end of Scenario 5.

INTRODUCTION NOTE. Please assess the following sentence according to your feelings after this simulation session.

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree		
11. I trust that AVs will provide adequate, effective, and responsive help under failure/error circumstances (FC2 - Trust in technology).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SCENARIO 6: Dangerous driving situation

At the end of Scenario 6.

INTRODUCTION NOTE. Please assess the following sentence according to your feelings after this simulation session.

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree		
32. Overall, AVs would help make journeys safer, reducing the impact of human errors of present cars. (FC1-Human errors).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Questions related to the scenarios at the end of all simulations

SCENARIO 1, favourable/unfavourable weather conditions

INTRODUCTION NOTE. Can you remember the simulation in which you were travelling under different weather conditions? Value the following sentences thinking in what you have felt during this scenario.

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree		
12. AVs are safer than conventional cars under any condition. (FC2 - Trust in technology).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
13. I trust the automotive industry to minimize potential risks of AVs to humans. (FC2 - Trust in technology).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
14. I will be happy to travel in a AVs without steering wheel. (FC2-Trust in Technology)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SCENARIOS 2 and 3 – Comfort vs sportive

INTRODUCTION NOTE. There have been two simulations with two different driving modes, one more sportive and one more comfortable. Value the following sentences thinking in what you have felt during these two scenarios.

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree		
15. I prefer a sportive driving on most of my AV displacements. (FC6 – Vehicle Behaviour)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
16. I prefer a comfort driving on most of my AV displacements. (FC6 – Vehicle Behaviour)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Scenario 4 simultaneity

INTRODUCTION NOTE. With AVs widespread used driving will be no more a need, and therefore, new opportunities for performing different tasks while travelling will be possible.

17. Which activities would you be interested in performing while travelling in your AVs? SPONTANEOUS ANSWER (FC2 - simultaneity).

<input type="checkbox"/> To relax/sleep/take a nap.
<input type="checkbox"/> To manage and organize personal agenda.
<input type="checkbox"/> To use an electronic device (mobile, laptop, tablet).
<input type="checkbox"/> To work in the car during my displacements
<input type="checkbox"/> To eat (finishing breakfast, having lunch, snacking...).

<input type="checkbox"/> To chat and interact without specific objective with other passengers.
<input type="checkbox"/> To care for other passengers (kids, elderly...).
<input type="checkbox"/> To perform activities requiring mental concentration (read a novel, sudoku,...).
<input type="checkbox"/> To perform simple handiworks (origamis, knitting, mending clothes,...).
<input type="checkbox"/> Final dressing and grooming (tie knot, cut nails, make-up).
<input type="checkbox"/> Other:

18. Assess your interest in performing the following activities while travelling in your AVs? **FORCED ANSWER – THE INTERVIEWER ASKS (FC2 - simultaneity).**

	Not interested at all				Fully interested			
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To relax/sleep/take a nap.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To manage and organize personal agenda.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To use an electronic device (mobile, laptop, tablet).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To work in the car during my displacements	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To eat (finishing breakfast, having lunch, snacking...).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To chat and interact without specific objective with other passengers.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To care for other passengers (kids, elderly...).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To perform activities requiring mental concentration (read a novel, sudoku,...).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To perform simple handiworks (origamis, knitting, mending clothes,...).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Final dressing and grooming (tie knot, cut nails, make-up).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Other:								

SCENARIO 5: Failure

INTRODUCTION NOTE. With AVs widespread used the way we understand driving and our daily displacements will be changed, the same will happen probably in the way we interact and communicate with AVs. Please answer the following questions focused on the interaction/communication with the AV considering what you have felt in the different simulations and what would you like the AVs b in 10- or 20-years' time.

32. Under **normal driving circumstances** I want to interact with the AVs by: **(FC6 – Human Machine Interface).**

Tick as many options as fitting and indicate next to it how frequently you are using it.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
<input type="checkbox"/> Voice commands	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Physical push buttons	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Text on display	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Text and images on display	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Text, voice and images on display	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	1	2	3	4	5

33. Under **emergency driving circumstances** I want to interact with the AVs by: **(FC6 – Human Machine Interface).**

Tick as many options as fitting and indicate next to it how frequently you are using it.

	Never	Rarely	Sometimes	Often	Always
<input type="checkbox"/> Voice commands	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Physical push buttons	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Text on display	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Text and images on display	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Text, voice and images on display	1	2	3	4	5
<input type="checkbox"/> Other (please indicate):	1	2	3	4	5

Final design/features related questions

Vehicle behaviour and control

The following questions are related to the behaviour of the AV and the degree of control you would like to keep, even if you are not controlling the steering wheel of the vehicle:

35. In an AV driving what I value the most is: (FC6 – Vehicle Behaviour).

Tick a maximum of three options

<input type="checkbox"/> A driving that maximises energy efficiency (reducing pollution impact)
<input type="checkbox"/> A driving that maximises the dynamic comfort of passengers (with smooth acceleration and deceleration)
<input type="checkbox"/> A driving with a strict fulfilment of traffic norms (example: not driving never under any situation through an amber traffic light)
<input type="checkbox"/> A driving that minimises the time to destination
<input type="checkbox"/> A driving that maximises the joy and excitement
<input type="checkbox"/> A driving that maximises the overall traffic efficiency

35. Which of the following characteristics are you willing to compromise in order to reduce the displacement time to reach your destination (FC6 – Vehicle Behaviour).

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree			
Energy efficiency	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Dynamic comfort of passengers	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Distance between vehicles to improve traffic flow and therefore reducing time to destination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Traffic flow to reduce my time to destination	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

36. AVs will take decisions independently, assess the importance of the different criteria used for these decisions by the Autonomous car. AVs should: (FC6 – Vehicle Behaviour).

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree			
Optimise traffic flow in order to improve overall circulation.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Optimise energy efficiency in order to reduce contamination.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Optimise the wellbeing of other road users (other cars, pedestrians, bikers...)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Reduce time of arrival.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Optimise the dynamic comfort of the passengers.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Facilitate the performance of other tasks (work).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Facilitate the interaction with other passengers.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

37. From the following aspects that can be controlled on the AV value the importance of keeping control of them. (FC6 – vehicle behaviour).

	Not important at all				Top important			
To select type of conduction (example: more sportive vs more comfort).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To select route to final destination.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To select variables related with ecological impact.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Speed	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Degree of fulfilment with traffic norms (example: not driving never under any situation through an amber traffic light, maintain always the safety distance...)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To select variables of interior comfort conditions.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
To select preferred interface interaction modes (voice, picture...).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

Design, space definition, accessibility,

38. Assess your agreement with the following assessments: (FC3 – Accessibility / space definition).

Tick a maximum of three options

<input type="checkbox"/> AVs should prioritize the mobility of elderly people and people with moderate mobility problems.
<input type="checkbox"/> AVs should prioritize transporting bulky loads (baggage, sports equipment, ...)
<input type="checkbox"/> AVs should prioritize kids' needs.
<input type="checkbox"/> AVs should prioritize pregnant women needs.
<input type="checkbox"/> AVs should prioritize oversized people need.
<input type="checkbox"/> AVs should prioritize the mobility of people with disability.
<input type="checkbox"/> AVs should prioritize the features making easier the weekly household shopping.
<input type="checkbox"/> Others...

39. Assess the importance of the following aspects of AVs shape: (FC6 - Vehicle shape).

	Not important at all				Top important			
Should be clearly differentiated from conventional car.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Should optimise aerodynamics of the vehicle to increase energy efficiency.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Should make easier the access of people with reduced mobility.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

40. After your experience during the validation, which adjective do you think better describe your concept of AV?

Tick a maximum of three options

<input type="checkbox"/> Modern
<input type="checkbox"/> Eco-friendly
<input type="checkbox"/> Smart
<input type="checkbox"/> Intelligent
<input type="checkbox"/> Cool
<input type="checkbox"/> Technological
<input type="checkbox"/> Expensive
<input type="checkbox"/> Other: _____

Interaction with the AV, information and training

42. Assess your agreement with the following sentences referred to the information required to interact with the AVs (FC6 – HMI):

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree			
Information provided by AV should be clear and easy to understand	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Information provided by the AVs should be kept to a minimum to reduce the number of disturbances	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I want detailed information of what is going on in my AV	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

43. Assess the importance of having easy access to different kind of information of AVs (FC6-HMI)

	Not important at all				Top important			
Information about the route like: time to destination, proposed path, traffic situation...	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Leisure and entertainment: radio stations, music, movies, videogames...	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Information about comfort parameters: climatic parameters inside the car.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Information about the driving characteristics: comfort or sportive mode	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

Other

44. Assess your agreement with the following sentences:

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree			
Training in AV driving will be easier than for conventional cars (FC1-Training).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I would be comfortable allowing my vehicle to transmit and share data to organisations that manage/maintain the roadway. (FC1 -Traffic management).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
The infrastructure where AVs move should be clearly and specifically identified and differentiated (FC6 - Infrastructure adaptation).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

SELECTION AND DISCARDING CRITERIA OF AVS

45. Assess the importance of the following potential benefits of AVs in order to purchase an AVs, given the fact that you not have any monetary limitation

	Not important at all				Top important			
AVs allow travelling people by car who has not the possibility to do so with conventional cars (elderly people, people with reduce mobility...) (FC6-Vehicule Shape)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
AVs will reduce the traffic flow (FC3 – Traffic efficiency)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
AVs will be faster in displacements (FC3 – Travel time)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
AVs will reduce the ecological impact (FC5 – Emissions)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
AVs are safer than conventional cars (FC1 – Human Errors)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
AVs allow performing different tasks while travelling (FC2-Simultaneity)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
AVs allow a greater degree of interaction with other passengers (FC2-Simultaneity)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

AV allow me not paying attention to parking (looking for a parking place and manoeuvring) (FC3 – Travel time)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

46. Assess the importance of the following potential inconvenient of AVs in order to do NOT purchase an AVs, even given the fact that you not have any monetary limitation

	Not important at all				Top important			
AVs will be too expensive (FC4 – Monetary cost)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I am suspicious of new technologies, I have serious doubts of their long-term reliability and performance. (FC3 – Trust in technology)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I feel AVs are unsafety in comparison to conventional cars (FC1 – Accident Rate)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I prefer to take my decisions. I don't like a machine taking decisions for me. (FC3 – Trust in technology)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
It would be very boring just "seating there" (FC2 - ?)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I think traffic flow is much fluid when persons take decisions (FC3 – Traffic efficiency)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
The whole system will be too complex (AVs and required infrastructure) (FC6 – Infrastructure)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	

Assess your agreement with the following statements:

	Strongly disagree				Strongly agree			
FC1. Safety&Security								
47. AVs will reduce accident rate. (FC1. Accident rate)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
48. AVs will increase traffic efficiency and management. (FC1. Traffic management / FC3. Traffic efficiency)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
FC2. Comfort								
49. I believe that I can depend and rely on AVs for my displacements. (FC2-Trust in Technology)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
50. AVs will allow passengers to perform different tasks while traveling. (FC2-Simultaneity).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
51. Travelling with an AV will be more boring in comparison to conventional cars.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
52. Travelling with an AV will be more pleasant in comparison to conventional cars.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
FC3. Mobility								
53. AVs would reduce the required time for my daily displacements. (FC3. Travel time).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
54. AVs will facilitate traffic flow. (FC3 – Congestion)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
55. I think AVs will facilitate the mobility of people who are not able to drive or to take a conventional car such as older people or people with disabilities. (FC3. Accessibility)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
FC4. Economy								
56. AVs will be more expensive than conventional cars. (FC4. Monetary cost)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
57. The overall cost (energy, maintenance, repairs) of AVs will be reduced compared to traditional cars. (FC4. Vehicle efficiency)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
FC5. Environment								
58. AVs will reduce emissions and pollution. (FC5. Emissions)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
59. AVs will reduce noise in our cities and roads. (FC5 - Noise).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
FC6. Design options								

60. For me is very important to keep a minimum sense of control of AVs even if I am not driving. (FC6 – vehicle behaviour).	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
--	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

61. **My knowledge of AVs and autonomous driving is?**

I don't know anything			I know everything			
1	2	3	4	5	6	7

62. **Technology Interest**

Please, indicate to what extent you agree or disagree with the statements in the table below. Read each statement carefully, and using the rating scale (1-7) opposite each phrase, tick the appropriate number to describe how accurately each statement fits your judgement (e.g. 1= Strongly disagree)

	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly agree
I am excited by the possibility to drive in an AV	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I have little to no interest to use an AV	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I would like to purchase an AV even though they might be expensive (FC4. Monetary cost)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Figure 28 Outline of the UESI questionnaires for the Use Case II.

DAD Survey Questionnaires (Use Case II)

UC-II - AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES SURVEY

GOAL: INCREASE THE ACCEPTANCE LEVEL OF AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES

Current situation (present):

The following questions are focused on the comparison of different aspects in relation to increasing the acceptance of autonomous vehicles up to level 3 of automation where the driver must still be prepared to intervene within some limited time when specified by the manufacturer or when called upon by the vehicle to do so. It includes issues related to safety and security, comfort, mobility, economy, environment and design options. We are therefore asking you to help us identify what you believe to be the most important characteristics in relation to increasing the acceptance of autonomous vehicles and tell us briefly why they are important.

1. SAFETY AND SECURITY

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT SAFETY AND SECURITY CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES.

A: 1.1. ACCIDENT RATE - Accidents which may lead to minor damages, moderate injuries and even deaths.

B: 1.2. HUMAN ERRORS – Human error of the person driving the car for example failing to look forward, and delayed discovery.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.1. ACCIDENT RATE - Accidents which may lead to minor damages, moderate injuries and even deaths.

B: 1.3. TRAINING - Additional training is provided to all existing drivers to ensure they are sufficiently skilled to drive an autonomous vehicle.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.1. ACCIDENT RATE - Accidents which may lead to minor damages, moderate and even deaths.

B: 1.4. TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT – Police and other agencies involved in traffic management are sufficiently trained to include legislative requirements for autonomous "driving", and are able to handle traffic when both automatic and non-automated vehicles coexist.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. HUMAN ERRORS – Human error of the person driving the car for example failing to look forward, and delayed discovery.

B: 1.3. TRAINING - Additional training is provided to all existing drivers to ensure they are sufficiently skilled to drive an autonomous vehicle.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. HUMAN ERRORS – Human error of the person driving the car for example failing to look forward, and delayed discovery.

B: 1.4. TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT - Police and other agencies involved in traffic management are sufficiently trained to include legislative requirements for autonomous “driving”, and are able to handle traffic when both automatic and non-automated vehicles coexist.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.3. TRAINING - Additional training is provided to all existing drivers to ensure they are sufficiently skilled to drive an autonomous vehicle.

B: 1.4. TRAFFIC MANAGEMENT - Police and other agencies involved in traffic management are sufficiently trained to include legislative requirements for autonomous “driving”, and are able to handle traffic when both automatic and non-automated vehicles coexist.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

2. COMFORT

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT COMFORT CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES.

A: 2.1. TRUST IN TECHNOLOGY - Driver trust in the capacity of the system to control the vehicle by itself.

B: 2.2. SIMULTANEITY - Automated vehicles enable their “passengers” to spend the travel time on doing other tasks like sending an email, reading a book...

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

3. MOBILITY

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT MOBILITY CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES.

A: 3.1. TRAFFIC EFFICIENCY - More vehicles can travel at the same time over a given area without congestion and loss of travel time.

B: 3.2. TRAVEL TIME - Time used in travelling from the origin to the destination is lower when using autonomous vehicles compared to non-autonomous vehicles system.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 3.1. TRAFFIC EFFICIENCY - More vehicles can travel at the same time over a given cross section without congestion and loss of travel time.

B: 3.3. CONGESTION - Reduction of traffic jams due to the connection of the car with the infrastructure. For example, the adaptation of car speeds so that the driver can go through the traffic light without stopping at the red light would contribute to the reduction of traffic jams.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 3.1. TRAFFIC EFFICIENCY - More vehicles can travel at the same time over a given cross section without congestion and loss of travel time.

B: 3.4. ACCESSIBILITY - Automated vehicles allow the inclusion in the transport system of people who does not drive much, respondents who are currently prevented from driving due to their physical condition, people that dislike driving, those living in more diffuse populations (i.e. rural and suburban locations).

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 3.2. TRAVEL TIME - Time used in travelling from the origin to the destination is lower when using autonomous vehicles compared to non-autonomous vehicles system.

B: 3.3. CONGESTION - Reduction of traffic jams due to the connection of the car with the infrastructure. For example, the adaptation of car speeds so that the driver can go through the traffic light without stopping at the red light would contribute to the reduction of traffic jams.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 3.2. TRAVEL TIME - Time used in travelling from the origin to the destination is lower when using autonomous vehicles compared to non-autonomous vehicles system.

B: 3.4. ACCESSIBILITY - Automated vehicles allow the inclusion in the transport system of people who does not drive much, respondents who are currently prevented from driving due to their physical condition, people that dislike driving, those living in more diffuse populations (i.e. rural and suburban locations).

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 3.3. CONGESTION - Reduction of traffic jams due to the connection of the car with the infrastructure. For example, the adaptation of car speeds so that the driver can go through the traffic light without stopping at the red light would contribute to the reduction of traffic jams.

B: 3.4. ACCESSIBILITY - Automated vehicles allow the inclusion in the transport system of people who does not drive much, respondents who are currently prevented from driving due to their physical condition, people that dislike driving, those living in more diffuse populations (i.e. rural and suburban locations).

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

4. ECONOMY

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT **ECONOMICAL** CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES.

A: 4.1. MONETARY COSTS - Costs related to fuel, new technologies, or the capital costs for these new vehicles.

B: 4.2. NON-MONETARY SAVINGS - Time saving, reducing environmental effects, or increasing traffic safety.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.1. MONETARY COSTS - - Costs related to fuel, new technologies, or the capital costs for these new vehicles.

B: 4.3. VEHICLE EFFICIENCY - Automated vehicles are more efficient in fuel consumption due to their control of the accelerator and brake pedals as well as by synchronising conflict points.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.2. NON-MONETARY SAVINGS - Time saving, reducing environmental effects, or increasing traffic safety.

B: 4.3. VEHICLE EFFICIENCY - Automated vehicles are more efficient in fuel consumption due to their control of the accelerator and brake pedals as well as by synchronising conflict points.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

5. ENVIRONMENT

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT **ENVIRONMENTAL** CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES.

A: 5.1. NOISE – Noise in automated vehicles is linked to how a smoother acceleration/deceleration and the optimization of the traffic flow will reduce vehicles' noise as well as the noise produced by road maintenance.

A: 5.2. EMISSIONS – This reduction of emissions (e.g. CO₂) is related to the reduction of fuel consumption due to optimized routing, smoother acceleration/deceleration, and traffic flow management.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 5.1. NOISE – Noise in automated vehicles is linked to how a smoother acceleration/deceleration and the optimization of the traffic flow will reduce vehicles' noise as well as the noise produced by road maintenance.

B: 5.3. PUBLIC HEALTH - Automated vehicles will increase the safety and reduce the air pollution which will affect the physical and mental health.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 5.2. EMISSIONS – This reduction of emissions (e.g. CO₂) is related to the reduction of fuel consumption due to optimized routing, smoother acceleration/deceleration, and traffic flow management.

B: 5.3. PUBLIC HEALTH - Automated vehicles will increase safety and reduce air pollution which will affect the physical and mental health.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

6. DESIGN OPTIONS

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT **DESIGN** CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES.

A: 6.1. INFRASTRUCTURE ADAPTATION - Marked lanes, specific road signs, or physical separation of tracks could support other traffic participants to understand the driving mode of the automated vehicles.

B: 6.2. VEHICLE SHAPE – The design of the vehicle should make it easy the differentiation of automated from non-automated vehicles as well as the vehicle's driving mode by the other drivers or people using the transport infrastructure. .

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 6.1. INFRASTRUCTURE ADAPTATION – Current internal road infrastructure being adapted to suit the separation of autonomous and non-autonomous vehicles.

B: 6.3. VEHICLE BEHAVIOUR – Autonomous vehicles are more predictable in their behaviour, have shorter reaction times, accelerations and decelerations are smoother and avoid inappropriate behaviours

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 6.1. INFRASTRUCTURE ADAPTATION - Current internal road infrastructure being adapted to suit the separation of autonomous and non-autonomous vehicles

B: 6.4. HUMAN MACHINE INTERFACE - The technology allows the driver to retrieve important information with one glance.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 6.2. VEHICLE SHAPE - The design of the vehicle should make it easy the differentiation of automated from non-automated vehicles as well as the vehicle's driving mode by the other drivers or people using the transport infrastructure.

B: 6.3. VEHICLE BEHAVIOUR - - Autonomous vehicles are more predictable in their behaviour, have shorter reaction times, accelerations and decelerations are smoother and avoid inappropriate behaviours.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 6.2. VEHICLE SHAPE - The design of the vehicle should make it easy the differentiation of automated from non-automated vehicles as well as the vehicle's driving mode by the other drivers or people using the transport infrastructure.

B: 6.4. HUMAN MACHINE INTERFACE - The technology allows the driver to retrieve important information with one glance.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 6.3. VEHICLE BEHAVIOUR - Autonomous vehicles are more predictable in their behaviour, have shorter reaction times, accelerations and decelerations are smoother and avoid inappropriate behaviours.

B: 6.4. HUMAN MACHINE INTERFACE - The technology allows the driver to retrieve important information with one glance.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

Future scenarios:

FULLY AUTOMATED VEHICLES

How do you rate your knowledge on fully automated vehicles?

- High
- Medium
- Low
- None

It has been said that by 2030 50% of passenger transport will be fully automated (Gheorghiu et al., 2017).

In your opinion, which factors will be more important for reaching this target?

A: 1. SAFETY AND SECURITY - People do not feel any additional risks while they are driving an autonomous vehicle.

B: 2. COMFORT - Feelings of wellness while driving their vehicle.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

A: 1. SAFETY AND SECURITY - People do not feel any additional risks while they are driving an autonomous vehicle.

B: 3. MOBILITY - Factors related to the levels of traffic during the travel.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

A: 1. SAFETY AND SECURITY - People do not feel any additional risks while they are driving an autonomous vehicle.

B: 4. ECONOMY – It is related to all those factors influencing on the economic decision of purchasing an autonomous vehicle, i.e. monetary costs (car maintenance, fuel, vehicle purchasing, new technologies), non-monetary improvements (e.g. time saving, increased safety, lower environmental impact) and vehicle efficiency (e.g. better traffic flows, smoother acceleration and deceleration).

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

A: 1. SAFETY AND SECURITY - People do not feel any additional risks while they are driving an autonomous vehicle.

B: 5. ENVIRONMENT – Environmental efficiency factors.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme

Why? (optional)

A: 1. SAFETY AND SECURITY - People do not feel any additional risks while they are driving an autonomous vehicle.

B: 6. DESIGN OPTIONS – Vehicle design is suited to infrastructure design adaptations.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

A: 2. COMFORT - Feelings of wellness while driving their vehicle.

B: 3. MOBILITY - Factors related to the levels of traffic during the travel.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

A: 2. COMFORT - Feelings of wellness experience while driving their vehicle.as above

B: 4. ECONOMY – It is related to all those factors influencing on the economic decision of purchasing an autonomous vehicle, i.e. monetary costs (car maintenance, fuel, vehicle purchasing, new technologies), non-monetary improvements (e.g. time saving, increased safety, lower environmental impact) and vehicle efficiency (e.g. better traffic flows, smoother acceleration and deceleration).

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

A: 2. COMFORT - Feelings of wellness experience while driving their vehicle.

B: 5. ENVIRONMENT – Environmental efficiency factors.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

A: 2. COMFORT - Feelings of wellness while driving their vehicle.

B: 6. DESIGN OPTIONS - Vehicle design is suited to infrastructure design adaptations.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)			

A: 3. MOBILITY - Factors related to the levels of traffic during the travel.

B: 4. ECONOMY – It is related to all those factors influencing on the economic decision of purchasing an autonomous vehicle, i.e. monetary costs (car maintenance, fuel, vehicle purchasing, new technologies), non-monetary improvements (e.g. time saving, increased safety, lower environmental impact) and vehicle efficiency (e.g. better traffic flows, smoother acceleration and deceleration).

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)				

A: 3. MOBILITY - Factors related to the levels of traffic during the travel.

B: 5. ENVIRONMENT - Environmental efficiency factors.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)				

A: 3. MOBILITY - Factors related to the levels of traffic during the travel.

B: 6. DESIGN OPTIONS - Vehicle design is suited to infrastructure design adaptations.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)				

A: 4. ECONOMY – It is related to all those factors influencing on the economic decision of purchasing an autonomous vehicle, i.e. monetary costs (car maintenance, fuel, vehicle purchasing, new technologies), non-monetary improvements (e.g. time saving, increased safety, lower environmental impact) and vehicle efficiency (e.g. better traffic flows, smoother acceleration and deceleration).

B: 5. ENVIRONMENT - Environmental efficiency factors.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)				

A: 4. ECONOMY – It is related to all those factors influencing on the economic decision of purchasing an autonomous vehicle, i.e. monetary costs (car maintenance, fuel, vehicle purchasing, new technologies), non-monetary improvements (e.g. time saving, increased safety, lower environmental impact) and vehicle efficiency (e.g. better traffic flows, smoother acceleration and deceleration).

B: 6. DESIGN OPTIONS - Vehicle design is suited to infrastructure design adaptations.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)				

A: 5. ENVIRONMENT - Environmental efficiency factors.

B: 6. DESIGN OPTIONS - Vehicle design is suited to infrastructure design adaptations.

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why? (optional)				

Figure 29 Outline of the DAD survey questionnaires for the Use Case II.

Annex 4 – Data collection tools (Use Case III)

Structured Data (Use Case III)

Table 14 The list of retrieved structured open data and structured proprietary data that were analysed and merged for the identification and characterization of a short list of relevant bike sharing docking stations managed by VELIB.

Data	Data typology	Indicators	Data Source	Year
Structured Open Data	Preliminary Data	Boundaries of the Paris Region (Petite Couronne)	Copernicus Land Monitoring Service	2012
		Boundaries of the census section of the Paris Region	National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies	2019
		Localization of the VELIB bike sharing docking stations	Open platform for French public data	2019
	Territorial Data	Localization of urban fabric on land use	Copernicus Land Monitoring	2012
		Localization of points of interest	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Socio-demographic Data	Total population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Age of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Gender of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
		Nationality of population per census section	National Statistics Institute	2011
	Mobility Data	Localization of public transport services	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of cycleway infrastructure	OpenStreetMap	2019
		Localization of parking facilities	OpenStreetMap	2019
	Bike Sharing Docking Stations Network Data	Docking stations capacity (No. bikes)	Open platform for French public data	2019

Structured Proprietary Data	Travel Demand Data	Number of users per docking stations per year	VELIB	2019
		Number of users per docking stations per month	VELIB	2019
		Origin/destination matrix of the users	VELIB	2019
		Average length of trips	VELIB	2019
		Average time duration of trips	VELIB	2019
	Accessibility and Spontaneity	Number of public campaigns on cycling in the past year	VELIB	2019
		Number of adverts on bike-sharing services in the past year	VELIB	2019
		Do you need any requirement for signing-up for membership?	VELIB	2019
		Type of requirement for signing-up for membership (credit/debit card, internet access, smartphone...)	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of cash payment members (if applicable)	VELIB	2019
		The entry cost of bike-sharing scheme (upfront cost)	VELIB	2019
		Rental charges above one hour	VELIB	2019
		Annual membership cost of the scheme	VELIB	2019
		Types of safety gear supplied by operator	VELIB	2019

		(e.g. Helmet, hi-vis vest, raincoat etc.)		
		Nature and type of insurance cover for bikes and users (i.e. damages, theft, accidents etc.) if available	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of docking stations at transport hubs	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of transport hubs with docking stations	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of low-income and minority neighbourhoods with docking stations	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of docking stations in low-income and minority neighbourhoods	VELIB	2019
		Number and Percentage of Bike-sharing stations in low-income and minority neighbourhoods	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of bikes with a child seat, trailers and carriages for carrying children and goods	VELIB	2019
		The number of practical cycling programs/training (how to cycle with children and goods) held in the past year.	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of docking stations with shelter	VELIB	2019

		Number and percentage of docking stations with toilet facilities	VELIB	2019
	Safety and Security	Percentage of bike network segregated from vehicular traffic	VELIB	2019
		Number of cycling training programmes organised in a year to educate cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road	VELIB	2019
		Number of public campaigns held to address harassment of cyclist in the past one year	VELIB	2019
		Number of public campaigns held to boost cyclists' confidence in the past one year	VELIB	2019
		Number and Percentage of docking stations with security devices (CCTV etc.)	VELIB	2019
		Number and Percentage of docking stations with CCTV	VELIB	2019
		Number and Percentage of bikes with well-functioning brakes, lights and reflectors etc.	VELIB	2019
		Number and Percentage of docking stations with information centres for users	VELIB	2019
		Speed limits on roads with cycle lanes (classified by road function)	VELIB	2019

		Percentage of roads with physically separated bike lanes from vehicular traffic	VELIB	2019
	Social Constrains	Number of campaigns targeted at low-income and minority groups/neighbourhoods to promote cycling as an acceptable form of transport	VELIB	2019
		Number of practical cycling training programmes	VELIB	2019
	Weather and Topography	Percentage of cycle network that is all-weather cycle friendly	VELIB	2019
		Number and percentage of electric bikes among bike fleet and at each docking station	VELIB	2019

Thematic maps related to the VELIB bike sharing docking stations

Figure 30 Localization of the docking stations managed by VELIB within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 31 Localization of urban fabric on land use within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 32 Localization and density distribution of points of interest within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 33 Density distribution of total population per census section within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 34 Density distribution of female population per census section within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 35 Density distribution of elderly population per census section within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 36 Density distribution of foreigner population per census section within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 37 Localization and density distribution of public transport services within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 38 Localization of cycleway infrastructures within the territory of the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Figure 39 Localization of the 20 selected docking stations managed by VELIB within the Metropolitan Area of Paris (France).

Observations – assessment checklist (Use Case III)

DIAMOND Use-case III Observation checklist

Name of Observer			
Objective of observation			
Docking station Address/location		<input type="checkbox"/> Residential	<input type="checkbox"/> Commercial
Description of docking station			
Date of observation			
Time of day			
Duration of Observation			

I. Accessibility and Spontaneity

Item	Influencing factor	Occurrence	Observations	
			Descriptive Notes	Reflective Notes
I.1	What is the minimum number of bikes recorded during the observation?			
I.2	What is the maximum number of bikes observed at the docking station?			
I.3	Number of other public modes of transport near the docking station			
I.4	Is it a low-income/minority neighbourhood?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
I.5	Number of docking stations in low-income and minority neighbourhoods			
I.6	How many vacant docks are currently available for use at the station?			
I.7	What number or percentage of the bikes have a child seat, child trailer or carriages for children?			
I.8	What number or percentage of the bikes have cargo trailers for carting goods or luggage?			
I.9	Is the docking station accessible for women with children and disability?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
I.10	Do you observe female users, or Does the station have female membership?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
I.11	Did you observe shortage of bikes during the observation period?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
I.12	Does the station have the following facilities?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Shelter <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Toilet facilities <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Female only Toilet <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No Changing facility <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
I.13	Is it a low-income/minority neighbourhood?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		

Item	Influencing factor	Occurrence	Observations	
			Descriptive Notes	Reflective Notes
I.14	Number of docking stations in low-income/minority neighbourhood			
I.15	Any additional observation worthy of mentioning			

2. Safety & Security

Item	Influencing factor	Occurrence	Observations	
			Descriptive Notes	Reflective Notes
2.1	Are there sufficient cycling infrastructure in the neighbourhood of the station?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
2.2	Do we have separate cycle infrastructure?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
2.3	Does the station have adequate lighting?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
2.4	Does the station have adequate security? (i.e. ... 1. CCTV 2. 3.	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
2.5	Are the cycle paths and lanes well illuminated at night?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
2.6	Is there a Do we have CCTV systems present and visible on the cycle network?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		

2.7	How safe are the cycle paths and lanes for cycling at night?	1. Very unsafe 2. Unsafe 3. Unsure 4. Safe 5. Very safe		
2.8	What is the speed limit on roads with cycle lanes?			
2.9	The number or % of users wearing hi-vis cycling clothing			
2.10	The number or % of road worthy bikes among the bike fleets (i.e. well-functioning brakes, lights etc)			
2.11	Are there roads with dedicated and enforced bike lanes	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
2.12	% of cycle lanes physically separated from vehicular traffic			

3. Social constraints

Item	Influencing factor	Occurrence	Observations	
			Descriptive Notes	Reflective Notes
3.1	Are there bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying things and carting cargo?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		

4. Weather & Topography

Item	Influencing factor	Occurrence	Observations	
			Descriptive Notes	Reflective Notes
4.1	Is the cycle network nearby the docking station weather cycle friendly?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
4.2	Availability of cycling raincoats for users	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		
4.3	What is the number or % of e-bikes among bike-share fleet?			

5. Other

Item	Influencing factor	Occurrence	Observations	
			Descriptive Notes	Reflective Notes
5.1	How many people by sex use the station?			
	Male			
	Female			
5.2	Approximate age band of users			
	<input type="checkbox"/> 18 -24			
	<input type="checkbox"/> 25-34			
	<input type="checkbox"/> 35-44			
	<input type="checkbox"/> 45-54			
	<input type="checkbox"/> 55-64			
	<input type="checkbox"/> 65-74			
	<input type="checkbox"/> >75			
5.3	Did you observe ethnic minority groups using bike-share?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		

Figure 40 Observation checklist for the Use Case III.

UESI questionnaires (Use Case III)

DIAMOND UESI Questionnaire Use Case III

SECTION A: DEMOGRAPHICS & GENERAL QUESTIONS

- 1. Residential Details. Where do you currently live?**
 - a. Spain
 - b. France
 - c. Italy
 - d. United Kingdom
 - e. Ireland
 - f. Poland
 - g. Serbia
 - h. Other

- 2. Do you consider yourself to live in:**
 - a. Rural environment
 - b. Urban environment
 - c. Suburban environment

- 3. What age bracket are you?**
 - a. 18-24 years
 - b. 25-34 years
 - c. 35-44 years
 - d. 45-54 years
 - e. 55-64 years
 - f. 65-74 years
 - g. >75 years
 - h. Prefer not to answer

- 4. What is the highest level of education you have achieved?**
 - a. Not formal education
 - b. Primary education
 - c. Lower secondary education
 - d. Upper secondary education
 - e. Post-secondary education
 - f. Short-cycle tertiary education
 - g. Degree
 - h. Master
 - i. Doctorate
 - j. Prefer not to answer

- 5. What is your average yearly income?**
 - a. No income
 - b. Less than 10,999 €
 - c. 11,000-20,999 €
 - d. 21,000-30,999 €
 - e. 31,000-40,999 €
 - f. 41,000-50,999 €
 - g. 51,000-70,999 €
 - h. >71,000 €
 - i. Prefer not to answer

- 6. What is your household type?**
 - a. Married/Civil partnership-Heterosexual
 - b. Married/Civil partnership-Same sex
 - c. Cohabiting
 - d. Lone parent
 - e. Single
 - f. Prefer not to say

7. In your family unit, do you live with any dependent person? (e.g. children, elderly, caring for disabled person).

- a. No
- b. Preschool age children (under 5 years)
- c. School age children (5-16 years)
- d. Elderly relative
- e. Disabled person

8. Do you travel on a weekly basis with a dependent person? (children, elderly, caring for disabled person).

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Prefer not to answer

9. What is your professional status?

- a. Paid employment
- b. Self-employed
- c. Non-paid work
- d. Student
- e. Keeping house/house maker Home maker
- f. Retired
- g. Unemployed (health reason)
- h. Unemployed (other reason)
- i. Other (please specify)
- j. Prefer not to answer

10. If in employment do you

- a. Work full time
- b. Work part time
- c. Other (please specify)

11. Do you currently have an illness, impairment or disability which affects how you work or travel that has an expected duration of 12 months or more?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Prefer not to answer

11 a. Does this health problem affect the kind of paid work that you might do?

- a. Yes
- b. No

11 b. Does this health problem affect the amount of paid work that you might do?

- a. Yes
- b. No

11 c. Does your health problem limit your use of transport?

- a. Yes
- b. No

12. What is your main citizenship?

13. Which ethnic group do you mostly identify with?

- a. White
- b. Mixed
- c. Asian
- d. Chinese
- e. Black
- f. Other
- g. Prefer not to answer

14. Which religious group do you most identify with?

- a. No religion
- b. Christian (all denominations)
- c. Muslim
- d. Hindu
- e. Buddhist
- f. Folk Religion
- g. Jewish
- h. Other
- i. Please specify-----
- j. Prefer not to answer

15. Do you identify as:

- a. Male:
- b. Female:
- c. Transsexual Woman:
- d. Transsexual man:
- e. Non-binary:
- f. Prefer not to answer

16. Do you consider yourself to be

- a. Heterosexual
- b. Homosexual
- c. Bisexual
- d. Other
- e. Please specify-----
- f. Prefer not to answer

17. Have you ever been discriminated using transport for your appearance? (aesthetics/the way you look)?

- a. Yes
- b. No

18. Your usual method of travel to work

- a. Car, van, minibus, works van
- b. Motorbike, moped, scooter
- c. Bicycle
- d. Bus, coach, private bus
- e. Taxi
- f. Railway – train
- g. Underground train/light railway/tram
- h. Walk
- i. Other way of travelling

19. How long does it usually take you to travel from home to work (enter time in minutes 180 = 180 minutes etc.)

minutes

20. How often do you cycle in a normal week? (enter the number of times in a week 2 = 2 times in a week etc.)

Times a week

21. Have you ever used bike-sharing services?

- a. Yes
- b. No

22. How often do you use bike-sharing services?

Times a week

SECTION B: BIKE SHARE USER EXPERIENCE

B1. SHARED BIKE USE

Which of the following trips can you or have you made with shared bike services?

		Yes	No	If No	
				Barriers	Needs
B1.1	Shopping	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.2	Work	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.3	College/Study	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.4	Gym/Exercise facility/Swimming Pool	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.5	Park	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.6	Crèche/Childcare Facility	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.7	Local/Corner Shop	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.8	Post Office/Bank/Credit Union	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.9	A public transport stop	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.10	A church or place of worship	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.11	Friend you visit most often	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.12	Family member you visit most often	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		
B1.13	School (e.g. if collecting children)	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>		

B2. ACCESSIBILITY AND SPONTANEITY

B2.1 Please, could you tell me the type of subscription pass you have?

B2.2 Which is the scheme of your annual membership?

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the statements below

		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
B2.3	I am aware that it is possible to cycle with children and goods	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.4	I am familiar with the cycling network in my neighbourhood	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.5	Signing-up for bike share membership is very easy and flexible.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.6	There is a cash payment option for membership and rental charges	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.7	I find it easy to book a bike for a bike-sharing trip	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.8	There is bike-sharing/docking station close to my residential neighbourhood	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.9	The cost of renting bike-share is very affordable	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.10	Rental charges above one hour are reasonably priced.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.11	Annual membership cost of the bike sharing scheme is reasonably priced and affordable	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.12	Cycling safety gear such as helmet, high visibility vest, safety flags and elbow and knee pads can be borrowed from the operators	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.13	I am familiar with the insurance policy of the bike sharing scheme	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.14	There are always bikes available to rent when needed	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B2.15	How much do you rely of bike sharing service to meet mobility needs?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

B2.16	There are always docking stations near	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.17	How easy is to accessing to bikes?	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.18	There is bike sharing station within residential and low income neighbourhoods	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.19	I am satisfied with the existing cycling network (routes and lanes)	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.20	The facilities at the bicycle docking stations meet my needs and expectation	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.21	The changing facilities are fit for purpose and meet my changing needs	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.22	Affordability of the entry cost of the bike sharing service	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.23	Your user level of satisfaction with long rental	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.24	Your user level of satisfaction about how easy is to find a bike for trip chaining	<input type="checkbox"/>						
B2.25	Your user level of satisfaction with practical cycling (with children and cargo) and cycling facilities	<input type="checkbox"/>						

- B2.26 Do the docking stations have toilets facilities suitable for women users?
Yes No
- B2.27 Does the bike sharing operator/s have insurance cover against liability, theft and damage?
Yes No
- B2.28 Are there cycle network and facilities to support trip chaining (a trip involving a single /multiple stop between the origin and destination e.g. Work-to-Shop-to-Home)?
Yes No
- B2.29 Are there accessories for cycling with children or cargo?
Yes No
- B2.30 Are you aware of any public awareness campaign or education on how to cycle with children and goods?
Yes No
- B2.31 Are you aware of any practical cycling education or programme in your locality (How to cycle with children and goods)?
Yes No
- B2.32 Does the existing cycling infrastructure (network and facilities) cycle friendly and encourage cycling?
Yes No
- B2.33 Do the docking stations have end of trip changing facilities?
Yes No
- B2.34 Do you need any requirement for signing-up for membership?
Yes No
- B2.35 Is there the possibility of paying by cash?
Yes No

B3. SAFETY AND SECURITY

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the statements below

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
B3.1 I am comfortable cycling on a segregated bicycle route than sharing the road space with cars	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.2 I am concerned about the attitude of drivers on the road when cycling on the road	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.3 I will cycle/ use bike-share more if all bicycle networks are segregated from vehicular traffic	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.4 The lighting/visibility on cycle routes is adequate for my security when cycling at night	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.5 The existing cycle network is safe enough to cycle with children.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.6 I am comfortable cycling with cars on the road as I am when cycling on a segregated cycle lane	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.7 The lighting/visibility at docking stations is adequate at night	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.8 There is adequate security (i.e. CCTV coverage) at docking stations for my security	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.9 User evaluation about the safety of cycling in the neighbourhood	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.10 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with cycle lanes will make me feel safer to cycle/use bike share	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B3.11 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with cycle lanes will make me cycle/use bike share more	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

B3.11-2 Are you aware of any cycling training programme in your neighbourhood?
Yes No

B4. SOCIAL CONSTRAINTS

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the statements below

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
B4.1 The existing cycle infrastructure provides a safe environment for cycling with children	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B4.2 Cycling and bike sharing are approved and legitimate forms transport	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B4.3 User level of satisfaction with the safety of the existing cycle infrastructure for cycling with children	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

B4.4 Are you familiar with the benefit of cycling?
Yes No

B4.5 Are you aware of the availability of cycling accessories for cycling with children?
Yes No

B4.6 Do the docking stations have changing facilities?
Yes No

B4.7 Are you familiar with the availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities?
 Yes No

B4.8 Are you familiar with the availability of educational courses on cycling with children and cargo?
 Yes No

B5. WEATHER & TOPOGRAPHY

Please indicate the extent to which you agree or disagree with the statements below

		Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither agree nor disagree	Somewhat Agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
B 5.1	Weather such as rain and extreme cold significantly affect cycling and bike share use	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
B5.2	Hilly terrains along cycling routes significantly deter me from cycling.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

B5.3 Does the bike share operator's bike fleet for rental include electric bikes?
 Yes No

B5.4 Does the cycling network in your community include lanes and paths on uphill or hilly terrain?
 Yes No

B5.5 Does the cycling network in your community include cycling rain ponchos?
 Yes No

Please use the space below to add any comments you have on the issues raised in the Questionnaire.

You are at the end of the questionnaire. Thank you very much for your participation!

Figure 41 Outline of the UESI questionnaires for the Use Case III.

DAD Survey Questionnaires (Use Case III)

UC-III - VEHICLE (BIKE) SHARING SURVEY

GOAL: INCREASE THE NUMBER OF PEOPLE USING SHARED BIKES

Current situation (present):

Current transport systems do not sufficiently take into account the physical and social characteristics of men and women in the design of products and services or in fostering people's employability in the industry. DIAMOND's main goal is to turn data into actionable knowledge with notions of fairness, in order to progress towards an inclusive and efficient transport system. We are therefore asking you to help us identify what you believe to be the most important characteristics in relation to people's increased use of bike sharing opportunities and tell us briefly why they are important.

I. ACCESSIBILITY AND SPONTANEITY

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT ACCESSIBILITY AND SPONTANEITY CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE BIKE SHARING FLEETS.

A: I.1. PUBLIC AWARENESS - More local campaigns and education on cycling, cycling routes and location of bike docking stations.

B: I.2. SIGN-UP AND BOOKING PROCESS - There should be a simple and flexible signing-up process.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: I.1. PUBLIC AWARENESS - More local campaigns and education on cycling, cycling routes and location of bike docking stations.

B: I.3. MEMBERSHIP COST - The membership and usage cost of bike-sharing schemes (such as entry cost, rental cost for long duration rental) should be reasonably priced as well as talking into consideration the insurance of the bikes.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: I.1. PUBLIC AWARENESS - More local campaigns and education on cycling, cycling routes and location of bike docking stations.

B: I.4. SPONTANEITY OF ACCESSING BIKE OR DOCK - Reliability and availability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: I.1. PUBLIC AWARENESS - More local campaigns and education on cycling, cycling routes and location of bike docking stations.

B: I.5. PROXIMITY OF DOCKING STATION - Bike sharing stations should be equally distributed, between major transport hubs and people living in residential and low-income communities.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme

Why is it more important? (Optional)	Low	Moderate	Extreme
--------------------------------------	-----	----------	---------

A: 1.1. PUBLIC AWARENESS - More local campaigns and education on cycling, cycling routes and location of bike docking stations.

B: 1.6. TRAVELING WITH CHILDREN OR CARRYING THINGS – The availability of bikes with child seats and carriers which can be used on a safe cycling infrastructure.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.1. PUBLIC AWARENESS - More local campaigns and education on cycling, cycling routes and location of bike docking stations.

B: 1.7. INSUFFICIENT INFRASTRUCTURE – Improved cycling infrastructure including dedicated paths and lanes, attractive changing facilities and toilets that meet the needs of men and women, and sheltered docking stations.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. SIGN-UP AND BOOKING PROCESS - There should be a simple and flexible signing-up process.

B: 1.3. MEMBERSHIP COST - The membership and usage cost of bike-sharing schemes (such as entry cost, rental cost for long duration rental) should be reasonably priced as well as talking into consideration the insurance of the bikes.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. SIGN-UP AND BOOKING PROCESS - There should be a simple and flexible signing-up process.

B: 1.4. SPONTANEITY OF ACCESSING BIKE OR DOCK -- Reliability and availability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. SIGN-UP AND BOOKING PROCESS - There should be a simple and flexible signing-up process.

B: 1.5. PROXIMITY OF DOCKING STATION - Bike sharing stations should be equally distributed, between major transport hubs and people living in residential and low-income communities.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. SIGN-UP AND BOOKING PROCESS - There should be a simple and flexible signing-up process.

B: 1.6. TRAVELING WITH CHILDREN OR CARRYING THINGS - The availability of bikes with child seats and carriers which can be used on a safe cycling infrastructure.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 1.2. SIGN-UP AND BOOKING PROCESS - There should be a simple and flexible signing-up process.
B: 1.7. INSUFFICIENT INFRASTRUCTURE - Improved cycling infrastructure including dedicated paths and lanes), attractive changing facilities and toilets that meet the needs of men and women, and sheltered docking stations.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 1.3. MEMBERSHIP COST - The membership and usage cost of bike-sharing schemes (such as entry cost, rental cost for long duration rental) should be reasonably priced as well as talking into consideration the insurance of the bikes.
B: 1.4. SPONTANEITY OF ACCESSING BIKE OR DOCK -- Reliability and availability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 1.3. MEMBERSHIP COST - The membership and usage cost of bike-sharing schemes (such as entry cost, rental cost for long duration rental) should be reasonably priced as well as talking into consideration the insurance of the bikes.
B: 1.5. PROXIMITY OF DOCKING STATION - Bike sharing stations should be equally distributed, between major transport hubs and people living in residential and low-income communities.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 1.3. MEMBERSHIP COST - The membership and usage cost of bike-sharing schemes (such as entry cost, rental cost for long duration rental) should be reasonably priced as well as talking into consideration the insurance of the bikes.
B: 1.6. TRAVELING WITH CHILDREN OR CARRYING THINGS - The availability of bikes with child seats and carriers which can be used on a safe cycling infrastructure.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 1.3. MEMBERSHIP COST - The membership and usage cost of bike-sharing schemes (such as entry cost, rental cost for long duration rental) should be reasonably priced as well as talking into consideration the insurance of the bikes.
B: 1.7. INSUFFICIENT INFRASTRUCTURE - Improved cycling infrastructure including dedicated paths and lanes), attractive changing facilities and toilets that meet the needs of men and women, and sheltered docking stations.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 1.4. SPONTANEITY OF ACCESSING BIKE OR DOCK -- Reliability and availability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs.

B: 1.5. PROXIMITY OF DOCKING STATION - Bike sharing stations should be equally distributed, between major transport hubs and people living in residential and low-income communities.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.4. SPONTANEITY OF ACCESSING BIKE OR DOCK -- Reliability and availability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs.

B: 1.6. TRAVELING WITH CHILDREN OR CARRYING THINGS - The availability of bikes with child seats and carriers which can be used on a safe cycling infrastructure.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.4. SPONTANEITY OF ACCESSING BIKE OR DOCK -- Reliability and availability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs.

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Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.5. PROXIMITY OF DOCKING STATION - Bike sharing stations should be equally distributed, between major transport hubs and people living in residential and low-income communities.

B: 1.6. TRAVELING WITH CHILDREN OR CARRYING THINGS - The availability of bikes with child seats and carriers which can be used on a safe cycling infrastructure.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.5. PROXIMITY OF DOCKING STATION - Bike sharing stations should be equally distributed, between major transport hubs and people living in residential and low-income communities.

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How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.6. TRAVELING WITH CHILDREN OR CARRYING THINGS - The availability of bikes with child seats and carriers which can be used on a safe cycling infrastructure.

B: 1.7. INSUFFICIENT INFRASTRUCTURE - Improved cycling infrastructure including dedicated paths and lanes), attractive changing facilities and toilets that meet the needs of men and women, and sheltered docking stations.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
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How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

2. SAFETY AND SECURITY

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT SAFETY AND SECURITY CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE BIKE SHARING FLEETS.

A: 2.1. DRIVER BEHAVIOUR - The need to educate drivers on the rights of cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring the safety of other road users (cyclist).

B: 2.2. SEPARATE INFRASTRUCTURE – Separate cycle lanes and paths from road traffic: Developing separate bicycle network away from the road and vehicular traffic.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.1. DRIVER BEHAVIOUR - The need to educate drivers on the rights of cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring the safety of other road users (cyclist).

B: 2.3. CONFIDENCE AND EXPERIENCE – Need to increase confidence of men and women to boost the usage of shared bikes, e.g. through training, in order to increase the skills and reduce the fear to use it.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.1. DRIVER BEHAVIOUR - The need to educate drivers on the rights of cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring the safety of other road users (cyclist).

B: 2.4. HARASSMENT - Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) and public awareness campaigns.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.1. DRIVER BEHAVIOUR - The need to educate drivers on the rights of cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring the safety of other road users (cyclist).

B: 2.5. SAFE ENVIRONMENT AND PERSONAL SAFETY - Where cyclist share the road with vehicles, traffic speeds should be lowered. Adequate lighting should be provided to enhance safety at night and provision of security devices such as CCTV on cycle paths.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.1. DRIVER BEHAVIOUR - The need to educate drivers on the rights of cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring the safety of other road users (cyclist).

B: 2.6. TRAFFIC SAFETY - There is the need to ensure the safety of cyclist sharing the road space with cars. There should be the provision of enforceable bicycle lanes on roads and education of drivers on their responsibility of ensuring the safety of cyclists.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.2. SEPARATE INFRASTRUCTURE - Separate cycle lanes and paths from road traffic: Developing separate bicycle network away from the road and vehicular traffic.

B: 2.3. CONFIDENCE AND EXPERIENCE - Need to increase confidence of men and women to boost the usage of shared bikes, e.g. through training, in order to increase the skills and reduce the fear to use it.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.2. SEPARATE INFRASTRUCTURE - Separate cycle lanes and paths from road traffic: Developing separate bicycle network away from the road and vehicular traffic.

B: 2.4. HARASSMENT - Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) and public awareness campaigns.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.2. SEPARATE INFRASTRUCTURE - Separate cycle lanes and paths from road traffic: Developing separate bicycle network away from the road and vehicular traffic.

B: 2.5. SAFE ENVIRONMENT AND PERSONAL SAFETY - Where cyclist share the road with vehicles, traffic speeds should be lowered. Adequate lighting should be provided to enhance safety at night and provision of security devices such as CCTV on cycle paths.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.2. SEPARATE INFRASTRUCTURE - Separate cycle lanes and paths from road traffic: Developing separate bicycle network away from the road and vehicular traffic.

B: 2.6. TRAFFIC SAFETY - There is the need to ensure the safety of cyclist sharing the road space with cars. There should be the provision of enforceable bicycle lanes on roads and education of drivers on their responsibility of ensuring the safety of cyclists.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.3. CONFIDENCE AND EXPERIENCE - Need to increase confidence of men and women to boost the usage of shared bikes, e.g. through training, in order to increase the skills and reduce the fear to use it.

B: 2.4. HARASSMENT - Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) and public awareness campaigns.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

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Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 2.3. CONFIDENCE AND EXPERIENCE - Need to increase confidence of men and women to boost the usage of shared bikes, e.g. through training, in order to increase the skills and reduce the fear to use it.

B: 2.6. TRAFFIC SAFETY - There is the need to ensure the safety of cyclist sharing the road space with cars. There should be the provision of enforceable bicycle lanes on roads and education of drivers on their responsibility of ensuring the safety of cyclists.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 2.4. HARASSMENT - Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) and public awareness campaigns.

B: 2.5. SAFE ENVIRONMENT AND PERSONAL SAFETY - Where cyclist share the road with vehicles, traffic speeds should be lowered. Adequate lighting should be provided to enhance safety at night and provision of security devices such as CCTV on cycle paths.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 2.4. HARASSMENT - Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) and public awareness campaigns.

B: 2.6. TRAFFIC SAFETY - There is the need to ensure the safety of cyclist sharing the road space with cars. There should be the provision of enforceable bicycle lanes on roads and education of drivers on their responsibility of ensuring the safety of cyclists.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

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Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

3. SOCIAL CONSTRAINTS

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT SOCIAL CONSTRAINTS CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE BIKE SHARING FLEETS.

A: 3.1. PEER INFLUENCE (SUBJECTIVE NORM) - Public education and awareness campaign about the recognition of cycling as an acceptable mode of transport.

B: 3.2. NEGATIVE PERCEPTIONS (SOCIO-CULTURAL CONSTRAINTS) - Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling to demystify the myth about cycling in low-income and minority neighbourhoods.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 3.1. PEER INFLUENCE (SUBJECTIVE NORM) - Public education and awareness campaign about the recognition of cycling as an acceptable mode of transport.

B: 3.3. FAMILY RESPONSIBILITIES - The provision of bicycle infrastructure and sharing services which meet the needs of men and women with child care responsibility who may need to travel with children.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

A: 3.2. NEGATIVE PERCEPTIONS (SOCIO-CULTURAL CONSTRAINTS) - Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling to demystify the myth about cycling in low-income and minority neighbourhoods.

B: 3.3. FAMILY RESPONSIBILITIES - The provision of bicycle infrastructure and sharing services which meet the needs of men and women with child care responsibility who may need to travel with children.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

4. WEATHER AND TOPOGRAPHY

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT WEATHER AND TOPOGRAPHY CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE BIKE SHARING FLEETS.

A: 4.1. WEATHER - Bicycle network should developed to user-friendly in bad weathers and bike-sharing providers should be able to supply for example, cyclist rain coats (poncho) on rainy days.

B: 4.2. TOPOGRAPHY - There is the need to avoid hilly terrain as much as possible when developing bicycle network and Bike sharing operators should include few electric bikes in their bike fleets.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance	
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong	<input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)				

Figure 42 Outline of the DAD survey questionnaires for the Use Case III.

Annex 5 – Data collection tools (Use Case IV)

Structured Data (Use Case IV)

Level 2 Fairness Characteristics	Job Segregation	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	All jobs are available and suitable for both men and women (and there is a more equal balance between genders across all occupations, levels and jobs in transport)	% women employees
		% men employees
		% women managers
		% men managers
		% women directors
		% men directors
		Recent recruitment - e.g.past 12 months - how many women employed?
		Recent recruitment - e.g.past 12 months -How many men employed?
		Recent recruitment - e.g.past 12 months -Roles of new employees?
		Recent recruitment - e.g.past 12 months -Level of new employees?
	On the job training for men and women to negate cultural	Number of courses training to avoid cultural stereotypes (last 3 years)
	School visits, open days, etc. to attract more women to the	Number of school visits/open days per year (last 3 years)
	Promoting a more gender-balanced career orientation: among students 'women-only' open days; and in general;	Number of women students that assists to these career orientation days (last 3 years)
		Number of men students that assists to these career orientation days (last 3 years)
		% of women employees recruited via open days (last 3 years)
	Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions;	% of men employees recruited via open days (last 3 years)
		Rate of salary women/men of employees
		Rate of salary women/men of managers
	Regularly reviewing the recruitment process for	Rate of salary women/men of directors
		Is it established within the company an equality policy? (Yes/No)
		Is there any procedure to review the fairness/equity in recruitment processes? (Yes/No)

Level 2 fairness Characteristics	Policy/Legal	Data Required	
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Ensure women are visible and active in policy- and decision-making and planning;	% women managers	
		% women directors	
		% men managers	
		% men directors	
	Equal employment policies: Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes for women, and meet national legal requirements (including Equal Employment policies);	% women employees	
		% men employees	
		% of disabled employees (male and female)	
		% of ethnic minority employees (male and female)	
		% of women with maternity leaving (in the last 3 years)	
		% of men with paternity leaving (in the last 3 years)	
		Duration of maternity leaving (weeks) (2019)	
		Duration of paternity leaving (weeks) (2019)	
		Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave;	% women employees
			% men employees
	% of employees who are parents		
	% of employees with caring responsibilities		
	% of part time workers		
	% of men working part time		
	% of women working part time		
	% of women working flexibly (including home working and flexible start and finish times)		
	% of men working flexibly (including home working and flexible start and finish times)		
	Anti-harassment policies;		Number of policies against harassment in a particular company
	Ensure that men and women have equal access to professional mobility (with support the professional	Women promoted in the last 3 years	
	Corporate policies to facilitate women in the workplace.	Men promoted in the last 3 years	
		Number of corporate policies to facilitate women access to a workplace	

Level 2 fairness Characteristics	Demand Factors	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Gender neutral recruitment policies should be in place;	Number of female applicants in 2018
		Number of male applicants in 2018
		Number of female employed in 2018
		Number of male employed in 2018
		Is there in place a gender neutral recruitment policy? (Yes/No)
	Design job offers so that both men and women can apply;	Are job offers designed to attract both men and women? (Yes/No)
	Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed;	Number of opportunities advertised in the last 3 years
	Targeted recruitment campaigns seek to reduce gender	Rate of opportunities advertised (%)
	Provision of training, scholarships, and internships to	Does the organisation conduct targeted recruitment campaigns? (Yes/No)
		Number of courses training to improve the skills of women (last 3 years)

Level 2 Fairness Characteristics	Terms and Conditions	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Safe working environments for women (sexual harassment, violence etc.);	Number of sexual harassments and violent actions against women (in the last 3 years) Does your company support and safety equipment (CCTV cameras, panic buttons, anti-
	Formal recognition of sexual harassment claims;	Number of tools to collect sexual harassment claims % of claims made by female (in the last 3 years)
	Part time workers provided with the same safeguards of	Are full time and part time employees provided with the same terms and conditions in % of employees on zero hours contracts
	Not using 'a-typical contracts' (zero hours etc.);	% of female employees on zero hours contracts % of male employees on zero hours contracts
	Employment terms and conditions support a work-life	Flexible working offered? (Yes/No)
	Wage structures that are predictable with no variable	Does your organization pay equally both women and men for equivalent positions?
Level 2 fairness Characteristics	HR Policies	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Targeted recruitment campaigns;	Number of recruitment campaigns targeted to women (in the last 3 years) % female new employees (in the last 3 years)
	Organisations should ensure that they maintain a gender mix among its newly hired managers, and plan for identifying obstacles hindering career development of women;	% male new employees (in the last 3 years)
		% female new managers (in the last 3 years)
		% male new managers (in the last 3 years)
		% female new directors (in the last 3 years)
		% Male new directors (in the last 3 years)
	Maternity leave or part-time work practices will not be taken into account when evaluating promotions or access	% female promoted (in the last 3 years) which had maternity leave or part-time work
		% male promoted (in the last 3 years) which had paternity leave or part-time work
	Ensure that the male–female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male–female ratio of the company staff;	N° Female/n° male in the company
		N° Female/n° male employees
		N° Female/ n° male managers (intermediate positions)
		N° Female/ n° male directors
		% female employees internally promoted (in the last 3 years)
		% male employees internally promoted (in the last 3 years)
% female managers internally promoted (in the last 3 years)		
% male managers internally promoted (in the last 3 years)		
Place someone in charge - assigning the responsibility to a	% female directors internally promoted (in the last 3 years)	
	% Male directors internally promoted (in the last 3 years)	
Is there a person or body in charge of developing and monitor actions to advance the		
Level 2 fairness Characteristics	Safety and Security	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Regulations and education regarding sexual harassment	Number of policies to avoid harassment
	Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance	Number of communications about zero tolerance (in the last 3 years)
	Training against third-party violence;	Number of courses against third-party violence in the last 3 years- Company level (in the
	Safety equipment - CCTV cameras, panic buttons, anti-	Number of measures to protect personnel
Security staff available to intervene in case of need.	Number of personnel from a security company present in the facilities	
Level 2 fairness Characteristics	Training Provision	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Women and men should have equal access to all training programmes;	% of part time female employees who have taken part in training in the previous 3 years?
		% of part time male employees who have taken part in training in the previous 3 years?
		% of full time female staff who have taken part in training in the previous 3 years?
		% of full time male staff who have taken part in training in the previous 3 years?
	A flexible training system to be introduced;	Number of flexible training systems (e.g. online courses, courses with flexible timetable,
Training and policies to promote a cultural change among	Does the organisation have an internal gender equality training and policy which it	
Continually assessing the relevance and quality of training	Is it implemented a method or procedure to evaluate the quality of teh training?	
Level 2 fairness Characteristics	Female Facilities	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Provision of female toilets and showers were required;	% of separated toilets
		Number of women/number of toilets for women Number of men/number of toilets for men
	Segregated changing rooms;	Number of separated changing rooms
		Number of common changing rooms

Level 2 Fairness Characteristics	Caring/Parenting responsibilities	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Supported career/carer breaks;	Number of men with supported career/carer breaks (in the last 3 years)
		Number of women with supported career/carer breaks (in the last 3 years)
	Guaranteeing the maintenance of salary levels during maternity leave;	Average duration of maternity leaves
		How many employees took a maternity leave in the last 3 years?
		How many employees on maternity leave received the full salary? (In the last 3 years)
	Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time;	Number of people with children under 5 years with change shifts or reduced working
		Number of people with children under 5 years without change shifts or reduced
	Part-time work, flexible working hours, and work from home options;	% of part time workers
		% of men working part time
		% of women working part time
% of women working flexibly (flexible start and finish times)		
% of men working flexibly (flexible start and finish times)		
% of men working from home		
		% of women working from home
Level 2 Fairness Characteristics	Economic deprivation	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Affordable child/social care;	Amount of money a company assigned to child/social care (in the last 3 years)
	Minimum hourly rate for low skilled part time work.	Minimum hourly rate for low skilled part time work
Level 2 fairness	Skills	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Robust training policies and systems;	Is there a training policy within the company? (Yes/No)
		How many general training programmes are provided for employees at all levels?
		How many general training programmes are provided only for managers?
		How many general training programmes are provided only for directors?
Level 3 Fairness	Build solid bridges between the world of work and training	Is there any cooperation established between the world of work and training providers
Level 3 Fairness Characteristics	Anticipating and building competencies for future needs;	How many women are attending training/upskilling? (in the last 3 years)
		How many men are attending training/upskilling? (in the last 3 years)
Level 3 Fairness	Ensuring broad access to training opportunities, for	How many training programmes exist that link work and skills?
Level 2 fairness	Health Status and Wellbeing	Data Required
Level 3 Fairness	Leave for caring responsibilities;	% of women leaving for caring responsibilities (in the last 3 years)

Figure 43 List of structured data regarding the women involved in professional jobs related to transport sector in EU Countries.

UESI questionnaires (Use Case IV)

1

THE DIAMOND PROJECT – Use Case IV WOMEN'S EMPLOYMENT IN THE TRANSPORT SECTOR SATISFACTION QUESTIONNAIRE

Dear Participant,

Thank you for agreeing to take part in this Employment Satisfaction questionnaire. This questionnaire is part of a project called 'DIAMOND'. The project aims to obtain information about gender specific needs for Europe's current and future transport systems and is funded by the European Commission's Horizon 2020 Programme (Project No. 8243267). Diamond is made up of fourteen international and interdisciplinary partners from across ten countries in Europe and includes, academics, transport operators, public authorities and experts in infrastructure assessment design.

In the questionnaire you will be asked a number of questions about your opinion on your work environment. The information gathered will be used to prepare publicly available reports for the European Commission, for academic publications and to help develop guidelines for transport operators to improve inclusive recruitment, retention and promotion of women in the sector.

All information gathered will be treated as anonymous and you will not be identified in any publications arising from the data collected from this questionnaire. No data will be revealed which could identify anyone taking part in this project.

A consent form will be provided at the start of this session. If you do not wish to complete this questionnaire you are free to withdraw your consent at any time up until the final report is written and are under no obligation to complete this questionnaire.

Thank you for your participation.

(Name of DIAMOND personnel facilitating the session)

A Note on the Questionnaire for you:

The purpose of this survey is to gain an understanding of *your* satisfaction levels as an employee in the transport sector.

The questionnaire aims to obtain information from you about barriers to you, characteristics of your employment, job factors relevant to you, fairness in your employment and other factors that you feel are relevant to you in your employment.

Your honest answers to the questions in this questionnaire are very important to us.

Remember...We want to know what you think.

There are no right and wrong answers. We apologise if some of the questions seem repetitive and we appreciate your patience. Please answer all questions. Everything you tell us will be kept confidential (secret). Thank you very much for your participation.

This section looks at the factors that affect women employees in the transport sector

The questions below are designed to assess your satisfaction in respect of certain job characteristics related to your experiences of employment in the transport sector. The overall characteristics and sub-categories of those characteristics are listed below. Please take some time to read them. Then please proceed to answer the questions in respect of ***your*** knowledge and experiences in your current or previous job. If possible, please use your most current role to answer these questions.

The Sections Explained:

The questions are divided into two sections, those related to job characteristics and those related to women's individual needs and circumstances. At the end of each section there is an 'Overall' question that asks you overall, how satisfied you are.

Start of Questionnaire

We have provided short statements related to concepts of fairness in relation to women's employment and would ask that you indicate how satisfied you are that these concepts are/have been implemented in your workplace in relation to women employed in the transport sector, your choices range from not at all, sometimes and almost always.

SECTION 1. Your Work Community

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider **your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/or previously worked in**

Job Segregation - Gender balance in jobs

What does this mean? This section looks at how available and suitable jobs are for both men and women in a country or an environment rather than a specific company

	Not at all		Sometimes			Almost Always	
In my community/country there is currently an equal balance between genders across occupations, levels and jobs in transport.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My community/country offers role model advertising in careers where traditionally less gender balance is achieved	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Recruitment & Promotion Process

What does this mean? This section looks at how policies/legal requirements are used/not used within a country or an environment rather than a specific company in terms of recruitment and promotion processes for women

	Not at all		Sometimes			Almost Always	
In my community/country National Laws and policies currently exist to support equal opportunity in terms of recruitment and promotion for both female and male candidates	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
There are existing initiatives with schools, colleges and universities that attract more women to the transport sector	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
How satisfied are you that the country you live in supports fairness and inclusiveness of women in transport?	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SECTION 2. Job Characteristics

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider **your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in**

3

	Not at all		Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company's HR policies facilitate fair recruitment, promotion, pay and contributory pension scheme for women in the workplace	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company's terms and conditions support maternity leave	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company's terms and conditions support paternity leave	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company's terms and conditions support employees in their caring role, i.e. family friendly policies	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my company there is prevention of dismissal or demotion during and after maternity periods;	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company offers flexible Working Hours e.g. Teleworking / Working from home arrangements to all employees	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my company part time and flexible workers have equal opportunity for promotion.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Company Culture Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider **your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in**

	Not at all		Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Where I work there is a company culture that promotes diversity as the accepted norm	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I feel comfortable and accepted in my current work environment	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my company female employees are accepted by the public using transport	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Where I work there is a good level of acceptance of female employees by male colleagues	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Safety and Security

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider **your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in**

	Not at all		Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

4

My working environment protects women from violence/harassment/assault	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My workplace design is ergonomically suitable for all employees	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my work place we have adequate safety equipment - CCTV cameras, panic buttons etc.	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Training

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in

	Not at all		Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my workplace all employees have equal access to all training programs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company provides special training and re-skilling after career breaks/maternity leave if required	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company facilitate up-skilling and training of women for roles that are more male dominated	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company provides training about unconscious bias in employment	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company provides cultural sensitivity training	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Accessibility to practical amenities

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in

	Not at all		Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my workplace the provision for female facilities (female toilets and showers, facilities for breastfeeding mothers etc.) are appropriate	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company meets all current Employment legislation requirements to support individuals with special intellectual needs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
My company meets all current Employment legislation requirements to support individuals with special physical needs	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Overall Job Characteristics Satisfaction

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
Overall, I am satisfied with the fairness and inclusiveness of women employees in my workplace?								

SECTION 3. Personal Circumstances

This section aims to look at employees' circumstances and their ability and desire to work and progress in the transport. Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in

Caring and parenting responsibilities

Are you a parent and/or do you have caring responsibilities outside the workplace? Please indicate 'Yes' or 'No'.
If you are not a carer or parent, please go to the next question.

Relevant (tick as appropriate): YES NO

I am a CARER YES NO

I am a PARENT YES NO

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I require working times that make it possible to accommodate work and family commitments (extended hours, variable start/ finish times, shift-work etc.								

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I require support in my workplace for dealing with chronic/long-term health conditions of those I care for							

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
In my workplace I regularly need to exceed my working hours							

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Overall how satisfied are you with the way your caring and parenting responsibility needs are supported by your employers?							

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
In my environment I feel the need for better access to professional qualification								

6

In my environment I feel the need for better access to promotion opportunities	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
--	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

In my environment I feel the need for better access to education to support my career goals	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

In my environment I feel the need for role models who are like me	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
---	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always
Overall how satisfied are you with the way your socio-economic needs have been supported in your workplace?	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Supports for You

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, **Specific** consider your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in. If the question is not applicable to you, please tick 'Not applicable to me'.

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always
I require better access to flexible and affordable childcare services	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Not applicable to me

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always
I require better access to the public/private transport to travel to work	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Not applicable to me

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always
I require better financial support for expenses related to travel to work	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Not applicable to me

Overall Personal Circumstances Satisfaction

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always
Overall how satisfied are you with the way your personal circumstances and needs are met in your workplace?	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SECTION 4: Individual Characteristics

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in

Health Status and Wellbeing

If this section is Not Applicable to you please continue to the next section.

I have a Long-term illness or disability: YES NO

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
My need to progress in my career in my workplace is affected by having a long-term illness/disability								
My training and development needs are met as much as other people in my organization								

Adaptability

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I have the capability to accommodate changing shifts and or working time in my workplace according to my needs								

About You

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in

Relevant (tick as appropriate):

In my work environment and in my current role I feel I belong to an ethnic minority:

YES NO

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
In my workplace, belonging to an ethnic minority group affects my career progression								

Relevant (tick as appropriate):

My age group is above 50: YES NO

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost always	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	
I feel that being an aging worker (above 50) negatively affects my job opportunities and career progression								

My age group is below 30: YES NO

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost always	

8

I feel that being a young worker (less than 30) negatively affects my job opportunities and career progression	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
--	---	---	---	---	---	---	---

Educational level and skills attainment

Please rate, in your opinion, whether you agree or disagree with the following statements. In your answer, consider your experience in the job, role and organisation you work/worked in

	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost always
I require specific skills training during work to access job opportunities and progression	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
I require more experience in specific roles to access job opportunities and progression	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

Overall individual characteristics evaluation

In your experience/opinion	Not at all			Sometimes			Almost Always
Overall how satisfied are you with the way your individual characteristics and needs have affected your job opportunities?	1	2	3	4	5	6	7

SECTION 5: *Demographic Information*: This last section tells us about you. Your responses to the next sections are important to help us identify potential unfairness in the existing systems.

1. **Where do you currently live?**
 - a. Spain
 - b. France
 - c. Italy
 - d. United Kingdom
 - e. Ireland
 - f. Poland
 - g. Serbia
 - h. Other

Please specify if you wish-----

2. **Do you consider yourself to live in a:**
 - a. Rural environment
 - b. An urban environment
 - c. Suburban environment

3. **What age bracket are you?**
 - a. 18-24 years
 - b. 25-34 years
 - c. 35-44 years
 - d. 45-54 years
 - e. 55-64 years
 - f. 65-74 years
 - g. 75 years or more
 - h. Prefer not to answer

4. **What is the highest level of education you have achieved?**
 - a. Not formal education
 - b. Primary education
 - c. Lower secondary education
 - d. Upper secondary education
 - e. Post-secondary education
 - f. Short-cycle tertiary education
 - g. Degree
 - h. Master
 - i. Doctorate
 - j. Prefer not to answer

5. **What is your average yearly income?**
 - a. No income
 - b. Less than 10,999 €
 - c. 11,000-20,999 €
 - d. 21,000-30,999 €
 - e. 31,000-40,999 €
 - f. 41,000-50,999 €
 - g. 51,000-70,999 €
 - h. More than 71,000 €
 - i. Prefer not to answer

6. **What is your household type?**
 - a. Married/Civil partnership-Heterosexual
 - b. Married/Civil partnership-Same sex
 - c. Cohabiting
 - d. Lone parent
 - e. Single
 - f. Prefer not to say

7. In your family unit, do you live with any dependent person? (e.g. children, elderly, caring for disabled person).

- a. No
- b. Preschool age children (under 5 years)
- c. School age children (5-16 years)
- d. Elderly relative
- e. Disabled person

8. Do you travel on a weekly basis with a dependent person? (children, elderly, caring for disabled person).

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Prefer not to answer

9. What is your professional status?

- a. Paid employment
- b. Self-employed
- c. Non-paid work
- d. Student
- e. Keeping house/house maker Home maker
- f. Retired
- g. Unemployed (health reason)
- h. Unemployed (other reason)
- i. Other
- j. Prefer not to answer

10. If in employment do you

- a. Work full time (30 hours per week or more)
- b. Work part time (less than 30 hours per week)
- c. Other

11. Do you currently have an illness, impairment or disability which affects how you work or travel that has an expected duration of 12 months or more?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Prefer not to answer

11a. Does this health problem affect the kind of paid work that you might do?

- a. Yes
- b. No

11b. Does this health problem affect the amount of paid work that you might do?

- a. Yes
- b. No

11c. Does your health problem limit your use of transport?

- a. Yes
- b. No

12. What is your (main) citizenship? _____

13. With which ethnic group do you mostly identify with?

- a. White
- b. Mixed
- c. Asian
- Please specify if you wish _____
- d. Black
- e. Other
- Please specify if you wish-----
- f. Prefer not to answer

14. Which religious group do you most identify with?

- a. No religion
- b. Christian (all denominations)
- c. Muslim
- d. Hindu
- e. Buddhist
- f. Folk Religion
- g. Jewish
- h. Other
- Please specify if you wish -----
- i. Prefer not to answer

15. Do you identify as:

- a. Male: A person assigned male at birth who feels as a man
- b. Female: A person assigned female at birth who feels as a woman
- c. Transsexual woman: A person assigned as male at birth but feels as a woman
- d. Transsexual man: A person assigned as female at birth but feels as a man
- e. Non-binary: A person who does not define oneself as a man or woman
- f. Prefer not to answer

16. Do you consider yourself to be

- a. Heterosexual
- b. Homosexual
- c. Bisexual
- d. Other
- Please specify if you wish-----
- e. Prefer not to answer

17. Have you ever been discriminated against using/working in transport for your appearance (aesthetics/the way you look)?

- a. Yes
- b. No

18. Are you currently working in transport?

- a. Yes Please answer Q18a to 18d
- b. No Please go to Q19

18a. If yes, which transport sector do you work in?

- a. Policy making and public authority
- b. Education
- c. Research, innovation and technology
- d. On-site job in the city private transport (planner, maintenance, administration...)
- e. Off-site job in the city private transport (driver)
- f. On-site job in the regional or international private transport (planner, maintenance, administration...)
- g. Off-site job in the regional or international private transport (driver)
- h. On-site job in the public transport (planner, maintenance, administration...)
- i. Off-site job in the public transport (driver)
- j. Other

18b. What mode of transport do you work with?

- a. Car
- b. Truck
- c. Bus
- d. Bike
- e. Taxi

- f. Train
- g. Tram
- h. Maritime
- i. Aviation
- j. Multimodal
- k. Other (Logistics forwarder)

18c. What is your job title? please specify

18d. What level is your role?

- a. Front Line operators
- b. Supervisor/Foreman
- c. Office administrative staff
- d. Middle Manager
- e. Director
- f. Other,

19. What is your usual method of travel to work

- a. Car, van, minibus, works van
- b. Motorbike, moped, scooter
- c. Bicycle
- d. Bus, coach, private bus
- e. Taxi
- f. Railway – train
- g. Underground train/light railway/tram
- h. Walk
- i. Other way of travelling

20. How long does it usually take you to travel from home to work (enter time in minutes 180 = 180 minutes etc.)

minutes

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Figure 44 Outline of the UESI questionnaires for the Use Case IV.

DAD Survey Questionnaires (Use Case IV)

UC-IV – EMPLOYEMENT IN TRANSPORT SURVEY

GOAL: TO INCREASE THE NUMBER OF PEOPLE WORKING IN ALL PARTS OF TRANSPORT

Current situation (present):

The following questions are focused on the comparison of different aspects of employment in current transport system; including issues related to job conditions, the influence of an individual's characteristics in jobs and careers, and fair job offers. We are therefore asking you to help us identify what you believe to be the most important characteristics in relation to increasing employment in the transport sector and tell us briefly why they are important.

1. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS

Please compare the two statements under each question and tick which (A or B) is more important for achieving a fair work environment. Then in the next line tick how much more important your choice (A or B) is. (If you tick that both are of equal importance then ignore that line). If you wish to, you can add an optional comment on why you think this is important.

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT SOCIO-ECONOMIC CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FAIRNESS OF A WORK ENVIRONMENT

A: 1.1. JOB SEGREGATION – All jobs are available and made suitable for both men and women (and there is a more equal balance between genders across all occupations, levels and jobs in transport).

B: 1.2. POLICY AND LEGAL - Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes, and that meet national legal requirements.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.1. JOB SEGREGATION – All jobs are available and suitable for both men and women (and there is a more equal balance between genders across all occupations, levels and jobs in transport).

B: 1.3. DEMAND FACTORS (JOB RECRUITMENT) – All recruitment, promotion and the design of the jobs are gender neutral processes and genuinely open equally to both men and women.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1.2. POLICY AND LEGAL - Policies are used within the organisation to support fair recruitment and promotion processes, and that meet national legal requirements

B: 1.3. DEMAND FACTORS (JOB RECRUITMENT) - All recruitment, promotion and the design of the jobs are gender neutral processes and genuinely open equally to both men and women.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

2. JOB CHARACTERISTICS

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT JOB CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FAIRNESS OF A WORK ENVIRONMENT

A: 2.1. TERMS AND CONDITIONS - The caring responsibilities that men and women may have outside of work are taken account of.

B: 2.2. HR POLICIES – Human Resources (HR) processes promote fairness in relation to gender (including in employment issues, staff development, pay conditions, recruitment and promotion).

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.1. TERMS AND CONDITIONS - The caring responsibilities that men and women may have outside of work are taken account of.

B: 2.3. FEMALE FACILITIES - Appropriate facilities are provided, e.g. separated toilets and changing rooms etc.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.1. TERMS AND CONDITIONS - The caring responsibilities that men and women may have outside of work are taken account of.

B: 2.4. SAFETY AND SECURITY - The working environment is safe for men and women, including prevention of violence and protection.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.1. TERMS AND CONDITIONS - The caring responsibilities that men and women may have outside of work are taken account of.

B: 2.5. TRAINING PROVISION - Flexible training proactively supports employment, promotion and retention in the work place is available to all.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.2. HR POLICIES - Human Resources (HR) processes promote fairness in relation to gender (including in employment issues, staff development, pay conditions, recruitment and promotion).

B: 2.4. SAFETY AND SECURITY- The working environment is safe for men and women, including prevention of violence and protection.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.2. HR POLICIES - Human Resources (HR) processes promote fairness in relation to gender (including in employment issues, staff development, pay conditions, recruitment and promotion).

B: 2.5. TRAINING PROVISION - Flexible training proactively supports employment, promotion and retention in the work place is available to all.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.2. HR POLICIES - Human Resources (HR) processes promote fairness in relation to gender (including in employment issues, staff development, pay conditions, recruitment and promotion).

B: 2.3. FEMALE FACILITIES - Appropriate facilities are provided, e.g. separated toilets and changing rooms etc.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

B: 2.3. FEMALE FACILITIES - Appropriate facilities are provided, e.g. separated toilets and changing rooms etc.

B: 2.4. SAFETY AND SECURITY-The working environment is safe for men and women, including prevention of violence and protection.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

B: 2.3. FEMALE FACILITIES - Appropriate facilities are provided, e.g. separated toilets and changing rooms etc.

B: 2.5 TRAINING PROVISION - Flexible training proactively supports employment, promotion and retention in the work place is available to all.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2.4. SAFETY AND SECURITY- The working environment is safe for men and women, including prevention of violence and protection.

B: 2.5. TRAINING PROVISION - Flexible training proactively supports employment, promotion and retention in the work place is available to all.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

3. PERSONAL CIRCUMSTANCES

COMPARE THE IMPORTANCE OF PERSONAL CIRCUMSTANCES ON THE FAIRNESS OF A WORK ENVIRONMENT

A: 3.1. CARING AND PARENTING RESPONSIBILITIES - Flexible working and career breaks (e.g. for childcare) do not negatively affect long-term careers in transport.

B: 3.2. ECONOMIC DEPRIVATION - Coming from a poor background or locality does not affect employees' job opportunities and career progression.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 3.1. CARING AND PARENTING RESPONSIBILITIES– Flexible working and career breaks (e.g. for childcare) do not negatively affect long-term careers in transport.

B: 3.3. ACCESS TO RESOURCES - Accessible, affordable and suitable childcare facilities and other resources needed to get and retain employment are available, residential location, choice of services, availability and cost of transport (different modes), multiple journeys , rural-urban

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 3.2. ECONOMIC DEPRIVATION - Coming from a poor background or locality does not affect employees' job opportunities and career progression.

B: 3.3. ACCESS TO RESOURCES - Accessible, affordable and suitable childcare facilities and other resources needed to get and retain employment are available, residential location, choice of services, availability and cost of transport (different modes), multiple journeys , rural-urban.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

4. INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS

COMPARE THE DIFFERENT INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS ACCORDING TO THEIR INFLUENCE ON THE FAIRNESS OF THE WORK ENVIRONMENT

A: 4.1. HEALTH STATUS AND WELLBEING – Support is provided for employees with chronic/long-term health conditions.

B: 4.2. ADAPTABILITY - Employees who are unable to be adaptable due to family circumstances (e.g. changing shift work etc.) are treated equally.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.1. HEALTH STATUS AND WELLBEING - Support is provided for employees with chronic/long-term health conditions.

B: 4.3. DEMOGRAPHIC - All employees are treated fairly and not discriminated against in employment regardless of age, gender, ethnicity, sexuality, etc.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.1. HEALTH STATUS AND WELLBEING - Support is provided for employees with chronic/long-term health conditions.

B: 4.4. SKILLS - Employers proactively support men and women to train and improve skills for future needs.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.1. HEALTH STATUS AND WELLBEING- Support is provided for employees with chronic/long-term health conditions.

B: 4.5. EDUCATIONAL LEVEL AND ATTAINMENT - Educational bodies (schools and colleges etc.) prepare and encourage men and women to enter employment in all parts of the transport sector.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.2. ADAPTABILITY- Employees who are unable to be adaptable due to family circumstances (e.g. changing shift work etc.) are treated equally.

B: 4.3. DEMOGRAPHIC - All employees are treated fairly and not discriminated against in employment regardless of age, gender, ethnicity, sexuality, etc.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.2. ADAPTABILITY- Employees who are unable to be adaptable due to family circumstances (e.g. changing shift work etc.) are treated equally.

B: 4.4. SKILLS - Employers proactively support men and women to train and improve skills for future needs.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.2. ADAPTABILITY- Employees who are unable to be adaptable due to family circumstances (e.g. changing shift work etc.) are treated equally.

B: 4.5. EDUCATIONAL LEVEL AND ATTAINMENT - Educational bodies (schools and colleges etc.) prepare and encourage men and women to enter employment in all parts of the transport sector.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.3. DEMOGRAPHIC- All employees are treated fairly and not discriminated against in employment regardless of age, gender, ethnicity, sexuality, etc.

B: 4.4. SKILLS - Employers proactively support men and women to train and improve skills for future needs.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.3. DEMOGRAPHIC- All employees are treated fairly and not discriminated against in employment regardless of age, gender, ethnicity, sexuality, etc.

B: 4.5. EDUCATIONAL LEVEL AND ATTAINMENT - Educational bodies (schools and colleges etc.) prepare and encourage men and women to enter employment in all parts of the transport sector.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 4.4. SKILLS - Employers proactively support men and women to train and improve skills for future needs.

B: 4.5. EDUCATIONAL LEVEL AND ATTAINMENT - Educational bodies (schools and colleges etc.) prepare and encourage men and women to enter employment in all parts of the transport sector.

Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for improving fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

Future scenarios:

FUTURE EMPLOYMENT IN DRONE LOGISTICS

- How do you rate your knowledge on drones?

- a. High
- b. Medium
- c. Low
- d. None

The use of drones in logistics is one of the possible scenarios of the future. It has been set that by 2030 **drone traffic logistics will employ a 1.5% of the total EU workforce** (Gheorghiu et al., 2017). Please, give your opinion regarding the influence of this new scenario in the importance of one characteristic or factor in front of the other.

From your point of view, which factor (A or B) will be more important for the participation of men and women in employment in drone logistics?

A: 1. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS - Wider societal acceptance and encouragement of men and women in drone logistics (cultural context - removal of gender stereotypes and occupational segregation).

B: 2. JOB CHARACTERISTICS – Absence of employer and job barriers to employment and progression in the drone logistics sector (terms and conditions, flexibility, training, health and safety).

Which of these characteristics in your point of view affects more an employee’s needs for fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS - Wider societal acceptance and encouragement of men and women in drone logistics (cultural context - removal of gender stereotypes and occupational segregation).

B: 3. PERSONAL CIRCUMSTANCES - Employees’ circumstances do not influence their ability and desire to work and progress in drone logistics (peer pressure on entering some jobs, role models, caring responsibilities).

Which of these characteristics in your point of view affects more an employee’s needs for fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 1. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS - Wider societal acceptance and encouragement of men and women in drone logistics (cultural context - removal of gender stereotypes and occupational segregation).

B: 4. INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS - Individual characteristics of employees (e.g. gender, age, ethnicity, immigrant status etc.) do not influence their employment in drone logistics.

Which of these characteristics in your point of view affects more an employee's needs for fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2. JOB CHARACTERISTICS: Absence of employer and job barriers to employment and progression in the drone logistics sector (terms and conditions, flexibility, training, health and safety).

B: 3. PERSONAL CIRCUMSTANCES - Employees' circumstances do not influence their ability and desire to work and progress in drone logistics (peer pressure on entering some jobs, role models, caring responsibilities).

Which of these characteristics in your point of view affects more an employee's needs for fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 2. JOB CHARACTERISTICS: Absence of employer and job barriers to employment and progression in the drone logistics sector (terms and conditions, flexibility, training, health and safety).

B: 4. INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS - *Individual* characteristics of employees (e.g. gender, age, ethnicity, immigrant status etc.) do not influence their employment.

Which of these characteristics in your point of view affects more an employee's needs for fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

A: 3. PERSONAL CIRCUMSTANCES - *Employees' circumstances* do not influence their ability and desire to work and progress in drone logistics (peer pressure on entering some jobs, role models, caring responsibilities).

B: 4. INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS - *Individual* characteristics of employees (e.g. gender, age, ethnicity, immigrant status etc.) do not influence their employment in the drone logistics sector.

Which of these characteristics in your point of view affects more an employee's needs for fairness?	<input type="checkbox"/> A	<input type="checkbox"/> B	<input type="checkbox"/> Of equal importance
How much more important?	<input type="checkbox"/> 3. Low	<input type="checkbox"/> 5. Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> 7. Strong <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Extreme
Why is it more important? (Optional)			

5. OVERALL RECOMMENDATIONS FOR THE FUTURE OF WOMEN'S EMPLOYMENT IN TRANSPORT

If you were to suggest a key recommendation related to each area below what would they be?

1. SOCIO-ECONOMIC CONDITIONS – Wider societal encouragement of men and women to enter and progress within the transport sector (including encouraging more people in STEM (Science Technology Engineering and Mathematic), cyber security etc.)

Recommendation:

2. JOB CHARACTERISTICS –Employers reduce job barriers to employment and progression in the transport sector (creating a corporate culture that encourages men and women in all sectors of the industry)

Recommendation:

3. PERSONAL CIRCUMSTANCES – Employees' circumstances do not influence people's desire to work and progress in the transport sector (peer pressure on entering some jobs, role models, caring responsibilities)

Recommendation:

4. INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS – Individual characteristics of employees (e.g. gender, age, ethnicity, immigrant etc.) do not influence their employment in the sector

Recommendation:

Figure 45 Outline of the DAD survey questionnaires for the Use Case IV.

Annex 6 – Cluster and validation of the Fairness Characteristics (FCs) by literature review

Validation and clustering of the FCs were performed by analysing the association of the factors with the literature reviews for each Use Case (I – IV).

The analysis was carried out by calculating:

- Cramer's V: used to determine the strength of the statistical relationship between the two variables; and
- χ^2 : used to determine if there is a significant relationship between two nominal (categorical) variables.

Cramér's V coefficient is a measure of association between two nominal variables (X and Y), giving a value between 0 and +1 (inclusive). It is based on Pearson's chi-squared statistic.

This measure is defined as:

$$V = \sqrt{\frac{\chi^2}{n \times t}}$$

where t is the smaller of the number of rows minus one or the number of columns minus one, $t = \min(r - 1, c - 1)$, in this study for each Use case $t=1$.

Cramer's V equals 0 when there is no relationship between the two variables, and generally has a maximum value of 1. This makes it possible to use Cramer's V to compare the strength of association between two variables.

A chi-square test is used to determine if there is a significant relationship between two nominal (categorical) variables. The null hypothesis for this test is that there is no relationship between X and Y variables. The alternative hypothesis is that there is a relationship between the variables. In this test, the frequency of each category for one nominal variable is compared across the categories of the second nominal variable. The data can be displayed in a contingency table where each row represents a category for one variable and each column represents a category for the other variable. Let X and Y are two categorical response variables, χ^2 relates to the 2x2 table (see Table 15) is determined by the relationship:

$$\chi^2 = \left(a - \frac{e \times g}{n}\right)^2 + \left(b - \frac{e \times h}{n}\right)^2 + \left(c - \frac{f \times g}{n}\right)^2 + \left(d - \frac{f \times h}{n}\right)^2$$

Where a, b, c, and d represent the frequencies of observation.

Table 15 Contingency table

		X		Total
		I	0	
Y	I	a	b	e =a+b
	0	c	d	f=c+d
Total		g=a+c	h=b+d	n

The p-value for this test statistic is based on the chi-square probability distribution. The chi-square distribution is defined by the following probability density function:

$$Y = Y_0 \times (\chi^2)^{\left(\frac{v}{2}-1\right)} \times e^{-\left(\frac{\chi^2}{2}\right)}$$

where Y_0 is a constant that depends on the number of degrees of freedom, v , and e is a constant equal to the base of the natural logarithm system. The degrees of freedom for tests of hypothesis that involve an $r \times c$ contingency table is equal to $(r - 1) \times (c - 1)$; thus, for any 2×2 table, $v = 1$. The area under the curve between 0 and a particular chi-square value is a cumulative probability associated with that chi-square value.

Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected if the p-value is less than significance level, called α . In this work, there are defined two significance levels: $\alpha = 0.10$, and $\alpha = 0.20$.

For $p - \text{value} \leq \alpha = 0.10$, the variables X and Y are strongly dependent, which corresponds to a confidence level $\geq 90\%$.

For $\alpha = 0.10 \geq p - \text{value} \geq \alpha = 0.20$, the variables X and Y are averagely dependent, which corresponds to a confidence level between 80% and 90%.

For example analysing the relationship between “Accessibility of the Service” and “Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision”, the null hypothesis is rejected with $\chi^2 = 4.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$, it follows that the two variables are highly dependent on each other.

Table 16 Contingency table for “Accessibility of the Service” and “Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision”

		Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision		Total
		0	I	
Accessibility of the Service	0	3	0	3
	I	6	11	17
Total		9	11	20

Since V-Cramer depends on chi-square, it is possible to define the V-Cramer threshold values for $\alpha = 0.1$ and $\alpha = 0.2$:

- For $\alpha = 0.1 \rightarrow V - \text{Cramer} = 0.37$; and
- For $\alpha = 0.2 \rightarrow V - \text{Cramer} = 0.29$.

In this way, for $V - \text{Cramer} \geq 0.37$ the X and Y variables are associated with strong relationship, and for $0.29 \leq V - \text{Cramer} \leq 0.37$ the X and Y variables are associated with weaker relationship

In the Table 17, Table 18, Table 19 and Table 20, the Cramer coefficients are reported for each pair of variables. Crossing the variables listed in rows and columns, it is possible to read the relative V-Cramer. Similarly in the Table 21,

Table 22, Table 23 and Table 24, the p-value of χ^2 are reported. In boldface statistically significant values were reported with 10% level of significance and in underline statistically significant values were reported with 20% level of significance.

The results show that, for all three cases of the literature review, there is an appreciable dependence between many (128 for Use Case I; 236 for Use Case II; 193 for Use Case III; and 148 for Use Case IV) of the inclusion factors with $V \geq 0.28$ with $p\text{-value} < 0.20$, **corresponding confidence level > 80%**.

In many cases it has been observed that the level II inclusion factors are strongly dependent with the related level I inclusion factors with $V > 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.10$, highlighting how this work is consistent with the identified factors.

For each use case, the main correlations are summarized below:

- 1) For **Use Case I** Literature Review (Figure 46) the following results should be highlighted (see Table 17 and Table 21):

Figure 46 Scheme of Use Case I Literature Review

- Accessibility of the service has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Service availability & efficiency: V-Cramers= 0.64 with p-value <0.01;
 - Travel & wayfinding information provision: V-Cramers = 0.46 with p-value =0.04;
 - Ticketing options & fares: V-Cramers = 0.64 with p-value <0.01;
- Design of the Infrastructure
 - Universal Design: V-Cramers = 0.33 with p-value 0.16;
 - Cleanliness and Maintenance: V-Cramers = 0.38 with p-value = 0.10;
 - Furniture & Facilities: V-Cramers = 0.49 with p-value <0.01;
- Safety & Security
 - Harassment and Pickpocketing: V-Cramers = 1.00 with p-value <0.01;
 - Overcrowding and Emergency Situations: V-Cramers= 0.46 with p-value 0.04.

- 2) For **Use Case II** Literature Review (Figure 47) the following results should be highlighted (see Table 18 and
- 3) Table 22):

Figure 47 Fairness characteristics for Use Case II

- Safety & Security has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Accident rate: V-Cramers= 0.34 with p-value = 0.09;
- Comfort has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Trust in technology: V-Cramers= 1.00 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Simultaneity: V-Cramers= 0.35 with p-value = 0.08;
- Mobility has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Traffic efficiency: V-Cramers = 0.60 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Congestion: V-Cramers = 0.38 with p-value = 0.06;
 - Accessibility: V-Cramers = 0.38 p-value = 0.06;
- Economy has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Monetary costs: V-Cramers = 0.82 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Non-monetary costs: V-Cramers = 0.43 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Vehicle efficiency: V-Cramers = 0.43 with p-value < 0.01;
- Environment has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Emissions: V-Cramers = 0.75with p-value < 0.01;
 - Public Health: V-Cramers = 0.58 with p-value < 0.01;
- Design options has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Infrastructure adaptation: V-Cramers = 0.61 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Vehicle shape:V-Cramers = 0.33 with p-value = 0.09;
 - Vehicle behavior: V-Cramers = 0.36 with p-value = 0.09;
 - Human Machine Interface: V-Cramers = 0.76 with p-value < 0.01;

4) For **Use Case III** Literature Review (Figure 48) the following results should be highlighted (see Table 19 and Table 23):

Figure 48 Fairness characteristics for Use Case III

- Accessibility and Spontainety has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Public awareness: V-Cramers = 0.41 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Sign-up & booking process: V-Cramers = 0.35 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Membership cost: V-Cramers = 0.35 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Proximity of docking station: V-Cramers = 0.45 with p-value < 0.01;
- Safety & Security has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Safe environment: V-Cramers = 0.40 with p-value = 0.056;
 - Traffic safety: V-Cramers = 0.70 with p-value < 0.01;
- Social constraints have a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Subjective norm: V-Cramers =0.49 with p-value =0.02;
 - Socio-cultural constrain: V-Cramers =0.78 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Family responsibilities: V-Cramers =0.49 with p-value =0.02;
- Weather & Topography has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Weather: V-Cramers =0.91 with p-value < 0.01;
 - Topography: V-Cramers =0.66 with p-value < 0.01.

- 5) For **Use Case IV** Literature Review (Figure 49) the following results should be highlighted (see Table 20 and Table 24):

Figure 49 Fairness characteristics for Use Case IV

- Socio-economic conditions have a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Demand Factors: V-Cramers = 0.42 with p-value=0.02;
 - Policy/Legal: V-Cramers = 0.48 with p-value=0.01;
 - HR Policies: V-Cramers = 0.56 with p-value ≤ 0.01;
- Job Characteristics conditions has a strong connection with the following second level factor:
 - Safety and Security: V-Cramers = 0.30 with p-value=0.09;
- Personal Circumstances has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Caring/Parenting responsibilities: V-Cramers = 0.29 with p-value=0.02;
- Individual Characteristics has a strong connection with the following second level factors:
 - Skills: V-Cramers = 0.40 with p-value=0.02;
 - Educational level/attainment: V-Cramers = 0.30 with p-value=0.09;
 - Demographic (Age, ethnicity, etc.): V-Cramers = 0.30 with p-value=0.09.

Another important result is that many second level factors are also associated with other second level factors related to different level fairness characteristics, highlighting that the identified inclusion factors are significant not only for their cluster but also for other clusters, such as for use case I literature review “Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision” and “Furniture & Facilities” are associated with $V = 0.452$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$.

These correlations express that these variables express a more complex phenomenology. Of particular importance, each factor is related to at least one other factor, thus inducing an association of chain inclusion factors, showing that these identified inclusion factors are well represented also by literature.

Table 17. Cramer's V for Use Case I Literature Review

Variables	V1 L3 - Public transport	V4 L1 - New technologies	V4 L2 - New business models	Accessibility of the Service	Design of the Infrastructure	Safety & Security	Service Availability & Efficiency	Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision	Ticketing Options & Fares	Travel Purpose	Universal Design	Cleanliness and Maintenance	Furniture & Facilities	Harassment and Pickpocketing	Overcrowding and Emergency Situations
V1 L3 - Public transport	1.00	0.69	0.55	0.10	0.55	0.10	<u>0.35</u>	0.21	0.15	0.13	0.69	0.21	0.46	0.10	0.25
V4 L1 - New technologies	0.69	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	0.14	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.15	<u>0.30</u>	0.22	0.19	1.00	0.03	0.25	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.37</u>
V4 L2 - New business models	0.55	<u>0.33</u>	1.00	0.18	0.61	0.22	0.03	0.38	0.28	0.24	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.49	0.22	0.46
Accessibility of the Service	0.10	0.14	0.18	1.00	0.18	0.18	0.64	0.46	0.64	0.24	0.14	0.10	0.21	0.18	0.10
Design of the Infr.	0.55	<u>0.33</u>	0.61	0.18	1.00	0.61	<u>0.34</u>	0.38	0.28	0.24	<u>0.33</u>	0.38	0.49	0.61	0.46
Saf. & Secu.	0.10	<u>0.33</u>	0.22	0.18	0.61	1.00	0.03	0.38	0.28	0.08	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.14	1.00	0.46
Ser. Availability & Efficiency	<u>0.35</u>	0.15	0.03	0.64	<u>0.34</u>	0.03	1.00	0.07	0.29	0.38	0.15	0.15	0.22	0.03	0.07
Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision	0.21	<u>0.30</u>	0.38	0.46	0.38	0.38	0.07	1.00	0.29	0.06	0.30	0.01	0.45	0.38	0.01
Ticketing Options & Fares	0.15	0.22	0.28	0.64	0.28	0.28	0.29	0.29	1.00	0.38	0.22	0.07	<u>0.33</u>	0.28	0.15
Travel Purpose	0.13	0.19	0.24	0.24	0.24	0.08	0.38	0.06	0.38	1.00	0.19	0.17	0.00	0.08	0.06
Universal Design	0.69	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	0.14	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.15	0.30	0.22	0.19	1.00	0.03	0.25	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.37</u>
Cleanliness and Maintenance	0.21	0.03	0.10	0.10	0.38	0.10	0.15	0.01	0.07	0.17	0.03	1.00	0.05	0.10	0.01
Furniture & Facilities	0.46	0.25	0.49	0.21	0.49	0.14	0.22	0.45	<u>0.33</u>	0.00	0.25	0.05	1.00	0.14	0.05
Harassment and Pickpocketing	0.10	<u>0.33</u>	0.22	0.18	0.61	1.00	0.03	0.38	0.28	0.08	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.14	1.00	0.46
Overcrowding and Emergency Situations	0.25	<u>0.37</u>	0.46	0.10	0.46	0.46	0.07	0.01	0.15	0.06	<u>0.37</u>	0.01	0.05	0.46	1.00

Note: **boldface** indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance; underline indicates statistically significant values with 20% level of significance.

Table 18. Cramer's V for Use Case II Literature Review

Variables	V2-L1. Vehicles today	V5-L1. Vehicles tom.	Safety	Comfort	Mobility	Economy	Environment	Design options	Accident rate	Human errors	Training	Traffic management	Trust in technology	Simultaneity	Traffic efficiency	Travel time	Congestion	Accessibility	Monetary costs	Non-monetary costs	Vehicle efficiency	Noise	Emissions	Public Health	Infr. adaptation	Vehicle shape	Vehicle behaviour	HMI)
V2-L1. Veh. today	1.00	0.15	0.11	0.23	0.18	<u>0.29</u>	0.16	0.18	0.13	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.23	0.08	<u>0.29</u>	0.04	0.09	0.09	0.12	0.06	0.69	0.04	0.12	0.09	0.11	0.06	0.06	0.13
V5-L1. Vehicles tom.	0.15	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	<u>0.30</u>	0.13	0.37	<u>0.30</u>	0.26	0.27	0.11	<u>0.32</u>	0.12	0.27	0.50	0.15	0.16	0.08	0.20	0.21	0.11	0.15	0.20	<u>0.32</u>	0.15	0.11	0.11	0.52
Safety	0.11	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	0.06	0.61	0.36	0.40	0.02	<u>0.33</u>	0.19	0.15	0.23	0.06	0.19	0.36	0.11	0.23	0.23	<u>0.30</u>	0.15	0.15	0.11	<u>0.30</u>	0.23	0.01	0.22	0.22	0.12
Comfort	0.23	0.12	0.06	1.00	0.07	0.24	0.02	0.24	0.04	<u>0.35</u>	0.28	0.04	1.00	<u>0.35</u>	0.06	0.23	0.04	0.41	0.24	<u>0.33</u>	0.03	0.23	0.05	0.04	<u>0.35</u>	0.03	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>
Mobility	0.18	<u>0.30</u>	0.61	0.07	1.00	0.42	0.48	0.14	0.02	0.19	0.05	0.15	0.07	<u>0.32</u>	0.60	0.18	0.38	0.38	<u>0.29</u>	0.25	0.25	0.18	<u>0.29</u>	0.15	0.02	0.05	<u>0.36</u>	0.39
Economy	<u>0.29</u>	0.13	0.36	0.24	0.42	1.00	0.55	0.12	0.13	0.27	0.21	0.40	0.24	0.00	0.25	<u>0.29</u>	0.63	<u>0.32</u>	0.82	0.43	0.43	<u>0.29</u>	0.20	0.40	0.07	0.11	0.21	0.26
Environment	0.16	0.37	0.40	0.02	0.48	0.55	1.00	0.13	0.07	0.03	0.08	<u>0.35</u>	0.02	0.03	0.37	0.27	<u>0.35</u>	0.12	0.55	0.39	0.08	0.27	0.75	0.58	0.03	0.08	0.23	0.50
Design options	0.18	<u>0.30</u>	0.02	0.24	0.14	0.12	0.13	1.00	0.20	0.19	0.05	<u>0.30</u>	0.24	<u>0.32</u>	0.06	0.25	<u>0.30</u>	0.38	<u>0.29</u>	0.05	0.25	0.25	<u>0.29</u>	0.15	0.61	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.76
Accident rate	0.13	0.26	<u>0.33</u>	0.04	0.02	0.13	0.07	0.20	1.00	0.03	0.14	0.20	0.04	0.03	0.06	<u>0.32</u>	0.20	0.04	0.26	0.14	0.19	<u>0.32</u>	0.05	0.20	<u>0.35</u>	0.14	0.14	0.01
Human errors	0.08	0.27	0.19	<u>0.35</u>	0.19	0.27	0.03	0.19	0.03	1.00	<u>0.34</u>	0.17	<u>0.35</u>	0.14	0.27	0.08	0.17	0.17	0.22	0.11	0.11	0.08	0.07	0.17	0.19	0.11	0.11	<u>0.31</u>
Training	0.06	0.11	0.15	0.28	0.05	0.21	0.08	0.05	0.14	<u>0.34</u>	1.00	0.13	0.28	0.11	0.11	0.06	0.13	0.27	0.17	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.17	0.13	0.15	0.09	0.09	0.14
Traffic management	0.09	<u>0.32</u>	0.23	0.04	0.15	0.40	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.20	0.17	0.13	1.00	0.04	0.17	0.40	0.09	0.10	0.20	0.52	0.13	0.13	0.09	0.00	0.40	<u>0.32</u>	0.27	0.13	0.04
Trust in technology	0.23	0.12	0.06	1.00	0.07	0.24	0.02	0.24	0.04	<u>0.35</u>	0.28	0.04	1.00	<u>0.35</u>	0.06	0.23	0.04	0.41	0.24	<u>0.33</u>	0.03	0.23	0.05	0.04	<u>0.35</u>	0.03	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>
Simultaneity	0.08	0.27	0.19	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.32</u>	0.00	0.03	<u>0.32</u>	0.03	0.14	0.11	0.17	<u>0.35</u>	1.00	0.00	0.08	0.17	0.17	0.22	0.11	<u>0.34</u>	0.08	0.07	0.17	0.19	0.11	0.11	0.24
Traffic efficiency	<u>0.29</u>	0.50	0.36	0.06	0.60	0.25	0.37	0.06	0.06	0.27	0.11	0.40	0.06	0.00	1.00	0.15	0.08	0.08	0.20	0.11	0.11	0.15	0.00	0.16	0.07	0.11	0.21	0.26
Travel time	0.04	0.15	0.11	0.23	0.18	<u>0.29</u>	0.27	0.25	<u>0.32</u>	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.23	0.08	0.15	1.00	0.47	0.09	0.36	0.69	0.06	1.00	0.36	0.09	0.41	0.06	0.06	0.13
Congestion	0.09	0.16	0.23	0.04	0.38	0.63	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.20	0.17	0.13	0.10	0.04	0.17	0.08	0.47	1.00	0.20	0.52	0.27	0.27	0.47	0.26	0.10	<u>0.32</u>	0.27	0.13	0.04
Accessibility	0.09	0.08	0.23	0.41	0.38	<u>0.32</u>	0.12	0.38	0.04	0.17	0.27	0.20	0.41	0.17	0.08	0.09	0.20	1.00	0.26	0.13	0.13	0.09	0.26	0.10	0.23	0.13	0.13	<u>0.29</u>
Monetary costs	0.12	0.20	<u>0.30</u>	0.24	<u>0.29</u>	0.82	0.55	<u>0.29</u>	0.26	0.22	0.17	0.52	0.24	0.22	0.20	0.36	0.52	0.26	1.00	0.52	0.17	0.36	0.11	0.52	0.18	0.17	0.17	0.16
Non-monetary costs	0.06	0.21	0.15	<u>0.33</u>	0.25	0.43	0.39	0.05	0.14	0.11	0.09	0.13	<u>0.33</u>	0.11	0.11	0.69	0.27	0.13	0.52	1.00	0.09	0.69	0.17	0.27	0.22	0.09	0.09	0.19
Vehicle efficiency	0.69	0.11	0.15	0.03	0.25	0.43	0.08	0.25	0.19	0.11	0.09	0.13	0.03	<u>0.34</u>	0.11	0.06	0.27	0.13	0.17	0.09	1.00	0.06	0.17	0.13	0.15	0.09	0.09	0.19
Noise	0.04	0.15	0.11	0.23	0.18	<u>0.29</u>	0.27	0.25	<u>0.32</u>	0.08	0.06	0.09	0.23	0.08	0.15	1.00	0.47	0.09	0.36	0.69	0.06	1.00	0.36	0.09	0.41	0.06	0.06	0.13
Emissions	0.12	0.20	<u>0.30</u>	0.05	<u>0.29</u>	0.20	0.75	<u>0.29</u>	0.05	0.07	0.17	0.00	0.05	0.07	0.00	0.36	0.26	0.26	0.11	0.17	0.17	0.36	1.00	0.26	0.06	0.17	0.17	0.37
Public Health	0.09	<u>0.32</u>	0.23	0.04	0.15	0.40	0.58	0.15	0.20	0.17	0.13	0.40	0.04	0.17	0.16	0.09	0.10	0.10	0.52	0.27	0.13	0.09	0.26	1.00	0.05	0.27	0.13	<u>0.29</u>
Infr.ad.	0.11	0.15	0.01	<u>0.35</u>	0.02	0.07	0.03	0.61	<u>0.35</u>	0.19	0.15	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.19	0.07	0.41	<u>0.32</u>	0.23	0.18	0.22	0.15	0.41	0.06	0.05	1.00	0.59	0.59	<u>0.35</u>
Vehicle shape	0.06	0.11	0.22	0.03	0.05	0.11	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.14	0.11	0.09	0.27	0.03	0.11	0.11	0.06	0.27	0.13	0.17	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.17	0.27	0.59	1.00	0.45	0.14
Vehicle behaviour	0.06	0.11	0.22	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.23	<u>0.36</u>	0.14	0.11	0.09	0.13	<u>0.33</u>	0.11	0.21	0.06	0.13	0.13	0.17	0.09	0.09	0.06	0.17	0.13	0.59	0.45	1.00	0.47
(HMI)	0.13	0.52	0.12	<u>0.33</u>	0.39	0.26	0.50	0.76	0.01	<u>0.31</u>	0.14	0.04	<u>0.33</u>	0.24	0.26	0.13	0.04	<u>0.29</u>	0.16	0.19	0.19	0.13	0.37	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.14	0.47	1.00

Note: **boldface** indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance; underline indicates statistically significant values with 20% level of significance.

Table 19. Cramer's V for Use Case III Literature Review

	VI L3 - Public transport.	V4 L1 - New tech.	V4 L2 - New bus.model s	Acc. & spont.	Safety & Security	Social constraints	Weather & Topograp hy	Public awareness	Sign-up	Memb. cost	Sp. of accessing bike	Prox.- docking stat.	Trav.with child.	Ins. Infr.	Dr. behaviour	Sep. Infr.	Harassme nt	Safe env.	Traffic safety	Subjective norm	Socio-cult.const r.	Family resp.	Weather	Topograp hy	Confidenc e
VI L3 - Public transport.	1.00	0.67	0.17	0.11	0.27	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.11	0.05	0.23	0.80	0.13	0.15	0.15	0.11	0.47	0.17	0.28	0.17	0.21	0.22	0.15
V4 L1 - New tech.	0.67	1.00	0.00	0.17	0.10	0.53	0.12	0.26	0.04	0.19	0.08	0.08	<u>0.35</u>	0.51	0.20	0.05	0.23	0.16	0.20	0.26	0.41	0.26	0.08	0.05	0.23
V4 L2 - New bus. models	0.17	0.00	1.00	0.07	0.26	0.10	0.15	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.00	0.49	0.15	<u>0.36</u>	0.00	0.18	0.06	0.00	0.05	0.11	0.14	<u>0.33</u>	0.00	0.18	0.18
Acc. & spont.	0.11	0.17	0.07	1.00	0.17	0.06	0.49	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.27	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.34</u>	0.17	0.12	0.19	0.27	0.03	<u>0.36</u>	0.16	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.12	0.12
Safety & Security	0.27	0.10	0.26	0.17	1.00	<u>0.30</u>	0.12	0.04	0.26	0.04	0.16	0.08	0.12	0.51	0.20	0.23	0.23	0.40	0.70	0.26	0.19	0.26	0.08	0.05	0.23
Social constraints	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.10	0.06	<u>0.30</u>	1.00	0.22	0.07	0.24	0.27	0.12	0.20	0.65	0.45	0.08	0.23	0.43	0.06	0.57	0.49	0.78	0.49	0.12	0.19	0.43
Weat. & Top.	0.08	0.12	0.15	0.49	0.12	0.22	1.00	<u>0.32</u>	0.02	<u>0.37</u>	0.18	0.39	0.24	0.03	<u>0.35</u>	0.03	0.40	0.18	0.07	0.05	0.02	0.15	0.91	0.66	0.19
Public awareness	0.03	0.26	0.14	<u>0.33</u>	0.04	0.07	<u>0.32</u>	1.00	0.17	<u>0.34</u>	0.12	0.41	0.15	0.09	0.19	0.15	0.15	0.24	0.04	0.24	0.01	0.05	0.24	0.15	0.15
Sign-up	0.03	0.04	0.14	<u>0.33</u>	0.26	0.24	0.02	0.17	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	0.41	0.10	0.19	0.16	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.12	0.15	0.14	0.17	0.53	0.12	<u>0.35</u>	0.06
Memb. cost	0.03	0.19	0.14	<u>0.35</u>	0.04	0.27	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.34</u>	<u>0.33</u>	1.00	0.24	0.27	0.02	0.16	0.41	0.27	0.15	<u>0.30</u>	0.04	0.05	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.34</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.27	0.06
Sp. of accessing bike	0.11	0.08	0.00	0.27	0.16	0.12	0.18	0.12	0.41	0.24	1.00	0.24	0.00	0.27	0.08	0.15	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.06	0.20	0.12	0.20	<u>0.31</u>	0.07	0.07
Prox.- docking stat.	0.05	0.08	0.49	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.20	0.39	0.41	0.10	0.27	0.24	1.00	0.22	0.06	0.08	0.40	0.02	0.12	0.17	<u>0.29</u>	0.10	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.19	0.19
Trav.with child.	0.23	<u>0.35</u>	0.15	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	0.65	0.24	0.15	0.19	0.02	0.00	0.22	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	0.03	0.66	0.18	<u>0.31</u>	0.75	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.18	0.19	0.66
Ins. Infr.	0.80	0.51	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.34</u>	0.51	0.45	0.03	0.09	0.16	0.16	0.27	0.06	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	0.17	0.19	0.19	0.00	0.59	0.22	<u>0.35</u>	0.22	0.27	0.12	0.19
Dr. behaviour	0.13	0.20	0.00	0.17	0.20	0.08	<u>0.35</u>	0.19	0.04	0.41	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.17	1.00	0.23	0.23	0.16	0.04	0.26	0.19	0.00	0.40	<u>0.32</u>	0.23
Sep. Infr.	0.15	0.05	0.18	0.12	0.23	0.23	0.03	0.15	0.06	0.27	0.15	0.40	0.03	0.19	0.23	1.00	0.01	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.06	0.15	0.41	0.07	0.24	0.24
Harassment	0.15	0.23	0.06	0.19	0.23	0.43	0.40	0.15	0.06	0.15	<u>0.29</u>	0.02	0.66	0.19	0.23	0.01	1.00	0.15	<u>0.33</u>	0.41	0.15	0.18	<u>0.36</u>	0.26	0.75
Safe env. & pers. safety	0.11	0.16	0.00	0.27	0.40	0.06	0.18	0.24	0.12	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.12	0.18	0.00	0.16	<u>0.36</u>	0.15	1.00	0.13	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.15	0.15
Traffic safety	0.47	0.20	0.05	0.03	0.70	0.57	0.07	0.04	0.15	0.04	0.06	0.17	<u>0.31</u>	0.59	0.04	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.13	1.00	0.37	0.41	0.37	0.06	0.12	<u>0.33</u>
Subjective norm	0.17	0.26	0.11	<u>0.36</u>	0.26	0.49	0.05	0.24	0.14	0.05	0.20	<u>0.29</u>	0.75	0.22	0.26	0.06	0.41	0.00	0.37	1.00	0.24	0.11	0.00	0.06	0.41
Socio-cult.const r.	0.28	0.41	0.14	0.16	0.19	0.78	0.02	0.01	0.17	<u>0.33</u>	0.12	0.10	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.19	0.15	0.15	0.06	0.41	0.24	1.00	0.43	0.06	0.06	0.15
Family resp.	0.17	0.26	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.26	0.49	0.15	0.05	0.53	<u>0.34</u>	0.20	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.22	0.00	0.41	0.18	0.00	0.37	0.11	0.43	1.00	0.20	0.06	0.41
Weather	0.21	0.08	0.00	0.53	0.08	0.12	0.91	0.24	0.12	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.18	0.27	0.40	0.07	<u>0.36</u>	0.06	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.20	1.00	0.51	0.15
Topography	0.22	0.05	0.18	0.12	0.05	0.19	0.66	0.15	<u>0.35</u>	0.27	0.07	0.19	0.19	0.12	<u>0.32</u>	0.24	0.26	0.15	0.12	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.51	1.00	0.01
Confidence	0.15	0.23	0.18	0.12	0.23	0.43	0.19	0.15	0.06	0.06	0.07	0.19	0.66	0.19	0.23	0.24	0.75	0.15	<u>0.33</u>	0.41	0.15	0.41	0.15	0.01	1.00

Note: **boldface** indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance; underline indicates statistically significant values with 20% level of significance.

Table 20. Cramer's V for Use Case IV Literature Review

Variables	V3 Job Holders Today	V6 Job Holders Tomorrow	Socio-economic Conditions	Job Characteristics	Personal Circumstances	Individual Characteristics	Job Segregation	Demand Factors	Policy/Legal	HR Policies	Terms and Conditions	Training Provision	Safety and Security	Female facilities	Caring/Parenting responsibilities	Economic Deprivation	Access to/ownership off resources	Skills	Adaptability attitudes	Educational level/attainment	Health Status and Wellbeing	Demographic
V3 Job Holders Today	1.00	1.00	0.06	0.80	0.21	0.21	0.45	0.16	0.12	0.27	0.12	0.20	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.45	0.12	0.04	0.18	0.20	0.00	0.18
V6 Job Holders Tomorrow	1.00	1.00	0.06	0.80	0.21	0.21	0.45	0.16	0.12	0.27	0.12	0.20	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.45	0.12	0.04	0.18	0.20	0.00	0.18
Socio-economic Conditions	0.06	0.06	1.00	0.04	0.07	0.48	0.07	0.42	0.48	0.56	0.07	0.13	0.15	0.17	0.06	0.13	0.08	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.23	0.13	0.14
Job Characteristics	0.80	0.80	0.04	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.29</u>	0.60	0.25	0.09	<u>0.36</u>	0.09	0.07	<u>0.30</u>	0.26	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.16	0.14	0.07	0.09	0.06
Personal Circumstance	0.21	0.21	0.07	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	0.43	<u>0.36</u>	0.10	0.14	0.21	0.14	0.09	0.06	0.01	0.21	0.07	0.07	0.19	0.01	0.09	0.07	0.11
Individual Characteristics	0.21	0.21	0.48	<u>0.29</u>	0.43	1.00	0.62	0.10	0.15	0.85	0.14	0.11	0.06	0.01	0.53	0.07	0.07	0.40	0.22	<u>0.30</u>	0.07	<u>0.30</u>
Job Segregation	0.45	0.45	0.07	0.60	<u>0.36</u>	0.62	1.00	0.06	0.16	0.45	0.16	0.21	0.15	0.27	0.45	0.06	0.02	0.12	0.04	0.21	0.12	0.01
Demand Factors	0.16	0.16	0.42	0.25	0.10	0.10	0.06	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	0.16	0.10	0.21	0.02	0.10	0.13	0.12	0.20	0.12	0.16	0.21	0.12	0.17
Policy/Legal	0.12	0.12	0.48	0.09	0.14	0.15	0.16	<u>0.36</u>	1.00	0.21	0.15	0.11	0.06	0.17	0.12	0.07	0.07	0.02	0.01	0.11	0.13	0.08
HR Policies	0.27	0.27	0.56	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.85	0.45	0.16	0.21	1.00	0.12	0.02	0.16	0.12	0.27	0.00	0.12	0.28	<u>0.31</u>	0.20	0.00	0.25
Terms and Conditions	0.12	0.12	0.07	0.09	0.14	0.14	0.16	0.10	0.15	0.12	1.00	0.11	<u>0.32</u>	0.17	0.12	0.26	0.18	0.02	0.01	<u>0.30</u>	0.13	<u>0.30</u>
Training Provision	0.20	0.20	0.13	0.07	0.09	0.11	0.21	0.21	0.11	0.02	0.11	1.00	0.12	0.15	0.20	0.13	0.19	0.04	0.13	<u>0.35</u>	0.13	0.04
Safety and Security	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.15	<u>0.30</u>	0.06	0.06	0.15	0.02	0.06	0.16	<u>0.32</u>	0.12	1.00	0.52	0.16	0.17	0.23	0.11	0.06	0.01	0.04	<u>0.31</u>
Female facilities	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.17	0.26	0.01	0.01	0.27	0.10	0.17	0.12	0.17	0.15	0.52	1.00	0.12	0.21	0.01	0.05	0.12	0.10	0.09	0.04
Caring/Parenting responsibilities	0.10	0.10	0.06	0.08	0.21	0.53	0.45	0.13	0.12	0.27	0.12	0.20	0.16	0.12	1.00	0.00	0.12	0.28	0.07	0.20	0.00	0.04
Economic Deprivation - social network	0.45	0.45	0.13	<u>0.36</u>	0.07	0.07	0.06	0.12	0.07	0.00	0.26	0.13	0.17	0.21	0.00	1.00	0.67	<u>0.29</u>	0.25	0.27	0.45	0.22
Access to/ownership off resources	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.21	0.07	0.07	0.02	0.20	0.07	0.12	0.18	0.19	0.23	0.01	0.12	0.67	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	0.27	<u>0.36</u>	0.67	0.26
Skills	0.04	0.04	<u>0.29</u>	0.16	0.19	0.40	0.12	0.12	0.02	0.28	0.02	0.04	0.11	0.05	0.28	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	0.67	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.35</u>
Adaptability, attitudes to work and travel to work	0.18	0.18	<u>0.31</u>	0.14	0.01	0.22	0.04	0.16	0.01	<u>0.31</u>	0.01	0.13	0.06	0.12	0.07	0.25	0.27	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	0.16	0.40	<u>0.31</u>
Educational level/attainment	0.20	0.20	0.23	0.07	0.09	<u>0.30</u>	0.21	0.21	0.11	0.20	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.01	0.10	0.20	0.27	<u>0.36</u>	0.67	0.16	1.00	0.27	0.22
Health Status and Wellbeing	0.00	0.00	0.13	0.09	0.07	0.07	0.12	0.12	0.13	0.00	0.13	0.13	0.04	0.09	0.00	0.45	0.67	<u>0.29</u>	0.40	0.27	1.00	0.04
Demographic	0.18	0.18	0.14	0.06	0.11	<u>0.30</u>	0.01	0.17	0.08	0.25	<u>0.30</u>	0.04	<u>0.31</u>	0.04	0.04	0.22	0.26	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.22	0.04	1.00

Note: **boldface** indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance; underline indicates statistically significant values with 20% level of significance.

Table 21. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case I Literature Review

	V1 L3 - Public transport	V4 L1 - New technologies	V4 L2 - New business models	Accessibility of the Service	Design of the Infrastructure	Safety & Security	Service Availability & Efficiency	Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision	Ticketing Options & Fares	Travel Purpose	Universal Design	Cleanliness and Maintenance	Furniture & Facilities	Harassment and Pickpocketing	Overcrowding and Emergency Situations
V1 L3 - Public transport	-	<0.01	0.01	0.69	0.01	0.69	<u>0.13</u>	0.38	0.53	0.58	<0.01	0.38	0.04	0.69	0.28
V4 L1 - New technologies	<0.01	-	<u>0.16</u>	0.56	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.16</u>	0.54	<u>0.20</u>	0.36	0.42	<0.01	0.89	0.29	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.11</u>
V4 L2 - New business models	0.01	<u>0.16</u>	-	0.46	<0.01	0.36	0.90	0.10	0.24	0.30	<u>0.16</u>	0.68	0.03	0.36	0.04
Accessibility of the Service	0.69	0.56	0.46	-	0.46	0.46	<0.01	0.04	<0.01	0.30	0.56	0.68	0.37	0.46	0.68
Design of the Infrastructure	0.01	<u>0.16</u>	<0.01	0.46	-	<0.01	<u>0.15</u>	0.10	0.24	0.30	<u>0.16</u>	0.10	0.03	<0.01	0.04
Safety & Security	0.69	<u>0.16</u>	0.36	0.46	<0.01	-	0.90	0.10	0.24	0.73	<u>0.16</u>	0.68	0.56	<0.01	0.04
Service Availability & Efficiency	0.13	0.54	0.90	<0.01	<u>0.15</u>	0.90	-	0.78	0.22	0.10	0.54	0.52	0.36	0.90	0.78
Travel and Wayfinding Information Provision	0.38	<u>0.20</u>	0.10	0.04	0.10	0.10	0.78	-	0.22	0.81	<u>0.20</u>	0.97	0.05	0.10	0.97
Ticketing Options & Fares	0.53	0.36	0.24	<0.01	0.24	0.24	0.22	0.22	-	0.10	0.36	0.78	<u>0.16</u>	0.24	0.52
Travel Purpose	0.58	0.42	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.73	0.10	0.81	0.10	-	0.42	0.46	1.00	0.73	0.81
Universal Design	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.16</u>	0.56	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.16</u>	0.54	0.20	0.36	0.42	-	0.89	0.29	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.11</u>
Cleanliness and Maintenance	0.38	0.89	0.68	0.68	0.10	0.68	0.52	0.97	0.78	0.46	0.89	-	0.83	0.68	0.97
Furniture & Facilities	0.04	0.29	0.03	0.37	0.03	0.56	0.36	0.05	0.16	1.00	0.29	0.83	-	0.56	0.83
Harassment and Pickpocketing	0.69	<u>0.16</u>	0.36	0.46	<0.01	<0.01	0.90	0.10	0.24	0.73	<u>0.16</u>	0.68	0.56	-	0.04
Overcrowding and Emergency Situations	0.28	<u>0.11</u>	0.04	0.68	0.04	0.04	0.78	0.97	0.52	0.81	<u>0.11</u>	0.97	0.83	0.04	-

Note: **boldface** indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance; underline indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance.

Table 22. p-value of χ^2 for Use Case II Literature Review

Variables	V2-L1. Veh. today	V5-L1. Veh. tomorrow	Safety	Comfort	Mobility	Economy	Environment	Design options	Accident rate	Human errors	Training	Traf. management	Trust in technology	Simultaneity	Traffic efficiency	Travel time	Congestion	Accessibility	Mon. costs	Non-monetary costs	Veh. efficiency	Noise	Emissions	Public Health	Infr. Adap.	Veh. shape	Veh. behaviour	HMI
V2-L1. Veh. today	<0.01	0.49	0.62	0.29	0.41	<u>0.16</u>	0.45	0.41	0.53	0.71	0.77	0.66	0.29	0.71	<u>0.16</u>	0.84	0.66	0.66	0.58	0.77	<0.01	0.84	0.58	0.66	0.62	0.77	0.77	0.53
V5-L1. Veh. tom.	0.49	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.58	<u>0.16</u>	0.56	0.08	<u>0.16</u>	0.22	0.21	0.62	<u>0.13</u>	0.58	0.21	0.01	0.49	0.46	0.71	0.34	0.32	0.62	0.49	0.34	<u>0.13</u>	0.50	0.62	0.62	0.01
Safety	0.62	<u>0.17</u>	<0.01	0.78	<0.01	0.08	0.05	0.94	<u>0.12</u>	0.36	0.47	0.28	0.78	0.36	0.08	0.62	0.28	0.28	<u>0.16</u>	0.47	0.47	0.62	<u>0.16</u>	0.28	0.96	0.31	0.31	0.57
Comfort	0.29	0.58	0.78	<0.01	0.74	0.27	0.92	0.26	0.86	0.10	<u>0.19</u>	0.86	<0.01	0.10	0.78	0.29	0.86	0.05	0.26	<u>0.12</u>	0.91	0.29	0.82	0.86	0.09	0.91	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>
Mobility	0.41	<u>0.16</u>	<0.01	0.74	<0.01	0.04	0.02	0.51	0.94	0.37	0.81	0.48	0.74	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	0.41	0.07	0.07	<u>0.17</u>	0.23	0.23	0.41	<u>0.17</u>	0.48	0.94	0.81	0.09	0.06
Economy	<u>0.16</u>	0.56	0.08	0.27	0.04	<0.01	0.01	0.58	0.55	0.21	0.32	0.06	0.27	1.00	0.24	<u>0.16</u>	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	0.04	0.04	<u>0.16</u>	0.34	0.06	0.74	0.62	0.32	0.22
Environment	0.45	0.08	0.05	0.92	0.02	0.01	<0.01	0.54	0.74	0.88	0.72	0.10	0.92	0.88	0.08	0.20	0.10	0.59	0.01	0.06	0.72	0.20	<0.01	<0.01	0.90	0.72	0.27	0.01
Design options	0.41	<u>0.16</u>	0.94	0.26	0.51	0.58	0.54	<0.01	0.35	0.37	0.81	<u>0.15</u>	0.26	<u>0.13</u>	0.78	0.25	<u>0.15</u>	0.07	<u>0.17</u>	0.81	0.23	0.25	<u>0.17</u>	0.48	<0.01	0.09	0.09	<0.01
Accident rate	0.53	0.22	<u>0.12</u>	0.86	0.94	0.55	0.74	0.35	<0.01	0.87	0.52	0.34	0.86	0.87	0.76	<u>0.12</u>	0.34	0.85	0.21	0.52	0.37	<u>0.12</u>	0.81	0.34	0.10	0.52	0.52	0.97
Human errors	0.71	0.21	0.36	0.10	0.37	0.21	0.88	0.37	0.87	<0.01	<u>0.10</u>	0.43	0.10	0.51	0.21	0.71	0.43	0.43	0.31	0.60	0.60	0.71	0.74	0.43	0.36	0.60	0.60	<u>0.14</u>
Training	0.77	0.62	0.47	<u>0.19</u>	0.81	0.32	0.72	0.81	0.52	<u>0.10</u>	<0.01	0.53	<u>0.19</u>	0.60	0.62	0.77	0.53	0.20	0.42	0.67	0.67	0.77	0.42	0.53	0.47	0.67	0.67	0.52
Traffic management	0.66	<u>0.13</u>	0.28	0.86	0.48	0.06	0.10	<u>0.15</u>	0.34	0.43	0.53	<0.01	0.86	0.43	0.06	0.66	0.64	0.35	0.01	0.53	0.53	0.66	1.00	0.05	<u>0.13</u>	0.20	0.53	0.85
Trust in tech.	0.29	0.58	0.78	<0.01	0.74	0.27	0.92	0.26	0.86	0.10	<u>0.19</u>	0.86	<0.01	0.10	0.78	0.29	0.86	0.05	0.26	<u>0.12</u>	0.91	0.29	0.82	0.86	0.09	0.91	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>
Simultaneity	0.71	0.21	0.36	0.10	<u>0.13</u>	1.00	0.88	<u>0.13</u>	0.87	0.51	0.60	0.43	0.10	<0.01	1.00	0.71	0.43	0.43	0.31	0.60	<u>0.10</u>	0.71	0.74	0.43	0.36	0.60	0.60	0.25
Traffic efficiency	<u>0.16</u>	0.01	0.08	0.78	<0.01	0.24	0.08	0.78	0.76	0.21	0.62	0.06	0.78	1.00	<0.01	0.49	0.71	0.71	0.34	0.62	0.62	0.49	1.00	0.46	0.74	0.62	0.32	0.22
Travel time	0.84	0.49	0.62	0.29	0.41	<u>0.16</u>	0.20	0.25	<u>0.12</u>	0.71	0.77	0.66	0.29	0.71	0.49	<0.01	0.02	0.66	0.08	<0.01	0.77	<0.01	0.08	0.66	0.05	0.77	0.77	0.53
Congestion	0.66	0.46	0.28	0.86	0.07	<0.01	0.10	<u>0.15</u>	0.34	0.43	0.53	0.64	0.86	0.43	0.71	0.02	<0.01	0.35	0.01	0.20	0.20	0.02	0.22	0.64	<u>0.13</u>	0.20	0.53	0.85
Accessibility	0.66	0.71	0.28	0.05	0.07	<u>0.13</u>	0.59	0.07	0.85	0.43	0.20	0.35	0.05	0.43	0.71	0.66	0.35	<0.01	0.22	0.53	0.53	0.66	0.22	0.64	0.28	0.53	0.53	<u>0.17</u>
Monetary costs	0.58	0.34	<u>0.16</u>	0.26	<u>0.17</u>	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.21	0.31	0.42	0.01	0.26	0.31	0.34	0.08	0.01	0.22	<0.01	0.01	0.42	0.08	0.61	0.01	0.41	0.42	0.42	0.46
Non-mon. costs	0.77	0.32	0.47	<u>0.12</u>	0.23	0.04	0.06	0.81	0.52	0.60	0.67	0.53	<u>0.12</u>	0.60	0.62	<0.01	0.20	0.53	0.01	<0.01	0.67	<0.01	0.42	0.20	0.31	0.67	0.67	0.37
Veh. efficiency	<0.01	0.62	0.47	0.91	0.23	0.04	0.72	0.23	0.37	0.60	0.67	0.53	0.91	<u>0.10</u>	0.62	0.77	0.20	0.53	0.42	0.67	<0.01	0.77	0.42	0.53	0.47	0.67	0.67	0.37
Noise	0.84	0.49	0.62	0.29	0.41	<u>0.16</u>	0.20	0.25	<u>0.12</u>	0.71	0.77	0.66	0.29	0.71	0.49	<0.01	0.02	0.66	0.08	<0.01	0.77	<0.01	0.08	0.66	0.05	0.77	0.77	0.53
Emissions	0.58	0.34	<u>0.16</u>	0.82	<u>0.17</u>	0.34	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.81	0.74	0.42	1.00	0.82	0.74	1.00	0.08	0.22	0.22	0.61	0.42	0.42	0.08	<0.01	0.22	0.78	0.42	0.42	0.07
Public Health	0.66	<u>0.13</u>	0.28	0.86	0.48	0.06	<0.01	0.48	0.34	0.43	0.53	0.05	0.86	0.43	0.46	0.66	0.64	0.64	0.01	0.20	0.53	0.66	0.22	<0.01	0.83	0.20	0.53	<u>0.17</u>
Infr.ad.	0.62	0.50	0.96	0.09	0.94	0.74	0.90	<0.01	0.10	0.36	0.47	<u>0.13</u>	0.09	0.36	0.74	0.05	<u>0.13</u>	0.28	0.41	0.31	0.47	0.05	0.78	0.83	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.10
Veh. shape	0.77	0.62	0.31	0.91	0.81	0.62	0.72	0.09	0.52	0.60	0.67	0.20	0.91	0.60	0.62	0.77	0.20	0.53	0.42	0.67	0.67	0.77	0.42	0.20	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.52
Veh. behaviour	0.77	0.62	0.31	<u>0.12</u>	0.09	0.32	0.27	0.09	0.52	0.60	0.67	0.53	<u>0.12</u>	0.60	0.32	0.77	0.53	0.53	0.42	0.67	0.67	0.77	0.42	0.53	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	0.02
(HMI)	0.53	0.01	0.57	<u>0.12</u>	0.06	0.22	0.01	<0.01	0.97	<u>0.14</u>	0.52	0.85	<u>0.12</u>	0.25	0.22	0.53	0.85	<u>0.17</u>	0.46	0.37	0.37	0.53	0.07	<u>0.17</u>	0.10	0.52	0.02	<0.01

Note: **boldface** indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance; underline indicates statistically significant values with 20% level of significance.

Table 23. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case III Literature Review

Variables	V1 L3.	V4 L1	V4 L2	Acc. and spont	Saf. & Sec.	Social constraints	Weather & Topography	Public awareness	Sign-up & book. process	Membership cost	Spo. of accessing bike.	Proximity of doc. stat.	Travelling with children	insufficient Infrastructure	Driver behaviour	Separate Infrastr.	Harassment	Safe env.	Traffic safety	Subjective norm	Socio-cul.constraints	Family responsibilities	Weather	Topography	Confidence
V1 L3	<0.01	<0.01	0.42	0.60	0.20	0.09	0.72	0.91	0.91	0.91	0.62	0.81	0.27	<0.01	0.53	0.47	0.47	0.62	0.02	0.42	0.19	0.42	0.32	0.31	0.47
V4 L1	<0.01	<0.01	1.00	0.43	0.64	0.01	0.59	0.22	0.86	0.38	0.71	0.73	0.10	0.01	0.35	0.83	0.28	0.46	0.34	0.22	0.05	0.22	0.71	0.83	0.28
V4 L2	0.42	1.00	<0.01	0.74	0.22	0.65	0.49	0.50	0.50	0.50	1.00	0.02	0.49	0.08	1.00	0.41	0.78	1.00	0.81	0.61	0.50	0.11	1.00	0.41	0.41
Acc. and spont.	0.60	0.43	0.74	<0.01	0.43	0.77	0.02	0.12	0.12	0.10	0.21	0.09	0.17	0.10	0.43	0.59	0.36	0.21	0.87	0.08	0.46	0.08	0.01	0.59	0.59
Saf. & Sec.	0.20	0.64	0.22	0.43	<0.01	0.15	0.59	0.86	0.22	0.86	0.46	0.73	0.59	0.01	0.35	0.28	0.28	0.06	<0.01	0.22	0.38	0.22	0.71	0.83	0.28
Social constraints	0.09	0.01	0.65	0.77	0.15	<0.01	0.31	0.74	0.26	0.20	0.58	0.35	<0.01	0.03	0.73	0.29	0.03	0.78	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.02	0.58	0.37	0.03
Weat. & Topog.	0.72	0.59	0.49	0.02	0.59	0.31	<0.01	0.12	0.92	0.08	0.39	0.06	0.25	0.88	0.10	0.90	0.05	0.39	0.74	0.82	0.92	0.49	<0.01	<0.01	0.39
Public awareness	0.91	0.22	0.50	0.12	0.86	0.74	0.12	<0.01	0.41	0.10	0.58	0.05	0.48	0.66	0.38	0.50	0.50	0.27	0.86	0.26	0.97	0.82	0.27	0.50	0.50
Sign-up	0.91	0.86	0.50	0.12	0.22	0.26	0.92	0.41	<0.01	0.12	0.04	0.65	0.36	0.46	0.86	0.78	0.78	0.58	0.50	0.50	0.41	0.01	0.58	0.09	0.78
Membership cost	0.91	0.38	0.50	0.10	0.86	0.20	0.08	0.10	0.12	<0.01	0.27	0.20	0.92	0.46	0.05	0.21	0.50	0.16	0.86	0.82	0.12	0.11	0.16	0.21	0.78
Spontaneity of accessing bike/dock	0.62	0.71	1.00	0.21	0.46	0.58	0.39	0.58	0.04	0.27	<0.01	0.26	1.00	0.21	0.71	0.50	0.17	0.14	0.76	0.34	0.58	0.34	0.14	0.74	0.74
Proximity of docking station	0.81	0.73	0.02	0.09	0.73	0.35	0.06	0.05	0.65	0.20	0.26	<0.01	0.31	0.77	0.73	0.05	0.94	0.58	0.43	0.17	0.65	0.17	0.16	0.37	0.37
Trav. with children	0.27	0.10	0.49	0.17	0.59	<0.01	0.25	0.48	0.36	0.92	1.00	0.31	<0.01	0.17	0.59	0.90	<0.01	0.39	0.14	<0.01	0.12	0.10	0.39	0.39	<0.01
In. Infrastr.	<0.01	0.01	0.08	0.10	0.01	0.03	0.88	0.66	0.46	0.46	0.21	0.77	0.17	<0.01	0.43	0.36	0.36	1.00	<0.01	0.31	0.10	0.31	0.21	0.59	0.36
Driver behaviour	0.53	0.35	1.00	0.43	0.35	0.73	0.10	0.38	0.86	0.05	0.71	0.73	0.59	0.43	<0.01	0.28	0.28	0.46	0.85	0.22	0.38	1.00	0.06	0.13	0.28
Sep. Infrastr.	0.47	0.83	0.41	0.59	0.28	0.29	0.90	0.50	0.78	0.21	0.50	0.05	0.90	0.36	0.28	<0.01	0.96	0.08	0.12	0.78	0.50	0.04	0.74	0.25	0.25
Harassment	0.47	0.28	0.78	0.36	0.28	0.03	0.05	0.50	0.78	0.50	0.17	0.94	<0.01	0.36	0.28	0.96	<0.01	0.50	0.12	0.04	0.50	0.41	0.08	0.21	<0.01
Safe env.	0.62	0.46	1.00	0.21	0.06	0.78	0.39	0.27	0.58	0.16	0.14	0.58	0.39	1.00	0.46	0.08	0.50	<0.01	0.55	1.00	0.78	1.00	0.77	0.50	0.50
Traffic safety	0.02	0.34	0.81	0.87	<0.01	<0.01	0.74	0.86	0.50	0.86	0.76	0.43	0.14	<0.01	0.85	0.12	0.12	0.55	<0.01	0.07	0.05	0.07	0.76	0.57	0.12
Subjective norm	0.42	0.22	0.61	0.08	0.22	0.02	0.82	0.26	0.50	0.82	0.34	0.17	<0.01	0.31	0.22	0.78	0.04	1.00	0.07	<0.01	0.26	0.61	1.00	0.78	0.04
Socio-cul. constraints	0.19	0.05	0.50	0.46	0.38	<0.01	0.92	0.97	0.41	0.12	0.58	0.65	0.12	0.10	0.38	0.50	0.50	0.78	0.05	0.26	<0.01	0.03	0.78	0.78	0.50
Family resp.	0.42	0.22	0.11	0.08	0.22	0.02	0.49	0.82	0.01	0.11	0.34	0.17	0.10	0.31	1.00	0.04	0.41	1.00	0.07	0.61	0.03	<0.01	0.34	0.78	0.04
Weather	0.32	0.71	1.00	0.01	0.71	0.58	<0.01	0.27	0.58	0.16	0.14	0.16	0.39	0.21	0.06	0.74	0.08	0.77	0.76	1.00	0.78	0.34	<0.01	0.01	0.50
Topography	0.31	0.83	0.41	0.59	0.83	0.37	<0.01	0.50	0.09	0.21	0.74	0.37	0.39	0.59	0.13	0.25	0.21	0.50	0.57	0.78	0.78	0.01	<0.01	0.96	
Confidence	0.47	0.28	0.41	0.59	0.28	0.03	0.39	0.50	0.78	0.78	0.74	0.37	<0.01	0.36	0.28	0.25	<0.01	0.50	0.12	0.04	0.50	0.04	0.50	0.96	<0.01

Note: **boldface** indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance; underline indicates statistically significant values with 20% level of significance.

Table 24. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case IV Literature Review

Variables	V3 Job Holders Today	V6 Job Holders Tomorrow	Socio-economic Conditions	Job Characteristics	Personal Circumstances	Individual Characteristics	Job Segregation	Demand Factors	Policy/Legal	HR Policies	Terms and Conditions	Training Provision	Safety and Security	Female facilities	Caring/Parenting responsibilities	Economic Deprivation -	Access to/ownership off resources	Skills	Adaptability attitudes	Educational level/attainment	Health Status and Wellbeing	Demographic
V3 Job Holders Today	<0.01	<0.01	0.76	<0.01	0.25	0.25	0.01	0.37	0.52	<u>0.13</u>	0.52	0.27	0.03	0.06	0.58	0.01	0.49	0.81	0.32	0.27	1.00	0.33
V6 Job Holders Tomorrow	<0.01	<0.01	0.76	<0.01	0.25	0.25	0.01	0.37	0.52	<u>0.13</u>	0.52	0.27	0.03	0.06	0.58	0.01	0.49	0.81	0.32	0.27	1.00	0.33
Socio-economic Conditions	0.76	0.76	<0.01	0.80	0.72	0.01	0.68	0.02	0.01	<0.01	0.72	0.46	0.40	0.34	0.76	0.49	0.64	<u>0.10</u>	0.08	<u>0.19</u>	0.49	0.43
Job Characteristics	<0.01	<0.01	0.80	<0.01	0.10	0.10	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.60	0.04	0.60	0.69	0.09	<u>0.14</u>	0.66	0.04	0.24	0.39	0.43	0.69	0.62	0.76
Personal Circumstances	0.25	0.25	0.72	0.10	<0.01	0.01	0.04	0.57	0.44	0.25	0.44	0.63	0.75	0.95	0.25	0.72	0.72	0.29	0.97	0.63	0.72	0.54
Individual Characteristics	0.25	0.25	0.01	0.10	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.57	0.42	<0.01	0.44	0.56	0.75	0.95	<0.01	0.72	0.72	0.02	0.21	0.09	0.72	0.09
Job Segregation	0.01	0.01	0.68	<0.01	0.04	<0.01	<0.01	0.75	0.38	0.01	0.38	0.25	0.40	<u>0.13</u>	0.01	0.74	0.91	0.50	0.82	0.25	0.51	0.98
Demand Factors	0.37	0.37	0.02	<u>0.17</u>	0.57	0.57	0.75	<0.01	0.04	0.37	0.57	0.25	0.91	0.59	0.46	0.51	0.27	0.50	0.39	0.25	0.51	0.35
Policy/Legal	0.52	0.52	0.01	0.60	0.44	0.42	0.38	0.04	<0.01	0.25	0.42	0.56	0.75	0.33	0.52	0.72	0.72	0.92	0.97	0.56	0.47	0.66
HR Policies	<u>0.13</u>	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	0.04	0.25	<0.01	0.01	0.37	0.25	<0.01	0.52	0.91	0.39	0.52	<u>0.13</u>	1.00	0.49	<u>0.11</u>	0.08	0.27	1.00	<u>0.15</u>
Terms and Conditions	0.52	0.52	0.72	0.60	0.44	0.44	0.38	0.57	0.42	0.52	<0.01	0.56	0.07	0.33	0.52	<u>0.14</u>	0.33	0.92	0.97	0.09	0.47	0.09
Training Provision	0.27	0.27	0.46	0.69	0.63	0.56	0.25	0.25	0.56	0.91	0.56	<0.01	0.52	0.41	0.27	0.46	0.28	0.83	0.46	0.05	0.46	0.85
Safety and Security	0.03	0.03	0.40	0.09	0.75	0.75	0.40	0.91	0.75	0.39	0.07	0.52	<0.01	<0.01	0.39	0.33	<u>0.20</u>	0.53	0.76	0.95	0.81	0.08
Female facilities	0.06	0.06	0.34	<u>0.14</u>	0.95	0.95	<u>0.13</u>	0.59	0.33	0.52	0.33	0.41	<0.01	<0.01	0.52	0.23	0.94	0.78	0.49	0.57	0.64	0.84
Caring/Parenting responsibilities	0.58	0.58	0.76	0.66	0.25	<0.01	0.01	0.46	0.52	<u>0.13</u>	0.52	0.27	0.39	0.52	<0.01	1.00	0.49	<u>0.11</u>	0.71	0.27	1.00	0.83
Economic Deprivation - social network	0.01	0.01	0.49	0.04	0.72	0.72	0.74	0.51	0.72	1.00	<u>0.14</u>	0.46	0.33	0.23	1.00	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.10</u>	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.13</u>	0.01	0.22
Access to/ownership off resources	0.49	0.49	0.64	0.24	0.72	0.72	0.91	0.27	0.72	0.49	0.33	0.28	<u>0.20</u>	0.94	0.49	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.10</u>	<u>0.13</u>	0.04	<0.01	<u>0.14</u>
Skills	0.81	0.81	<u>0.10</u>	0.39	0.29	0.02	0.50	0.50	0.92	<u>0.11</u>	0.92	0.83	0.53	0.78	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.10</u>	<u>0.10</u>	<0.01	<u>0.10</u>	<0.01	<u>0.10</u>	0.04
Adaptability, attitudes to work	0.32	0.32	0.08	0.43	0.97	0.21	0.82	0.39	0.97	0.08	0.97	0.46	0.76	0.49	0.71	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.13</u>	<u>0.10</u>	<0.01	0.37	0.02	0.08
Ed. level	0.27	0.27	<u>0.19</u>	0.69	0.63	0.09	0.25	0.25	0.56	0.27	0.09	0.05	0.95	0.57	0.27	<u>0.13</u>	0.04	<0.01	0.37	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.21
Health Status and Wellbeing	1.00	1.00	0.49	0.62	0.72	0.72	0.51	0.51	0.47	1.00	0.47	0.46	0.81	0.64	1.00	0.01	<0.01	<u>0.10</u>	0.02	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	0.81
Demographic	0.33	0.33	0.43	0.76	0.54	0.09	0.98	0.35	0.66	<u>0.15</u>	0.09	0.85	0.08	0.84	0.83	0.22	<u>0.14</u>	0.04	0.08	0.21	0.81	<0.01

Note: **boldface** indicates statistically significant values with 10% level of significance; underline indicates statistically significant values with 20% level of significance.

In a second phase, the degree of association between the second and third level factors were analysed for each use case and each fairness factor of first level.

- **Use Case I** - Railways public transport infrastructures

Use case I includes 3 fairness factors of first level: Accessibility of the Service (ASI_1), Design of the Infrastructure (DI1_1), and Safety & Security (SSI_1).

Accessibility of the Service (AS 1) fairness includes 2 factor of second level and 9 factors of third level (Table 11).

Table 25. Summary statistics for Use Case I - Accessibility of the Service

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
ASI_1	Accessibility of the Service	0.842	0.375
ASI_2	Ticketing Options & Fares	0.842	0.375
AS2_2	Travel Purpose	0.421	0.507
ASI_3	Affordability of the service in general in comparison to use of privately-owned vehicles;	0.684	0.478
AS2_3	Discounted fares;	0.211	0.419
AS3_3	Flexible fare options for multiple and intermodal trips, group trips, family trips, transferable tickets;	0.263	0.452
AS4_3	Pay-per-use options;	0.105	0.315
AS5_3	Subscription or monthly payment options;	0.158	0.375
AS6_3	Electronic ticket and flexible payment methods using cash, smartphones and mobile apps;	0.263	0.452
AS7_3	Availability of ATMs, ticket machines, ticket office and alternative sale points inside and outside of stations.	0.158	0.375
AS8_3	Travel purpose (e.g., work; shopping; personal business; leisure; education, etc.);	0.421	0.507
AS9_3	Travel destination.	0.211	0.419

The results (Table 26 and Table 27) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **ASI_2 Ticketing Options & Fares** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - ASI_3 Affordability of the service in general in comparison to use of privately-owned vehicles with V-Cramers= 0.64 and p-value<0.01;
 - AS8_3 Travel purpose V-Cramers= 0.37 and p-value=0.12;
- **AS2_2 Travel Purpose** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - ASI_3 Affordability of the service in general in comparison to use of privately-owned vehicles with V-Cramers= 0.58 and p-value=0.01;
 - AS3_3 Flexible fare options for multiple and intermodal trips, group trips, family trips, transferable tickets with V-Cramers= 0.46 and p-value=0.05;
 - AS4_3 Pay-per-use options with V-Cramers= 0.40 and p-value=0.09;
 - AS5_3 Subscription or monthly payment options with V-Cramers= 0.51 and p-value=0.03;
 - AS8_3 Travel purpose with V-Cramers= 1.00 and p-value<0.01;
 - AS9_3 Travel destination with V-Cramers= 0.61 and p-value=0.01.

Table 26. V-Cramer for Use Case I – Accessibility of the Service Literature Review

	AS1_2	AS2_2	AS1_3	AS2_3	AS3_3	AS4_3	AS5_3	AS6_3	AS7_3	AS8_3	AS9_3
AS1_2	1.00	0.37	0.64	0.22	0.26	0.15	0.19	0.26	0.19	<u>0.37</u>	0.22
AS2_2	0.37	1.00	0.58	0.08	0.46	0.40	0.51	0.22	0.08	1.00	0.61
AS1_3	0.64	0.58	1.00	0.07	0.41	0.23	0.29	0.41	<u>0.33</u>	0.58	<u>0.35</u>
AS2_3	0.22	0.08	0.07	1.00	0.28	0.24	0.22	0.02	0.22	0.08	0.05
AS3_3	0.26	0.46	0.41	0.28	1.00	0.18	0.26	0.36	0.26	0.46	0.57
AS4_3	0.15	0.40	0.23	0.24	0.18	1.00	<u>0.32</u>	0.18	0.15	0.40	0.66
AS5_3	0.19	0.51	0.29	0.22	0.26	<u>0.32</u>	1.00	0.72	0.21	0.51	0.13
AS6_3	0.26	0.22	0.41	0.02	0.36	0.18	0.72	1.00	0.07	0.22	0.02
AS7_3	0.19	0.08	<u>0.33</u>	0.22	0.26	0.15	0.21	0.07	1.00	0.08	0.22
AS8_3	<u>0.37</u>	1.00	0.58	0.08	0.46	0.40	0.51	0.22	0.08	1.00	0.61
AS9_3	0.22	0.61	<u>0.35</u>	0.05	0.57	0.66	0.13	0.02	0.22	0.61	1.00

Table 27. p-value of χ^2 for Use Case I – Accessibility of the Service Literature Review

	AS1_2	AS2_2	AS1_3	AS2_3	AS3_3	AS4_3	AS5_3	AS6_3	AS7_3	AS8_3	AS9_3
AS1_2	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.36	0.28	0.54	0.44	0.28	0.44	<u>0.12</u>	0.36
AS2_2	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.01	0.74	0.05	0.09	0.03	0.37	0.75	<0.01	0.01
AS1_3	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.77	0.08	0.34	0.22	0.08	<u>0.17</u>	0.01	<u>0.14</u>
AS2_3	0.36	0.74	0.77	<0.01	0.25	0.32	0.36	0.95	0.36	0.74	0.84
AS3_3	0.28	0.05	0.08	0.25	<0.01	0.45	0.28	<u>0.13</u>	0.28	0.05	0.01
AS4_3	0.54	0.09	0.34	0.32	0.45	<0.01	<u>0.18</u>	0.45	0.54	0.09	<0.01
AS5_3	0.44	0.03	0.22	0.36	0.28	<u>0.18</u>	<0.01	<0.01	0.39	0.03	0.59
AS6_3	0.28	0.37	0.08	0.95	<u>0.13</u>	0.45	<0.01	<0.01	0.78	0.37	0.95
AS7_3	0.44	0.75	<u>0.17</u>	0.36	0.28	0.54	0.39	0.78	<0.01	0.75	0.36
AS8_3	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.01	0.74	0.05	0.09	0.03	0.37	0.75	<0.01	0.01
AS9_3	0.36	0.01	<u>0.14</u>	0.84	0.01	<0.01	0.59	0.95	0.36	0.01	<0.01

Design of the Infrastructure fairness includes 4 factor of second level and 26 factors of third level (Table 28).

Table 28. Descriptive statistics for Use Case I - Design of the Infrastructure

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
D11_1	Design of the Infrastructure	1.000	0.000
D11_2	Universal Design	0.947	0.229
D12_2	Cleanliness & Maintenance	0.474	0.513
D13_2	Furniture & Facilities	0.842	0.375
D11_3	Lift with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair to access the station and transfer within the stations;	0.632	0.496
D12_3	Ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair to access the station and transfer within the stations;	0.684	0.478
D13_3	Bright colour contrasting handrail to help people with visual impairment to identify support quickly;	0.158	0.375
D14_3	Tactile surfaces to provide wayfinding information to people with reduced visual capabilities;	0.211	0.419
D15_3	Signposting with bright colour contrasting and large font to help people with visual impairment;	0.211	0.419
D16_3	Safe and easily accessible drop-off and pick-up points;	0.105	0.315
D17_3	Safe and step free pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations;	0.737	0.452
D18_3	Positioning ticket machines and wayfinding information at convenient height for a wide variety of users;	0.105	0.315
D19_3	Fare gates to accommodate a wide variety of users;	0.263	0.452
D110_3	Appropriate height steps or step-free access to trains;	0.737	0.452
D111_3	Handles suited at convenient height for all users including women, children and disabled people or vertical grab bars;	0.263	0.452
D112_3	Adequate lighting in the stations and the surrounding area of stations.	0.684	0.478
D113_3	Clean and hygienic environment especially for handholds and toilets;	0.421	0.507
D114_3	Waste recycling baskets;	0.053	0.229
D115_3	Maintenance of deterioration, graffiti and vandalism.	0.263	0.452
D116_3	Separated toilets for women;	0.316	0.478
D117_3	Allocated seats to pregnant women, parents with young children and elderly;	0.211	0.419
D118_3	Waiting areas with seating arrangements;	0.263	0.452
D119_3	Baby changing facilities in both men and women toilets;	0.105	0.315
D120_3	Vending machines;	0.053	0.229
D121_3	Left luggage and lost property offices;	0.053	0.229
D122_3	Wi-Fi or 3G/4G connection;	0.053	0.229
D123_3	Car and moto public parking places;	0.316	0.478
D124_3	Bicycles storage facilities and bicycles racks;	0.158	0.375
D125_3	Weather protected pedestrian routes between transit modes where applicable;	0.053	0.229
D126_3	Sheltered waiting areas for buses, taxis, etc.	0.158	0.375

The results (Table 29 and

factors: Table 30) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level

- **D11_2 Universal Design** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - D12_3 Ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair to access the station and transfer within the stations; with $V = 0.35$ and $pvalue = 0.15$;
 - D17_3 Safe and step free pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations; with $V = 0.39$ and $pvalue = 0.09$;
 - D110_3 Appropriate height steps or step-free access to trains; with $V = 0.39$ and $pvalue = 0.09$;
 - D112_3 Adequate lighting in the stations and the surrounding area of stations. with $V = 0.35$ and $pvalue = 0.15$;
 - D122_3 Wi-Fi or 3G/4G connection; with $V = 1$ and $pvalue = 0$;
 - D124_3 Bicycles storage facilities and bicycles racks; with $V = 0.54$ and $pvalue = 0.02$;
- **D12_2 Cleanliness & Maintenance** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - D11_3 Lift with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair to access the station and transfer within the stations; with $V = 0.37$ and $pvalue = 0.12$;
 - D17_3 Safe and step free pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations; with $V = 0.39$ and $pvalue = 0.1$;
 - D18_3 Positioning ticket machines and wayfinding information at convenient height for a wide variety of users; with $V = 0.33$ and $pvalue = 0.17$;
 - D19_3 Fare gates to accommodate a wide variety of users; with $V = 0.57$ and $pvalue = 0.01$;
 - D110_3 Appropriate height steps or step-free access to trains; with $V = 0.63$ and $pvalue = 0$;
 - D111_3 Handles suited at convenient height for all users including women, children and disabled people or vertical grab bars; with $V = 0.33$ and $pvalue = 0.17$;
 - D113_3 Clean and hygienic environment especially for handholds and toilets; with $V = 0.9$ and $pvalue = 0$;
 - D115_3 Maintenance of deterioration, graffiti and vandalism. with $V = 0.63$ and $pvalue = 0$;
 - D118_3 Waiting areas with seating arrangements; with $V = 0.33$ and $pvalue = 0.17$;
 - D119_3 Baby changing facilities in both men and women toilets; with $V = 0.33$ and $pvalue = 0.17$;
- **D13_2 Furniture & Facilities** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - D12_3 Ramps and escalator with enough room to carry shopping bags, baby strollers, luggage and wheelchair to access the station and transfer within the stations; with $V = 0.33$ and $pvalue = 0.17$;
 - D17_3 Safe and step free pedestrian crossings and sidewalks surrounding the stations; with $V = 0.72$ and $pvalue = 0$;
 - D110_3 Appropriate height steps or step-free access to trains; with $V = 0.4$ and $pvalue = 0.09$;
 - D112_3 Adequate lighting in the stations and the surrounding area of stations. with $V = 0.33$ and $pvalue = 0.17$;
 - D113_3 Clean and hygienic environment especially for handholds and toilets; with $V = 0.51$ and $pvalue = 0.03$;
 - D115_3 Maintenance of deterioration, graffiti and vandalism. with $V = 0.4$ and $pvalue = 0.09$;

Table 29. V-Cramer for Use Case II – Design of the Infrastructure Literature Review

	DI1_2	DI2_2	DI3_2	DI1_3	DI2_3	DI3_3	DI4_3	DI5_3	DI6_3	DI7_3	DI8_3	DI9_3	DI10_3	DI11_3	DI12_3	DI13_3	DI14_3	DI15_3	DI16_3	DI17_3	DI18_3	DI19_3	DI20_3	DI21_3	DI22_3	DI23_3	DI24_3	DI25_3	DI26_3	
DI1_2	1.00	0.25	0.10	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.39	0.08	0.14	0.39	0.14	<u>0.35</u>	0.28	0.06	0.14	0.16	0.12	0.14	0.08	0.06	1.00	0.16	0.54	0.06	0.10		
DI2_2	0.25	1.00	0.46	<u>0.37</u>	0.26	0.12	0.23	0.23	0.02	0.39	<u>0.33</u>	0.57	0.63	<u>0.33</u>	0.04	0.90	0.25	0.63	0.19	0.23	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.25	0.22	0.25	0.19	0.12	0.22	0.17	
DI3_2	0.10	0.46	1.00	0.27	<u>0.33</u>	0.19	0.22	0.22	0.15	0.72	0.15	0.26	0.40	0.07	<u>0.33</u>	0.51	0.10	0.40	<u>0.29</u>	0.22	0.26	0.15	0.10	0.10	0.10	<u>0.29</u>	0.19	0.10	0.19	
DI1_3	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.27	1.00	0.89	<u>0.33</u>	0.39	0.39	0.26	0.29	0.26	0.46	0.53	0.04	0.05	0.45	<u>0.31</u>	0.04	0.28	0.39	0.21	0.09	<u>0.31</u>	0.18	<u>0.31</u>	0.05	0.03	0.18	0.03	
DI2_3	<u>0.35</u>	0.26	<u>0.33</u>	0.89	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.23	<u>0.37</u>	0.23	0.41	<u>0.37</u>	0.11	0.03	<u>0.34</u>	0.16	0.15	0.22	<u>0.35</u>	0.15	0.14	0.16	0.16	<u>0.35</u>	0.03	0.02	0.16	<u>0.29</u>	
DI3_3	0.10	0.12	0.19	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	0.48	0.84	<u>0.32</u>	0.26	0.79	0.40	0.26	0.07	<u>0.29</u>	0.08	0.10	0.26	<u>0.33</u>	0.13	0.40	<u>0.32</u>	0.10	0.54	0.10	<u>0.33</u>	0.21	0.54	0.60	
DI4_3	0.12	0.23	0.22	0.39	<u>0.35</u>	0.48	1.00	0.68	0.24	<u>0.31</u>	0.24	0.02	<u>0.31</u>	0.02	0.20	0.18	0.12	<u>0.31</u>	0.07	<u>0.37</u>	0.28	0.18	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.20	0.22	0.12	0.13	
DI5_3	0.12	0.23	0.22	0.39	<u>0.35</u>	0.84	0.68	1.00	0.24	<u>0.31</u>	0.66	0.28	<u>0.31</u>	0.02	0.07	0.18	0.12	<u>0.31</u>	0.20	0.05	0.57	0.24	0.12	0.46	0.12	0.48	0.13	0.46	0.48	
DI6_3	0.08	0.02	0.15	0.26	0.23	<u>0.32</u>	0.24	0.24	1.00	0.20	0.44	0.18	0.18	0.18	0.23	0.05	0.08	0.18	0.23	0.18	0.20	0.12	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.50	0.15	0.08	0.15	
DI7_3	0.39	0.39	0.72	0.29	<u>0.37</u>	0.26	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.20	1.00	0.20	<u>0.36</u>	0.46	0.09	0.62	0.46	0.14	0.19	0.41	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.20	0.14	0.14	0.39	0.41	0.40	0.14	0.26	
DI8_3	0.08	<u>0.33</u>	0.15	0.26	0.23	0.79	0.24	0.66	0.44	0.20	1.00	0.57	0.20	0.18	0.23	<u>0.29</u>	0.08	0.20	0.14	0.18	0.18	0.44	0.08	0.69	0.08	0.50	<u>0.32</u>	0.69	<u>0.32</u>	
DI9_3	0.14	0.57	0.26	0.46	0.41	0.40	0.02	0.28	0.18	<u>0.36</u>	0.57	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	0.46	0.41	0.51	0.14	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.28	0.19	0.18	0.14	0.39	0.14	0.11	0.07	0.39	0.07	
DI10_3	0.39	0.63	0.40	0.53	<u>0.37</u>	0.26	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.18	0.46	0.20	<u>0.36</u>	1.00	0.09	0.11	0.70	0.39	0.46	0.41	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.20	0.39	0.14	0.39	0.15	0.07	0.14	0.07	
DI11_3	0.14	<u>0.33</u>	0.07	0.04	0.11	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.18	0.09	0.18	0.46	0.09	1.00	0.15	0.27	0.14	<u>0.36</u>	0.11	0.28	0.09	0.20	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.26	0.14	0.26	
DI12_3	<u>0.35</u>	0.04	<u>0.33</u>	0.05	0.03	<u>0.29</u>	0.20	0.07	0.23	0.62	0.23	0.41	0.11	0.15	1.00	0.11	0.16	0.15	0.46	0.07	0.15	0.23	0.16	0.16	<u>0.35</u>	0.22	<u>0.33</u>	0.16	<u>0.29</u>	
DI13_3	0.28	0.90	0.51	0.45	<u>0.34</u>	0.08	0.18	0.18	0.05	0.46	<u>0.29</u>	0.51	0.70	0.27	0.11	1.00	0.28	0.46	<u>0.35</u>	0.18	0.27	<u>0.29</u>	0.28	0.20	0.28	0.12	0.08	0.20	0.22	
DI14_3	0.06	0.25	0.10	<u>0.31</u>	0.16	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.14	0.08	0.14	0.39	0.14	0.16	0.28	1.00	0.39	0.16	0.12	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.06	0.06	0.16	0.10	0.06	0.54	
DI15_3	0.14	0.63	0.40	0.04	0.15	0.26	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.18	0.19	0.20	<u>0.36</u>	0.46	<u>0.36</u>	0.15	0.46	0.39	1.00	0.15	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.20	0.39	0.14	0.14	0.15	0.26	0.14	0.07	
DI16_3	0.16	0.19	<u>0.29</u>	0.28	0.22	<u>0.33</u>	0.07	0.20	0.23	0.41	0.14	<u>0.37</u>	0.41	0.11	0.46	<u>0.35</u>	0.16	0.15	1.00	0.20	0.11	0.14	0.16	<u>0.35</u>	0.16	0.22	0.02	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.33</u>	
DI17_3	0.12	0.23	0.22	0.39	<u>0.35</u>	0.13	<u>0.37</u>	0.05	0.18	<u>0.31</u>	0.18	0.28	<u>0.31</u>	0.28	0.07	0.18	0.12	<u>0.31</u>	0.20	1.00	0.28	0.18	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.12	<u>0.35</u>	0.22	0.12	0.13
DI18_3	0.14	<u>0.33</u>	0.26	0.21	0.15	0.40	0.28	0.57	0.20	<u>0.36</u>	0.18	0.19	<u>0.36</u>	0.09	0.15	0.27	0.14	<u>0.36</u>	0.11	0.28	1.00	0.57	0.14	0.39	0.14	<u>0.37</u>	0.07	0.39	0.40	
DI19_3	0.08	<u>0.33</u>	0.15	0.09	0.14	<u>0.32</u>	0.18	0.24	0.12	0.20	0.44	0.18	0.20	0.23	<u>0.29</u>	0.08	0.20	0.14	0.18	0.57	1.00	0.08	0.69	0.08	0.50	0.08	0.50	<u>0.32</u>	0.69	<u>0.32</u>
DI20_3	0.06	0.25	0.10	<u>0.31</u>	0.16	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.14	0.08	0.14	0.39	0.14	0.16	0.28	1.00	0.39	0.16	0.12	0.14	0.08	1.00	0.06	0.06	0.16	0.10	0.06	0.54	
DI21_3	0.06	0.22	0.10	0.18	0.16	0.54	0.12	0.46	0.08	0.14	0.69	0.39	0.14	0.14	0.16	0.20	0.06	0.14	<u>0.35</u>	0.12	0.39	0.69	0.06	1.00	0.06	<u>0.35</u>	0.54	1.00	0.54	
DI22_3	1.00	0.25	0.10	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.10	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.39	0.08	0.14	0.39	0.14	<u>0.35</u>	0.28	0.06	0.14	0.16	0.12	0.14	0.08	0.06	0.06	1.00	0.16	0.54	0.06	0.10	
DI23_3	0.16	0.19	<u>0.29</u>	0.05	0.03	<u>0.33</u>	0.20	0.48	0.50	0.41	0.50	0.11	0.15	0.15	0.22	0.12	0.16	0.15	0.22	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.50	0.16	<u>0.35</u>	0.16	1.00	0.02	<u>0.35</u>	0.02	
DI24_3	0.54	0.12	0.19	0.03	0.02	0.21	0.22	0.13	0.15	0.40	<u>0.32</u>	0.07	0.07	0.26	<u>0.33</u>	0.08	0.10	0.26	0.02	0.22	0.07	<u>0.32</u>	0.10	0.54	0.54	0.02	1.00	0.54	0.21	
DI25_3	0.06	0.22	0.10	0.18	0.16	0.54	0.12	0.46	0.08	0.14	0.69	0.39	0.14	0.14	0.16	0.20	0.06	0.14	<u>0.35</u>	0.12	0.39	0.69	0.06	1.00	0.06	<u>0.35</u>	0.54	1.00	0.54	
DI26_3	0.10	0.17	0.19	0.03	<u>0.29</u>	0.60	0.13	0.48	0.15	0.26	<u>0.32</u>	0.07	0.07	0.26	<u>0.29</u>	0.22	0.54	0.07	<u>0.33</u>	0.13	0.40	<u>0.32</u>	0.54	0.54	0.10	0.02	0.21	0.54	1.00	

Table 30. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case I – Design of the Infrastructure Literature Review

	DI1_2	DI2_2	DI3_2	DI1_3	DI2_3	DI3_3	DI4_3	DI5_3	DI6_3	DI7_3	DI8_3	DI9_3	DI10_3	DI11_3	DI12_3	DI13_3	DI14_3	DI15_3	DI16_3	DI17_3	DI18_3	DI19_3	DI20_3	DI21_3	DI22_3	DI23_3	DI24_3	DI25_3	DI26_3
DI1_2	<0.01	0.31	0.68	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.15</u>	0.68	0.62	0.62	0.74	0.09	0.74	0.57	0.09	0.57	<u>0.15</u>	0.25	0.82	0.57	0.51	0.62	0.57	0.74	0.82	0.82	<0.01	0.51	0.02	0.82	0.68
DI2_2	0.31	<0.01	0.05	<u>0.12</u>	0.28	0.62	0.34	0.34	0.94	0.10	<u>0.17</u>	0.01	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.88	<0.01	0.31	<0.01	0.43	0.34	<u>0.17</u>	<u>0.17</u>	0.31	0.36	0.31	0.43	0.62	0.36	0.49
DI3_2	0.68	0.05	<0.01	0.27	<u>0.17</u>	0.44	0.36	0.36	0.54	<0.01	0.54	0.28	0.09	0.78	<u>0.17</u>	0.03	0.68	0.09	0.22	0.36	0.28	0.54	0.68	0.68	0.68	0.22	0.44	0.68	0.44
DI1_3	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.27	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.09	0.09	0.28	0.23	0.28	0.05	0.02	0.87	0.84	0.05	<u>0.20</u>	0.87	0.24	0.09	0.39	0.70	<u>0.20</u>	0.46	<u>0.20</u>	0.84	0.90	0.46	0.90
DI2_3	<u>0.15</u>	0.28	<u>0.17</u>	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	<u>0.14</u>	<u>0.14</u>	0.34	<u>0.12</u>	0.34	0.08	<u>0.12</u>	0.66	0.92	<u>0.16</u>	0.51	0.54	0.37	<u>0.14</u>	0.54	0.58	0.51	0.51	<u>0.15</u>	0.92	0.95	0.51	0.22
DI3_3	0.68	0.62	0.44	<u>0.17</u>	0.22	<0.01	0.04	<0.01	<u>0.18</u>	0.28	<0.01	0.09	0.28	0.78	0.22	0.75	0.68	0.28	<u>0.17</u>	0.59	0.09	<u>0.18</u>	0.68	0.02	0.68	<u>0.17</u>	0.39	0.02	0.01
DI4_3	0.62	0.34	0.36	0.09	<u>0.14</u>	0.04	<0.01	<0.01	0.32	<u>0.20</u>	0.32	0.95	<u>0.20</u>	0.95	0.40	0.46	0.62	<u>0.20</u>	0.77	<u>0.12</u>	0.25	0.47	0.62	0.62	0.62	0.40	0.36	0.62	0.59
DI5_3	0.62	0.34	0.36	0.09	<u>0.14</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.32	<u>0.20</u>	<0.01	0.25	<u>0.20</u>	0.95	0.77	0.46	0.62	<u>0.20</u>	0.40	0.84	0.01	0.32	0.62	0.05	0.62	0.04	0.59	0.05	0.04
DI6_3	0.74	0.94	0.54	0.28	0.34	<u>0.18</u>	0.32	0.32	<0.01	0.40	0.06	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.34	0.82	0.74	0.45	0.34	0.47	0.40	0.63	0.74	0.74	0.74	0.03	0.54	0.74	0.54
DI7_3	0.09	0.10	<0.01	0.23	<u>0.12</u>	0.28	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.20</u>	0.40	<0.01	0.40	<u>0.13</u>	0.05	0.73	<0.01	0.05	0.57	0.45	0.08	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.13</u>	0.40	0.57	0.57	0.09	0.08	0.09	0.57	0.28
DI8_3	0.74	<u>0.17</u>	0.54	0.28	0.34	<0.01	0.32	<0.01	0.06	0.40	<0.01	0.01	0.40	0.45	0.34	0.22	0.74	0.40	0.58	0.47	0.45	0.06	0.74	<0.01	0.74	0.03	<u>0.18</u>	<0.01	<u>0.18</u>
DI9_3	0.57	0.01	0.28	0.05	0.08	0.09	0.95	0.25	0.45	<u>0.13</u>	0.01	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.05	0.08	0.03	0.57	<u>0.13</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.25	0.45	0.45	0.57	0.09	0.57	0.66	0.78	0.09	0.78
DI10_3	0.09	<0.01	0.09	0.02	<u>0.12</u>	0.28	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.20</u>	0.45	0.05	0.40	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	0.73	0.66	<0.01	0.09	0.05	0.08	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.13</u>	0.40	0.09	0.57	0.09	0.54	0.78	0.57	0.78
DI11_3	0.57	<u>0.17</u>	0.78	0.87	0.66	0.78	0.95	0.95	0.45	0.73	0.45	0.05	0.73	<0.01	0.54	0.27	0.57	<u>0.13</u>	0.66	0.25	0.73	0.40	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.54	0.28	0.57	0.28
DI12_3	<u>0.15</u>	0.88	<u>0.17</u>	0.84	0.92	0.22	0.40	0.77	0.34	<0.01	0.34	0.08	0.66	0.54	<0.01	0.66	0.51	0.54	0.05	0.77	0.54	0.34	0.51	0.51	<u>0.15</u>	0.37	<u>0.17</u>	0.51	0.22
DI13_3	0.25	<0.01	0.03	0.05	<u>0.16</u>	0.75	0.46	0.46	0.82	0.05	0.22	0.03	<0.01	0.27	0.66	<0.01	0.25	0.05	<u>0.14</u>	0.46	0.27	0.22	0.25	0.41	0.25	0.62	0.75	0.41	0.38
DI14_3	0.82	0.31	0.68	<u>0.20</u>	0.51	0.68	0.62	0.62	0.74	0.57	0.74	0.57	0.09	0.57	0.51	0.25	<0.01	0.09	0.51	0.62	0.57	0.74	<0.01	0.82	0.82	0.51	0.68	0.82	0.02
DI15_3	0.57	<0.01	0.09	0.87	0.54	0.28	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.20</u>	0.45	0.45	0.40	<u>0.13</u>	0.05	<u>0.13</u>	0.54	0.05	0.09	<0.01	0.54	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.13</u>	0.40	0.09	0.57	0.57	0.54	0.28	0.57	0.78
DI16_3	0.51	0.43	0.22	0.24	0.37	<u>0.17</u>	0.77	0.40	0.34	0.08	0.58	<u>0.12</u>	0.08	0.66	0.05	<u>0.14</u>	0.51	0.54	<0.01	0.40	0.66	0.58	0.51	<u>0.15</u>	0.51	0.37	0.95	<u>0.15</u>	<u>0.17</u>
DI17_3	0.62	0.34	0.36	0.09	<u>0.14</u>	0.59	<u>0.12</u>	0.84	0.47	<u>0.20</u>	0.47	0.25	<u>0.20</u>	0.25	0.77	0.46	0.62	<u>0.20</u>	0.40	<0.01	0.25	0.47	0.62	0.62	0.62	<u>0.14</u>	0.36	0.62	0.59
DI18_3	0.57	<u>0.17</u>	0.28	0.39	0.54	0.09	0.25	0.01	0.40	<u>0.13</u>	0.45	0.45	<u>0.13</u>	0.73	0.54	0.27	0.57	<u>0.13</u>	0.66	0.25	<0.01	0.01	0.57	0.09	0.57	<u>0.12</u>	0.78	0.09	0.09
DI19_3	0.74	<u>0.17</u>	0.54	0.70	0.58	<u>0.18</u>	0.47	0.32	0.63	0.40	0.06	0.45	0.40	0.40	0.34	0.22	0.74	0.40	0.58	0.47	0.01	<0.01	0.74	<0.01	0.74	0.03	<u>0.18</u>	<0.01	<u>0.18</u>
DI20_3	0.82	0.31	0.68	<u>0.20</u>	0.51	0.68	0.62	0.62	0.74	0.57	0.74	0.57	0.09	0.57	0.51	0.25	<0.01	0.09	0.51	0.62	0.57	0.74	<0.01	0.82	0.82	0.51	0.68	0.82	0.02
DI21_3	0.82	0.36	0.68	0.46	0.51	0.02	0.62	0.05	0.74	0.57	<0.01	0.09	0.57	0.57	0.51	0.41	0.82	0.57	<u>0.15</u>	0.62	0.09	<0.01	0.82	<0.01	0.82	<u>0.15</u>	0.02	<0.01	0.02
DI22_3	<0.01	0.31	0.68	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.15</u>	0.68	0.62	0.62	0.74	0.09	0.74	0.57	0.09	0.57	<u>0.15</u>	0.25	0.82	0.57	0.51	0.62	0.57	0.74	0.82	0.82	<0.01	0.51	0.02	0.82	0.68
DI23_3	0.51	0.43	0.22	0.84	0.92	<u>0.17</u>	0.40	0.04	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.66	0.54	0.54	0.37	0.62	0.51	0.54	0.37	<u>0.14</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.03	0.51	<u>0.15</u>	0.51	<0.01	0.95	<u>0.15</u>	0.95
DI24_3	0.02	0.62	0.44	0.90	0.95	0.39	0.36	0.59	0.54	0.09	<u>0.18</u>	0.78	0.78	0.28	<u>0.17</u>	0.75	0.68	0.28	0.95	0.36	0.78	<u>0.18</u>	0.68	0.02	0.02	0.95	<0.01	0.02	0.39
DI25_3	0.82	0.36	0.68	0.46	0.51	0.02	0.62	0.05	0.74	0.57	<0.01	0.09	0.57	0.57	0.51	0.41	0.82	0.57	<u>0.15</u>	0.62	0.09	<0.01	0.82	<0.01	0.82	<u>0.15</u>	0.02	<0.01	0.02
DI26_3	0.68	0.49	0.44	0.90	0.22	0.01	0.59	0.04	0.54	0.28	<u>0.18</u>	0.78	0.78	0.28	0.22	0.38	0.02	0.78	<u>0.17</u>	0.59	0.09	<u>0.18</u>	0.02	0.02	0.68	0.95	0.39	0.02	<0.01

Safety & Security (SS1_1) fairness includes 2 factor of second level and 11 factors of third level (Table 31).

Table 31. Descriptive statistics for Use Case 1 - Safety & Security

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
SS1_1	Safety & Security	0.947	0.229
SS1_2	Harassment and Pickpocketing	0.789	0.419
SS2_2	Overcrowding and Emergency Situations	0.684	0.478
SS1_3	Presence and visibility of CCTV system;	0.316	0.478
SS2_3	SOS emergency phone;	0.316	0.478
SS3_3	Presence of police and security personnel including women police to be a deterrent for perpetrators;	0.316	0.478
SS4_3	Visibility of the surrounding area of the station;	0.316	0.478
SS5_3	Complaint Information in case of violations to personal safety;	0.211	0.419
SS6_3	Availability of hospitality rooms where to ask for help in case of aggression or need;	0.158	0.375
SS7_3	Gender-sensitive training for transport employees and security personnel;	0.211	0.419
SS8_3	Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers.	0.368	0.496
SS9_3	Offering adequate personal space;	0.684	0.478
SS10_3	Improved ventilation and air-conditioning;	0.105	0.315
SS11_3	Improved layout of seating (longitudinal seating included less social interaction compared to transverse seating).	0.105	0.315

The results (Table 32 and Table 33) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **SS1_2 Harassment and Pickpocketing** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - SS1_3 Presence and visibility of CCTV system with V-Cramers= 0.35 and p-value=0.14;
 - SS2_3 SOS emergency phone with V-Cramers= 0.35 and p-value=0.14;
 - SS3_3 Presence of police and security personnel including women police to be a deterrent for perpetrators with V-Cramers= 0.35 and p-value=0.14;
 - SS4_3 Visibility of the surrounding area of the station with V-Cramers= 0.35 and p-value=0.14;
 - SS8_3 Display advertisements for public awareness campaigns and for publicizing helpline numbers with V-Cramers= 0.39 and p-value=0.09.
- **SS2_2 Overcrowding and Emergency Situations** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - SS6_3 Availability of hospitality rooms where to ask for help in case of aggression or need with V-Cramers= 0.33 and p-value=0.17;
 - SS9_3 Offering adequate personal space with V-Cramers= 1.00 and p-value<0.01.

Table 32. V-Cramer for Use Case 1 – Safety & Security Literature Review

	SS1_2	SS2_2	SS1_3	SS2_3	SS3_3	SS4_3	SS5_3	SS6_3	SS7_3	SS8_3	SS9_3	SS10_3	SS11_3
SS1_2	1.00	0.07	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.35	0.27	0.22	0.27	0.39	0.07	0.18	0.18
SS2_2	0.07	1.00	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.07	0.33	0.20	0.19	1.00	0.23	0.23
SS1_3	0.35	0.27	1.00	0.03	0.76	0.27	0.07	0.33	0.48	0.65	0.27	0.50	0.14
SS2_3	0.35	0.27	0.03	1.00	0.03	0.03	0.07	0.33	0.20	0.19	0.27	0.23	0.23
SS3_3	0.35	0.27	0.76	0.03	1.00	0.03	0.35	0.33	0.20	0.42	0.27	0.50	0.14
SS4_3	0.35	0.27	0.27	0.03	0.03	1.00	0.07	0.02	0.20	0.42	0.27	0.23	0.14
SS5_3	0.27	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.35	0.07	1.00	0.22	0.37	0.14	0.07	0.18	0.18
SS6_3	0.22	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.02	0.22	1.00	0.13	0.27	0.33	0.32	0.32
SS7_3	0.27	0.20	0.48	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.37	0.13	1.00	0.68	0.20	0.18	0.18
SS8_3	0.39	0.19	0.65	0.19	0.42	0.42	0.14	0.27	0.68	1.00	0.19	0.09	0.45
SS9_3	0.07	1.00	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.07	0.33	0.20	0.19	1.00	0.23	0.23
SS10_3	0.18	0.23	0.50	0.23	0.50	0.23	0.18	0.32	0.18	0.09	0.23	1.00	0.44
SS11_3	0.18	0.23	0.14	0.23	0.14	0.14	0.18	0.32	0.18	0.45	0.23	0.44	1.00

Table 33. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case I – Safety & Security Literature Review

	SS1_2	SS2_2	SS1_3	SS2_3	SS3_3	SS4_3	SS5_3	SS6_3	SS7_3	SS8_3	SS9_3	SS10_3	SS11_3
SS1_2	<0.01	0.77	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.14	0.27	0.36	0.27	0.09	0.77	0.47	0.47
SS2_2	0.77	<0.01	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.77	0.17	0.40	0.45	<0.01	0.34	0.34
SS1_3	0.14	0.27	<0.01	0.92	<0.01	0.27	0.77	0.17	0.04	<0.01	0.27	0.03	0.58
SS2_3	0.14	0.27	0.92	<0.01	0.92	0.92	0.77	0.17	0.40	0.45	0.27	0.34	0.34
SS3_3	0.14	0.27	<0.01	0.92	<0.01	0.92	0.14	0.17	0.40	0.07	0.27	0.03	0.58
SS4_3	0.14	0.27	0.27	0.92	0.92	<0.01	0.77	0.95	0.40	0.07	0.27	0.34	0.58
SS5_3	0.27	0.77	0.77	0.77	0.14	0.77	<0.01	0.36	0.12	0.57	0.77	0.47	0.47
SS6_3	0.36	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.17	0.95	0.36	<0.01	0.59	0.27	0.17	0.18	0.18
SS7_3	0.27	0.40	0.04	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.12	0.59	<0.01	<0.01	0.40	0.47	0.47
SS8_3	0.09	0.45	<0.01	0.45	0.07	0.07	0.57	0.27	<0.01	<0.01	0.45	0.70	0.05
SS9_3	0.77	<0.01	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.77	0.17	0.40	0.45	<0.01	0.34	0.34
SS10_3	0.47	0.34	0.03	0.34	0.03	0.34	0.47	0.18	0.47	0.70	0.34	<0.01	0.06
SS11_3	0.47	0.34	0.58	0.34	0.58	0.58	0.47	0.18	0.47	0.05	0.34	0.06	<0.01

- Use Case II - Autonomous vehicles

Use case II includes 6 fairness factors of first level: Safety/Security (SI_1), Comfort (CI_1), Mobility (MI_1), Economy (EI_1), Environment (Envl_1), and Design options (DOI_1).

Safety/Security (SI_1) fairness includes 3 factor of second level and 22 factors of third level (Table 34).

Table 34. Descriptive statistics for Use Case II - Safety/Security

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
SI_1	Safety/Security	0.771	0.426
SI_2	Accident rate	0.286	0.458
S2_2	Human errors	0.171	0.382
S3_2	Training	0.143	0.355
S4_2	Traffic management	0.171	0.382
SI_3	Reduce fatal accidents, since (human) driver errors will be reduced due to no driver is needed.	0.057	0.236
S2_3	AVs are safer than conventional cars	0.114	0.323
S3_3	AVs are more dangerous than conventional cars	0.086	0.284
S4_3	AVs will be introduced on a mass scale when they are as safer as today's vehicles.	0.086	0.284
SS_3	Avoid distraction, inattention, inebriation or fatigue.	0.057	0.236
S6_3	Relates to mental workload.	0.086	0.284
S7_3	Training both initial and regular to refresh knowledge will be needed.	0.057	0.236
S8_3	Training in AV driving will be easier than for conventional cars.	0.086	0.284
S9_3	Improved training methods that more closely align with preferred learning strategies may help to adoption of fully autonomous vehicles.	0.086	0.284
SI0_3	Addressing anxiety-related responses towards automated cars and accentuating especially the pleasurable effects of automated cards reduce differences between men and women.	0.086	0.284
SI1_3	Testing AV navigate through a course with different ground conditions, traffic rules and obstacles will make drivers more proactive to automated vehicles.	0.057	0.236
SI2_3	The experience with driver assistance systems influences the risk assessment on different levels.	0.057	0.236
SI3_3	Traffic control and management should be automated to take the new AV functional possibilities into account.	0.057	0.236
SI4_3	AV will fulfil advices from traffic control more disciplined and more precisely than humans do.	0.057	0.236
SI5_3	The more predictable and cooperative the traffic participants behave the more precise and better vehicle and traffic control systems can become.	0.057	0.236
SI6_3	RTMS (Road Transport Management System) should manage instantaneously the tactical behaviour of thousands of vehicles	0.057	0.236
SI7_3	High-income countries are particularly uncomfortable with the idea that their vehicle shares data to insurance companies, tax authorities or roadway organisations	0.057	0.236
SI8_3	Vehicles automatization will depend on policy goals and on the actions of several players in the transport field	0.057	0.236
SI9_3	Women lack of real and perceived safety in mobility needs be addressed in AVs, specially for MaaS.	0.171	0.382

The results (Table 26 and Table 27) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Accident rate** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S1_3 Reduce fatal accidents, since (human) driver errors will be reduced due to no driver is needed. with $V = 0.26$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S2_3 AVs are safer than conventional cars with $V = 0.12$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - S3_3 AVs are more dangerous than conventional cars with $V = 0.26$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - S4_3 AVs will be introduced on a mass scale when they are as safer as today's vehicles. with $V = 0.12$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - S6_3 Relates to mental workload (inaccurate perceptions, insufficient attention and inefficient information processing). with $V = 0.03$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - S8_3 Training in AV driving will be easier than for conventional cars. with $V = 0.12$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
- **Human errors** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S1_3 Reduce fatal accidents, since (human) driver errors will be reduced due to no driver is needed. with $V = 0.13$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S2_3 AVs are safer than conventional cars with $V = 0.54$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S3_3 AVs are more dangerous than conventional cars with $V = 0.67$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S5_3 Avoid distraction, inattention, inebriation or fatigue. with $V = 0.4$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S6_3 Relates to mental workload (inaccurate perceptions, insufficient attention and inefficient information processing). with $V = 0.13$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S8_3 Training in AV driving will be easier than for conventional cars. with $V = 0.21$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S10_3 Addressing anxiety related responses towards automated cars and accentuating especially the pleasurable effects of automated cards reduce differences between men and women. with $V = 0.11$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$.
- **Training** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S1_3 Reduce fatal accidents, since (human) driver errors will be reduced due to no driver is needed. with $V = 0.17$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S2_3 AVs are safer than conventional cars with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S3_3 AVs are more dangerous than conventional cars with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S5_3 Avoid distraction, inattention, inebriation or fatigue. with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - S6_3 Relates to mental workload (inaccurate perceptions, insufficient attention and inefficient information processing). with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S7_3 Training both initial and regular to refresh knowledge will be needed. with $V = 0.17$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - S8_3 Training in AV driving will be easier than for conventional cars. with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S9_3 Improved training methods that more closely align with preferred learning strategies may help to adoption of fully autonomous vehicles. with $V = 0.1$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S11_3 Testing AV navigate through a course with different ground conditions, traffic rules and obstacles will make drivers more proactive to automated vehicles. with $V = 0.1$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
- **Traffic management** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S2_3 AVs are safer than conventional cars with $V = 0.21$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$;
 - S3_3 AVs are more dangerous than conventional cars with $V = 0.13$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$.

Table 35. Cramer's V for Use Case II - Safety/security Literature Review

Variables	S1_2	S2_2	S3_2	S4_2	S1_3	S2_3	S3_3	S4_3	S5_3	S6_3	S7_3	S8_3	S9_3	S10_3	S11_3	S12_3	S13_3	S14_3	S15_3	S16_3	S17_3	S18_3	S19_3	
S1_2	1.00	0.22	0.28	0.38	0.39	<u>0.37</u>	0.26	0.26	0.12	0.26	0.12	0.26	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.12	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.05
S2_2	0.22	1.00	0.46	0.20	0.54	0.55	0.40	0.13	0.54	0.67	0.21	0.40	0.13	0.40	0.21	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.01
S3_2	0.28	0.46	1.00	0.25	0.60	0.62	0.46	0.17	0.25	0.46	0.25	0.46	0.46	0.17	0.25	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.03
S4_2	0.38	0.20	0.25	1.00	0.21	<u>0.31</u>	0.40	0.13	0.21	0.13	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.21	0.11	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.01
S1_3	0.39	0.54	0.60	0.21	1.00	0.69	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.47	0.80	0.47	0.80	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.47	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.21
S2_3	<u>0.37</u>	0.55	0.62	<u>0.31</u>	0.69	1.00	0.85	0.53	<u>0.30</u>	0.53	<u>0.30</u>	0.85	0.53	0.53	<u>0.30</u>	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.09	<u>0.30</u>	0.09	<u>0.31</u>
S3_3	0.26	0.40	0.46	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.85	1.00	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.08	0.64	0.64	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.40
S4_3	0.26	0.13	0.17	0.13	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.64	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.08	0.64	0.64	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.67
S5_3	0.12	0.54	0.25	0.21	0.47	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	1.00	0.80	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.47	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.21
S6_3	0.26	0.67	0.46	0.13	0.80	0.53	0.27	0.27	0.80	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	0.64	0.27	0.27	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.13
S7_3	0.12	0.21	0.25	0.11	0.47	<u>0.30</u>	0.08	0.08	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.06	0.47	0.11
S8_3	0.26	0.40	0.46	0.13	0.80	0.85	0.64	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	1.00	0.64	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.40
S9_3	0.03	0.13	0.46	0.13	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.64	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.08	0.64	1.00	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.40
S10_3	0.03	0.40	0.17	0.13	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.64	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.08	0.64	0.64	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.40
S11_3	0.12	0.21	0.25	0.21	0.47	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.47	<u>0.36</u>	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	1.00	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.21
S12_3	0.16	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.47	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	1.00	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.06	0.47	0.11
S13_3	0.16	0.11	0.10	0.21	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.47	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.47	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.47	0.06	0.47	0.11	
S14_3	0.16	0.11	0.10	0.21	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.47	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.47	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.47	0.06	0.47	0.11	
S15_3	0.16	0.11	0.10	0.21	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.47	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.47	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.47	0.06	0.47	0.11	
S16_3	0.12	0.11	0.10	0.21	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.47	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	1.00	0.06	0.47	0.11
S17_3	0.16	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.06	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.06	0.08	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	1.00	0.06	0.21
S18_3	0.16	0.11	0.10	0.11	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.08	0.47	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.06	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.06	1.00	0.11
S19_3	0.05	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.21	<u>0.31</u>	0.40	0.67	0.21	0.13	0.11	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.21	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.21	0.11	1.00

Table 36. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case II - Safety/security Literature Review

Variables	S1_2	S2_2	S3_2	S4_2	S1_3	S2_3	S3_3	S4_3	S5_3	S6_3	S7_3	S8_3	S9_3	S10_3	S11_3	S12_3	S13_3	S14_3	S15_3	S16_3	S17_3	S18_3	S19_3	
S1_2	<0.01	0.21	0.10	0.02	0.02	0.03	<u>0.13</u>	<u>0.13</u>	0.50	<u>0.13</u>	0.50	<u>0.13</u>	0.85	0.85	0.50	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.50	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.78
S2_2	0.21	<0.01	<0.01	0.26	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.45	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.02	0.45	0.02	0.22	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.97
S3_2	0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.15</u>	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.34	<u>0.15</u>	0.01	<u>0.15</u>	0.01	0.01	0.34	<u>0.15</u>	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.57	0.86
S4_2	0.02	0.26	<u>0.15</u>	<0.01	0.22	0.07	0.02	0.45	0.22	0.45	0.52	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.22	0.52	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.52	0.52	0.97
S1_3	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.22
S2_3	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.08	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.08	0.61	0.07	
S3_3	<u>0.13</u>	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.03	0.67	0.02	
S4_3	<u>0.13</u>	0.45	0.34	0.45	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.03	0.67	<0.01	
S5_3	0.50	<0.01	<u>0.15</u>	0.22	<0.01	0.08	0.03	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	0.03	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.22
S6_3	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	0.01	0.45	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.45
S7_3	0.50	0.22	<u>0.15</u>	0.52	<0.01	0.08	0.67	0.67	0.73	0.03	<0.01	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	0.52
S8_3	<u>0.13</u>	0.02	0.01	0.45	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.03	0.67	0.02	
S9_3	0.85	0.45	0.01	0.45	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.03	0.67	0.02	
S10_3	0.85	0.02	0.34	0.45	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.03	0.67	0.02	
S11_3	0.50	0.22	<u>0.15</u>	0.22	<0.01	0.08	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.03	0.73	0.03	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.22
S12_3	0.37	0.52	0.57	0.52	0.73	0.61	0.67	0.67	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	0.52
S13_3	0.37	0.52	0.57	0.22	0.73	0.61	0.67	0.67	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	0.52
S14_3	0.37	0.52	0.57	0.22	0.73	0.61	0.67	0.67	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	0.52
S15_3	0.37	0.52	0.57	0.22	0.73	0.61	0.67	0.67	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	0.52
S16_3	0.50	0.52	0.57	0.22	0.73	0.61	0.67	0.67	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	0.52
S17_3	0.37	0.52	0.57	0.52	0.73	0.08	0.03	0.03	0.73	0.67	0.73	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	0.73	<0.01	0.73	0.22
S18_3	0.37	0.52	0.57	0.52	0.73	0.61	0.67	0.67	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.67	0.67	0.67	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	0.52
S19_3	0.78	0.97	0.86	0.97	0.22	0.07	0.02	<0.01	0.22	0.45	0.52	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.22	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.22	0.52	<0.01

Comfort (C1_1) fairness includes 2 factor of second level and 14 factors of third (Table 37).

Table 37. Descriptive statistics for Use Case II – Comfort

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
C1_1	Comfort	0.429	0.502
C1_2	Trust in technology	0.429	0.502
C2_2	Simultaneity	0.143	0.355
C1_3	User's confidence in successfully interacting with the system.	0.057	0.236
C2_3	Trust towards the system's capabilities under different situations (weather conditions, speed, driving style)	0.171	0.382
C3_3	The automated system needs to be calibrated.	0.057	0.236
C4_3	More information and knowledge about this technology is required.	0.114	0.323
C5_3	Unclear interaction and communication between self-driving cars and other vehicles.	0.086	0.284
C6_3	People are unsure how it can work if there is no driver sitting behind the steering wheel. They prefer to rely on themselves.	0.086	0.284
C7_3	Technology explained in simple language could be useful: what, how and when to do if something goes wrong.	0.086	0.284
C8_3	Perceived benefits and barriers of the technologies.	0.086	0.284
C9_3	Control of private information vs insecurity due to the access to drivers' data and movements.	0.057	0.236
C10_3	Catching up on emails, conversing with other passengers or reading the news.	0.086	0.284
C11_3	AV increase the ease of driving.	0.086	0.284
C12_3	AV allows sparing time.	0.171	0.382
C13_3	Driving less fun.	0.086	0.284
C14_3	Users trust the automotive industry to minimize potential risks of AVs to humans.	0.114	0.323
C15_3	Users are suspicious of new technologies, I have serious doubts of their long-term reliability and performance.	0.114	0.323
C16_3	Users prefer to take my decisions. I don't like a machine taking decisions for me.	0.114	0.323
C17_3	Users believe that they can depend and rely on AVs for my displacements.	0.086	0.284
C18_3	Population subgroups of society systematically differ in their willingness to use automated cars	0.171	0.382
C19_3	To have experience of use with this assisting mechanisms is positively correlated with the willingness to use Avs	0.086	0.284
C20_3	Still is difficult to understand what Avs means in practical terms	0.114	0.323

The results (Table 38 and Table 39) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Trust in technology has a strong connection with the following third level factors:**
 - C1_3 User's confidence in successfully interacting with the system. with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.10$;
 - C2_3 Trust towards the system's capabilities under different situations (weather conditions, speed, driving style) with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - C3_3 The automated system needs to be calibrated. with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.10$;
 - C4_3 More information and knowledge about this technology is required. with $V = 0.23$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.18$;
 - C8_3 Perceived benefits and barriers of the technologies. with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$;
 - C10_3 Catching up on emails, conversing with other passengers or reading the news. with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$;
 - C11_3 AV increase the ease of driving. with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$;
 - C12_3 AV allows sparing time. with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - C13_3 Driving less fun. with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$;
 - C14_3 Users trust the automotive industry to minimize potential risks of AVs to humans. with $V = 0.23$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.18$;
 - C15_3 Users are suspicious of new technologies, I have serious doubts of their long-term reliability and performance. with $V = 0.23$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.18$;

- C16_3 Users prefer to take my decisions. I don't like a machine taking decisions for me. with $V = 0.23$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.18$;
- C18_3 Population subgroups of society systematically differ in their willingness to use automated cars with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
- C20_3 Still is difficult to understand what Avs means in practical terms with $V = 0.23$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.18$.
- **Simultaneity has a strong connection with the following third level factors:**
 - C1_3 User's confidence in successfully interacting with the system with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - C2_3 Trust towards the system's capabilities under different situations (weather conditions, speed, driving style) with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - C3_3 The automated system needs to be calibrated with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - C4_3 More information and knowledge about this technology is required with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - C6_3 People are unsure how it can work if there is no driver sitting behind the steering wheel. They prefer to rely on themselves with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - C7_3 Technology explained in simple language could be useful: what, how and when to do if something goes wrong with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - C8_3 Perceived benefits and barriers of the technologies with $V = 0.75$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - C9_3 Control of private information vs insecurity due to the access to drivers' data and movements with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - C10_3 Catching up on emails, conversing with other passengers or reading the news with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - C11_3 AV increase the ease of driving with $V = 0.75$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - C12_3 AV allows sparing time with $V = 0.68$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - C13_3 Driving less fun with $V = 0.75$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - C14_3 Users trust the automotive industry to minimize potential risks of AVs to humans with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - C15_3 Users are suspicious of new technologies, I have serious doubts of their long-term reliability and performance with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - C16_3 Users prefer to take my decisions. I don't like a machine taking decisions for me with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - C18_3 Population subgroups of society systematically differ in their willingness to use automated cars with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - C20_3 Still is difficult to understand what Avs means in practical terms with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$.

Table 38. V-Cramer for Use Case II - Comfort Literature Review

	C1_1	C1_2	C2_2	C1_3	C2_3	C3_3	C4_3	C5_3	C6_3	C7_3	C8_3	C9_3	C10_3	C11_3	C12_3	C13_3	C14_3	C15_3	C16_3	C17_3	C18_3	C19_3	C20_3
C1_1	1.00	1.00	0.47	0.28	0.37	0.28	0.23	0.06	0.15	0.15	<u>0.35</u>	0.04	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.53	<u>0.35</u>	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.15	0.37	0.15	0.23
C1_2	1.00	1.00	0.47	0.28	0.37	0.28	0.23	0.06	0.15	0.15	<u>0.35</u>	0.04	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.53	<u>0.35</u>	0.23	0.23	0.23	0.15	0.37	0.15	0.23
C2_2	0.47	0.47	1.00	0.25	0.25	0.25	<u>0.37</u>	0.17	0.46	0.46	0.75	0.25	0.46	0.75	0.68	0.75	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.17	0.25	0.17	<u>0.37</u>
C1_3	0.28	0.28	0.25	1.00	0.54	1.00	<u>0.30</u>	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	0.69	0.69	0.69	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.30</u>
C2_3	0.37	0.37	0.25	0.54	1.00	0.54	0.07	0.13	0.40	0.40	0.13	0.11	0.67	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.79	0.79	0.79	0.40	0.20	0.40	0.55
C3_3	0.28	0.28	0.25	1.00	0.54	1.00	<u>0.30</u>	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	0.69	0.69	0.69	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.30</u>
C4_3	0.23	0.23	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.07	<u>0.30</u>	1.00	0.21	0.53	0.53	0.53	<u>0.30</u>	0.21	0.53	0.55	0.21	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.21	0.07	0.21	0.15
C5_3	0.06	0.06	0.17	0.08	0.13	0.08	0.21	1.00	0.64	0.64	0.09	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.09	0.14	0.09	0.21
C6_3	0.15	0.15	0.46	<u>0.36</u>	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.64	1.00	1.00	0.27	0.08	0.64	0.64	0.40	0.64	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.53
C7_3	0.15	0.15	0.46	<u>0.36</u>	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.64	1.00	1.00	0.27	0.08	0.64	0.64	0.40	0.64	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.53
C8_3	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.75	<u>0.36</u>	0.13	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.09	0.27	0.27	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.64	0.67	0.64	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.21
C9_3	0.04	0.04	0.25	0.06	0.11	0.06	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	1.00	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.08	0.09	0.09	0.09	0.08	0.11	0.08	0.09
C10_3	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.46	<u>0.36</u>	0.67	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.27	0.64	0.64	0.27	0.08	1.00	0.64	0.67	0.64	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.53
C11_3	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.75	<u>0.36</u>	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.53	0.27	0.64	0.64	0.64	<u>0.36</u>	0.64	1.00	0.67	0.64	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.53
C12_3	0.53	0.53	0.68	0.21	0.40	0.21	0.55	0.13	0.40	0.40	0.67	0.21	0.67	0.67	1.00	0.67	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.13	0.01	0.13	<u>0.31</u>
C13_3	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.75	<u>0.36</u>	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.27	0.64	0.64	0.64	0.08	0.64	0.64	0.67	1.00	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.53
C14_3	0.23	0.23	<u>0.37</u>	0.69	0.79	0.69	0.15	0.21	0.53	0.53	0.21	0.09	0.53	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	0.53	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	0.53	0.72
C15_3	0.23	0.23	<u>0.37</u>	0.69	0.79	0.69	0.15	0.21	0.53	0.53	0.21	0.09	0.53	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	0.53	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	0.53	0.72
C16_3	0.23	0.23	<u>0.37</u>	0.69	0.79	0.69	0.15	0.21	0.53	0.53	0.21	0.09	0.53	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	0.53	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	0.53	0.72
C17_3	0.15	0.15	0.17	<u>0.36</u>	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.09	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.08	0.27	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.53	0.53	0.53	1.00	0.67	1.00	0.53
C18_3	0.37	0.37	0.25	0.21	0.20	0.21	0.07	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.13	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.01	0.13	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.67	1.00	0.67	0.55
C19_3	0.15	0.15	0.17	<u>0.36</u>	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.09	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.08	0.27	0.27	0.13	0.27	0.53	0.53	0.53	1.00	0.67	1.00	0.53
C20_3	0.23	0.23	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.55	<u>0.30</u>	0.15	0.21	0.53	0.53	0.21	0.09	0.53	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	0.53	0.72	0.72	0.72	0.53	0.55	0.53	1.00

Table 39. p-value of χ^2 for Use Case II - Comfort Literature Review

Variables	C1_1	C1_2	C2_2	C1_3	C2_3	C3_3	C4_3	C5_3	C6_3	C7_3	C8_3	C9_3	C10_3	C11_3	C12_3	C13_3	C14_3	C15_3	C16_3	C17_3	C18_3	C19_3	C20_3
C1_1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.10	0.03	0.10	<u>0.18</u>	0.74	0.40	0.40	0.04	0.84	0.04	0.04	<0.01	0.04	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	0.40	0.03	0.40	<u>0.18</u>
C1_2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.10	0.03	0.10	<u>0.18</u>	0.74	0.40	0.40	0.04	0.84	0.04	0.04	<0.01	0.04	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	0.40	0.03	0.40	<u>0.18</u>
C2_2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.15</u>	<u>0.15</u>	<u>0.15</u>	0.03	0.34	0.01	0.01	<0.01	<u>0.15</u>	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.34	<u>0.15</u>	0.34	0.03
C1_3	0.10	0.10	<u>0.15</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.08	0.67	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.73	0.03	0.03	0.22	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.22	0.03	0.08
C2_3	0.03	0.03	<u>0.15</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.67	0.45	0.02	0.02	0.45	0.52	<0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.26	0.02	<0.01
C3_3	0.10	0.10	<u>0.15</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.08	0.67	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.73	0.03	0.03	0.22	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.22	0.03	0.08
C4_3	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	0.03	0.08	0.67	0.08	<0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.08	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.38	0.38	0.38	0.22	0.67	0.22	0.38
C5_3	0.74	0.74	0.34	0.67	0.45	0.67	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.59	0.03	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.59	0.42	0.59	0.22
C6_3	0.40	0.40	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01
C7_3	0.40	0.40	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01
C8_3	0.04	0.04	<0.01	0.03	0.45	0.03	<0.01	0.59	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.03	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.22	0.22	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	0.22
C9_3	0.84	0.84	<u>0.15</u>	0.73	0.52	0.73	0.08	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.03	<0.01	0.67	0.03	0.22	0.67	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.67	0.52	0.67	0.61
C10_3	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.03	<0.01	0.03	0.22	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01
C11_3	0.04	0.04	<0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01
C12_3	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.02	0.22	<0.01	0.45	0.02	0.02	<0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	0.07	0.07	0.45	0.97	0.45	0.07
C13_3	0.04	0.04	<0.01	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.22	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01
C14_3	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.38	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.61	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01
C15_3	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.38	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.61	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01
C16_3	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.38	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.61	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01
C17_3	0.40	0.40	0.34	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.22	0.59	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
C18_3	0.03	0.03	<u>0.15</u>	0.22	0.26	0.22	0.67	0.42	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.52	0.45	0.45	0.97	0.45	0.07	0.07	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
C19_3	0.40	0.40	0.34	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.22	0.59	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.67	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.45	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
C20_3	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.18</u>	0.03	0.08	<0.01	0.08	0.38	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.61	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

Mobility (M1_1) fairness includes 4 factor of second level and 11 factors of third level Table 40.

Table 40. Descriptive statistics for Use Case II - Mobility

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
M1_1	Mobility	0.583	0.493
M1_2	Traffic efficiency	0.333	0.482
M2_2	Travel time	0.042	0.204
M3_2	Congestion	0.167	0.381
M4_2	Accessibility	0.167	0.381
M1_3	The identification of the traffic situation is also the main control parameter for optimal, adaptive traffic control.	0.042	0.204
M2_3	Private cars can drive more densely, requiring less space. Space between cars can be reduced.	0.042	0.204
M3_3	Consequences related to stopping vehicles.	0.042	0.204
M4_3	AV will increase road capacity with a better traffic distribution.	0.042	0.204
M5_3	Lower delays due to parking search.	0.042	0.204
M6_3	AVs save travel time.	0.042	0.204
M7_3	Travel patterns will change.	0.042	0.204
M8_3	AVs influence the quantity of trips and the number of vehicles as well as the traffic flow.	0.083	0.282
M9_3	Green wave technology will reduce traffic jams.	0.042	0.204
M10_3	Benefit mobility for older people, people with disabilities and persons without driving licenses.	0.125	0.338
M11_3	Promotions and campaigns to help children, young people, older will increase automated vehicles use.	0.042	0.204

The results (Table 41 and Table 42) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Traffic efficiency** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - M5_3 AV speeds may be slower than conventional cars, one may expect AVs to reinforce (and perhaps even magnify) existing gender differences in commuting with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
- **Travel time** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - M1_3 Private cars can drive more densely, requiring less space. Space between cars can be reduced with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - M4_3 AVs save travel time with $V = 0.8$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - M5_3 AV speeds may be slower than conventional cars, one may expect AVs to reinforce (and perhaps even magnify) existing gender differences in commuting with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - M6_3 Travel patterns will change with $V = 0.8$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - M7_3 AVs influence the quantity of trips and the number of vehicles as well as the traffic flow with $V = 0.64$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - M10_3 Promotions and campaigns to help children, young people, older will increase automated vehicles use with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - M11_3 Women and men have different patterns of mobility. Trip chaining vs. Simple commute from A to B with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$;
 - M12_3 The predominant users of carshare schemes are men with at least a university-level education with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

Table 41. V-Cramer for Use Case II – Mobility Literature Review

Variables	M1_2	M2_2	M3_2	M4_2	M1_3	M2_3	M3_3	M4_3	M5_3	M6_3	M7_3	M8_3	M9_3	M10_3	M11_3	M12_3
M1_2	1.00	0.26	0.22	0.22	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.12	<u>0.37</u>	0.12	0.03	0.16	0.03	0.12	0.16	0.17
M2_2	0.26	1.00	0.67	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.80	0.53	0.80	0.64	0.08	0.11	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.53
M3_2	0.22	0.67	1.00	1.00	0.20	0.21	0.11	0.54	<u>0.31</u>	0.54	0.67	0.21	0.16	0.21	0.15	<u>0.31</u>
M4_2	0.22	0.40	0.20	1.00	0.11	0.11	0.11	0.21	<u>0.31</u>	0.21	0.13	0.11	0.55	0.54	0.15	<u>0.31</u>
M1_3	0.16	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.11	1.00	0.47	0.47	0.47	<u>0.09</u>	0.47	<u>0.36</u>	0.47	<u>0.30</u>	0.06	0.12	0.09
M2_3	0.16	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.47	1.00	1.00	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.08	0.47	<u>0.30</u>	0.06	0.12	0.09
M3_3	0.16	0.08	0.11	0.11	0.47	1.00	1.00	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.08	0.47	<u>0.30</u>	0.06	0.12	0.09
M4_3	0.12	0.80	0.54	0.54	0.47	0.06	0.06	1.00	<u>0.30</u>	1.00	0.80	0.06	0.09	0.47	0.18	<u>0.30</u>
M5_3	<u>0.37</u>	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.09	0.09	0.09	<u>0.30</u>	1.00	<u>0.30</u>	0.21	0.09	0.13	<u>0.30</u>	0.72	0.72
M6_3	0.12	0.80	0.54	<u>0.31</u>	0.47	0.06	0.06	1.00	<u>0.30</u>	1.00	0.80	0.06	0.09	0.47	0.18	<u>0.30</u>
M7_3	0.03	0.64	0.67	0.13	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.80	0.21	0.80	1.00	0.08	0.11	<u>0.36</u>	0.10	0.21
M8_3	0.16	0.08	0.21	0.11	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.06	0.09	0.06	0.08	1.00	<u>0.30</u>	0.06	0.12	0.09
M9_3	0.03	0.11	0.16	0.55	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.09	0.13	0.09	0.11	<u>0.30</u>	1.00	<u>0.30</u>	0.18	0.13
M10_3	0.12	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	0.54	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.47	<u>0.30</u>	0.47	<u>0.36</u>	0.06	<u>0.30</u>	1.00	0.18	<u>0.30</u>
M11_3	0.16	<u>0.36</u>	0.15	0.15	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.18	0.72	0.18	0.10	0.12	0.18	0.18	1.00	0.49
M12_3	0.17	0.53	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.09	0.09	0.09	<u>0.30</u>	0.72	<u>0.30</u>	0.21	0.09	0.13	<u>0.30</u>	0.49	1.00

Table 42. p-value of χ^2 Use Case II – Mobility Literature Review

	M1_2	M2_2	M3_2	M4_2	M1_3	M2_3	M3_3	M4_3	M5_3	M6_3	M7_3	M8_3	M9_3	M10_3	M11_3	M12_3
M1_2	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.21	0.21	0.37	0.37	0.37	0.50	0.03	0.50	0.85	0.37	0.87	0.50	0.36	0.33
M2_2	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.03	0.67	0.67	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.67	0.53	0.03	0.04	<0.01
M3_2	0.21	<0.01	<0.01	0.26	0.22	0.52	0.52	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.35	0.22	0.38	0.07
M4_2	0.21	0.02	0.26	<0.01	0.52	0.52	0.52	0.22	0.07	0.22	0.45	0.52	<0.01	<0.01	0.38	0.07
M1_3	0.37	0.03	0.22	0.52	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.61	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	0.08	0.73	0.48	0.61
M2_3	0.37	0.67	0.52	0.52	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	0.61	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.08	0.73	0.48	0.61
M3_3	0.37	0.67	0.52	0.52	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	0.61	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.08	0.73	0.48	0.61
M4_3	0.50	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	<0.01	0.73	0.73	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	0.61	<0.01	0.29	0.08
M5_3	0.03	<0.01	0.07	0.07	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.08	<0.01	0.08	0.22	0.61	0.46	0.08	<0.01	<0.01
M6_3	0.50	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	<0.01	0.73	0.73	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	0.61	<0.01	0.29	0.08
M7_3	0.85	<0.01	<0.01	0.45	0.03	0.67	0.67	<0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	0.67	0.53	0.03	0.56	0.22
M8_3	0.37	0.67	0.22	0.52	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.73	0.61	0.73	0.67	<0.01	0.08	0.73	0.48	0.61
M9_3	0.87	0.53	0.35	<0.01	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.61	0.46	0.61	0.53	0.08	<0.01	0.08	0.30	0.46
M10_3	0.50	0.03	0.22	<0.01	0.73	0.73	0.73	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	0.03	0.73	0.08	<0.01	0.29	0.08
M11_3	0.36	0.04	0.38	0.38	0.48	0.48	0.48	0.29	<0.01	0.29	0.56	0.48	0.30	0.29	<0.01	<0.01
M12_3	0.33	<0.01	0.07	0.07	0.61	0.61	0.61	0.08	<0.01	0.08	0.22	0.61	0.46	0.08	<0.01	<0.01

- **Congestion** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - M4_3 AVs save travel time with $V = 0.54$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - M5_3 AV speeds may be slower than conventional cars, one may expect AVs to reinforce (and perhaps even magnify) existing gender differences in commuting with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$;
 - M6_3 Travel patterns will change with $V = 0.54$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - M7_3 AVs influence the quantity of trips and the number of vehicles as well as the traffic flow with $V = 0.67$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - M12_3 The predominant users of carshare schemes are men with at least a university-level education with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$;
- **Accessibility** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - M1_3 Private cars can drive more densely, requiring less space. Space between cars can be reduced with $V = 0.11$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.52$;
 - M4_3 AVs save travel time with $V = 0.21$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.22$;
 - M5_3 AV speeds may be slower than conventional cars, one may expect AVs to reinforce (and perhaps even magnify) existing gender differences in commuting with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$;
 - M6_3 Travel patterns will change with $V = 0.21$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.22$;
 - M7_3 AVs influence the quantity of trips and the number of vehicles as well as the traffic flow with $V = 0.13$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.45$;
 - M10_3 Promotions and campaigns to help children, young people, older will increase automated vehicles use with $V = 0.54$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - M12_3 The predominant users of carshare schemes are men with at least a university-level education with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$;

Economy (E1_1) fairness includes 3 factor of second level and 9 factors of third level (Table 43).

Table 43. Descriptive statistics for Use Case II – Economy

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
E1_1	Economy	0.314	0.471
E1_2	Monetary costs	0.257	0.443
E2_2	Non-monetary costs	0.114	0.323
E3_2	Vehicle efficiency	0.114	0.323
E1_3	Save fuel. For example, green wave technology will reduce fuel consumption.	0.114	0.323
E2_3	Costs of the new technologies.	0.057	0.236
E3_3	Higher capital costs for vehicles.	0.057	0.236
E4_3	Save time value private/work trips.	0.057	0.236
E5_3	Save environmental effects.	0.086	0.284
E6_3	Increase traffic safety.	0.086	0.284
E7_3	Losing driving skills.	0.086	0.284
E8_3	AV will allow a more efficient use of cars.	0.143	0.355
E9_3	Travel will be faster.	0.057	0.236
E10_3	Many experts expect level 4+ to be affordable and commonplace 2040s	0.086	0.284

The results (Table 39 and Table 45) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Monetary costs** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - E1_3 Save fuel. For example, green wave technology will reduce fuel consumption with $V = 0.61$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - E2_3 Costs of the new technologies with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - E3_3 Higher capital costs for vehicles with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - E4_3 Save time value private/work trips with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - E5_3 Save environmental effects with $V = 0.52$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - E6_3 Increase traffic safety with $V = 0.52$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;

- E7_3 Losing driving skills with $V = 0.29$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$;
- E10_3 Many experts expect level 4+ to be affordable and commonplace 2040s with $V = 0.29$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$;
- **Non Monetary costs** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - E1_3 Save fuel. For example, green wave technology will reduce fuel consumption with $V = 0.44$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - E2_3 Costs of the new technologies with $V = 0.69$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - E3_3 Higher capital costs for vehicles with $V = 0.69$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - E4_3 Save time value private/work trips with $V = 0.69$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - E5_3 Save environmental effects with $V = 0.85$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - E6_3 Increase traffic safety with $V = 0.85$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - E8_3 AV will allow a more efficient use of cars with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - E9_3 Travel will be faster with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
- **Vehicle efficiency** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - E3_3 Higher capital costs for vehicles with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - E4_3 Save time value private/work trips with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - E8_3 AV will allow a more efficient use of cars with $V = 0.62$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - E9_3 Travel will be faster with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;

Table 44. V-Cramer for Use Case II - Economy Literature Review

Variables	E1_2	E2_2	E3_2	E1_3	E2_3	E3_3	E4_3	E5_3	E6_3	E7_3	E8_3	E9_3	E10_3
E1_2	1.00	0.61	0.20	0.61	0.42	0.42	0.42	0.52	0.52	0.29	0.13	0.14	0.29
E2_2	0.61	1.00	0.44	0.44	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.85	0.85	0.21	0.37	0.30	0.21
E3_2	0.20	0.44	1.00	0.15	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.62	0.30	0.21
E1_3	0.61	0.44	0.15	1.00	0.69	0.69	0.69	0.53	0.53	0.21	0.37	0.30	0.21
E2_3	0.42	0.69	0.30	0.69	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.80	0.36	0.60	0.47	0.36
E3_3	0.42	0.69	0.30	0.69	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.80	0.36	0.60	0.47	0.36
E4_3	0.42	0.69	0.30	0.69	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.80	0.36	0.60	0.47	0.36
E5_3	0.52	0.85	0.21	0.53	0.80	0.80	0.80	1.00	1.00	0.27	0.46	0.36	0.27
E6_3	0.52	0.85	0.21	0.53	0.80	0.80	0.80	1.00	1.00	0.27	0.46	0.36	0.27
E7_3	0.29	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.27	0.27	1.00	0.17	0.80	0.27
E8_3	0.13	0.37	0.62	0.37	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.46	0.46	0.17	1.00	0.25	0.17
E9_3	0.14	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.47	0.47	0.47	0.36	0.36	0.80	0.25	1.00	0.36
E10_3	0.29	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.36	0.36	0.36	0.27	0.27	0.27	0.17	0.36	1.00

Table 45. p-value of χ^2 for Use Case II - Economy Literature Review

	E1_2	E2_2	E3_2	E1_3	E2_3	E3_3	E4_3	E5_3	E6_3	E7_3	E8_3	E9_3	E10_3
E1_2	<0.01	<0.01	0.25	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.09	0.44	0.43	0.09
E2_2	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.03	0.08	0.22
E3_2	0.25	0.01	<0.01	0.38	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.22	0.22	0.22	<0.01	0.08	0.22
E1_3	<0.01	0.01	0.38	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.03	0.08	0.22
E2_3	0.01	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
E3_3	0.01	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
E4_3	0.01	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.03
E5_3	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.12	0.01	0.03	0.12
E6_3	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.12	0.01	0.03	0.12
E7_3	0.09	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.12	<0.01	0.34	<0.01	0.12
E8_3	0.44	0.03	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.34	<0.01	0.15	0.34
E9_3	0.43	0.08	0.08	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.15	<0.01	0.03
E10_3	0.09	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.12	0.12	0.34	0.03	<0.01

Environment (Env1_1) fairness includes 3 factor of second level and 5 factors of third level (Table 46).

Table 46. Descriptive statistics for Use Case II - Environment

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
Env1_1	Environment	0.343	0.482
Env1_2	Noise	0.114	0.323
Env2_2	Emissions	0.257	0.443
Env3_2	Public Health	0.171	0.382
Env1_3	More smooth acceleration/deceleration and optimization of the traffic flow.	0.086	0.284
Env2_3	AV will reduce emissions due to less fuel consumption and traffic optimization.	0.229	0.426
Env3_3	More smooth acceleration/deceleration will produce less emissions.	0.114	0.323
Env4_3	Arriving relaxed at the destination. Reduce the pressure associated with driving in stressful scenarios.	0.143	0.355
Env5_3	Service (MaaS) aims to greatly reduce the number of privately-owned cars and improve cities	0.057	0.236

The results (Table 42 and Table 48) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Noise** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - Env1_3 More smooth acceleration/deceleration and optimization of the traffic flow with $V = 0.85$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - Env2_3 AV will reduce emissions due to less fuel consumption and traffic optimization with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - Env3_3 More smooth acceleration/deceleration will produce less emissions with $V = 0.72$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - Env4_3 Arriving relaxed at the destination. Reduce the pressure associated with driving in stressful scenarios with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - Env5_3 Service (MaaS) aims to greatly reduce the number of privately-owned cars and improve cities with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
- **Emissions** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - Env1_3 More smooth acceleration/deceleration and optimization of the traffic flow with $V = 0.52$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - Env2_3 AV will reduce emissions due to less fuel consumption and traffic optimization with $V = 0.93$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - Env3_3 More smooth acceleration/deceleration will produce less emissions with $V = 0.61$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - Env4_3 Arriving relaxed at the destination. Reduce the pressure associated with driving in stressful scenarios with $V = 0.51$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;

Table 47. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case II – Environment Literature Review

Variables	Env1_2	Env2_2	Env3_2	Env1_3	Env2_3	Env3_3	Env4_3	Env5_3
Env1_2	1.00	0.50	0.81	0.63	0.42	0.75	0.50	0.39
Env2_2	0.50	1.00	0.61	<u>0.31</u>	0.85	0.45	0.72	<u>0.37</u>
Env3_2	0.81	0.61	1.00	0.43	0.52	0.93	0.61	0.51
Env1_3	0.63	<u>0.31</u>	0.43	1.00	0.40	0.47	0.55	0.68
Env2_3	0.42	0.85	0.52	0.40	1.00	0.56	0.85	0.46
Env3_3	0.75	0.45	0.93	0.47	0.56	1.00	0.66	0.56
Env4_3	0.50	0.72	0.61	0.55	0.85	0.66	1.00	0.62
Env5_3	0.39	<u>0.37</u>	0.51	0.68	0.46	0.56	0.62	1.00

Table 48. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case II – Environment Literature Review

Variables	Env1_2	Env2_2	Env3_2	Env1_3	Env2_3	Env3_3	Env4_3	Env5_3
Env1_2	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.08
Env2_2	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.43
Env3_2	0.07	0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.52
Env1_3	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.67
Env2_3	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.44
Env3_3	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.61
Env4_3	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.57
Env5_3	0.08	0.43	0.52	0.67	0.44	0.61	0.57	<0.01

Design options (DOI 1) fairness includes 3 factor of second level and 21 factors of third level (Error! Reference source not found.).

Table 49. Descriptive statistics for Use Case II - Design options

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
DOI_1	Design options	0.371	0.490
DOI_2	Infrastructure adaptation	0.229	0.426
DO2_2	Vehicle shape	0.143	0.355
DO3_2	Vehicle behaviour	0.143	0.355
DO4_2	Human Machine Interface (HMI)	0.286	0.458
DOI_3	Reduce the number of potential conflicts when separated lanes are used.	0.114	0.323
DO2_3	Private cars can drive more densely, requiring less space, which can result in narrower lanes and fewer streets.	0.057	0.236
DO3_3	Applicable in high-speed and low-speed scenarios.	0.057	0.236
DO4_3	Building special lanes for AVs with mixed traffic.	0.114	0.323
DO5_3	No differentiation for vehicles with multiple automation levels.	0.057	0.236
DO6_3	Shorter reaction time and better vehicles' coordination.	0.086	0.284
DO7_3	Lower acceleration and deceleration.	0.086	0.284
DO8_3	AV will avoid suboptimal behaviour like inappropriate time headways and speeds.	0.086	0.284
DO9_3	The AV interface allows the driver to retrieve important information with one glance.	0.143	0.355
DOI10_3	Drivers need to know how to interact with them.	0.143	0.355
DOI1_3	Different interfaces for different manufacturers will difficult the driver.	0.114	0.323
DOI2_3	Connectivity allows for internet in-vehicle internet services and for vehicles to communicate with each other or infrastructure to inform you of the most appropriate speed to safely and comfortable merge with the motorway traffic.	0.086	0.284
DOI3_3	Badly designed user interfaces may lead to distraction, confusion, frustration and disuse.	0.086	0.284
DOI4_3	Human centred design has been overshadowed by technology-led innovation	0.114	0.323
DOI5_3	Human-centred innovation has to be women inclusive	0.086	0.284
DOI6_3	The public opinion on automated driving cars is different from that of regular cars, where the discussion topics for fully automated cars are more on handling, safety, innovation, and trust and less on the engine, transmission, and styling	0.114	0.323

The results (Table 50 and Table 51) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Infrastructure adaptation** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - DOI_3 Reduce the number of potential conflicts when separated lanes are used with $V = 0.66$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO3_3 Applicable in high-speed and low-speed scenarios with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO4_3 Building special lanes for AVs with mixed traffic with $V = 0.66$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO5_3 No differentiation for vehicles with multiple automation levels with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO8_3 AV will avoid suboptimal behaviour like inappropriate time headways and speeds with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
 - DO9_3 The AV interface allows the driver to retrieve important information with one glance with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DOI10_3 Drivers need to know how to interact with them with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DOI1_3 Different interfaces for different manufacturers will difficult the driver with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DOI2_3 Connectivity allows for internet in-vehicle internet services and for vehicles to communicate with each other or infrastructure to inform you of the most appropriate speed to safely and comfortable merge with the motorway traffic with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;

- DO13_3 Badly designed user interfaces may lead to distraction, confusion, frustration and disuse with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
- DO14_3 Human centred design has been overshadowed by technology-led innovation with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
- DO15_3 Human-centred innovation has to be women inclusive with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
- DO16_3 The public opinion on automated driving cars is different from that of regular cars, where the discussion topics for fully automated cars are more on handling, safety, innovation, and trust and less on the engine, transmission, and styling with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
- **Vehicle shape** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - DO1_3 Reduce the number of potential conflicts when separated lanes are used with $V = 0.62$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO3_3 Applicable in high-speed and low-speed scenarios with $V = 0.6$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO4_3 Building special lanes for AVs with mixed traffic with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DO5_3 No differentiation for vehicles with multiple automation levels with $V = 0.6$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO8_3 AV will avoid suboptimal behaviour like inappropriate time headways and speeds with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO9_3 The AV interface allows the driver to retrieve important information with one glance with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - DO10_3 Drivers need to know how to interact with them with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - DO11_3 Different interfaces for different manufacturers will difficult the driver with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DO12_3 Connectivity allows for internet in-vehicle internet services and for vehicles to communicate with each other or infrastructure to inform you of the most appropriate speed to safely and comfortable merge with the motorway traffic with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO13_3 Badly designed user interfaces may lead to distraction, confusion, frustration and disuse with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO14_3 Human centred design has been overshadowed by technology-led innovation with $V = 0.62$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO15_3 Human-centred innovation has to be women inclusive with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO16_3 The public opinion on automated driving cars is different from that of regular cars, where the discussion topics for fully automated cars are more on handling, safety, innovation, and trust and less on the engine, transmission, and styling with $V = 0.62$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- **Vehicle behavior** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - DO1_3 Reduce the number of potential conflicts when separated lanes are used with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DO3_3 Applicable in high-speed and low-speed scenarios with $V = 0.6$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO4_3 Building special lanes for AVs with mixed traffic with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DO5_3 No differentiation for vehicles with multiple automation levels with $V = 0.6$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO8_3 AV will avoid suboptimal behaviour like inappropriate time headways and speeds with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO9_3 The AV interface allows the driver to retrieve important information with one glance with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO10_3 Drivers need to know how to interact with them with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO11_3 Different interfaces for different manufacturers will difficult the driver with $V = 0.62$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO12_3 Connectivity allows for internet in-vehicle internet services and for vehicles to communicate with each other or infrastructure to inform you of the most appropriate speed to safely and comfortable merge with the motorway traffic with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO13_3 Badly designed user interfaces may lead to distraction, confusion, frustration and disuse with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO14_3 Human centred design has been overshadowed by technology-led innovation with $V = 0.62$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO15_3 Human-centred innovation has to be women inclusive with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - DO16_3 The public opinion on automated driving cars is different from that of regular cars, where the discussion topics for fully automated cars are more on handling, safety, innovation, and trust and less on the engine, transmission, and styling with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;

- **Human Machine Interface (HMI)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - DO1_3 Reduce the number of potential conflicts when separated lanes are used with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DO3_3 Applicable in high-speed and low-speed scenarios with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - DO4_3 Building special lanes for AVs with mixed traffic with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DO5_3 No differentiation for vehicles with multiple automation levels with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - DO7_3 Lower acceleration and deceleration with $V = 0.48$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO8_3 AV will avoid suboptimal behaviour like inappropriate time headways and speeds with $V = 0.26$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - DO9_3 The AV interface allows the driver to retrieve important information with one glance with $V = 0.65$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO10_3 Drivers need to know how to interact with them with $V = 0.65$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO11_3 Different interfaces for different manufacturers will difficult the driver with $V = 0.57$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - DO12_3 Connectivity allows for internet in-vehicle internet services and for vehicles to communicate with each other or infrastructure to inform you of the most appropriate speed to safely and comfortable merge with the motorway traffic with $V = 0.26$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - DO13_3 Badly designed user interfaces may lead to distraction, confusion, frustration and disuse with $V = 0.26$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - DO14_3 Human centred design has been overshadowed by technology-led innovation with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - DO15_3 Human-centred innovation has to be women inclusive with $V = 0.26$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;

Table 50. V-Cramer for Use Case II – Design options Literature Review

Variables	DOI_2	DO2_2	DO3_2	DO4_2	DOI_3	DO2_3	DO3_3	DO4_3	DO5_3	DO6_3	DO7_3	DO8_3	DO9_3	DOI0_3	DOI1_3	DOI2_3	DOI3_3	DOI4_3	DOI5_3	DOI6_3
DOI_2	1.00	0.75	0.75	0.56	0.66	0.16	0.45	0.66	0.45	0.08	0.08	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.45	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.32</u>	0.45	<u>0.32</u>	0.45
DO2_2	0.75	1.00	0.77	0.46	0.62	0.10	0.60	<u>0.37</u>	0.60	0.17	0.17	0.46	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.46	0.46	0.62	0.46	0.62
DO3_2	0.75	0.77	1.00	0.65	<u>0.37</u>	0.10	0.60	<u>0.37</u>	0.60	0.17	0.17	0.46	0.53	0.53	0.62	0.46	0.46	0.62	0.46	<u>0.37</u>
DO4_2	0.56	0.46	0.65	1.00	<u>0.37</u>	0.16	0.39	<u>0.37</u>	0.39	0.03	0.48	0.26	0.65	0.65	0.57	0.26	0.26	<u>0.37</u>	0.26	0.17
DOI_3	0.66	0.62	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.37</u>	1.00	0.09	0.69	0.72	0.69	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.11	0.11	0.44	0.21	0.21	0.15	0.21	0.44
DO2_3	0.16	0.10	0.10	0.16	0.09	1.00	0.06	<u>0.30</u>	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	0.08	0.08	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.08	0.08	0.09	0.08	0.09
DO3_3	0.45	0.60	0.60	0.39	0.69	0.06	1.00	0.69	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.25	0.25	0.69	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.30</u>
DO4_3	0.66	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.72	<u>0.30</u>	0.69	1.00	0.69	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.11	0.11	0.44	0.21	0.21	0.15	0.21	0.15
DO5_3	0.45	0.60	0.60	0.39	0.69	0.06	1.00	0.69	1.00	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.25	0.25	0.69	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.30</u>
DO6_3	0.08	0.17	0.17	0.03	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	1.00	0.09	0.09	0.13	0.13	0.21	0.09	0.09	0.11	0.09	0.11
DO7_3	0.08	0.17	0.17	0.48	0.21	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	0.09	1.00	0.27	0.46	0.17	0.21	0.27	0.27	0.21	0.27	0.21
DO8_3	<u>0.32</u>	0.46	0.46	0.26	0.21	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	0.09	0.27	1.00	0.46	0.46	0.21	1.00	1.00	0.53	0.27	0.53
DO9_3	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.53	0.65	0.11	0.10	0.25	0.11	0.25	0.13	0.46	0.46	1.00	0.77	0.62	0.46	0.46	<u>0.37</u>	0.17	<u>0.37</u>
DOI0_3	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.53	0.65	0.11	0.10	0.25	0.11	0.25	0.13	0.17	0.46	0.77	1.00	0.62	0.46	0.46	<u>0.37</u>	0.17	<u>0.37</u>
DOI1_3	0.45	<u>0.37</u>	0.62	0.57	0.44	0.09	0.69	0.44	0.69	0.21	0.21	0.21	0.62	0.62	1.00	0.21	0.21	0.15	0.21	0.15
DOI2_3	<u>0.32</u>	0.46	0.46	0.26	0.21	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	0.09	0.27	1.00	0.46	0.46	0.21	1.00	1.00	0.53	0.27	0.53
DOI3_3	<u>0.32</u>	0.46	0.46	0.26	0.21	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	0.09	0.27	1.00	0.46	0.46	0.21	1.00	1.00	0.53	0.27	0.53
DOI4_3	0.45	0.62	0.62	<u>0.37</u>	0.15	0.09	<u>0.30</u>	0.15	<u>0.30</u>	0.11	0.21	0.53	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.15	0.53	0.53	1.00	0.85	0.72
DOI5_3	<u>0.32</u>	0.46	0.46	0.26	0.21	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	0.21	<u>0.36</u>	0.09	0.27	0.27	0.17	0.17	0.21	0.27	0.27	0.85	1.00	0.53
DOI6_3	0.45	0.62	<u>0.37</u>	0.17	0.44	0.09	<u>0.30</u>	0.15	<u>0.30</u>	0.11	0.21	0.53	<u>0.37</u>	<u>0.37</u>	0.15	0.53	0.53	0.72	0.53	1.00

Table 51. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case II – Design options Literature Review

Variables	DOI_2	DO2_2	DO3_2	DO4_2	DOI_3	DO2_3	DO3_3	DO4_3	DO5_3	DO6_3	DO7_3	DO8_3	DO9_3	DOI0_3	DOI1_3	DOI2_3	DOI3_3	DOI4_3	DOI5_3	DOI6_3
DOI_2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.36	0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.66	0.66	0.06	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.06	0.06	0.01	0.06	0.01
DO2_2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.57	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	0.34	0.34	0.01	0.08	0.08	0.03	0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01
DO3_2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.57	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	0.34	0.34	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.03
DO4_2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.37	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.85	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	<u>0.13</u>	0.03	<u>0.13</u>	0.33
DOI_3	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.61	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.53	0.53	0.01	0.22	0.22	0.38	0.22	0.01
DO2_3	0.36	0.57	0.57	0.37	0.61	<0.01	0.73	0.08	0.73	0.03	0.67	0.67	0.57	0.57	0.61	0.67	0.67	0.61	0.67	0.61
DO3_3	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	<u>0.15</u>	<u>0.15</u>	<0.01	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.08
DO4_3	<0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.53	0.53	0.01	0.22	0.22	0.38	0.22	0.38
DO5_3	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.73	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	<u>0.15</u>	<u>0.15</u>	<0.01	0.03	0.03	0.08	0.03	0.08
DO6_3	0.66	0.34	0.34	0.85	0.22	0.03	0.03	0.22	0.03	<0.01	0.59	0.59	0.47	0.47	0.22	0.59	0.59	0.53	0.59	0.53
DO7_3	0.66	0.34	0.34	<0.01	0.22	0.67	0.03	0.22	0.03	0.59	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.01	0.34	0.22	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.22	<u>0.12</u>	0.22
DO8_3	0.06	0.01	0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.22	0.67	0.03	0.22	0.03	0.59	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01
DO9_3	0.03	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	0.53	0.57	<u>0.15</u>	0.53	<u>0.15</u>	0.47	0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.34	0.03
DOI0_3	0.03	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	0.53	0.57	<u>0.15</u>	0.53	<u>0.15</u>	0.47	0.34	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.34	0.03
DOI1_3	0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.61	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.22	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.22	0.38	0.22	0.38
DOI2_3	0.06	0.01	0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.22	0.67	0.03	0.22	0.03	0.59	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01
DOI3_3	0.06	0.01	0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.22	0.67	0.03	0.22	0.03	0.59	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.22	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01
DOI4_3	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.38	0.61	0.08	0.38	0.08	0.53	0.22	<0.01	0.03	0.03	0.38	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
DOI5_3	0.06	0.01	0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.22	0.67	0.03	0.22	0.03	0.59	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.34	0.34	0.22	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
DOI6_3	0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.33	0.01	0.61	0.08	0.38	0.08	0.53	0.22	<0.01	0.03	0.03	0.38	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

- **Use Case III – Bicycle sharing services**

Use case III includes 4 first level fairness: Accessibility and Spontaneity (ASPI_1), Safety & Security (S&SI_1), Social constraints (SCI_1), and Weather & Topography (WTI_1).

The Accessibility and Spontaneity (ASPI_1) includes 7 factor of second level and 31 factors of third level (Table 52).

Table 52. Descriptive statistics for Use Case III - Accessibility and Spontaneity

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
ASP1_1	Accessibility and Spontaneity	1.000	0.000
ASP2_1	Public awareness	0.542	0.509
ASP2_2	Sign-up & booking process	0.375	0.495
ASP2_3	Membership cost	0.417	0.504
ASP2_4	Spontaneity of accessing bike/dock	0.542	0.509
ASP2_5	Proximity of docking station	0.417	0.504
ASP2_6	Travelling with children/ Carrying things	0.667	0.482
ASP2_7	Insufficient Infrastructure	0.792	0.415
ASP3_1	Creating public awareness about practical cycling	0.417	0.504
ASP3_2	Creating public awareness of cycling routes	0.417	0.504
ASP3_3	Advertising bike sharing services and locations of docking stations	0.375	0.495
ASP3_4	Simple and flexible signing-up process	0.375	0.495
ASP3_5	The requirement to sign-up for membership	0.333	0.482
ASP3_6	Availability of cash payment option	0.250	0.442
ASP3_7	Entry cost (upfront cost)	0.417	0.504
ASP3_8	Rental charges for trips above one hour	0.167	0.381
ASP3_9	Annual membership cost	0.375	0.495
ASP3_10	Accessories cost (helmet, clothing etc.)	0.125	0.338
ASP3_11	Fear of liability resulting from overage fees, damages and theft of the bike	0.125	0.338
ASP3_12	The availability of a shared bike and a vacant dock when required	0.167	0.381
ASP3_13	Reliability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs	0.167	0.381
ASP3_14	Availability and coverage of docking stations	0.542	0.509
ASP3_15	Coverage at major transport hubs	0.125	0.338
ASP3_16	Efficient planning and sufficient distribution of bikes to low-income and minority communities	0.333	0.482
ASP3_17	Easy access to bike (easy booking, unlocking and payment system)	0.250	0.442
ASP3_18	Distribution of bike-sharing services to minority and low-income communities	0.292	0.464
ASP3_19	Inclusive spatial distribution of bikes and docking station	0.292	0.464
ASP3_20	Spatial distribution of bike-sharing and docking stations close to residential and low-income neighbourhood.	0.208	0.415
ASP3_21	Strategic location/ spatial distribution of bike docking stations	0.333	0.482
ASP3_22	A well-planned bicycle infrastructure that allows trip-chaining	0.208	0.415
ASP3_23	Availability of bikes with child seat, trailers and carriages for travelling with children and carrying luggage	0.167	0.381
ASP3_24	Public education and creating general awareness about the possibility of cycling with children and baggage	0.167	0.381
ASP3_25	Practical cycling lessons	0.208	0.415
ASP3_26	Comprehensive and attractive bicycle network (separate and safe cycle paths) that allows trip-chaining, and enables cycling with children	0.458	0.509
ASP3_27	Adequate bicycle infrastructure (docks and cycle facilities)	0.583	0.504
ASP3_28	Sheltered docking stations	0.083	0.282
ASP3_29	Attrrative changing facilities	0.292	0.464
ASP3_30	Improve cycling infrastructure	0.458	0.509
ASP3_31	Toilet facilities at the bike docking stations	0.042	0.204

The results (Table 53 and

Table 54) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Public awareness (ASP2_1)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - AS3_1 Creating public awareness about practical cycling (cycling with children and cargo) with $V = 0.78$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_2 Creating public awareness of cycling routes with $V = 0.78$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_3 Advertising bike sharing services and locations of docking stations with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_6 Availability of cash payment option with $V = 0.34$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
 - AS3_7 Entry cost (upfront cost) with $V = 0.44$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - AS3_9 Annual membership cost with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - AS3_11 Fear of liability resulting from overage fees, damages and theft of the bike with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.10$;
 - AS3_14 Availability and coverage of docking stations with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.12$;
 - AS3_26 Comprehensive and attractive bicycle network that allows trip-chaining, and enables cycling with children with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.12$;
 - AS3_28 Sheltered docking stations with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.12$;
 - AS3_29 Attractive changing facilities with $V = 0.51$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
- **Sign-up & booking (ASP2_2)** process has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - AS3_3 Advertising bike sharing services and locations of docking stations with $V = 0.29$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.17$;
 - AS3_4 Simple and flexible signing-up process with $V = 1$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_5 The requirement to sign-up for membership (credit/debit card, internet access and smart phone) with $V = 0.91$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_6 Availability of cash payment option (Availability cash membership) with $V = 0.75$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_7 Entry cost (upfront cost) with $V = 0.57$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_8 Rental charges for trips above one hour with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.1$;
 - AS3_9 Annual membership cost with $V = 0.64$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_10 Accessories cost (helmet, clothing etc.) with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - AS3_11 Fear of liability resulting from overage fees, damages and theft of the bike with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - AS3_14 Availability and coverage of docking stations with $V = 0.54$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - AS3_16 Efficient planning and sufficient distribution of bikes to low-income and minority communities with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - AS3_20 Spatial distribution of bike-sharing and docking stations close to residential and low-income neighbourhood with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - AS3_24 Public education and creating general awareness about the possibility of cycling with children and baggage with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.10$;
 - AS3_29 Attractive changing facilities with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.14$.
- **Membership cost (ASP2_3)** process has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - AS3_3 Advertising bike sharing services and locations of docking stations with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
 - AS3_4 Simple and flexible signing-up process with $V = 0.57$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_5 The requirement to sign-up for membership (credit/debit card, internet access and smart phone) with $V = 0.48$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - AS3_6 Availability of cash payment option with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - AS3_7 Entry cost (upfront cost) with $V = 1$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_8 Rental charges for trips above one hour with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - AS3_9 Annual membership cost with $V = 0.92$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_10 Accessories cost (helmet, clothing etc.) with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - AS3_11 Fear of liability resulting from overage fees, damages and theft of the bike with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - AS3_14 Availability and coverage of docking stations with $V = 0.44$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - AS3_21 Strategic location/ spatial distribution of bike docking stations with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$;
 - AS3_25 Practical cycling lessons with $V = 0.4$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
 - AS3_29 Attractive changing facilities with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$.
- **Spontaneity of accessing bike/dock (ASP2_4)** process has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - AS3_4 Simple and flexible signing-up process with $V = 0.54$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - AS3_5 The requirement to sign-up for membership (credit/debit card, internet access and smart phone) with $V = 0.47$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;

- AS3_6 Availability of cash payment option with $V = 0.34$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
- AS3_7 Entry cost (upfront cost) with $V = 0.44$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
- AS3_9 Annual membership cost with $V = 0.54$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
- AS3_10 Accessories cost (helmet, clothing etc.) with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.1$;
- AS3_11 Fear of liability resulting from overage fees, damages and theft of the bike with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.1$;
- AS3_12 The availability of a shared bike and a vacant dock when required with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
- AS3_13 Reliability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
- AS3_14 Availability and coverage of docking stations with $V = 1$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- AS3_15 Coverage at major transport hubs with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.1$;
- AS3_16 Efficient planning and sufficient distribution of bikes to low-income and minority communities with $V = 0.65$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- AS3_17 Easy access to bike with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
- AS3_18 Distribution of bike-sharing services to minority and low-income communities with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
- AS3_19 Inclusive spatial distribution of bikes and docking station with $V = 0.59$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- AS3_20 Spatial distribution of bike-sharing and docking stations close to residential and low-income neighbourhood with $V = 0.47$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
- AS3_21 Strategic location/ spatial distribution of bike docking stations with $V = 0.47$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
- AS3_28 Sheltered docking stations with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.12$.
- **Proximity of docking station (ASP2_5)** process has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - AS3_7 Entry cost (upfront cost) with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - AS3_12 The availability of a shared bike and a vacant dock when required with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - AS3_13 Reliability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - AS3_14 Availability and coverage of docking stations with $V = 0.61$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_16 Efficient planning and sufficient distribution of bikes to low-income and minority communities with $V = 0.66$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_17 Easy access to bike with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - AS3_18 Distribution of bike-sharing services to minority and low-income communities with $V = 0.76$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_19 Inclusive spatial distribution of bikes and docking station with $V = 0.76$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_20 Spatial distribution of bike-sharing and docking stations close to residential and low-income neighbourhood with $V = 0.61$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_21 Strategic location/ spatial distribution of bike docking stations with $V = 0.84$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_22 A well-planned bicycle infrastructure that allows trip-chaining with $V = 0.4$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
 - AS3_27 Adequate bicycle infrastructure with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$.
- **Travelling with children/ Carrying (ASP2_6)** things process has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - AS3_10 Accessories cost with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - AS3_12 The availability of a shared bike and a vacant dock when required with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - AS3_13 Reliability of bike sharing services to meet mobility needs with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - AS3_21 Strategic location/ spatial distribution of bike docking stations with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.14$;
 - AS3_22 A well-planned bicycle infrastructure that allows trip-chaining with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - AS3_23 Availability of bikes with child seat, trailers and carriages for travelling with children and carrying luggage with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - AS3_24 Public education and creating general awareness about the possibility of cycling with children and baggage with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$;
 - AS3_25 Practical cycling lessons with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - AS3_26 Comprehensive and attractive bicycle network that allows trip-chaining, and enables cycling with children with $V = 0.65$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AS3_27 Adequate bicycle infrastructure with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$;
 - AS3_30 Improve cycling infrastructure with $V = 0.47$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - AS3_31 Toilet facilities at the bike docking stations with $V = 0.29$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$.

Table 53. Cramer's V for Use Case III - Accessibility and Spontaneity Literature Review

	AS2_1	AS2_2	AS2_3	AS2_4	AS2_5	AS2_6	AS2_7	AS3_1	AS3_2	AS3_3	AS3_4	AS3_5	AS3_6	AS3_7	AS3_8	AS3_9	AS3_10	AS3_11	AS3_12	AS3_13	AS3_14	AS3_15	AS3_16	AS3_17	AS3_18	AS3_19	AS3_20	AS3_21	AS3_22	AS3_23	AS3_24	AS3_25	AS3_26	AS3_27	AS3_28	AS3_29	AS3_30	AS3_31
AS2_1	1.00	0.19	0.44	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	<u>0.30</u>	0.27	0.78	0.78	0.71	0.19	0.12	<u>0.34</u>	0.44	0.19	<u>0.37</u>	0.09	<u>0.35</u>	0.19	0.04	<u>0.33</u>	0.16	0.06	0.14	0.04	0.04	0.15	0.12	0.15	0.26	0.26	0.06	<u>0.33</u>	0.27	<u>0.33</u>	0.51	0.16	0.19
AS2_2	0.19	1.00	0.57	0.54	0.04	0.18	0.19	0.22	0.22	0.29	1.00	0.91	0.75	0.57	<u>0.35</u>	0.64	0.49	0.49	0.12	0.12	0.54	0.23	<u>0.37</u>	0.15	0.26	0.26	0.45	0.00	0.24	0.12	<u>0.35</u>	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.23	<u>0.31</u>	0.02	0.16
AS2_3	0.44	0.57	1.00	0.44	<u>0.31</u>	0.12	0.19	<u>0.31</u>	0.49	0.39	0.57	0.48	0.49	1.00	0.53	0.92	0.45	0.45	0.08	0.15	0.44	0.06	0.12	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.19	<u>0.30</u>	0.02	0.08	0.08	0.40	0.10	0.14	0.25	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.18
AS2_4	<u>0.33</u>	0.54	0.44	1.00	0.61	0.12	0.06	0.10	0.27	<u>0.37</u>	0.54	0.47	<u>0.34</u>	0.44	0.19	0.54	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.41	0.41	1.00	<u>0.35</u>	0.65	0.53	0.41	0.59	0.47	0.47	0.27	0.26	0.04	0.15	0.16	0.10	<u>0.33</u>	0.15	0.16	0.23
AS2_5	0.10	0.04	<u>0.31</u>	0.61	1.00	0.24	0.40	0.03	0.14	0.22	0.04	0.12	0.10	<u>0.31</u>	0.08	0.22	0.06	0.06	<u>0.30</u>	0.53	0.61	0.19	0.66	0.49	0.76	0.76	0.61	0.84	0.40	0.08	0.08	0.19	0.10	<u>0.31</u>	0.25	0.02	0.27	0.18
AS2_6	<u>0.30</u>	0.18	0.12	0.12	0.24	1.00	0.07	0.12	0.12	0.00	0.18	0.25	0.20	0.12	0.08	0.18	0.53	0.27	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.32</u>	0.12	0.27	0.13	0.00	0.26	0.06	0.15	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.65	<u>0.30</u>	0.21	0.06	0.47	<u>0.29</u>
AS2_7	0.27	0.19	0.19	0.06	0.40	0.07	1.00	0.19	0.40	0.03	0.19	0.15	0.06	0.19	0.05	0.03	0.19	0.12	0.23	0.05	0.06	0.19	0.07	0.41	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.24	<u>0.29</u>	0.24	0.05	0.23	0.01	0.47	0.61	0.15	<u>0.33</u>	0.47	0.11
AS3_1	0.78	0.22	<u>0.31</u>	0.10	0.03	0.12	0.19	1.00	0.83	0.57	0.22	0.12	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.08	0.22	0.19	0.45	<u>0.30</u>	0.08	0.10	<u>0.32</u>	0.24	0.10	0.20	0.02	0.02	0.12	0.02	0.15	0.15	0.02	0.27	0.14	0.25	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.25
AS3_2	0.78	0.22	0.49	0.27	0.14	0.12	0.40	0.83	1.00	0.57	0.22	0.12	<u>0.29</u>	0.49	<u>0.30</u>	0.39	0.19	0.45	<u>0.30</u>	0.08	0.27	<u>0.32</u>	0.24	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.02	0.12	0.02	0.15	0.15	0.02	0.27	0.14	0.25	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.18
AS3_3	0.71	0.29	0.39	<u>0.37</u>	0.22	0.00	0.03	0.57	0.57	1.00	0.29	<u>0.37</u>	0.55	0.39	0.12	0.29	0.23	0.49	0.12	0.12	<u>0.37</u>	0.03	0.18	0.15	0.26	0.07	0.03	<u>0.37</u>	0.03	0.12	0.12	0.24	0.19	0.04	0.23	<u>0.31</u>	0.02	0.16
AS3_4	0.19	1.00	0.57	0.54	0.04	0.18	0.19	0.22	0.22	0.29	1.00	0.91	0.75	0.57	<u>0.35</u>	0.64	0.49	0.49	0.12	0.12	0.54	0.23	<u>0.37</u>	0.15	0.26	0.26	0.45	0.00	0.24	0.12	<u>0.35</u>	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.23	<u>0.31</u>	0.02	0.16
AS3_5	0.12	0.91	0.48	0.47	0.12	0.25	0.15	0.12	0.12	<u>0.37</u>	0.91	1.00	0.82	0.48	0.16	0.55	0.53	0.53	0.08	0.08	0.47	0.27	0.44	0.20	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.32</u>	0.51	0.06	<u>0.29</u>	0.08	0.40	0.07	0.12	0.12	0.21	0.26	0.12	0.15
AS3_6	<u>0.34</u>	0.75	0.49	<u>0.34</u>	0.10	0.20	0.06	<u>0.29</u>	<u>0.29</u>	0.55	0.75	0.82	1.00	0.49	0.26	0.55	<u>0.36</u>	0.65	0.00	0.00	<u>0.34</u>	0.07	0.20	<u>0.33</u>	0.05	0.05	0.18	0.00	0.18	0.00	0.26	0.18	0.14	0.10	0.17	0.37	0.14	0.12
AS3_7	0.44	0.57	1.00	0.44	<u>0.31</u>	0.12	0.19	<u>0.31</u>	0.49	0.39	0.57	0.48	0.49	1.00	0.53	0.92	0.45	0.45	0.08	0.15	0.44	0.06	0.12	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.19	<u>0.30</u>	0.02	0.08	0.08	0.40	0.10	0.14	0.25	<u>0.36</u>	0.27	0.18
AS3_8	0.19	<u>0.35</u>	0.53	0.19	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.08	<u>0.30</u>	0.12	<u>0.35</u>	0.16	0.26	0.53	1.00	0.58	0.17	0.17	0.40	0.10	0.19	0.17	0.08	0.26	0.04	0.20	0.05	0.08	0.05	0.10	0.40	<u>0.32</u>	0.26	0.08	0.13	0.29	0.04	0.09
AS3_9	<u>0.37</u>	0.64	0.92	0.54	0.22	0.18	0.03	0.22	0.39	0.29	0.64	0.55	0.55	0.92	0.58	1.00	0.49	0.49	0.12	0.12	0.54	0.03	0.18	0.15	0.07	0.26	0.24	0.18	0.03	0.12	0.12	0.24	0.02	0.04	0.23	<u>0.31</u>	0.19	0.16
AS3_10	0.09	0.49	0.45	<u>0.35</u>	0.06	0.53	0.19	0.19	0.19	0.23	0.49	0.53	<u>0.36</u>	0.45	0.17	0.49	1.00	0.62	0.17	0.17	<u>0.35</u>	0.24	0.00	0.22	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.00	0.19	0.17	0.17	0.19	<u>0.35</u>	0.06	0.11	0.03	<u>0.35</u>	0.08
AS3_11	<u>0.35</u>	0.49	0.45	<u>0.35</u>	0.06	0.27	0.12	0.45	0.45	0.49	0.49	0.53	0.65	0.45	0.17	0.49	0.62	1.00	0.17	0.17	<u>0.35</u>	0.14	0.00	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.00	0.12	0.17	0.17	0.19	<u>0.35</u>	0.06	0.11	0.24	<u>0.35</u>	0.08
AS3_12	0.19	0.12	0.08	0.41	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.32</u>	0.23	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.00	0.08	0.40	0.12	0.17	0.17	1.00	0.70	0.41	0.17	0.16	0.26	0.20	0.20	0.05	0.40	0.05	0.10	0.10	0.05	0.26	0.15	0.13	0.20	0.04	0.09
AS3_13	0.04	0.12	0.15	0.41	0.53	<u>0.32</u>	0.05	0.08	0.08	0.12	0.12	0.08	0.00	0.15	0.10	0.12	0.17	0.17	0.70	1.00	0.41	0.17	0.40	0.52	0.45	0.45	<u>0.32</u>	0.63	<u>0.32</u>	0.10	0.10	0.05	0.04	0.08	0.13	0.20	0.19	0.09
AS3_14	<u>0.33</u>	0.54	0.44	1.00	0.61	0.12	0.06	0.10	0.27	<u>0.37</u>	0.54	0.47	<u>0.34</u>	0.44	0.19	0.54	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.41	0.41	1.00	<u>0.35</u>	0.65	0.53	0.41	0.59	0.47	0.47	0.27	0.26	0.04	0.15	0.16	0.10	<u>0.33</u>	0.15	0.16	0.23
AS3_15	0.16	0.23	0.06	<u>0.35</u>	0.19	0.27	0.19	<u>0.32</u>	<u>0.32</u>	0.03	0.23	0.27	0.07	0.06	0.17	0.03	0.24	0.14	0.17	0.17	<u>0.35</u>	1.00	0.53	<u>0.36</u>	0.03	0.03	0.12	0.27	0.19	0.17	0.17	0.19	0.09	0.19	0.11	<u>0.31</u>	0.09	0.08
AS3_16	0.06	<u>0.37</u>	0.12	0.65	0.66	0.13	0.07	0.24	0.24	0.18	<u>0.37</u>	0.44	0.20	0.12	0.08	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.16	0.40	0.65	0.53	1.00	0.61	0.52	0.52	0.73	0.63	<u>0.29</u>	0.08	0.16	0.07	0.06	0.12	0.21	0.06	0.06	0.15
AS3_17	0.14	0.15	0.10	0.53	0.49	0.00	0.41	0.10	0.10	0.15	0.15	0.20	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.26	0.15	0.22	0.07	0.26	0.52	0.53	<u>0.36</u>	0.61	1.00	0.26	0.48	0.41	0.41	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.06	0.14	<u>0.29</u>	0.17	0.16	0.14	0.12
AS3_18	0.04	0.26	0.20	0.41	0.76	0.26	<u>0.35</u>	0.20	0.20	0.26	0.26	<u>0.32</u>	0.05	0.20	0.20	0.26	0.03	0.03	0.20	0.45	0.59	0.03	0.52	0.48	0.80	1.00	0.80	0.52	0.57	0.29	0.20	0.10	0.22	0.39	0.19	0.01	0.22	0.13
AS3_19	0.04	0.26	0.20	0.59	0.76	0.06	<u>0.35</u>	0.02	0.20	0.07	0.26	<u>0.32</u>	0.05	0.20	0.20	0.26	0.03	0.03	0.20	0.45	0.59	0.03	0.52	0.48	0.80	1.00	0.80	0.52	0.57	0.29	0.20	0.10	0.22	0.39	0.19	0.01	0.22	0.13
AS3_20	0.15	0.45	0.19	0.47	0.61	0.15	0.24	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.45	0.51	0.18	0.19	0.05	0.24	0.12	0.12	0.05	<u>0.32</u>	0.47	0.12	0.73	0.41	0.80	0.80	1.00	0.51	0.49	0.23	<u>0.32</u>	0.01	0.06	0.19	0.15	0.10	0.06	0.11
AS3_21	0.12	0.00	<u>0.30</u>	0.47	0.84	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	0.12	<u>0.37</u>	0.00	0.06	0.00	<u>0.30</u>	0.08	0.18	0.00	0.00	0.40	0.63	0.47	0.27	0.63	0.41	0.71	0.52	0.51	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	0.16	0.08	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	<u>0.30</u>	0.21	0.13	<u>0.30</u>	0.15
AS3_22	0.15	0.24	0.02	0.27	0.40	<u>0.36</u>	0.24	0.02	0																													

AS3_2 1	0.58	1.00	<u>0.16</u>	0.02	<0.01	<u>0.14</u>	<u>0.17</u>	0.58	0.58	0.08	1.00	0.77	1.00	<u>0.16</u>	0.71	0.39	1.00	1.00	0.06	<0.01	0.02	0.21	<0.01	0.05	<0.01	0.01	0.01	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.46	0.71	<u>0.17</u>	0.58	<u>0.16</u>	0.32	0.55	<u>0.16</u>	0.49
AS3_2 2	0.50	0.26	0.94	0.21	0.05	0.08	0.25	0.94	0.94	0.90	0.26	<u>0.17</u>	0.41	0.94	0.83	0.90	0.36	0.59	0.83	<u>0.13</u>	0.21	0.36	<u>0.17</u>	0.41	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.17</u>	<0.01	0.83	<u>0.13</u>	0.96	0.78	0.05	0.47	0.63	0.21	0.62
AS3_2 3	0.22	0.59	0.73	0.22	0.73	<u>0.13</u>	0.83	0.48	0.48	0.59	0.59	0.71	1.00	0.73	0.64	0.59	0.43	0.43	0.64	0.64	0.22	0.43	0.71	1.00	0.85	<u>0.17</u>	0.28	0.46	0.83	<0.01	0.05	<0.01	0.86	0.73	0.53	0.34	0.38	0.66
AS3_2 4	0.22	0.10	0.73	0.86	0.73	<u>0.13</u>	0.28	0.48	0.48	0.59	0.10	0.06	0.22	0.73	0.05	0.59	0.43	0.43	0.64	0.64	0.86	0.43	0.46	1.00	0.34	0.34	<u>0.13</u>	0.71	<u>0.13</u>	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.48	0.53	0.85	0.22	0.66
AS3_2 5	0.78	0.90	0.05	0.50	0.37	0.08	0.96	0.94	0.94	0.26	0.90	0.74	0.41	0.05	<u>0.13</u>	0.26	0.36	0.36	0.83	0.83	0.50	0.36	0.74	0.78	0.57	0.63	0.96	<u>0.17</u>	0.96	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.50	0.94	0.47	0.63	0.50	0.62
AS3_2 6	<u>0.12</u>	0.92	0.65	0.45	0.65	<0.01	0.02	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.20</u>	0.36	0.92	0.58	0.50	0.65	0.22	0.92	0.10	0.10	0.22	0.86	0.45	0.66	0.78	0.50	0.30	0.30	0.78	0.58	0.78	0.86	0.22	0.50	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.86	<0.01	0.37
AS3_2 7	<u>0.20</u>	0.84	0.51	0.65	<u>0.13</u>	<u>0.16</u>	<0.01	0.51	0.51	0.84	0.84	0.58	0.65	0.51	0.73	0.84	0.77	0.77	0.48	0.73	0.65	0.37	0.58	<u>0.17</u>	0.06	0.06	0.37	<u>0.16</u>	0.05	0.73	0.48	0.94	<0.01	<0.01	0.23	0.43	<0.01	0.25
AS3_2 8	<u>0.12</u>	0.27	0.23	<u>0.12</u>	0.23	0.32	0.47	0.23	0.23	0.27	0.27	0.32	0.42	0.23	0.53	0.27	0.60	0.60	0.53	0.53	<u>0.12</u>	0.60	0.32	0.42	0.37	0.37	0.47	0.32	0.47	0.53	0.53	0.47	<u>0.12</u>	0.23	<0.01	0.02	<u>0.12</u>	0.77
AS3_2 9	0.01	<u>0.14</u>	0.09	0.50	0.94	0.76	<u>0.12</u>	0.09	0.09	<u>0.14</u>	<u>0.14</u>	0.22	0.07	0.09	<u>0.17</u>	<u>0.14</u>	0.87	0.25	0.34	0.34	0.50	<u>0.14</u>	0.76	0.46	0.97	0.97	0.63	0.55	0.63	0.34	0.85	0.63	0.86	0.43	0.02	<0.01	0.86	0.53
AS3_3 0	0.45	0.92	<u>0.20</u>	0.45	<u>0.20</u>	0.02	0.02	<u>0.20</u>	<u>0.20</u>	0.92	0.92	0.58	0.50	<u>0.20</u>	0.86	0.36	0.10	0.10	0.86	0.38	0.45	0.66	0.78	0.50	0.30	0.30	0.78	<u>0.16</u>	0.21	0.38	0.22	0.50	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.86	<0.01	0.37
AS3_3 1	0.37	0.45	0.41	0.29	0.41	<u>0.16</u>	0.62	0.25	0.41	0.45	0.45	0.49	0.58	0.41	0.66	0.45	0.71	0.71	0.66	0.66	0.29	0.71	0.49	0.58	0.53	0.53	0.62	0.49	0.62	0.66	0.66	0.62	0.37	0.25	0.77	0.53	0.37	<0.01

- **Insufficient Infrastructure (ASP2_7)** process has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - AS3_2 Creating public awareness of cycling routes with V =0.4 and p-value=0.05;
 - AS3_17 Easy access to bike with V =0.41 and p-value=0.04;
 - AS3_18 Distribution of bike-sharing services to minority and low-income communities with V =0.35 and p-value=0.1;
 - AS3_19 Inclusive spatial distribution of bikes and docking station with V =0.35 and p-value=0.1;
 - AS3_21 Strategic location/ spatial distribution of bike docking stations with V =0.29 and p-value=0.17;
 - AS3_26 Comprehensive and attractive bicycle network that allows trip-chaining, and enables cycling with children with V =0.47 and p-value=0.02;
 - AS3_27 Adequate bicycle infrastructure with V =0.61 and p-value<0.01;
 - AS3_29 Attractive changing facilities with V =0.33 and p-value=0.12;
 - AS3_30 Improve cycling infrastructure with V =0.47 and p-value=0.02.

The Safety & Security (S&S1_1) includes 5 factor of second level and 25 factors of third level (Table 67).

Table 55. Descriptive statistics for Use Case III - Safety & Security

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
S&S1_1	Safety & Security	0.875	0.338
S&S2_1	Driver behaviour	0.500	0.511
S&S2_2	Separate Infrastructure	0.750	0.442
S&S2_3	Confidence/ experience	0.542	0.509
S&S2_4	Harassment	0.375	0.495
S&S2_5	Safe environment & personal safety	0.542	0.509
S&S3_1	Traffic safety	0.833	0.381
S&S3_2	Improved cycle infrastructure	0.250	0.442
S&S3_3	Educating drivers on the right of the cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring safety on the road	0.292	0.464
S&S3_4	Physical separation of bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic	0.500	0.511
S&S3_5	Separate cyclist from vehicular traffic	0.750	0.442
S&S3_6	Segregated cycle routes	0.583	0.504
S&S3_7	Physically separated bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic	0.500	0.511
S&S3_8	Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes	0.250	0.442
S&S3_9	Lessons on cycling to boost confidence	0.333	0.482
S&S3_10	Visibility of the cycle paths and stations	0.167	0.381
S&S3_11	Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers)	0.208	0.415
S&S3_12	Public awareness campaigns	0.333	0.482
S&S3_13	Presence of CCTV systems	0.042	0.204
S&S3_14	Visibility and adequate lighting on cycle paths and lanes	0.292	0.464
S&S3_15	Presence of CCTV systems to improve user perception of security	0.250	0.442
S&S3_16	Presence of security devices	0.250	0.442
S&S3_17	The visibility of the cyclist to other road users	0.208	0.415
S&S3_18	Roadworthiness of the shared bikes (well-functioning bikes and lights on bikes)	0.083	0.282
S&S3_19	Set up information point at bike sharing and docking stations to provide cyclists personal safety tips.	0.000	0.000
S&S3_20	Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes	0.417	0.504
S&S3_21	Dedicated and mandatory cycle lanes on roads	0.708	0.464
S&S3_22	Physically separated cycle paths from vehicular traffic	0.750	0.442
S&S3_23	Safe cycling paths for cycling with children	0.208	0.415
S&S3_24	Educating drivers and cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road	0.417	0.504
S&S3_25	Safety of the environment around the cyclist to prevent accident	0.500	0.511

The results (Table 56 and Table 57) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Driver behaviour (S&S2_1)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S&S3_1 Traffic safety with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - S&S3_2 Improved cycle infrastructure with $V = 0.58$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_3 Educating drivers on the right of the cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.64$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_4 Physical separation of bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 1$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_5 Separate cyclist from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.58$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_6 Segregated cycle routes with $V = 0.68$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_7 Physically separated bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.67$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_8 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes with $V = 0.38$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
 - S&S3_9 Lessons on cycling to boost confidence with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$;
 - S&S3_10 Visibility of the cycle paths and stations with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - S&S3_11 Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) with $V = 0.51$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S&S3_12 Public awareness campaigns with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_14 Visibility and adequate lighting on cycle paths and lanes with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.19$;
 - S&S3_18 Roadworthiness of the shared bikes (well-functioning bikes and lights on bikes) with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$;
 - S&S3_20 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes with $V = 0.34$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
 - S&S3_21 Dedicated and mandatory cycle lanes on roads with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S&S3_22 Physically separated cycle paths from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.38$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
 - S&S3_24 Educating drivers and cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.51$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$.
- **Separate Infrastructure (S&S2_2)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S&S3_1 Traffic safety with $V = 0.52$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S&S3_2 Improved cycle infrastructure with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
 - S&S3_3 Educating drivers on the right of the cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$;
 - S&S3_4 Physical separation of bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.58$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_5 Separate cyclist from vehicular traffic with $V = 1$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_6 Segregated cycle routes with $V = 0.68$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_7 Physically separated bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.58$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_8 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
 - S&S3_11 Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$;
 - S&S3_12 Public awareness campaigns with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
 - S&S3_14 Visibility and adequate lighting on cycle paths and lanes with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$;
 - S&S3_15 Presence of CCTV systems to improve user perception of security with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
 - S&S3_16 Presence of security devices with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
 - S&S3_17 The visibility of the cyclist to other road users with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$;
 - S&S3_20 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S&S3_21 Dedicated and mandatory cycle lanes on roads with $V = 0.48$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S&S3_22 Physically separated cycle paths from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
 - S&S3_24 Educating drivers and cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$.
- **Confidence/ experience (S&S2_3)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S&S3_3 Educating drivers on the right of the cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.59$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_4 Physical separation of bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.59$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_5 Separate cyclist from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.43$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - S&S3_6 Segregated cycle routes with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
 - S&S3_7 Physically separated bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.92$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_8 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S&S3_9 Lessons on cycling to boost confidence with $V = 0.65$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_10 Visibility of the cycle paths and stations with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
 - S&S3_11 Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) with $V = 0.47$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S&S3_12 Public awareness campaigns with $V = 0.65$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;

- S&S3_18 Roadworthiness of the shared bikes (well-functioning bikes and lights on bikes) with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.19$;
- S&S3_22 Physically separated cycle paths from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.43$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
- S&S3_24 Educating drivers and cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.44$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$.
- **Harassment (S&S2_4)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S&S3_1 Traffic safety with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.1$;
 - S&S3_2 Improved cycle infrastructure with $V = 0.55$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S&S3_3 Educating drivers on the right of the cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.83$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_4 Physical separation of bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.77$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_5 Separate cyclist from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - S&S3_6 Segregated cycle routes with $V = 0.65$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_7 Physically separated bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.77$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_8 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.1$;
 - S&S3_9 Lessons on cycling to boost confidence with $V = 0.55$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S&S3_10 Visibility of the cycle paths and stations with $V = 0.58$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_11 Gender sensitive training for other road users (drivers) with $V = 0.66$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_12 Public awareness campaigns with $V = 0.91$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_18 Roadworthiness of the shared bikes with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
 - S&S3_21 Dedicated and mandatory cycle lanes on roads with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.14$;
 - S&S3_24 Educating drivers and cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$.
- **Safe environment & personal safety (S&S2_5)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - S&S3_1 Traffic safety with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S&S3_3 Educating drivers on the right of the cyclist and their responsibility of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
 - S&S3_4 Physical separation of bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$;
 - S&S3_5 Separate cyclist from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.63$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_6 Segregated cycle routes with $V = 0.58$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_7 Physically separated bike paths or lanes from vehicular traffic with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$;
 - S&S3_8 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S&S3_10 Visibility of the cycle paths and stations with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
 - S&S3_14 Visibility and adequate lighting on cycle paths and lanes with $V = 0.59$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_15 Presence of CCTV systems to improve user perception of security with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S&S3_16 Presence of security devices with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - S&S3_17 The visibility of the cyclist to other road users with $V = 0.47$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - S&S3_18 Roadworthiness of the shared bikes with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.19$;
 - S&S3_20 Lowering traffic speeds on roads with on-road cycle lanes with $V = 0.78$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_21 Dedicated and mandatory cycle lanes on roads with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.12$;
 - S&S3_24 Educating drivers and cyclist on their responsibilities of ensuring safety on the road with $V = 0.61$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - S&S3_25 Safety of the environment around the cyclist to prevent accident with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$.

Table 56. p-value of χ^2 for Use Case III - Safety/security Literature Review

	S&S2_1	S&S2_2	S&S2_3	S&S2_4	S&S2_5	S&S3_1	S&S3_2	S&S3_3	S&S3_4	S&S3_5	S&S3_6	S&S3_7	S&S3_8	S&S3_9	S&S3_10	S&S3_11	S&S3_12	S&S3_13	S&S3_14	S&S3_15	S&S3_16	S&S3_17	S&S3_18	S&S3_20	S&S3_21	S&S3_22	S&S3_23	S&S3_24	S&S3_25
S&S2_1	1.00	0.58	0.59	0.77	0.42	0.45	0.58	0.64	1.00	0.58	0.68	0.67	0.38	0.35	0.45	0.51	0.71	0.21	0.28	0.19	0.19	0.10	0.30	0.34	0.46	0.38	0.10	0.51	0.17
S&S2_2	0.58	1.00	0.43	0.45	0.63	0.52	0.33	0.37	0.58	1.00	0.68	0.58	0.33	0.20	0.26	0.30	0.41	0.12	0.37	0.33	0.33	0.30	0.17	0.49	0.48	0.33	0.06	0.49	0.19
S&S2_3	0.59	0.43	1.00	0.71	0.33	0.49	0.34	0.59	0.59	0.43	0.41	0.92	0.53	0.65	0.41	0.47	0.65	0.19	0.22	0.14	0.14	0.06	0.28	0.10	0.15	0.43	0.27	0.44	0.08
S&S2_4	0.77	0.45	0.71	1.00	0.19	0.35	0.55	0.83	0.77	0.45	0.65	0.77	0.35	0.55	0.58	0.66	0.91	0.27	0.26	0.15	0.15	0.19	0.39	0.04	0.31	0.25	0.03	0.39	0.09
S&S2_5	0.42	0.63	0.33	0.19	1.00	0.49	0.05	0.41	0.42	0.63	0.58	0.42	0.53	0.12	0.41	0.27	0.12	0.19	0.59	0.53	0.53	0.47	0.28	0.78	0.33	0.24	0.27	0.61	0.42
S&S3_1	0.45	0.52	0.49	0.35	0.49	1.00	0.26	0.29	0.45	0.52	0.53	0.45	0.26	0.32	0.20	0.23	0.32	0.09	0.29	0.26	0.26	0.23	0.13	0.38	0.70	0.77	0.23	0.38	0.45
S&S3_2	0.58	0.33	0.34	0.55	0.05	0.26	1.00	0.26	0.58	0.33	0.49	0.38	0.33	0.20	0.00	0.41	0.61	0.36	0.05	0.11	0.11	0.18	0.17	0.10	0.16	0.11	0.06	0.10	0.00
S&S3_3	0.64	0.37	0.59	0.83	0.41	0.29	0.26	1.00	0.64	0.37	0.54	0.64	0.48	0.32	0.70	0.80	0.71	0.32	0.39	0.26	0.26	0.10	0.47	0.20	0.21	0.16	0.12	0.57	0.09
S&S3_4	1.00	0.58	0.59	0.77	0.42	0.45	0.58	0.64	1.00	0.58	0.68	0.67	0.38	0.35	0.45	0.51	0.71	0.21	0.28	0.19	0.19	0.10	0.30	0.34	0.46	0.38	0.10	0.51	0.17
S&S3_5	0.58	1.00	0.43	0.45	0.63	0.52	0.33	0.37	0.58	1.00	0.68	0.58	0.33	0.20	0.26	0.30	0.41	0.12	0.37	0.33	0.33	0.30	0.17	0.49	0.48	0.33	0.06	0.49	0.19
S&S3_6	0.68	0.68	0.41	0.65	0.58	0.53	0.49	0.54	0.68	0.68	1.00	0.51	0.29	0.42	0.38	0.43	0.60	0.18	0.54	0.49	0.49	0.23	0.25	0.54	0.57	0.29	0.02	0.54	0.51
S&S3_7	0.67	0.58	0.92	0.77	0.42	0.45	0.38	0.64	0.67	0.58	0.51	1.00	0.58	0.53	0.45	0.51	0.71	0.21	0.28	0.19	0.19	0.10	0.30	0.17	0.28	0.38	0.31	0.51	0.00
S&S3_8	0.38	0.33	0.53	0.35	0.53	0.26	0.33	0.48	0.38	0.33	0.29	0.58	1.00	0.41	0.52	0.18	0.20	0.12	0.48	0.33	0.33	0.06	0.52	0.29	0.37	0.33	0.18	0.49	0.19
S&S3_9	0.35	0.20	0.65	0.55	0.12	0.32	0.20	0.32	0.35	0.20	0.42	0.53	0.41	1.00	0.63	0.07	0.63	0.29	0.52	0.41	0.41	0.07	0.43	0.06	0.26	0.41	0.07	0.12	0.18
S&S3_10	0.45	0.26	0.41	0.58	0.41	0.20	0.00	0.70	0.45	0.26	0.38	0.45	0.52	0.63	1.00	0.32	0.63	0.47	0.70	0.52	0.52	0.05	0.67	0.08	0.29	0.26	0.05	0.30	0.22
S&S3_11	0.51	0.30	0.47	0.66	0.27	0.23	0.41	0.80	0.51	0.30	0.43	0.51	0.18	0.07	0.32	1.00	0.51	0.41	0.12	0.06	0.06	0.01	0.15	0.40	0.10	0.06	0.24	0.40	0.10
S&S3_12	0.71	0.41	0.65	0.91	0.12	0.32	0.61	0.71	0.71	0.41	0.60	0.71	0.20	0.63	0.63	0.51	1.00	0.29	0.32	0.20	0.20	0.15	0.43	0.06	0.26	0.20	0.15	0.30	0.00
S&S3_13	0.21	0.12	0.19	0.27	0.19	0.09	0.36	0.32	0.21	0.12	0.18	0.21	0.12	0.29	0.47	0.41	0.29	1.00	0.32	0.36	0.36	0.41	0.06	0.25	0.13	0.12	0.41	0.25	0.21
S&S3_14	0.28	0.37	0.22	0.26	0.59	0.29	0.05	0.39	0.28	0.37	0.54	0.28	0.48	0.52	0.70	0.12	0.32	0.32	1.00	0.90	0.90	0.57	0.47	0.39	0.41	0.16	0.12	0.39	0.46
S&S3_15	0.19	0.33	0.14	0.15	0.53	0.26	0.11	0.26	0.19	0.33	0.49	0.19	0.33	0.41	0.52	0.06	0.20	0.36	0.90	1.00	1.00	0.65	0.52	0.29	0.37	0.11	0.18	0.49	0.58
S&S3_16	0.19	0.33	0.14	0.15	0.53	0.26	0.11	0.26	0.19	0.33	0.49	0.19	0.33	0.41	0.52	0.06	0.20	0.36	0.90	1.00	1.00	0.65	0.52	0.29	0.37	0.11	0.18	0.49	0.58
S&S3_17	0.10	0.30	0.06	0.19	0.47	0.23	0.18	0.10	0.10	0.30	0.23	0.10	0.06	0.07	0.05	0.01	0.15	0.41	0.57	0.65	0.65	1.00	0.15	0.40	0.10	0.06	0.49	0.19	0.31
S&S3_18	0.30	0.17	0.28	0.39	0.28	0.13	0.17	0.47	0.30	0.17	0.25	0.30	0.52	0.43	0.67	0.15	0.43	0.06	0.47	0.52	0.52	0.15	1.00	0.25	0.19	0.17	0.15	0.36	0.30
S&S3_20	0.34	0.49	0.10	0.04	0.78	0.38	0.10	0.20	0.34	0.49	0.54	0.17	0.29	0.06	0.08	0.40	0.06	0.25	0.39	0.29	0.29	0.40	0.25	1.00	0.36	0.10	0.19	0.49	0.34
S&S3_21	0.46	0.48	0.15	0.31	0.33	0.70	0.16	0.21	0.46	0.48	0.57	0.28	0.37	0.26	0.29	0.10	0.26	0.13	0.41	0.37	0.37	0.10	0.19	0.36	1.00	0.69	0.10	0.36	0.64
S&S3_22	0.38	0.33	0.43	0.25	0.24	0.77	0.11	0.16	0.38	0.33	0.29	0.38	0.33	0.41	0.26	0.06	0.20	0.12	0.16	0.11	0.11	0.06	0.17	0.10	0.69	1.00	0.30	0.10	0.38
S&S3_23	0.10	0.06	0.27	0.03	0.27	0.23	0.06	0.12	0.10	0.06	0.02	0.31	0.18	0.07	0.05	0.24	0.15	0.41	0.12	0.18	0.18	0.49	0.15	0.19	0.10	0.30	1.00	0.19	0.31
S&S3_24	0.51	0.49	0.44	0.39	0.61	0.38	0.10	0.57	0.51	0.49	0.54	0.51	0.49	0.12	0.30	0.40	0.30	0.25	0.39	0.49	0.49	0.19	0.36	0.49	0.36	0.10	0.19	1.00	0.34
S&S3_25	0.17	0.19	0.08	0.09	0.42	0.45	0.00	0.09	0.17	0.19	0.51	0.00	0.19	0.18	0.22	0.10	0.00	0.21	0.46	0.58	0.58	0.31	0.30	0.34	0.64	0.38	0.31	0.34	1.00

Table 57. Cramer's V for Use Case III - Safety/security Literature Review

	S&S2_1	S&S2_2	S&S2_3	S&S2_4	S&S2_5	S&S3_1	S&S3_2	S&S3_3	S&S3_4	S&S3_5	S&S3_6	S&S3_7	S&S3_8	S&S3_9	S&S3_10	S&S3_11	S&S3_12	S&S3_13	S&S3_14	S&S3_15	S&S3_16	S&S3_17	S&S3_18	S&S3_20	S&S3_21	S&S3_22	S&S3_23	S&S3_24	S&S3_25
S&S2_1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.04	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.06	0.09	0.03	0.01	<0.01	0.33	<u>0.19</u>	0.37	0.37	0.63	<u>0.15</u>	<u>0.11</u>	0.02	0.06	0.63	0.01	0.44
S&S2_2	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.11</u>	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.11</u>	0.34	0.22	<u>0.16</u>	0.05	0.58	0.07	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.16</u>	0.42	0.02	0.02	<u>0.11</u>	0.78	0.02	0.37
S&S2_3	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.02	<u>0.11</u>	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.05	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.05	0.02	<0.01	0.37	0.30	0.50	0.50	0.78	<u>0.19</u>	0.65	0.50	0.03	0.21	0.03	0.70
S&S2_4	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.36	0.10	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.10	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.20</u>	0.22	0.49	0.49	0.39	0.06	0.84	<u>0.14</u>	0.24	0.90	0.06	0.69
S&S2_5	0.04	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.36	<0.01	0.02	0.82	0.05	0.04	<0.01	<0.01	0.04	0.01	0.58	0.05	0.21	0.58	0.37	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	<u>0.19</u>	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.26	0.21	<0.01	0.04
S&S3_1	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.10	0.02	<0.01	0.22	<u>0.17</u>	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.22	<u>0.13</u>	0.35	0.28	<u>0.13</u>	0.66	<u>0.17</u>	0.22	0.22	0.28	0.53	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	0.28	0.07	0.03
S&S3_2	<0.01	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.11</u>	0.01	0.82	0.22	<0.01	0.21	<0.01	<u>0.11</u>	0.02	0.06	<u>0.11</u>	0.34	1.00	0.04	<0.01	0.08	0.81	0.61	0.61	0.41	0.42	0.65	0.46	0.61	0.78	0.65	1.00
S&S3_3	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	<u>0.17</u>	0.21	<0.01	<0.01	0.07	0.01	<0.01	0.02	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.06	0.21	0.21	0.63	0.02	0.35	0.32	0.46	0.57	<0.01	0.67
S&S3_4	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.04	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.06	0.09	0.03	0.01	<0.01	0.33	<u>0.19</u>	0.37	0.37	0.63	<u>0.15</u>	<u>0.11</u>	0.02	0.06	0.63	0.01	0.44
S&S3_5	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.11</u>	0.07	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.11</u>	0.34	0.22	<u>0.16</u>	0.05	0.58	0.07	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.16</u>	0.42	0.02	0.02	<u>0.11</u>	0.78	0.02	0.37
S&S3_6	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.04	0.07	0.03	<0.01	0.41	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.29	0.23	0.01	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.94	0.01	0.01
S&S3_7	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.04	0.03	0.06	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.03	0.01	<0.01	0.33	<u>0.19</u>	0.37	0.37	0.63	<u>0.15</u>	0.43	<u>0.19</u>	0.06	<u>0.14</u>	0.01	1.00
S&S3_8	0.06	<u>0.11</u>	0.01	0.10	0.01	0.22	<u>0.11</u>	0.02	0.06	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.17</u>	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	0.01	0.41	0.34	0.58	0.02	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.11</u>	0.78	0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.07	<u>0.11</u>	0.41	0.02	0.37
S&S3_9	0.09	0.34	<0.01	0.01	0.58	<u>0.13</u>	0.34	<u>0.12</u>	0.09	0.34	0.04	0.01	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.74	<0.01	<u>0.16</u>	0.01	0.05	0.05	0.74	0.04	0.78	0.22	0.05	0.74	0.58	0.41
S&S3_10	0.03	0.22	0.05	<0.01	0.05	0.35	1.00	<0.01	0.03	0.22	0.07	0.03	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.01	0.01	0.83	<0.01	0.73	<u>0.17</u>	0.22	0.83	<u>0.15</u>	0.29
S&S3_11	0.01	<u>0.16</u>	0.02	<0.01	0.21	0.28	0.04	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.16</u>	0.03	0.01	0.41	0.74	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	0.01	0.05	0.57	0.78	0.78	0.96	0.47	0.05	0.63	0.78	0.25	0.05	0.63
S&S3_12	<0.01	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.58	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.34	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.34	0.34	0.50	0.04	0.78	0.22	0.34	0.50	<u>0.16</u>	1.00
S&S3_13	0.33	0.58	0.37	<u>0.20</u>	0.37	0.66	0.08	<u>0.12</u>	0.33	0.58	0.41	0.33	0.58	<u>0.16</u>	0.02	0.05	<u>0.16</u>	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.08	0.08	0.05	0.77	0.25	0.53	0.58	0.05	0.25	0.33
S&S3_14	<u>0.19</u>	0.07	0.30	0.22	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.81	0.06	<u>0.19</u>	0.07	0.01	<u>0.19</u>	0.02	0.01	<0.01	0.57	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	0.06	0.05	0.46	0.57	0.06	0.02
S&S3_15	0.37	<u>0.11</u>	0.50	0.49	0.01	0.22	0.61	0.21	0.37	<u>0.11</u>	0.02	0.37	<u>0.11</u>	0.05	0.01	0.78	0.34	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.07	0.61	0.41	0.02	<0.01
S&S3_16	0.37	<u>0.11</u>	0.50	0.49	0.01	0.22	0.61	0.21	0.37	<u>0.11</u>	0.02	0.37	<u>0.11</u>	0.05	0.01	0.78	0.34	0.08	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.07	0.61	0.41	0.02	<0.01
S&S3_17	0.63	<u>0.16</u>	0.78	0.39	0.02	0.28	0.41	0.63	0.63	<u>0.16</u>	0.29	0.63	0.78	0.74	0.83	0.96	0.50	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.47	0.05	0.63	0.78	0.01	0.37	<u>0.14</u>
S&S3_18	<u>0.15</u>	0.42	<u>0.19</u>	0.06	<u>0.19</u>	0.53	0.42	0.02	<u>0.15</u>	0.42	0.23	<u>0.15</u>	0.01	0.04	<0.01	0.47	0.04	0.77	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.47	<0.01	0.23	0.37	0.42	0.47	0.09	<u>0.15</u>
S&S3_20	<u>0.11</u>	0.02	0.65	0.84	<0.01	0.07	0.65	0.35	<u>0.11</u>	0.02	0.01	0.43	<u>0.17</u>	0.78	0.73	0.05	0.78	0.25	0.06	<u>0.17</u>	<u>0.17</u>	0.05	0.23	<0.01	0.09	0.65	0.37	0.02	<u>0.11</u>
S&S3_21	0.02	0.02	0.50	<u>0.14</u>	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.46	0.32	0.02	0.02	<0.01	<u>0.19</u>	0.07	0.22	<u>0.17</u>	0.63	0.22	0.53	0.05	0.07	0.07	0.63	0.37	0.09	<0.01	<0.01	0.63	0.09	<0.01
S&S3_22	0.06	<u>0.11</u>	0.03	0.24	0.26	<0.01	0.61	0.46	0.06	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.17</u>	0.06	<u>0.11</u>	0.05	0.22	0.78	0.34	0.58	0.46	0.61	0.61	0.78	0.42	0.65	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.16</u>	0.65	0.06
S&S3_23	0.63	0.78	0.21	0.90	0.21	0.28	0.78	0.57	0.63	0.78	0.94	<u>0.14</u>	0.41	0.74	0.83	0.25	0.50	0.05	0.57	0.41	0.41	0.01	0.47	0.37	0.63	<u>0.16</u>	<0.01	0.37	<u>0.14</u>
S&S3_24	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.06	<0.01	0.07	0.65	<0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.58	<u>0.15</u>	0.05	<u>0.16</u>	0.25	0.06	0.02	0.02	0.37	0.09	0.02	0.09	0.65	0.37	<0.01	<u>0.11</u>
S&S3_25	0.44	0.37	0.70	0.69	0.04	0.03	1.00	0.67	0.44	0.37	0.01	1.00	0.37	0.41	0.29	0.63	1.00	0.33	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.14</u>	<u>0.15</u>	<u>0.11</u>	<0.01	0.06	<u>0.14</u>	<u>0.11</u>	<0.01

Social constraints (SC1_1) fairness includes 3 factor of second level and 8 factors of third level (Table 58).

Table 58. Descriptive statistics for Use Case III - Social constraints

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
SC1_1	Social constraints	0.542	0.509
SC2_1	Subjective norm (peer influence)	0.500	0.511
SC2_2	Socio-cultural constraints (negative perception)	0.417	0.504
SC2_3	Family responsibilities	0.292	0.464
SC3_1	Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities	0.250	0.442
SC3_2	Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling	0.333	0.482
SC3_3	Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling to demystify the myth about cycling in low-income and minority neighbourhoods	0.333	0.482
SC3_4	Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling	0.292	0.464
SC3_5	Promote cycling as a legitimate form of transportation	0.333	0.482
SC3_6	Education on practical cycling (cycling with children and cargo)	0.292	0.464
SC3_7	Safe cycle routes for cycling with children	0.167	0.381
SC3_8	Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo.	0.083	0.282

The results (Table 59 and Table 55) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Subjective norm (peer influence) (SC2_1)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - SC3_1 Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities with $V = 0.58$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_2 Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_3 Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling to demystify the myth about cycling in low-income and minority neighbourhoods with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_4 Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - SC3_5 Promote cycling as a legitimate form of transportation with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_6 Education on practical cycling (cycling with children and cargo) with $V = 0.64$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_7 Safe cycle routes for cycling with children with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - SC3_8 Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.15$.
- **Socio-cultural constraints (SC2_2)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - SC3_1 Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities with $V = 0.29$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.17$;
 - SC3_2 Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling with $V = 0.48$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - SC3_3 Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling to demystify the myth about cycling in low-income and minority neighbourhoods with $V = 0.84$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_4 Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling with $V = 0.76$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_5 Promote cycling as a legitimate form of transportation with $V = 0.84$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_6 Education on practical cycling with $V = 0.57$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_7 Safe cycle routes for cycling with children with $V = 0.53$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - SC3_8 Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$.
- **Family responsibilities (SC2_3)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - SC3_1 Availability of end-of-trip cycling facilities with $V = 0.26$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.21$;
 - SC3_2 Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_3 Public awareness campaign on the benefits of cycling to demystify the myth about cycling in low-income and minority neighbourhoods with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_4 Better and safe cycling facilities to encourage cycling with $V = 0.6$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_5 Promote cycling as a legitimate form of transportation with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_6 Education on practical cycling (cycling with children and cargo) with $V = 1$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_7 Safe cycle routes for cycling with children with $V = 0.7$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - SC3_8 Bikes with child seats and trailers for carrying kids and carting cargo with $V = 0.47$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$.

Table 59 Cramer's V for Use Case III - Social constraints Literature Review

	SC2_1	SC2_2	SC2_3	SC3_1	SC3_2	SC3_3	SC3_4	SC3_5	SC3_6	SC3_7	SC3_8
SC2_1	1.00	0.68	0.64	0.58	0.71	0.71	0.46	0.71	0.64	0.45	<u>0.30</u>
SC2_2	0.68	1.00	0.57	<u>0.29</u>	0.48	0.84	0.76	0.84	0.57	0.53	<u>0.36</u>
SC2_3	0.64	0.57	1.00	0.26	0.71	0.71	0.60	0.71	1.00	0.70	0.47
SC3_1	0.58	<u>0.29</u>	0.26	1.00	0.00	0.20	0.05	0.41	0.26	0.26	0.52
SC3_2	0.71	0.48	0.71	0.00	1.00	0.63	0.52	0.44	0.71	0.40	0.11
SC3_3	0.71	0.84	0.71	0.20	0.63	1.00	0.71	0.81	0.71	0.63	0.43
SC3_4	0.46	0.76	0.60	0.05	0.52	0.71	1.00	0.71	0.60	0.45	0.14
SC3_5	0.71	0.84	0.71	0.41	0.44	0.81	0.71	1.00	0.71	0.63	0.43
SC3_6	0.64	0.57	1.00	0.26	0.71	0.71	0.60	0.71	1.00	0.70	0.47
SC3_7	0.45	0.53	0.70	0.26	0.40	0.63	0.45	0.63	0.70	1.00	0.67
SC3_8	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.47	0.52	0.11	0.43	0.14	0.43	0.47	0.67	1.00

Table 60. p-value of χ^2 for Use Case III - Social constraints Literature Review

	SC2_1	SC2_2	SC2_3	SC3_1	SC3_2	SC3_3	SC3_4	SC3_5	SC3_6	SC3_7	SC3_8
SC2_1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<u>0.15</u>
SC2_2	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.09
SC2_3	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.21	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02
SC3_1	<0.01	<u>0.17</u>	0.21	<0.01	1.00	0.34	0.81	0.05	0.21	0.22	0.01
SC3_2	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	1.00	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.03	<0.01	0.06	0.62
SC3_3	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.34	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.04
SC3_4	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	0.81	0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.52
SC3_5	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.05	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.04
SC3_6	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.21	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.02
SC3_7	0.03	0.01	<0.01	0.22	0.06	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
SC3_8	<u>0.15</u>	0.09	0.02	0.01	0.62	0.04	0.52	0.04	0.02	<0.01	<0.01

Weather & Topography (WT1_1) fairness includes 5 factor of second level and 6 factors of third level (Table 56).

Table 61. Descriptive statistics for Use Case III - Weather & Topography

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
WT1_1	Weather & Topography	0.417	0.504
WT2_1	Weather	0.375	0.495
WT2_2	Topography	0.167	0.381
WT3_1	All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure	0.375	0.495
WT3_2	Cycling rain Poncho	0.167	0.381
WT3_3	Electric bikes in bike-share fleet	0.125	0.338
WT3_4	Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible.	0.083	0.282

The results (Table 62 and Table 58

Table 63) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Weather (WT2_1)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - WT3_1 All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure with $V = 1$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - WT3_2 Cycling rain Poncho with $V = 0.58$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - WT3_4 Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$.
- **Topography (WT2_1)** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:

- WT3_1 All weather cycle-friendly infrastructure with $V = 0.35$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.1$;
- WT3_2 Cycling rain Poncho with $V = 0.4$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
- WT3_3 Electric bikes in bike-share fleet with $V = 0.85$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- WT3_4 Avoid hilly terrain in the development of cycle networks where possible with $V = 0.67$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$.

Table 62 Cramer's V for Use Case III - Weather & Topography Literature Review

	WT1_1	WT2_1	WT2_2	WT3_1	WT3_2	WT3_3	WT3_4
WT1_1	1.00	0.92	0.53	0.92	0.53	0.45	<u>0.36</u>
WT2_1	0.92	1.00	<u>0.35</u>	1.00	0.58	0.23	0.39
WT2_2	0.53	<u>0.35</u>	1.00	<u>0.35</u>	0.40	0.85	0.67
WT3_1	0.92	1.00	<u>0.35</u>	1.00	0.58	0.23	0.39
WT3_2	0.53	0.58	0.40	0.58	1.00	0.17	0.67
WT3_3	0.45	0.23	0.85	0.23	0.17	1.00	<u>0.34</u>
WT3_4	<u>0.36</u>	0.39	0.67	0.39	0.67	<u>0.34</u>	1.00

Table 63. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case III - Weather & Topography Literature Review

	WT1_1	WT2_1	WT2_2	WT3_1	WT3_2	WT3_3	WT3_4
WT1_1	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.03	0.09
WT2_1	<0.01	<0.01	0.10	<0.01	<0.01	0.28	0.06
WT2_2	0.01	0.10	<0.01	0.10	0.05	<0.01	<0.01
WT3_1	<0.01	<0.01	0.10	<0.01	<0.01	0.28	0.06
WT3_2	0.01	<0.01	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	0.43	<0.01
WT3_3	0.03	0.28	<0.01	0.28	0.43	<0.01	0.10
WT3_4	0.09	0.06	<0.01	0.06	<0.01	0.10	<0.01

Use Case III – Employment

Use case IV includes 4 first level fairness: Accessibility of the service Job Characteristics (JCI_1), Policy and Legal, and Female Facilities.

The Job Segregation (JSI_1) includes 4 factor of second level and 20 factors of third level (Table 64)

Table 64. Descriptive statistics for Use Case IV - Job Segregation

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
AoS1_1	Accessibility of the service	1.000	0.000
AoS1_2	Job Segregation	0.969	0.177
AoS2_2	Demand Factors	0.719	0.457
AoS3_2	Policy and Legal	0.906	0.296
AoS4_2	Female Facilities	0.438	0.504
AoS1_3	On the job training for men and women to negate cultural stereotypes associated with women and specific roles and tasks in the transport sector	0.969	0.177
AoS2_3	School visits and open days to attract more women to the sector	0.531	0.507
AoS3_3	Promoting a more gender-balanced career orientation among students 'women-only' open days	0.656	0.483
AoS4_3	Ensuring gender pay equality for equivalent positions	0.938	0.246
AoS5_3	More media representation of women in the transport sector (role models)	0.625	0.492
AoS6_3	Regularly reviewing the recruitment process for unconscious bias.	0.594	0.499
AoS7_3	Gender neutral recruitment policies should be in place	0.531	0.507
AoS8_3	Design job offers so that both men and women can apply	0.188	0.397
AoS9_3	Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed	0.281	0.457
AoS10_3	Ensure employment decisions are based on objective issues related to the job	0.281	0.457
AoS11_3	Provision of training, scholarships, and internships to improve the skills of women.	0.656	0.483
AoS12_3	Equal employment policies;	0.688	0.471
AoS13_3	Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave	0.531	0.507
AoS14_3	Anti-harassment policies	0.250	0.440
AoS15_3	Ensure that men and women have equal access to professional mobility;	0.469	0.507
AoS16_3	Corporate policies to facilitate women in the workplace.	0.594	0.499
AoS17_3	Provision of female toilets and showers were required;	0.281	0.457
AoS18_3	Provision of suitable female PPE;	0.375	0.492
AoS19_3	Segregated changing rooms;	0.250	0.440
AoS20_3	Breast feeding rooms.	0.063	0.246

The results (Table 65 and Table 66) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **Demand Factors has a strong connection with the following third level factors:**
 - AoS1_3 On the job training for men and women to negate cultural stereotypes associated with women and specific roles and tasks in the transport sector with $V=1$ and $p\text{-value}<0.01$;
 - AoS9_3 Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed with $V=0.29$ and $p\text{-value}=0.11$;
- **Demand Factors has a strong connection with the following third level factors:**
 - AoS3_3 Promoting a more gender-balanced career orientation among students 'women-only' open days with $V=0.28$ and $p\text{-value}=0.12$;
 - AoS7_3 Gender neutral recruitment policies should be in place with $V=0.67$ and $p\text{-value}<0.01$;
 - AoS8_3 Design job offers so that both men and women can apply with $V=0.3$ and $p\text{-value}=0.09$;
 - AoS9_3 Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed with $V=0.39$ and $p\text{-value}=0.03$;

- AoS10_3 Ensure employment decisions are based on objective issues related to the job with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
- AoS11_3 Provision of training, scholarships, and internships to improve the skills of women. with $V = 0.86$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- AoS13_3 Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
- AoS17_3 Provision of female toilets and showers were required with $V = 0.24$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.19$;
- AoS18_3 Provision of suitable female PPE; with $V = 0.34$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
- AoS19_3 Segregated changing rooms; with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$.
- **Policy and Legal has a strong connection with the following third level factors:**
 - AoS7_3 Gender neutral recruitment policies should be in place with $V = 0.34$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
 - AoS12_3 Equal employment policies; with $V = 0.48$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - AoS13_3 Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave with $V = 0.34$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$;
 - AoS15_3 Ensure that men and women have equal access to professional mobility; with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$;
 - AoS16_3 Corporate policies to facilitate women in the workplace. with $V = 0.39$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$;
 - AoS18_3 Provision of suitable female PPE; with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.17$.
- **Female Facilities has a strong connection with the following third level factors:**
 - AoS3_3 Promoting a more gender-balanced career orientation among students ‘women-only’ open days with $V = 0.24$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.19$;
 - AoS9_3 Employment opportunities should be advertised widely and all applications welcomed with $V = 0.29$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
 - AoS10_3 Ensure employment decisions are based on objective issues related to the job with $V = 0.57$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AoS11_3 Provision of training, scholarships, and internships to improve the skills of women. with $V = 0.24$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.19$;
 - AoS13_3 Family friendly policies – maternity and paternity leave with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
 - AoS15_3 Ensure that men and women have equal access to professional mobility; with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$;
 - AoS16_3 Corporate policies to facilitate women in the workplace. with $V = 0.34$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$;
 - AoS17_3 Provision of female toilets and showers were required; with $V = 0.71$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AoS18_3 Provision of suitable female PPE; with $V = 0.88$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AoS19_3 Segregated changing rooms; with $V = 0.65$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - AoS20_3 Breast feeding rooms. with $V = 0.29$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.10$;

Table 65. Cramer's V for Use Case IV - Job Segregation Literature Review

	AoS1_2	AoS2_2	AoS3_2	AoS4_2	AoS1_3	AoS2_3	AoS3_3	AoS4_3	AoS5_3	AoS6_3	AoS7_3	AoS8_3	AoS9_3	AoS10_3	AoS11_3	AoS12_3	AoS13_3	AoS14_3	AoS15_3	AoS16_3	AoS17_3	AoS18_3	AoS19_3	AoS20_3
AoS1_2	1.00	0.11	0.06	0.16	1.00	0.17	0.13	0.05	0.14	0.22	0.17	0.09	0.29	0.11	0.13	0.12	0.19	0.10	0.17	0.15	0.11	0.14	0.10	0.05
AoS2_2	0.11	1.00	0.28	0.41	0.11	0.03	0.28	0.16	0.05	0.05	0.67	<u>0.30</u>	0.39	0.39	0.86	0.03	0.39	0.04	0.17	0.05	0.24	<u>0.34</u>	<u>0.36</u>	0.16
AoS3_2	0.06	0.28	1.00	0.28	0.06	0.09	0.01	0.08	0.03	0.17	<u>0.34</u>	0.15	0.20	0.20	0.22	0.48	<u>0.34</u>	0.19	<u>0.30</u>	0.39	0.20	0.25	0.19	0.08
AoS4_2	0.16	0.41	0.28	1.00	0.16	0.06	0.24	0.03	0.23	0.09	0.20	0.22	0.29	0.57	0.24	0.05	0.45	0.07	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.34</u>	0.71	0.88	0.65	<u>0.29</u>
AoS1_3	1.00	0.11	0.06	0.16	1.00	0.17	0.13	0.05	0.14	0.22	0.17	0.09	0.29	0.11	0.13	0.12	0.19	0.10	0.17	0.15	0.11	0.14	0.10	0.05
AoS2_3	0.17	0.03	0.09	0.06	0.17	1.00	0.37	0.02	<u>0.31</u>	0.37	0.00	0.13	0.17	0.11	0.02	0.18	0.12	0.18	0.12	0.01	0.11	0.08	0.04	0.27
AoS3_3	0.13	0.28	0.01	0.24	0.13	0.37	1.00	0.08	0.12	<u>0.34</u>	0.24	0.01	0.01	0.16	<u>0.31</u>	0.08	0.11	0.04	0.02	0.07	<u>0.31</u>	0.29	0.11	0.08
AoS4_3	0.05	0.16	0.08	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.08	1.00	0.07	0.21	0.02	0.12	0.13	0.16	0.19	0.10	0.24	0.15	0.27	0.05	0.16	0.07	0.15	0.07
AoS5_3	0.14	0.05	0.03	0.23	0.14	<u>0.31</u>	0.12	0.07	1.00	0.12	0.08	0.04	0.20	0.09	0.02	0.03	0.08	0.00	0.05	0.12	0.09	0.07	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.33</u>
AoS6_3	0.22	0.05	0.17	0.09	0.22	0.37	<u>0.34</u>	0.21	0.12	1.00	0.12	0.25	0.09	0.19	0.07	0.13	0.24	0.04	0.14	0.17	0.23	0.12	0.04	0.05
AoS7_3	0.17	0.67	<u>0.34</u>	0.20	0.17	0.00	0.24	0.02	0.08	0.12	1.00	0.45	0.17	0.17	0.64	<u>0.31</u>	0.50	0.04	0.13	0.01	0.17	0.08	0.25	0.24
AoS8_3	0.09	<u>0.30</u>	0.15	0.22	0.09	0.13	0.01	0.12	0.04	0.25	0.45	1.00	0.12	0.41	<u>0.35</u>	0.15	0.45	0.28	0.13	0.09	0.06	0.29	0.09	0.12
AoS9_3	0.29	0.39	0.20	0.29	0.29	0.17	0.01	0.13	0.20	0.09	0.17	0.12	1.00	0.23	<u>0.31</u>	0.27	0.03	0.20	0.03	0.09	0.23	0.38	0.12	0.16
AoS10_3	0.11	0.39	0.20	0.57	0.11	0.11	0.16	0.16	0.09	0.19	0.17	0.41	0.23	1.00	<u>0.31</u>	0.12	0.17	0.28	0.17	0.38	0.38	0.52	0.44	0.13
AoS11_3	0.13	0.86	0.22	0.24	0.13	0.02	<u>0.31</u>	0.19	0.02	0.07	0.64	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	1.00	0.06	0.37	0.04	0.15	0.06	0.16	0.29	0.27	0.08
AoS12_3	0.12	0.03	0.48	0.05	0.12	0.18	0.08	0.10	0.03	0.13	<u>0.31</u>	0.15	0.27	0.12	0.06	1.00	0.45	0.23	0.09	0.13	0.03	0.10	0.08	0.17
AoS13_3	0.19	0.39	<u>0.34</u>	0.45	0.19	0.12	0.11	0.24	0.08	0.24	0.50	0.45	0.03	0.17	0.37	0.45	1.00	0.11	0.38	0.01	0.17	0.47	0.40	0.24
AoS14_3	0.10	0.04	0.19	0.07	0.10	0.18	0.04	0.15	0.00	0.04	0.04	0.28	0.20	0.28	0.04	0.23	0.11	1.00	0.11	0.11	0.12	0.15	0.00	0.15
AoS15_3	0.17	0.17	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.17	0.12	0.02	0.27	0.05	0.14	0.13	0.13	0.03	0.17	0.15	0.09	0.38	0.11	1.00	0.12	0.39	<u>0.31</u>	0.04	0.27
AoS16_3	0.15	0.05	0.39	<u>0.34</u>	0.15	0.01	0.07	0.05	0.12	0.17	0.01	0.09	0.09	0.38	0.06	0.13	0.01	0.11	0.12	1.00	0.09	0.25	0.48	0.21
AoS17_3	0.11	0.24	0.20	0.71	0.11	0.11	<u>0.31</u>	0.16	0.09	0.23	0.17	0.06	0.23	0.38	0.16	0.03	0.17	0.12	0.39	0.09	1.00	0.66	0.12	0.13
AoS18_3	0.14	<u>0.34</u>	0.25	0.88	0.14	0.08	0.29	0.07	0.07	0.12	0.08	0.29	0.38	0.52	0.29	0.10	0.47	0.15	<u>0.31</u>	0.25	0.66	1.00	0.45	0.07
AoS19_3	0.10	<u>0.36</u>	0.19	0.65	0.10	0.04	0.11	0.15	<u>0.30</u>	0.04	0.25	0.09	0.12	0.44	0.27	0.08	0.40	0.00	0.04	0.48	0.12	0.45	1.00	0.45
AoS20_3	0.05	0.16	0.08	<u>0.29</u>	0.05	0.27	0.08	0.07	<u>0.33</u>	0.05	0.24	0.12	0.16	0.13	0.08	0.17	0.24	0.15	0.27	0.21	0.13	0.07	0.45	1.00

Table 66. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case IV - Job Segregation Literature Review

	AoS1_2	AoS2_2	AoS3_2	AoS4_2	AoS1_3	AoS2_3	AoS3_3	AoS4_3	AoS5_3	AoS6_3	AoS7_3	AoS8_3	AoS9_3	AoS10_3	AoS11_3	AoS12_3	AoS13_3	AoS14_3	AoS15_3	AoS16_3	AoS17_3	AoS18_3	AoS19_3	AoS20_3
AoS1_2	<0.01	0.54	0.75	0.39	<0.01	0.36	0.48	0.80	0.45	0.23	0.36	0.64	<u>0.11</u>	0.54	0.48	0.51	0.29	0.57	0.36	0.42	0.54	0.45	0.57	0.80
AoS2_2	0.54	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.02	0.54	0.87	<u>0.12</u>	0.38	0.77	0.79	<0.01	0.09	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.88	0.03	0.83	0.35	0.79	<u>0.19</u>	0.06	0.04	0.38
AoS3_2	0.75	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.75	0.63	0.97	0.65	0.88	0.35	0.06	0.40	0.27	0.27	0.23	0.01	0.06	0.31	0.09	0.03	0.27	<u>0.17</u>	0.31	0.65
AoS4_2	0.39	0.02	<u>0.12</u>	<0.01	0.39	0.76	<u>0.19</u>	0.86	0.21	0.63	0.28	0.22	<u>0.11</u>	<0.01	<u>0.19</u>	0.78	0.01	0.69	0.09	0.05	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.10
AoS1_3	<0.01	0.54	0.75	0.39	<0.01	0.36	0.48	0.80	0.45	0.23	0.36	0.64	<u>0.11</u>	0.54	0.48	0.51	0.29	0.57	0.36	0.42	0.54	0.45	0.57	0.80
AoS2_3	0.36	0.87	0.63	0.76	0.36	<0.01	0.03	0.93	0.09	0.04	0.98	0.48	0.35	0.55	0.91	0.33	0.51	0.32	0.51	0.95	0.55	0.66	0.84	<u>0.13</u>
AoS3_3	0.48	<u>0.12</u>	0.97	<u>0.19</u>	0.48	0.03	<0.01	0.64	0.52	0.06	<u>0.18</u>	0.95	0.94	0.38	0.09	0.66	0.54	0.84	0.91	0.70	0.09	<u>0.11</u>	0.53	0.64
AoS4_3	0.80	0.38	0.65	0.86	0.80	0.93	0.64	<0.01	0.72	0.24	0.93	0.50	0.49	0.38	0.31	0.57	<u>0.18</u>	0.42	<u>0.13</u>	0.79	0.38	0.72	0.42	0.72
AoS5_3	0.45	0.77	0.88	0.21	0.45	0.09	0.52	0.72	<0.01	0.53	0.66	0.82	0.28	0.63	0.93	0.85	0.66	1.00	0.79	0.53	0.63	0.72	0.10	0.06
AoS6_3	0.23	0.79	0.35	0.63	0.23	0.04	0.06	0.24	0.53	<0.01	0.53	<u>0.16</u>	0.61	0.30	0.70	0.48	<u>0.18</u>	0.84	0.45	0.36	<u>0.20</u>	0.53	0.84	0.79
AoS7_3	0.36	<0.01	0.06	0.28	0.36	0.98	<u>0.18</u>	0.93	0.66	0.53	<0.01	0.01	0.35	0.35	<0.01	0.08	<0.01	0.84	0.48	0.95	0.35	0.66	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.18</u>
AoS8_3	0.64	0.09	0.40	0.22	0.64	0.48	0.95	0.50	0.82	<u>0.16</u>	0.01	<0.01	0.50	0.02	0.05	0.41	0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.48	0.62	0.76	<u>0.11</u>	0.61	0.50
AoS9_3	<u>0.11</u>	0.03	0.27	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.11</u>	0.35	0.94	0.49	0.28	0.61	0.35	0.50	<0.01	0.21	0.09	<u>0.13</u>	0.87	0.27	0.87	0.61	0.21	0.03	0.51	0.38
AoS10_3	0.54	0.03	0.27	<0.01	0.54	0.55	0.38	0.38	0.63	0.30	0.35	0.02	0.21	<0.01	0.09	0.51	0.35	<u>0.12</u>	0.35	0.03	0.03	<0.01	0.01	0.49
AoS11_3	0.48	<0.01	0.23	<u>0.19</u>	0.48	0.91	0.09	0.31	0.93	0.70	<0.01	0.05	0.09	0.09	<0.01	0.74	0.03	0.84	0.40	0.73	0.38	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.14</u>	0.64
AoS12_3	0.51	0.88	0.01	0.78	0.51	0.33	0.66	0.57	0.85	0.48	0.08	0.41	<u>0.13</u>	0.51	0.74	<0.01	0.01	<u>0.20</u>	0.61	0.48	0.88	0.57	0.67	0.34
AoS13_3	0.29	0.03	0.06	0.01	0.29	0.51	0.54	<u>0.18</u>	0.66	<u>0.18</u>	<0.01	0.01	0.87	0.35	0.03	0.01	<0.01	0.55	0.03	0.95	0.35	0.01	0.02	<u>0.18</u>
AoS14_3	0.57	0.83	0.31	0.69	0.57	0.32	0.84	0.42	1.00	0.84	0.84	<u>0.12</u>	0.27	<u>0.12</u>	0.84	<u>0.20</u>	0.55	<0.01	0.55	0.55	0.51	0.42	1.00	0.42
AoS15_3	0.36	0.35	0.09	0.09	0.36	0.51	0.91	<u>0.13</u>	0.79	0.45	0.48	0.48	0.87	0.35	0.40	0.61	0.03	0.55	<0.01	0.53	0.03	0.09	0.84	<u>0.13</u>
AoS16_3	0.42	0.79	0.03	0.05	0.42	0.95	0.70	0.79	0.53	0.36	0.95	0.62	0.61	0.03	0.73	0.48	0.95	0.55	0.53	<0.01	0.61	<u>0.17</u>	0.01	0.24
AoS17_3	0.54	<u>0.19</u>	0.27	<0.01	0.54	0.55	0.09	0.38	0.63	<u>0.20</u>	0.35	0.76	0.21	0.03	0.38	0.88	0.35	0.51	0.03	0.61	<0.01	<0.01	0.51	0.49
AoS18_3	0.45	0.06	<u>0.17</u>	<0.01	0.45	0.66	<u>0.11</u>	0.72	0.72	0.53	0.66	<u>0.11</u>	0.03	<0.01	<u>0.11</u>	0.57	0.01	0.42	0.09	<u>0.17</u>	<0.01	<0.01	0.01	0.72
AoS19_3	0.57	0.04	0.31	<0.01	0.57	0.84	0.53	0.42	0.10	0.84	<u>0.16</u>	0.61	0.51	0.01	<u>0.14</u>	0.67	0.02	1.00	0.84	0.01	0.51	0.01	<0.01	0.01
AoS20_3	0.80	0.38	0.65	0.10	0.80	<u>0.13</u>	0.64	0.72	0.06	0.79	<u>0.18</u>	0.50	0.38	0.49	0.64	0.34	<u>0.18</u>	0.42	<u>0.13</u>	0.24	0.49	0.72	0.01	<0.01

The Job Characteristics (JSI_1) includes 5 factor of second level and 28 factors of third level (Table 67)

Table 67. Descriptive statistics for Use Case IV - Job Characteristics

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
JC1_1	Job Characteristics	1.00	<0.01
JC1_2	HR Policies	0.78	0.42
JC2_2	Terms and Conditions	0.81	0.40
JC3_2	Flexible Working	0.56	0.50
JC4_2	Training Provision	0.94	0.25
JC5_2	Safety and Security	0.66	0.48
JC1_3	Targeted recruitment campaigns;	0.66	0.48
JC2_3	Organisations should ensure that they maintain a gender mix among its newly hired managers,	0.22	0.42
JC3_3	Maternity leave or part-time work practices will not be taken into account when evaluating promotions or access to greater responsibilities;	0.22	0.42
JC4_3	Integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities, particularly when advertising jobs;	0.38	0.49
JC5_3	Ensure that the male-female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male-female ratio of the company staff;	0.13	0.34
JC6_3	Improved maternity provisions and re-entry policy;	0.19	0.40
JC7_3	Place someone in charge - assigning the responsibility to a specific person or body to identify, put in motion and monitor the actions that can be taken to advance the position of women within a company.	0.41	0.50
JC8_3	Safe working environments for women (sexual harassment, violence etc.);	0.44	0.50
JC9_3	Formal recognition of sexual harassment claims;	0.06	0.25
JC10_3	Part time workers provided with the same safeguards of employment as full time workers	0.38	0.49
JC11_3	Personal development training;	0.47	0.51
JC12_3	Not using 'a-typical contracts' (zero hours etc.);	0.28	0.46
JC13_3	Support the professional progression of women;	0.50	0.51
JC14_3	Wage structures that are predictable with no variable components.	0.38	0.49
JC15_3	Part-time work, flexible working hours, and work from home options;	0.38	0.49
JC16_3	Employees with small children are allowed the possibility of flexible working times;	0.19	0.40
JC17_3	Employees having more input of shift rota;	0.16	0.37
JC18_3	Opportunity for job sharing.	0.38	0.49
JC19_3	Women and men should have equal access to all training programmes	0.88	0.34
JC20_3	A flexible training system to be introduced;	0.44	0.50
JC21_3	Training to promote a cultural change among the male colleagues	0.59	0.50
JC22_3	Training for all involved in key decision-making roles in relation to potentially discriminating practices	0.72	0.46
JC23_3	Continually assessing the relevance and quality of training institutions and programmes	0.59	0.50
JC24_3	Regulations and education regarding sexual harassment between colleagues	0.31	0.47
JC25_3	Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment;	0.31	0.47
JC26_3	Training against third-party violence;	0.16	0.37
JC27_3	Safety equipment - CCTV cameras, panic buttons, anti-theft equipment, closed cabins etc. to protect drivers and other personnel from aggressive third-party behaviour;	0.41	0.50
JC28_3	Security staff available to intervene in case of need.	0.06	0.25

The results (Table 68 and Table 69) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **JC1_2 HR Policies** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - JC1_3 Targeted recruitment campaigns; with $V = 0.73$ and $p\text{-value} = 0$
 - JC2_3 Organisations should ensure that they maintain a gender mix among its newly hired managers, with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.12$
 - JC3_3 Maternity leave or part-time work practices will not be taken into account when evaluating promotions or access to greater responsibilities; with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.12$
 - JC4_3 Integrate the company's commitment to gender equality into all of its communication activities, particularly when advertising jobs; with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$
 - JC6_3 Improved maternity provisions and re-entry policy; with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$

- JC7_3 Place someone in charge - assigning the responsibility to a specific person or body to identify, put in motion and monitor the actions that can be taken to advance the position of women within a company. with $V = 0.44$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$
- JC8_3 Safe working environments for women (sexual harassment, violence etc.); with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$
- JC10_3 Part time workers provided with the same safeguards of employment as full time workers with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$
- JC12_3 Not using 'a-typical contracts' (zero hours etc.); with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.06$
- JC14_3 Wage structures that are predictable with no variable components. with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$
- JC15_3 Part-time work, flexible working hours, and work from home options; with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$
- JC18_3 Opportunity for job sharing. with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$
- JC25_3 Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment; with $V = 0.36$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.05$
- JC27_3 Safety equipment - CCTV cameras, panic buttons, anti-theft equipment, closed cabins etc. to protect drivers and other personnel from aggressive third-party behaviour; with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.12$
- **JC2_2 Terms and Conditions** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - JC1_3 Targeted recruitment campaigns; with $V = 0.33$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$
 - JC3_3 Maternity leave or part-time work practices will not be taken into account when evaluating promotions or access to greater responsibilities; with $V = 0.25$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.16$
 - JC8_3 Safe working environments for women (sexual harassment, violence etc.); with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$
 - JC10_3 Part time workers provided with the same safeguards of employment as full time workers with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$
 - JC11_3 Personal development training; with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$
 - JC12_3 Not using 'a-typical contracts' (zero hours etc.); with $V = 0.3$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$
 - JC13_3 Support the professional progression of women; with $V = 0.48$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$
 - JC14_3 Wage structures that are predictable with no variable components. with $V = 0.37$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.04$
 - JC17_3 Employees having more input of shift rota; with $V = 0.23$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.2$
 - JC25_3 Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment; with $V = 0.32$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.07$
 - JC27_3 Safety equipment - CCTV cameras, panic buttons, anti-theft equipment, closed cabins etc. to protect drivers and other personnel from aggressive third-party behaviour; with $V = 0.23$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.2$;
- **JC3_2 Flexible Working** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - JC10_3 Part time workers provided with the same safeguards of employment as full time workers with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$
 - JC11_3 Personal development training; with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$
 - JC12_3 Not using 'a-typical contracts' (zero hours etc.); with $V = 0.27$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.13$
 - JC14_3 Wage structures that are predictable with no variable components. with $V = 0.68$ and $p\text{-value} = 0$
 - JC15_3 Part-time work, flexible working hours, and work from home options; with $V = 0.68$ and $p\text{-value} = 0$
 - JC16_3 Employees with small children are allowed the possibility of flexible working times; with $V = 0.42$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$
 - JC17_3 Employees having more input of shift rota; with $V = 0.38$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.03$
 - JC18_3 Opportunity for job sharing. with $V = 0.68$ and $p\text{-value} = 0$
 - JC20_3 A flexible training system to be introduced; with $V = 0.27$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.14$
- **JC4_2 Training Provision** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - JC5_3 Ensure that the male–female ratio of internal promotions in different job categories is in line with the average male–female ratio of the company staff; with $V = 0.29$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.10$;
 - JC19_3 Women and men should have equal access to all training programmes with $V = 0.68$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
 - JC21_3 Training to promote a cultural change among the male colleagues with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - JC22_3 Training for all involved in key decision-making roles in relation to potentially discriminating practices with $V = 0.41$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.02$;
 - JC23_3 Continually assessing the relevance and quality of training institutions and programmes with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
 - JC28_3 Security staff available to intervene in case of need. with $V = 0.47$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
- **JC5_2 Safety and Security** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - JC1_3 Targeted recruitment campaigns; with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.09$;

- JC8_3 Safe working environments for women (sexual harassment, violence etc.); with $V = 0.51$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- JC11_3 Personal development training; with $V = 0.28$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.11$;
- JC22_3 Training for all involved in key decision-making roles in relation to potentially discriminating practices with $V = 0.45$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
- JC23_3 Continually assessing the relevance and quality of training institutions and programmes with $V = 0.46$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.01$;
- JC24_3 Regulations and education regarding sexual harassment between colleagues with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- JC25_3 Applying and actively communicating a zero-tolerance policy to sexual harassment; with $V = 0.49$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;
- JC26_3 Training against third-party violence; with $V = 0.31$ and $p\text{-value} = 0.08$;
- JC27_3 Safety equipment - CCTV cameras, panic buttons, anti-theft equipment, closed cabins etc. to protect drivers and other personnel from aggressive third-party behaviour; with $V = 0.6$ and $p\text{-value} < 0.01$;

Table 68. Cramer's V for Use Case IV - Job Characteristics Literature Review

	JC1_2	JC2_2	JC3_2	JC4_2	JC5_2	JC1_3	JC2_3	JC3_3	JC4_3	JC5_3	JC6_3	JC7_3	JC8_3	JC9_3	JC10_3	JC11_3	JC12_3	JC13_3	JC14_3	JC15_3	JC16_3	JC17_3	JC18_3	JC19_3	JC20_3	JC21_3	JC22_3	JC23_3	JC24_3	JC25_3	JC26_3	JC27_3	JC28_3
JC1_2	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.18	0.25	0.73	0.28	0.28	0.41	0.20	0.25	0.44	<u>0.31</u>	0.14	0.25	0.04	<u>0.33</u>	0.08	0.25	0.25	0.06	0.23	0.25	0.03	0.01	0.18	0.01	0.18	0.03	<u>0.36</u>	0.23	0.28	0.18
JC2_2	<u>0.33</u>	1.00	0.06	0.12	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.06	0.25	0.04	0.06	0.23	0.09	0.42	0.12	0.37	0.45	<u>0.30</u>	0.48	0.37	0.04	0.18	0.23	0.12	0.18	0.22	0.09	0.12	0.07	0.02	<u>0.32</u>	0.21	0.23	0.12
JC3_2	<u>0.30</u>	0.06	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	0.02	0.16	0.01	0.01	0.16	0.24	0.06	0.22	0.02	0.03	0.42	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.27</u>	0.13	0.68	0.68	0.42	0.38	0.68	0.05	0.27	0.04	0.15	0.09	0.19	0.08	0.14	0.22	0.03
JC4_2	0.18	0.12	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	0.19	0.08	0.18	0.14	0.20	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	0.21	0.23	0.07	0.07	0.02	0.13	0.00	0.20	0.20	0.12	0.11	0.20	0.68	0.23	<u>0.31</u>	0.41	<u>0.31</u>	0.10	0.17	0.11	0.05	0.47
JC5_2	0.25	<u>0.33</u>	0.02	0.19	1.00	<u>0.31</u>	0.06	0.06	0.02	0.12	0.01	0.06	0.51	0.19	0.15	0.28	0.01	0.20	0.02	0.02	0.16	0.23	0.15	0.07	0.16	0.06	0.45	0.46	0.49	0.49	<u>0.31</u>	0.60	0.19
JC1_3	0.73	<u>0.33</u>	0.16	0.08	<u>0.31</u>	1.00	0.22	0.22	0.15	0.07	0.18	0.46	0.37	0.19	0.29	0.15	<u>0.31</u>	0.07	0.02	0.15	0.01	0.05	0.15	0.07	0.11	0.06	0.01	0.21	0.08	0.20	<u>0.31</u>	0.46	0.08
JC2_3	0.28	0.06	0.01	0.18	0.06	0.22	1.00	0.09	0.06	0.03	<u>0.33</u>	0.18	0.14	0.14	0.37	0.19	0.01	0.08	0.10	0.21	0.06	0.19	0.21	0.03	0.14	0.13	<u>0.34</u>	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.18	0.14
JC3_3	0.28	0.25	0.01	0.14	0.06	0.22	0.09	1.00	0.06	0.20	0.52	0.18	<u>0.30</u>	0.18	0.06	0.04	0.17	0.08	0.21	0.06	0.13	0.02	0.06	0.20	0.14	0.13	0.01	0.13	0.13	<u>0.30</u>	0.19	0.18	0.14
JC4_3	0.41	0.04	0.16	0.20	0.02	0.15	0.06	0.06	1.00	0.10	0.12	0.15	0.10	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.33</u>	0.21	0.09	0.26	0.20	0.07	0.21	0.02	0.07	0.10	0.03	0.38	0.05	0.25	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.20	0.02	0.07
JC5_3	0.20	0.06	0.24	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	0.07	0.03	0.20	0.10	1.00	0.18	0.12	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.10	0.17	0.18	0.19	0.10	<u>0.29</u>	0.18	0.16	<u>0.29</u>	0.43	<u>0.33</u>	0.07	0.03	0.12	0.25	0.05	0.16	0.12	0.10
JC6_3	0.25	0.23	0.06	0.12	0.01	0.18	<u>0.33</u>	0.52	0.12	0.18	1.00	0.09	0.38	0.21	0.12	0.03	0.06	0.16	0.12	0.12	0.03	0.01	0.12	0.18	0.38	0.23	0.12	0.07	0.15	0.02	0.45	0.09	0.12
JC7_3	0.44	0.09	0.22	0.21	0.06	0.46	0.18	0.18	0.15	0.12	0.09	1.00	0.17	0.05	0.28	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.02	0.28	0.09	0.17	0.28	<u>0.31</u>	0.17	0.22	0.05	<u>0.30</u>	0.01	0.15	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.35</u>	0.05
JC8_3	<u>0.31</u>	0.42	0.02	0.23	0.51	0.37	0.14	<u>0.30</u>	0.10	<u>0.33</u>	0.38	0.17	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	0.10	0.43	0.01	0.38	0.10	0.03	0.26	0.38	0.03	0.14	0.02	0.22	0.13	0.04	0.08	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.55	0.23
JC9_3	0.14	0.12	0.03	0.07	0.19	0.19	0.14	0.18	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.21	0.05	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	0.07	0.27	0.13	0.26	0.07	0.20	0.12	0.11	0.20	0.10	0.03	0.21	0.16	0.21	0.17	0.38	0.24	0.05	0.07
JC10_3	0.25	0.37	0.42	0.07	0.15	0.29	0.37	0.06	<u>0.33</u>	0.10	0.12	0.28	0.10	0.07	1.00	<u>0.34</u>	0.38	0.13	0.47	<u>0.33</u>	0.21	0.16	0.20	<u>0.29</u>	0.03	0.02	0.23	0.02	0.03	0.20	0.41	0.07	
JC11_3	0.04	0.45	<u>0.31</u>	0.02	0.28	0.15	0.19	0.04	0.21	0.17	0.03	0.01	0.43	0.27	<u>0.34</u>	1.00	<u>0.31</u>	0.81	0.21	0.13	0.23	0.21	0.17	0.20	0.12	0.03	0.01	0.09	<u>0.31</u>	0.11	0.01	0.02	
JC12_3	<u>0.33</u>	<u>0.30</u>	0.27	0.13	0.01	<u>0.31</u>	0.01	0.17	0.09	0.18	0.06	0.09	0.01	0.13	0.38	<u>0.31</u>	1.00	0.21	0.38	0.05	0.12	0.08	0.05	0.39	0.01	0.23	0.08	0.05	0.27	0.03	0.27	0.19	0.16
JC13_3	0.08	0.48	0.13	0.00	0.20	0.07	0.08	0.08	0.26	0.19	0.16	0.06	0.38	0.26	0.13	0.81	0.21	1.00	0.00	0.16	0.26	0.13	0.19	0.13	0.06	0.07	0.06	0.13	0.27	0.09	0.06	0.00	
JC14_3	0.25	0.37	0.68	0.20	0.02	0.02	0.10	0.21	0.20	0.10	0.12	0.02	0.10	0.07	0.47	0.21	0.38	0.00	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	0.12	0.02	0.20	0.10	0.10	0.25	0.20	0.28	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.15	0.07
JC15_3	0.25	0.04	0.68	0.20	0.02	0.15	0.21	0.06	0.07	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	0.28	0.03	0.20	<u>0.33</u>	0.21	0.05	0.00	<u>0.33</u>	1.00	0.45	0.56	0.87	0.10	0.23	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.17	0.10	0.02	0.28	0.07
JC16_3	0.06	0.18	0.42	0.12	0.16	0.01	0.06	0.13	0.21	0.18	0.03	0.09	0.26	0.12	0.21	0.13	0.12	0.16	0.12	0.45	1.00	0.45	0.62	0.18	0.22	0.07	0.06	0.09	0.19	0.15	0.01	0.07	0.21
JC17_3	0.23	0.23	0.38	0.11	0.23	0.05	0.19	0.02	0.02	0.16	0.01	0.17	0.38	0.11	0.16	0.23	0.08	0.26	0.02	0.56	0.45	1.00	0.56	0.16	0.14	0.01	0.08	0.18	0.08	0.10	0.19	0.18	0.11
JC18_3	0.25	0.12	0.68	0.20	0.15	0.15	0.21	0.06	0.07	<u>0.29</u>	0.12	0.28	0.03	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.05	0.13	0.20	0.87	0.62	0.56	1.00	0.10	<u>0.36</u>	0.02	0.09	0.15	<u>0.31</u>	0.10	0.02	0.28	0.07
JC19_3	0.03	0.18	0.05	0.68	0.07	0.07	0.03	0.20	0.10	0.43	0.18	<u>0.31</u>	0.14	0.10	<u>0.29</u>	0.17	0.39	0.19	0.10	0.10	0.18	0.16	0.10	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	0.07	0.18	0.07	0.15	0.05	0.16	0.07	<u>0.29</u>
JC20_3	0.01	0.22	0.27	0.23	0.16	0.11	0.14	0.14	0.03	<u>0.33</u>	0.38	0.17	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.20	0.01	0.13	0.10	0.23	0.22	0.14	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.33</u>	1.00	0.09	0.13	0.09	0.19	0.46	0.14	0.04	0.03
JC21_3	0.18	0.09	0.04	<u>0.31</u>	0.06	0.06	0.13	0.13	0.38	0.07	0.23	0.22	0.22	0.21	0.02	0.12	0.23	0.06	0.25	0.02	0.07	0.01	0.02	0.07	0.09	1.00	0.19	0.04	0.01	0.28	0.01	0.04	0.05
JC22_3	0.01	0.12	0.15	0.41	0.45	0.01	<u>0.34</u>	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.12	0.05	0.13	0.16	0.23	0.03	0.08	0.07	0.20	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.09	0.18	0.13	0.19	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	0.48	0.18	0.11	0.19	0.41
JC23_3	0.18	0.07	0.09	<u>0.31</u>	0.46	0.21	0.02	0.13	0.25	0.12	0.07	<u>0.30</u>	0.04	0.21	0.02	0.01	0.05	0.06	0.28	0.02	0.09	0.18	0.15	0.07	0.09	0.04	<u>0.33</u>	1.00	0.27	0.01	0.01	0.22	<u>0.31</u>
JC24_3	0.03	0.02	0.19	0.10	0.49	0.08	0.03	0.13	<u>0.31</u>	0.25	0.15	0.01	0.08	0.17	0.03	0.09	0.27	0.13	0.03	0.17	0.19	0.08	<u>0.31</u>	0.15	0.19	0.01	0.48	0.27	1.00	0.42	0.08	0.27	0.38
JC25_3	<u>0.36</u>	<u>0.32</u>	0.08	0.17	0.49	0.20	0.03	<u>0.30</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.05	0.02	0.15	<u>0.36</u>	0.38	0.03	<u>0.31</u>	0.03	0.27	0.03	0.10	0.15	0.10	0.10	0.05	0.46	0.28	0.18	0.01	0.42	1.00	0.08	0.13	0.17
JC26_3	0.23	0.21	0.14	0.11	<u>0.31</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.02	0.19	0.20	0.16	0.45	<u>0.35</u>	<u>0.31</u>	0.24	0.20	0.11	0.27	0.09	0.02	0.02	0.01	0.19	0.02	0.16	0.14	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.08	0.08	1.00	0.17	0.24
JC27_3	0.28	0.23	0.22	0.05	0.60	0.46	0.18	0.18	0.02	0.12	0.09	<u>0.35</u>	0.55	0.05	0.41	0.01	0.19	0.06	0.15	0.28	0.07	0.18	0.28	0.07	0.04	0.04	0.19	0.22	0.27	0.13	0.17	1.00	0.05
JC28_3	0.18	0.12	0.03	0.47	0.19	0.08	0.14	0.14	0.07	0.10	0.12	0.05	0.23	0.07	0.07	0.02	0.16	0.00	0.07	0.07	0.21	0.11	0.07	<u>0.29</u>	0.03	0.05	0.41	<u>0.31</u>	0.38	0.17	0.24	0.05	1.00

Table 69. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case IV - Job Characteristics Literature Review

	JC1_2	JC2_2	JC3_2	JC4_2	JC5_2	JC1_3	JC2_3	JC3_3	JC4_3	JC5_3	JC6_3	JC7_3	JC8_3	JC9_3	JC10_3	JC11_3	JC12_3	JC13_3	JC14_3	JC15_3	JC16_3	JC17_3	JC18_3	JC19_3	JC20_3	JC21_3	JC22_3	JC23_3	JC24_3	JC25_3	JC26_3	JC27_3	JC28_3	
JC1_2	0.00	0.07	0.10	0.34	<u>0.16</u>	0.00	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.12</u>	0.02	0.27	<u>0.16</u>	0.01	0.08	0.46	<u>0.16</u>	0.82	0.06	0.68	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.16</u>	0.74	0.21	<u>0.16</u>	0.88	0.96	0.33	0.98	0.33	0.87	0.05	0.21	<u>0.12</u>	0.34	
JC2_2	0.07	0.00	0.74	0.50	0.07	0.07	0.74	<u>0.16</u>	0.82	0.74	<u>0.20</u>	0.62	0.02	0.50	0.04	0.01	0.09	0.01	0.04	0.82	0.33	<u>0.20</u>	0.50	0.32	0.22	0.62	0.50	0.70	0.91	0.07	0.26	<u>0.20</u>	0.50	
JC3_2	0.10	0.74	0.00	0.10	0.89	0.39	0.96	0.96	0.37	<u>0.19</u>	0.74	0.23	0.93	0.86	0.02	0.09	<u>0.13</u>	0.49	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.00	0.80	<u>0.14</u>	0.83	0.42	0.63	0.31	0.64	0.44	0.23	0.86	
JC4_2	0.34	0.50	0.10	0.00	0.31	0.64	0.34	0.46	0.27	0.10	0.50	0.24	0.21	0.72	0.72	0.93	0.49	1.00	0.27	0.27	0.50	0.54	0.27	0.00	0.21	0.08	0.02	0.08	0.57	0.34	0.54	0.79	0.01	
JC5_2	<u>0.16</u>	0.07	0.89	0.31	0.00	0.09	0.73	0.73	0.93	0.50	0.95	0.73	0.00	0.31	0.40	<u>0.11</u>	0.94	0.28	0.93	0.93	0.39	<u>0.20</u>	0.40	0.68	0.39	0.73	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.08	0.00	0.31	
JC1_3	0.00	0.07	0.39	0.64	0.09	0.00	0.22	0.22	0.40	0.68	0.33	0.01	0.04	0.31	<u>0.11</u>	0.40	0.09	0.72	0.93	0.40	0.95	0.78	0.40	0.68	0.56	0.73	0.01	0.26	0.66	0.26	0.08	0.01	0.64	
JC2_3	<u>0.12</u>	0.74	0.96	0.34	0.73	0.22	0.00	0.64	0.75	0.88	0.07	0.33	0.44	0.46	0.04	0.29	0.98	0.68	0.60	0.24	0.74	0.30	0.24	0.88	0.44	0.48	0.06	0.90	0.87	0.87	0.92	0.33	0.46	
JC3_3	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.16</u>	0.96	0.46	0.73	0.22	0.64	0.00	0.75	0.27	0.00	0.33	0.10	0.34	0.75	0.82	0.34	0.68	0.24	0.75	0.47	0.92	0.75	0.27	0.44	0.48	0.98	0.48	0.47	0.10	0.30	0.33	0.46	
JC4_3	0.02	0.82	0.37	0.27	0.93	0.40	0.75	0.75	0.00	0.60	0.50	0.42	0.60	0.06	0.06	0.25	0.63	<u>0.15</u>	0.27	0.72	0.26	0.90	0.72	0.60	0.86	0.03	0.77	<u>0.17</u>	0.08	0.08	0.27	0.93	0.72	
JC5_3	0.27	0.74	<u>0.19</u>	0.10	0.50	0.68	0.88	0.27	0.60	0.00	0.32	0.51	0.06	0.60	0.60	0.36	0.31	0.30	0.60	0.10	0.32	0.37	0.10	0.01	0.06	0.69	0.89	0.51	<u>0.16</u>	0.78	0.37	0.51	0.60	
JC6_3	<u>0.16</u>	<u>0.20</u>	0.74	0.50	0.95	0.33	0.07	0.00	0.50	0.32	0.00	0.62	0.03	0.26	0.50	0.87	0.76	0.38	0.50	0.50	0.89	0.94	0.50	0.32	0.03	<u>0.20</u>	0.50	0.70	0.41	0.91	0.01	0.62	0.50	
JC7_3	0.01	0.62	0.23	0.24	0.73	0.01	0.33	0.33	0.42	0.51	0.62	0.00	0.36	0.79	<u>0.12</u>	0.95	0.61	0.73	0.93	<u>0.12</u>	0.62	0.35	<u>0.12</u>	0.08	0.36	0.22	0.79	0.10	0.96	0.43	0.05	0.05	0.79	
JC8_3	0.08	0.02	0.93	0.21	0.00	0.04	0.44	0.10	0.60	0.06	0.03	0.36	0.00	0.10	0.60	0.01	0.96	0.03	0.60	0.86	<u>0.15</u>	0.03	0.86	0.44	0.93	0.23	0.47	0.83	0.64	0.05	0.08	0.00	0.21	
JC9_3	0.46	0.50	0.86	0.72	0.31	0.31	0.46	0.34	0.06	0.60	0.26	0.79	0.10	0.00	0.72	<u>0.13</u>	0.49	<u>0.15</u>	0.72	0.27	0.50	0.54	0.27	0.60	0.86	0.24	0.38	0.24	0.34	0.03	<u>0.18</u>	0.79	0.72	
JC10_3	<u>0.16</u>	0.04	0.02	0.72	0.40	<u>0.11</u>	0.04	0.75	0.06	0.60	0.50	<u>0.12</u>	0.60	0.72	0.00	0.06	0.03	0.48	0.01	0.06	0.26	0.40	0.27	0.10	0.86	0.93	<u>0.20</u>	0.93	0.85	0.85	0.27	0.02	0.72	
JC11_3	0.82	0.01	0.09	0.93	<u>0.11</u>	0.40	0.29	0.82	0.25	0.36	0.87	0.95	0.01	<u>0.13</u>	0.06	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.25	0.25	0.48	<u>0.20</u>	0.25	0.36	0.28	0.53	0.87	0.95	0.61	0.08	0.54	0.95	0.93	
JC12_3	0.06	0.09	<u>0.13</u>	0.49	0.94	0.09	0.98	0.34	0.63	0.31	0.76	0.61	0.96	0.49	0.03	0.09	0.00	0.25	0.03	0.77	0.50	0.67	0.77	0.03	0.96	<u>0.20</u>	0.65	0.79	<u>0.13</u>	0.88	<u>0.14</u>	0.30	0.38	
JC13_3	0.68	0.01	0.49	1.00	0.28	0.72	0.68	0.68	<u>0.15</u>	0.30	0.38	0.73	0.03	<u>0.15</u>	0.48	0.00	0.25	0.00	1.00	1.00	0.38	<u>0.15</u>	0.48	0.30	0.49	0.73	0.71	0.73	0.46	<u>0.14</u>	0.64	0.73	1.00	
JC14_3	<u>0.16</u>	0.04	0.00	0.27	0.93	0.93	0.60	0.24	0.27	0.60	0.50	0.93	0.60	0.72	0.01	0.25	0.03	1.00	0.00	0.06	0.50	0.90	0.27	0.60	0.60	<u>0.17</u>	0.28	<u>0.12</u>	0.85	0.85	0.90	0.42	0.72	
JC15_3	<u>0.16</u>	0.82	0.00	0.27	0.93	0.40	0.24	0.75	0.72	0.10	0.50	<u>0.12</u>	0.86	0.27	0.06	0.25	0.77	1.00	0.06	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.21	0.93	0.77	0.93	0.34	0.57	0.90	<u>0.12</u>	0.72	
JC16_3	0.74	0.33	0.02	0.50	0.39	0.95	0.74	0.47	0.26	0.32	0.89	0.62	<u>0.15</u>	0.50	0.26	0.48	0.50	0.38	0.50	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.32	0.22	0.70	0.76	0.62	0.29	0.41	0.94	0.70	0.26	
JC17_3	0.21	<u>0.20</u>	0.03	0.54	<u>0.20</u>	0.78	0.30	0.92	0.90	0.37	0.94	0.35	0.03	0.54	0.40	<u>0.20</u>	0.67	<u>0.15</u>	0.90	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.37	0.44	0.98	0.67	0.32	0.66	0.57	0.31	0.32	0.54	
JC18_3	<u>0.16</u>	0.50	0.00	0.27	0.40	0.40	0.24	0.75	0.72	0.10	0.50	<u>0.12</u>	0.86	0.27	0.27	0.25	0.77	0.48	0.27	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.04	0.93	0.63	0.42	0.08	0.57	0.90	<u>0.12</u>	0.72	
JC19_3	0.88	0.32	0.80	0.00	0.68	0.68	0.88	0.27	0.60	0.01	0.32	0.08	0.44	0.60	0.10	0.36	0.03	0.30	0.60	0.60	0.32	0.37	0.60	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.63	0.47	0.63	0.31	0.01	0.44	0.83	0.86
JC20_3	0.96	0.22	<u>0.14</u>	0.21	0.39	0.56	0.44	0.44	0.86	0.06	0.03	0.36	0.93	0.86	0.86	0.28	0.96	0.49	0.60	0.21	0.22	0.44	0.04	0.06	0.00	0.63	0.47	0.63	0.31	0.01	0.44	0.83	0.86	
JC21_3	0.33	0.62	0.83	0.08	0.73	0.73	0.48	0.48	0.03	0.69	<u>0.20</u>	0.22	0.23	0.24	0.93	0.53	<u>0.20</u>	0.73	<u>0.17</u>	0.93	0.70	0.98	0.93	0.69	0.63	0.00	0.30	0.84	0.96	<u>0.12</u>	0.98	0.84	0.79	
JC22_3	0.98	0.50	0.42	0.02	0.01	0.94	0.06	0.98	0.77	0.89	0.50	0.79	0.47	0.38	<u>0.20</u>	0.87	0.65	0.71	0.28	0.77	0.76	0.67	0.63	0.31	0.47	0.30	0.00	0.06	0.01	0.33	0.54	0.30	0.02	
JC23_3	0.33	0.70	0.63	0.08	0.01	0.26	0.90	0.48	<u>0.17</u>	0.51	0.70	0.10	0.83	0.24	0.93	0.95	0.79	0.73	<u>0.12</u>	0.93	0.62	0.32	0.42	0.69	0.63	0.84	0.06	0.00	<u>0.14</u>	0.96	0.98	0.22	0.08	
JC24_3	0.87	0.91	0.31	0.57	0.00	0.66	0.87	0.47	0.08	<u>0.16</u>	0.41	0.96	0.64	0.34	0.85	0.61	<u>0.13</u>	0.46	0.85	0.34	0.29	0.66	0.08	0.40	0.31	0.96	0.01	<u>0.14</u>	0.00	0.02	0.66	<u>0.14</u>	0.03	
JC25_3	0.05	0.07	0.64	0.34	0.00	0.26	0.87	0.10	0.08	0.78	0.91	0.43	0.05	0.03	0.85	0.08	<u>0.14</u>	0.85	0.57	0.41	0.57	0.57	0.78	0.01	<u>0.12</u>	0.33	0.96	0.02	0.00	0.66	0.48	0.34		
JC26_3	0.21	0.26	0.44	0.54	0.08	0.08	0.92	0.30	0.27	0.37	0.01	0.05	0.08	<u>0.18</u>	0.27	0.54	<u>0.14</u>	0.64	0.90	0.90	0.94	0.31	0.90	0.37	0.44	0.98	0.54	0.98	0.66	0.66	0.00	0.35	<u>0.18</u>	
JC27_3	<u>0.12</u>	<u>0.20</u>	0.23	0.79	0.00	0.01	0.33	0.33	0.93	0.51	0.62	0.05	0.00	0.79	0.02	0.95	0.30	0.73	0.42	<u>0.12</u>	0.70	0.32	<u>0.12</u>	0.69	0.83	0.84	0.30	0.22	<u>0.14</u>	0.48	0.35	0.00	0.79	
JC28_3	0.34	0.50	0.86	0.01	0.31	0.64	0.46	0.46	0.72	0.60	0.50	0.79	0.21	0.72	0.72	0.93	0.38	1.00	0.72	0.72	0.26	0.54	0.72	0.10	0.86	0.79	0.02	0.08	0.03	0.34	<u>0.18</u>	0.79	0.00	

The Personal Circumstances (PC1_1) includes 4 factor of second level and 20 factors of third level (Table 70)

Table 70. Descriptive statistics for Use Case IV - Personal Circumstances

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
PC_1	Personal Circumstances	0.969	0.177
PC1_2	Caring/Parenting Responsibilities	0.469	0.507
PC2_2	Economic Deprivation	0.625	0.492
PC3_2	Residential Location	0.625	0.492
PC4_2	Access to Transport	0.313	0.471
PC1_3	Supported career/carer breaks	0.313	0.471
PC2_3	Guaranteeing the maintenance of salary levels during maternity leave;	0.344	0.483
PC3_3	Publishing, disseminating and updating a handbook on maternity and parental leave;	0.063	0.246
PC4_3	Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time;	0.188	0.397
PC5_3	Employees with small children to choose whether or not to continue working overtime	0.219	0.420
PC6_3	Where possible, leave periods are reconciled with school holidays.	0.188	0.397
PC7_3	Have access to funds to travel to work;	0.313	0.471
PC8_3	Affordable child/social care;	0.188	0.397
PC9_3	Public transport and flexible and adaptable jobs;	0.156	0.369
PC10_3	Minimum hourly rate for low skilled part time work.	0.375	0.492
PC11_3	Childcare impacts on commuting time (short distances);	0.438	0.504
PC12_3	Fewer job choices;	0.563	0.504
PC13_3	Choice of residence favours partner's job location;	0.188	0.397
PC14_3	Increased commuting time.	0.344	0.483
PC15_3	Availability and cost of public transport;	0.250	0.440
PC16_3	Timetabling of transport (does it suit working hours?);	0.125	0.336
PC17_3	Multiple trips to and from work (e.g. for childcare, shopping etc.);	0.156	0.369
PC18_3	Access to private or shared vehicle.	0.313	0.471

The results (Table 71 and Table 72) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **PC1_2 Caring/Parenting Responsibilities** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - PC1_3 Supported career/carer breaks with V-Cramers= 0.72 and p-value< 0.01;
 - PC2_3 Guaranteeing the maintenance of salary levels during maternity leave with V-Cramers= 0.77 and p-value< 0.01;
 - PC4_3 Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time with V-Cramers= 0.51 and p-value< 0.01;
 - PC5_3 Employees with small children to choose whether or not to continue working overtime with V-Cramers= 0.56 and p-value< 0.01;
 - PC6_3 Where possible, leave periods are reconciled with school holidays with V-Cramers= 0.51 and p-value< 0.01;
- **PC2_2 Economic Deprivation** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - PC7_3 Have access to funds to travel to work with V-Cramers= 0.52 and p-value< 0.01;
 - PC8_3 Affordable child/social care with V-Cramers= 0.37 and p-value=0.04;
 - PC9_3 Public transport and flexible and adaptable jobs with V-Cramers= 0.33 and p-value=0.06;
 - PC10_3 Minimum hourly rate for low skilled part time work with V-Cramers= 0.60 and p-value< 0.01;
 - PC11_3 Childcare impacts on commuting time (short distances) with V-Cramers= 0.36 and p-value< 0.01;
 - PC16_2 Timetabling of transport (does it suit working hours?) with V-Cramers= 0.29 and p-value=0.10;
- **PC3_2 Residential Location** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - PS4_3 Those with small children to be given the opportunity to change shifts or to reduce their working time with V-Cramers= 0.37 and p-value=0.04;
 - PS6_3 Where possible, leave periods are reconciled with school holidays with V-Cramers= 0.37 and p-value=0.04;

- PS11_3 Childcare impacts on commuting time (short distances) with V-Cramers= 0.68 and p-value<0.01;
- PS12_3 Fewer job choices with V-Cramers= 0.88 and p-value<0.01;
- PS13_2 Choice of residence favours partner's job location with V-Cramers= 0.37 and p-value=0.04;
- PS14_2 Increased commuting time with V-Cramers= 0.56 and p-value<0.01;
- **PC4_2 Access to Transport** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - PS7_3 Have access to funds to travel to work with V-Cramers= 0.42 and p-value=0.02;
 - PS15_3 Availability and cost of public transport with V-Cramers= 0.86 and p-value<0.01;
 - PS16_3 Timetabling of transport (does it suit working hours?) with V-Cramers= 0.56 and p-value<0.01;
 - PS17_3 Multiple trips to and from work (e.g. for childcare, shopping etc.) with V-Cramers= 0.64 and p-value<0.01;
 - PS18_3 Access to private or shared vehicle with V-Cramers= 1.00 and p-value<0.01;

Table 71. Cramer's V for Use Case IV - Personal Circumstances Literature Review

PC1_1	PC1_2	PC2_2	PC3_2	PC4_2	PC1_3	PC2_3	PC3_3	PC4_3	PC5_3	PC6_3	PC7_3	PC8_3	PC9_3	PC10_3	PC11_3	PC12_3	PC13_3	PC14_3	PC15_3	PC16_3	PC17_3	PC18_3
PC1_2	1.00	0.05	0.08	0.04	0.72	0.77	0.27	0.51	0.56	0.51	0.04	0.03	0.23	0.05	0.06	0.20	0.19	0.02	0.04	0.17	0.11	0.04
PC2_2	0.05	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	0.24	0.10	0.12	0.20	0.12	0.21	0.04	0.52	0.37	<u>0.33</u>	0.60	<u>0.36</u>	0.16	0.12	0.02	0.15	<u>0.29</u>	0.16	0.24
PC3_2	0.08	<u>0.33</u>	1.00	0.03	0.03	0.29	0.07	0.37	0.06	0.37	0.17	0.04	0.38	0.20	0.68	0.88	0.37	0.56	<0.01	0.10	0.16	0.03
PC4_2	0.04	0.24	0.03	1.00	0.02	0.08	0.10	0.02	0.13	0.15	0.42	0.02	0.10	0.03	0.19	0.05	0.15	0.08	0.86	0.56	0.64	1.00
PC1_3	0.72	0.10	0.03	0.02	1.00	0.51	0.38	0.19	0.13	<u>0.37</u>	0.27	0.19	<u>0.29</u>	0.17	0.19	0.05	0.15	0.20	0.08	0.05	0.08	0.02
PC2_3	0.77	0.12	0.29	0.08	0.51	1.00	0.08	0.50	0.41	0.66	0.06	0.18	0.13	0.02	0.16	0.37	<u>0.33</u>	0.03	0.04	0.07	0.05	0.08
PC3_3	0.27	0.20	0.07	0.10	0.38	0.08	1.00	0.21	0.18	0.21	0.38	0.54	0.11	0.07	0.03	0.03	0.21	0.19	0.15	<u>0.29</u>	0.24	0.10
PC4_3	0.51	0.12	0.37	0.02	0.19	0.50	0.21	1.00	<u>0.33</u>	0.59	0.15	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.38	0.42	0.38	<u>0.33</u>	0.09	0.06	0.23	0.02
PC5_3	0.56	0.21	0.06	0.13	0.13	0.41	0.18	<u>0.33</u>	1.00	0.13	0.03	0.13	0.23	0.06	0.14	0.01	<u>0.33</u>	0.06	0.04	0.03	0.19	0.13
PC6_3	0.51	0.04	0.37	0.15	<u>0.37</u>	0.66	0.21	0.59	0.13	1.00	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.12	0.38	0.42	0.38	0.01	0.09	0.06	0.01	0.15
PC7_3	0.04	0.52	0.17	0.42	0.27	0.06	0.38	0.15	0.03	0.02	1.00	<u>0.37</u>	0.08	0.17	0.19	0.08	0.15	0.06	0.39	<u>0.36</u>	0.45	0.42
PC8_3	0.03	0.37	0.04	0.02	0.19	0.18	0.54	0.03	0.13	0.03	<u>0.37</u>	1.00	0.21	0.12	0.06	0.10	0.03	0.16	0.09	0.06	0.01	0.02
PC9_3	0.23	<u>0.33</u>	0.38	0.10	<u>0.29</u>	0.13	0.11	0.01	0.23	0.01	0.08	0.21	1.00	0.02	0.21	<u>0.31</u>	0.01	0.13	0.05	0.10	0.05	0.10
PC10_3	0.05	0.60	0.20	0.03	0.17	0.02	0.07	0.04	0.06	0.12	0.17	0.12	0.02	1.00	<u>0.29</u>	0.10	0.04	0.15	<0.01	<u>0.29</u>	0.02	0.03
PC11_3	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	0.68	0.19	0.19	0.16	0.03	0.38	0.14	0.38	0.19	0.06	0.21	<u>0.29</u>	1.00	0.52	0.54	<u>0.29</u>	0.22	0.14	0.03	0.19
PC12_3	0.20	0.16	0.88	0.05	0.05	0.37	0.03	0.42	0.01	0.42	0.08	0.10	<u>0.31</u>	0.10	0.52	1.00	0.42	0.64	0.07	0.05	0.21	0.05
PC13_3	0.19	0.12	0.37	0.15	0.15	<u>0.33</u>	0.21	0.38	<u>0.33</u>	0.38	0.15	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.54	0.42	1.00	0.16	0.09	0.06	0.01	0.15
PC14_3	0.02	0.02	0.56	0.08	0.20	0.03	0.19	<u>0.33</u>	0.06	0.01	0.06	0.16	0.13	0.15	<u>0.29</u>	0.64	0.16	1.00	0.04	0.07	0.23	0.08
PC15_3	0.04	0.15	<0.01	0.86	0.08	0.04	0.15	0.09	0.04	0.09	0.39	0.09	0.05	<0.01	0.22	0.07	0.09	0.04	1.00	0.65	0.75	0.86
PC16_3	0.17	<u>0.29</u>	0.10	0.56	0.05	0.07	<u>0.29</u>	0.06	0.03	0.06	<u>0.36</u>	0.06	0.10	<u>0.29</u>	0.14	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.65	1.00	0.62	0.56
PC17_3	0.11	0.16	0.16	0.64	0.08	0.05	0.24	0.23	0.19	0.01	0.45	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.03	0.21	0.01	0.23	0.75	0.62	1.00	0.64
PC18_3	0.04	0.24	0.03	1.00	0.02	0.08	0.10	0.02	0.13	0.15	0.42	0.02	0.10	0.03	0.19	0.05	0.15	0.08	0.86	0.56	0.64	1.00

Table 72. p -value of χ^2 for Use Case IV - Personal Circumstances Literature Review

PC1_1	PC1_2	PC2_2	PC3_2	PC4_2	PC1_3	PC2_3	PC3_3	PC4_3	PC5_3	PC6_3	PC7_3	PC8_3	PC9_3	PC10_3	PC11_3	PC12_3	PC13_3	PC14_3	PC15_3	PC16_3	PC17_3	PC18_3
PC1_2	<0.01	0.79	0.66	0.82	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.13</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.82	0.87	<u>0.20</u>	0.79	0.76	0.28	0.30	0.91	0.84	0.36	0.54	0.82
PC2_2	0.79	<0.01	0.06	<u>0.18</u>	0.57	0.52	0.27	0.50	0.24	0.82	<0.01	0.04	0.06	<0.01	0.04	0.37	0.50	0.93	0.42	0.10	0.40	<u>0.18</u>
PC3_2	0.66	0.06	<0.01	0.85	0.85	<u>0.11</u>	0.72	0.04	0.75	0.04	0.34	0.82	0.03	0.27	<0.01	<0.01	0.04	<0.01	1.00	0.60	0.40	0.85
PC4_2	0.82	<u>0.18</u>	0.85	<0.01	0.92	0.66	0.57	0.91	0.47	0.41	0.02	0.91	0.57	0.85	0.31	0.78	0.41	0.66	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
PC1_3	<0.01	0.57	0.85	0.92	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.29	0.47	0.04	<u>0.13</u>	0.29	<u>0.11</u>	0.34	0.31	0.78	0.41	0.26	0.67	0.78	0.66	0.92
PC2_3	<0.01	0.52	<u>0.11</u>	0.66	<0.01	<0.01	0.64	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.74	0.33	0.48	0.93	0.39	0.04	0.07	0.87	0.84	0.68	0.78	0.66
PC3_3	<u>0.13</u>	0.27	0.72	0.57	0.03	0.64	<0.01	0.26	0.34	0.26	0.03	<0.01	0.54	0.72	0.86	0.86	0.26	0.31	0.42	0.10	<u>0.18</u>	0.57
PC4_3	<0.01	0.50	0.04	0.91	0.29	<0.01	0.26	<0.01	0.07	<0.01	0.41	0.89	0.94	0.82	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.07	0.61	0.74	<u>0.20</u>	0.91
PC5_3	<0.01	0.24	0.75	0.47	0.47	0.02	0.34	0.07	<0.01	0.47	0.87	0.47	0.21	0.75	0.44	0.96	0.07	0.73	0.81	0.88	0.30	0.47
PC6_3	<0.01	0.82	0.04	0.41	0.04	<0.01	0.26	<0.01	0.47	<0.01	0.91	0.89	0.94	0.50	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.95	0.61	0.74	0.94	0.41
PC7_3	0.82	<0.01	0.34	0.02	<u>0.13</u>	0.74	0.03	0.41	0.87	0.91	<0.01	0.04	0.66	0.34	0.31	0.64	0.41	0.74	0.03	0.05	0.01	0.02
PC8_3	0.87	0.04	0.82	0.91	0.29	0.33	<0.01	0.89	0.47	0.89	0.04	<0.01	0.26	0.50	0.74	0.58	0.89	0.39	0.61	0.74	0.94	0.91
PC9_3	<u>0.20</u>	0.06	0.03	0.57	<u>0.11</u>	0.48	0.54	0.94	0.21	0.94	0.66	0.26	<0.01	0.90	0.26	0.08	0.94	0.48	0.79	0.60	0.78	0.57
PC10_3	0.79	<0.01	0.27	0.85	0.34	0.93	0.72	0.82	0.75	0.50	0.34	0.50	0.90	<0.01	0.10	0.60	0.82	0.40	1.00	0.10	0.90	0.85
PC11_3	0.76	0.04	<0.01	0.31	0.31	0.39	0.86	0.03	0.44	0.03	0.31	0.74	0.26	0.10	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<u>0.11</u>	0.23	0.44	0.86	0.31
PC12_3	0.28	0.37	<0.01	0.78	0.78	0.04	0.86	0.02	0.96	0.02	0.64	0.58	0.08	0.60	<0.01	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.69	0.80	0.26	0.78
PC13_3	0.30	0.50	0.04	0.41	0.41	0.07	0.26	0.03	0.07	0.03	0.41	0.89	0.94	0.82	<0.01	0.02	<0.01	0.39	0.61	0.74	0.94	0.41
PC14_3	0.91	0.93	<0.01	0.66	0.26	0.87	0.31	0.07	0.73	0.95	0.74	0.39	0.48	0.40	<u>0.11</u>	<0.01	0.39	<0.01	0.84	0.68	<u>0.20</u>	0.66
PC15_3	0.84	0.42	1.00	<0.01	0.67	0.84	0.42	0.61	0.81	0.61	0.03	0.61	0.79	1.00	0.23	0.69	0.61	0.84	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
PC16_3	0.36	0.10	0.60	<0.01	0.78	0.68	0.10	0.74	0.88	0.74	0.05	0.74	0.60	0.10	0.44	0.80	0.74	0.68	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
PC17_3	0.54	0.40	0.40	<0.01	0.66	0.78	<u>0.18</u>	<u>0.20</u>	0.30	0.94	0.01	0.94	0.78	0.90	0.86	0.26	0.94	<u>0.20</u>	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
PC18_3	0.82	<u>0.18</u>	0.85	<0.01	0.92	0.66	0.57	0.91	0.47	0.41	0.02	0.91	0.57	0.85	0.31	0.78	0.41	0.66	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01

The Individual Characteristics (IC1_1) includes 3 factor of second level and 12 factors of third level (Table 73)

Table 73. Descriptive statistics for Use Case IV - Individual Characteristics

Code	Variable	Mean	Std. deviation
IC1_1	Individual Characteristics	1.000	0.000
IC1_2	Skills	0.969	0.177
IC2_2	Adaptability	0.594	0.499
IC3_2	Educational Attainment	0.656	0.483
IC1_3	Strategic skills development framework	0.563	0.504
IC2_3	Robust training policies and systems	0.750	0.440
IC3_3	Build solid bridges between the world of work and training providers in order to match skills provision to the needs of enterprises	0.594	0.499
IC4_3	Continuous workplace training and lifelong learning	0.531	0.507
IC5_3	Anticipating and building competencies for future needs	0.813	0.397
IC6_3	Ensuring broad access to training opportunities	0.625	0.492
IC7_3	Extended hours make it difficult and at times impossible to reconcile work and family commitments;	0.594	0.499
IC8_3	Child care arrangements (nursery/school hours).	0.406	0.499
IC9_3	Good-quality basic education for all is an essential prerequisite for further skills development	0.156	0.369
IC10_3	Links between organisations, schools and colleges to ensure education and training is suited to the demands of the work place - anchor the world of learning in the world of work;	0.375	0.492
IC11_3	Lifelong learning - enabling women and men of all ages to fulfil their aspirations	0.156	0.369
IC12_3	working with vocational institutions to encourage female participation in relevant courses	0.438	0.504

The results (Table 74 and Table 75) have been highlighted the following associations between the second and third level factors:

- **IC1_2 Skills** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - IC2_3 Robust training policies and systems with V-Cramers= 0.31 and p-value=0.08
 - IC5_3 Anticipating and building competencies for future needs with V-Cramers= 0.37 and p-value=0.035
 - IC6_3 Ensuring broad access to training opportunities, for women and men, and particularly for those groups facing greater difficulties, in particular youth, lower skilled workers, workers with disabilities, rural communities with V-Cramers= 0.24 and p-value=0.20
- **IC2_2 Adaptability** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - IC6_3 Ensuring broad access to training opportunities, for women and men, and particularly for those groups facing greater difficulties, in particular youth, lower skilled workers, workers with disabilities, rural communities with V-Cramers= 0.41 and p-value=0.02;
 - IC7_3 Extended hours, variable start/ finish times, shift-work, and 24/7 operations sometimes for 365 days a year) make it difficult and at times impossible to reconcile work and family commitments with V-Cramers= 1.00 and p-value<0.01;
 - IC8_3 Child care arrangements with V-Cramers= 0.68 and p-value<0.01;
- **IC3_2 Educational Attainment** has a strong connection with the following third level factors:
 - IC10_3 Links between organisations, schools and colleges to ensure education and training is suited to the demands of the work place with V-Cramers= 0.56 and p-value<0.01;
 - IC11_3 Lifelong learning - enabling women and men of all ages to fulfil their aspirations with V-Cramers= 0.31 and p-value=0.08;
 - IC12_3 working with vocational institutions to encourage female participation in relevant courses with V-Cramers= 0.63 and p-value<0.01.

Table 74. Cramer's V for Use Case IV - Individual Characteristics Literature Review

IC1_1	IC1_2	IC2_2	IC3_2	IC1_3	IC2_3	IC3_3	IC4_3	IC5_3	IC6_3	IC7_3	IC8_3	IC9_3	IC10_3	IC11_3	IC12_3
IC1_2	1.00	0.22	0.13	0.20	<u>0.31</u>	0.22	0.19	0.37	0.23	0.22	0.15	0.08	0.23	0.08	0.20
IC2_2	0.22	1.00	0.07	0.09	0.11	0.04	0.01	0.25	0.41	1.00	0.68	0.18	0.02	0.17	0.04
IC3_2	0.13	0.07	1.00	0.11	0.19	<u>0.33</u>	0.11	0.01	0.02	0.07	0.06	<u>0.31</u>	0.56	<u>0.31</u>	0.64
IC1_3	0.20	0.09	0.11	1.00	0.07	0.04	<u>0.31</u>	0.06	0.10	0.09	0.17	0.03	0.16	0.03	0.02
IC2_3	<u>0.31</u>	0.11	0.19	0.07	1.00	0.26	0.18	0.09	<0.01	0.11	0.18	0.05	<0.01	0.25	0.22
IC3_3	0.22	0.04	<u>0.33</u>	0.04	0.26	1.00	0.14	0.42	0.15	0.04	0.09	0.17	0.28	0.01	0.04
IC4_3	0.19	0.01	0.11	<u>0.31</u>	0.18	0.14	1.00	0.13	0.05	0.01	0.01	0.11	0.21	0.23	0.06
IC5_3	0.37	0.25	0.01	0.06	0.09	0.42	0.13	1.00	0.29	0.25	0.07	0.01	0.29	0.21	0.06
IC6_3	0.23	0.41	0.02	0.10	<0.01	0.15	0.05	0.29	1.00	0.41	0.38	0.02	0.07	0.16	0.10
IC7_3	0.22	1.00	0.07	0.09	0.11	0.04	0.01	0.25	0.41	1.00	0.68	0.18	0.02	0.17	0.04
IC8_3	0.15	0.68	0.06	0.17	0.18	0.09	0.01	0.07	0.38	0.68	1.00	0.18	0.02	0.01	0.04
IC9_3	0.08	0.18	<u>0.31</u>	0.03	0.05	0.17	0.11	0.01	0.02	0.18	0.18	1.00	0.20	0.19	0.03
IC10_3	0.23	0.02	0.56	0.16	<0.01	0.28	0.21	0.29	0.07	0.02	0.02	0.20	1.00	0.02	0.49
IC11_3	0.08	0.17	<u>0.31</u>	0.03	0.25	0.01	0.23	0.21	0.16	0.17	0.01	0.19	0.02	1.00	0.03
IC12_3	0.20	0.04	0.64	0.02	0.22	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.10	0.04	0.04	0.03	0.49	0.03	1.00

Table 75. p-value of χ^2 for Use Case IV - Individual Characteristics Literature Review

IC1_1	IC1_2	IC2_2	IC3_2	IC1_3	IC2_3	IC3_3	IC4_3	IC5_3	IC6_3	IC7_3	IC8_3	IC9_3	IC10_3	IC11_3	IC12_3
IC1_2	<0.01	0.23	0.48	0.26	0.08	0.23	0.29	0.04	<u>0.20</u>	0.23	0.42	0.67	<u>0.20</u>	0.67	0.26
IC2_2	0.23	<0.01	0.70	0.63	0.55	0.84	0.95	<u>0.16</u>	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	0.32	0.93	0.35	0.83
IC3_2	0.48	0.70	<0.01	0.56	0.30	0.06	0.54	0.95	0.93	0.70	0.73	0.08	<0.01	0.08	<0.01
IC1_3	0.26	0.63	0.56	<0.01	0.69	0.83	0.09	0.74	0.60	0.63	0.36	0.86	0.37	0.86	0.93
IC2_3	0.08	0.55	0.30	0.69	<0.01	<u>0.16</u>	0.32	0.61	1.00	0.55	0.31	0.79	1.00	<u>0.17</u>	0.23
IC3_3	0.23	0.84	0.06	0.83	<u>0.16</u>	<0.01	0.45	0.02	0.42	0.84	0.61	0.35	<u>0.12</u>	0.98	0.83
IC4_3	0.29	0.95	0.54	0.09	0.32	0.45	<0.01	0.48	0.79	0.95	0.95	0.54	0.25	<u>0.20</u>	0.76
IC5_3	0.04	<u>0.16</u>	0.95	0.74	0.61	0.02	0.48	<0.01	<u>0.11</u>	<u>0.16</u>	0.70	0.94	<u>0.11</u>	0.26	0.74
IC6_3	<u>0.20</u>	0.02	0.93	0.60	1.00	0.42	0.79	<u>0.11</u>	<0.01	0.02	0.03	0.90	0.72	0.40	0.60
IC7_3	0.23	<0.01	0.70	0.63	0.55	0.84	0.95	<u>0.16</u>	0.02	<0.01	<0.01	0.32	0.93	0.35	0.83
IC8_3	0.42	<0.01	0.73	0.36	0.31	0.61	0.95	0.70	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	0.32	0.93	0.98	0.83
IC9_3	0.67	0.32	0.08	0.86	0.79	0.35	0.54	0.94	0.90	0.32	0.32	<0.01	0.27	0.31	0.86
IC10_3	<u>0.20</u>	0.93	<0.01	0.37	1.00	<u>0.12</u>	0.25	<u>0.11</u>	0.72	0.93	0.93	0.27	<0.01	0.90	<0.01
IC11_3	0.67	0.35	0.08	0.86	<u>0.17</u>	0.98	<u>0.20</u>	0.26	0.40	0.35	0.98	0.31	0.90	<0.01	0.86
IC12_3	0.26	0.83	<0.01	0.93	0.23	0.83	0.76	0.74	0.60	0.83	0.83	0.86	<0.01	0.86	<0.01

Annex 7 – DAD Survey questionnaires Validation

The validation of the questionnaires was divided into two phases. In the first phase, the validity of the questionnaire was analysed. In the second phase, the reliability of the questionnaire was analysed.

In the first phase, the validity of the questionnaires was assessed by verifying that the questions reflect the following characteristics (Garcia et al., 2009):

- Simplicity, viability, and patient, user and researcher acceptance (feasibility).
- Reliability and precision, in other words, mistake free measurements.
- Adequacy for the problem intended for measure (content validity).
- Reflection underlying theory in the phenomenon or concept to be measured (construct validity).
- Capable of measuring change, both in different individuals as in the response of the same individual through time (sensitivity to change).

Since the questions are asked with clarity and coherence and reflect the above characteristics, the four questionnaires are validated. In detail, it is possible to observe that:

- The questions are structured in two parts, for each questionnaire: the first part is composed of an explanation of the problem, in the second part there are three alternatives of answers A, B and C (Of equal importance). The first part is repeated for all the questions in the questionnaire, which makes the questionnaire very intuitive and easy to answer, reflecting the characteristics of **simplicity and viability**.
- Three possible answers are explained in detail for each question; therefore, the simplicity of these answers reduces the possibility of making mistakes in measuring the questions, ensuring **reliability and precision**.
- Each questionnaire is made up of sub-questions, this scheme allows explaining the meaning of each question, ensuring **adequacy for the problem intended for measure** and **a reflection underlying theory in the phenomenon or concept to be measured**.
- The possible answers are repeated in more questions, changing the combinations of these answers allows **for measuring change, both in different individuals as in the response to the same individual through time**.

In the second phase, the reliability was assessed. Reliability is the degree with which an instrument accurately measures something free of error. Reliability measures the proportion in the variation of measurements that is due to the diversity of values that the variable adopts and that are not a product of error; in other words, reliability measures the proportion of the total variance owed to true differences between the subjects (García et al., 2009).

The answers of these questionnaires are represented by three possible alternatives of equal importance: A, B, and C. To measure the proportion of the total variance owed to true differences between the subjects, the Catanova test was used, according to the methodology developed by Light & Margolin (1971, 1974). They introduced an analysis of variance for categorical data based on the decomposition the total sum of squares (TSS) into total within-group Variation (or Within-group Sum of Squares - WSS) and between-group variation (or Between sum of squares - BSS) in a one-way categorical ANOVA, known as CATANOVA (CATegorical ANalysis of VAriance) to emphasize the categorical nature of the data..

Denote n_{ij} as counts of the i – th category in the j – th group ($i = 1, \dots, I$ and $j = 1, \dots, G$). The group marginal $n_{+j} = \sum_{i=1}^I n_{ij}$ is the sample size of group j ; the category marginal $n_{+i} = \sum_{j=1}^G n_{ij}$ is the count of the i – th category in the full data; and the total sample size is $N = \sum_{i=1}^I n_{i+} = \sum_{j=1}^G n_{+j} = \sum_{j=1}^G \sum_{i=1}^I n_{ij}$. The (TSS) is given by:

$$TSS = \frac{N}{2} - \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^I n_{i+}^2$$

For the j – th group, the $SS(j)$ is given by:

$$SS(j) = \frac{n_{+j}}{2} - \frac{1}{2n_{+j}} \sum_{i=1}^I n_{ij}^2$$

summing $SS(j)$ over all j – yields the WSS,

$$WSS = \sum_{j=1}^G \left(\frac{n_{+j}}{2} - \frac{1}{2n_{+j}} \sum_{i=1}^I n_{ij}^2 \right) = \frac{N}{2} - \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^G \sum_{i=1}^I \frac{n_{ij}^2}{n_{+j}}$$

and defining $TSS = BSS + WSS$ leads:

$$BSS = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=1}^G \sum_{i=1}^I \frac{n_{ij}^2}{n_{+j}} - \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^I n_{i+}^2$$

Light and Margolin further proposed BSS/TSS as the categorical analogue of the ANOVA R^2 , through an alternative test statistic, CATANOVA (C) given by:

$$C = (N - 1)(I - 1) \frac{BSS}{TSS} = (N - 1)(I - 1)R^2$$

The approximate distribution of C is χ^2 with $[(\text{number of groups} - 1) \times (\text{number of attributes} - 1)]$ degrees of freedom (dF) (Figure 50), from which it is possible to calculate the p-value, equal to the area subtended by the curve at that point (Figure 51).

Figure 50. χ^2 distribution for different degrees of freedom (dF)

Figure 51 Example of p-value for χ^2 with dF = 3

In this analysis, the CATANOVA C-Statistic is used to test the null hypothesis that the proportions of each category in all groups are equal. The decision to reject or fail to reject the null hypothesis is determined by the p-value associated at the C-Statistic value. If the p-value is smaller than the level of significance $\alpha = 0.05$ the null hypothesis is rejected, showing that the answers are associated with the questions, showing that there is consistency in the administration of the questions. Furthermore, Margolin and Light (1974) found that in small samples the null distribution of Catanova statistic is better

approximated by a chi-square distribution than is the null distribution of chi-square statistic, being able to use this methodology also for a study pilot having a small number of observations.

Being this pilot study, it was decided to administer the questionnaires to 30 women, referring to a clear statistic rule. To confirm that sample size was appropriate, the power analysis was carried out. Statistical power in a hypothesis test is the probability that the test will detect an effect that exists. The power of a statistical test is the probability that the test will reject a false null hypothesis (i.e. that it will not make a type II error). Given the null hypothesis H_0 and an alternative hypothesis H_1 , we can define power in the following way. First, the type I error is the probability to incorrectly reject the null hypothesis. In this study, the power analysis procedure for one-way ANOVA with count data introduced by Mai and Zhang (2017) was carried out, (using the following link <https://webpower.psychstat.org/models/means07/>).

The result of the analysis (Figure 52) showed that with a sample of 30 subjects and imposing an alpha of 0.05 with a size effect of 0.75 the power of the analysis is equal to 0.95. Thus, the number of subjects is appropriate to the analysis.

Parameters (Help)	
Number of groups	3
Sample size	30
Effect size (Calculator)	0.75
Significance level	0.05
Power	
Type of analysis	Overall ▾
Power curve	Show power curve ▾
Note	Count ANOVA

Output

One-way Analogous ANOVA with Count Data

k	n	V	alpha	power
3	30	0.75	0.05	0.9998

NOTE: n is the total sample size
 URL: <http://psychstat.org/anovacount>

Figure 52 one-way ANOVA with count

Catanova C-statistic test was calculated only globally, because some use case questionnaire are composed by one only question. In this case, it was not possible to evaluate the variation of measurements. The correlation analysis shows that for all four questionnaires the p-value associated at C-Statistic is smaller 0.05, demonstrating that there is consistency in the administration of the questions (Table 76).

Table 76. Results of CATANOVA test.

	TSS	BSS	N	I	C-Test	dF	p-value
Use Case I	126.46	11.69	390	3	71.93	24	0.09
Use Case II	398.58	52.38	1200	3	315.15	24	2.96E-30
Use Case III	393.54	27.47	1200	3	167.39	24	1.79E-08
Use Case IV	318.08	28.03	960	3	169.05	24	7.31E-12

The summary statistics of the pilot study are reported in Table 77,

Table 77. Summary statistic: UC-I - PUBLIC TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE. RAILWAYS SURVEY

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	A	B	Of equal importance	Total
A: 1.1. Service availability and efficiency - B: 1.2. Information provision	17	8	5	30
A: 1.1. Service availability and efficiency B: 1.3. Ticketing options and fares	18	8	4	30
A: 1.1. Service availability and efficiency B: 1.4. Travel purpose	17	6	7	30
A: 1.2. Information provision B: 1.3. Ticketing options and fares	14	8	8	30
A: 1.2. Information provision B: 1.4. Travel purpose	14	8	8	30
A: 1.3. Ticketing options and fares B: 1.4. Travel purpose	10	8	12	30
A: 2.1. Universal design B: 2.2. Cleanliness and maintenance	8	18	4	30
A: 2.1. Universal design B: 2.3. Furniture and facilities	7	18	5	30
A: 2.2. Cleanliness and maintenance B: 2.3. Furniture and facilities	6	19	5	30
A: 3.1. Harassment and pickpocketing B: 3.2. Overcrowding and emergency situations	16	8	6	30
A: 1. Accessibility of the service B: 2. Design of the infrastructure	17	6	7	30
A: 1. Accessibility of the service B: 3. Safety and security	14	13	3	30
A: 2. Design of the infrastructure B: 3. Safety and security	7	6	17	30
Total	165	134	91	390

Table 78. Summary statistic: UC-II - AUTONOMOUS VEHICLES SURVEY

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	A	B	Of equal importance	Total
A: 1.1. Accident rate - b: 1.2. Human errors	12	15	3	30
A: 1.1. Accident rate - b: 1.3. Training	21	5	4	30
A: 1.1. Accident rate - b: 1.4. Traffic management	18	10	2	30
A: 1.2. Human errors - b: 1.3. Training	15	3	12	30
A: 1.2. Human errors - b: 1.4. Traffic management	16	2	12	30
A: 1.3. Training - b: 1.4. Traffic management	17	1	12	30
A: 2.1. Trust in technology - b: 2.2. Simultaneity	6	6	18	30
A: 3.1. Traffic efficiency - b: 3.2. Travel time	8	19	3	30
A: 3.1. Traffic efficiency - b: 3.3. Congestion	6	16	8	30
A: 3.1. Traffic efficiency - b: 3.4. Accessibility	6	16	8	30
A: 3.2. Travel time - b: 3.3. Congestion	18	9	3	30
A: 3.2. Travel time - b: 3.4. Accessibility	7	5	18	30
A: 3.3. Congestion - b: 3.4. Accessibility	7	5	18	30
A: 4.1. Monetary costs - b: 4.2. Non-monetary savings	12	15	3	30
A: 4.1. Monetary costs - b: 4.3. Vehicle efficiency	11	16	3	30
A: 4.2. Non-monetary savings - b: 4.3. Vehicle efficiency	3	11	16	30
A: 5.1. Noise - b:5.2. Emissions	2	11	17	30
A: 5.1. Noise - b: 5.3. Public health	2	10	18	30
A: 5.2. Emissions -- b: 5.3. Public health	2	6	22	30
A: 6.1. Infrastructure adaptation - b: 6.2. Vehicle shape	14	13	3	30
A: 6.1. Infrastructure adaptation - b: 6.3. Vehicle behaviour	14	14	2	30
A: 6.1. Infrastructure adaptation - b: 6.4. Human machine interface	14	12	4	30
A: 6.2. Vehicle shape - b: 6.3. Vehicle behaviour	7	4	19	30
A: 6.3. Vehicle behaviour - b: 6.4. Human machine interface	9	4	17	30
A: 6.2. Vehicle shape - b: 6.4. Human machine interface	12	4	14	30
A: 1. Safety and security - b: 2. Comfort	12	10	8	30
A: 1. Safety and security - b: 3. Mobility	18	8	4	30
A: 1. Safety and security - b: 4. Economy	15	11	4	30
A: 1. Safety and security - b: 5. Environment	6	6	18	30
A: 1. Safety and security - b: 6. Design options	17	4	9	30
A: 2. Comfort - b: 3. Mobility	9	7	14	30
A: 2. Comfort - b: 4. Economy	8	10	12	30
A: 2. Comfort - b: 5. Environment	17	5	8	30
A: 2. Comfort - b: 6. Design options	7	9	14	30
A: 3. Mobility - b: 4. Economy	9	13	8	30
A: 3. Mobility - b: 5. Environment	17	6	7	30
A: 3. Mobility - b: 6. Design option	12	9	9	30
A: 4. Economy - b: 5. Environment	14	9	7	30
A: 4. Economy - b: 6. Design options	8	8	14	30
A: 5. Environment - b: 6. Design options	8	8	14	30
Total	436	355	409	1200

Table 79. Summary statistic: UC-III - VEHICLE (BIKE) SHARING SURVEY

Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view?	A	B	Of equal importance	Total
A: 1.1. Public awareness B: 1.2. Sign-up and booking process	18	6	6	30
A: 1.1. Public awareness B: 1.3. Membership cost	14	12	4	30
A: 1.1. Public awareness B: 1.4. Spontaneity of accessing bike or dock	14	11	5	30
A: 1.1. Public awareness B: 1.5. Proximity of docking station	13	8	9	30
A: 1.1. Public awareness B: 1.6. Traveling with children or carrying things	12	8	10	30
A: 1.1. Public awareness B: 1.7. Insufficient infrastructure	3	15	12	30
A: 1.2. Sign-up and booking process B: 1.3. Membership cost	6	18	6	30
A: 1.2. Sign-up and booking process B: 1.4. Spontaneity of accessing bike or dock	4	18	8	30
A: 1.2. Sign-up and booking process B: 1.5. Proximity of docking station	4	20	6	30
A: 1.2. Sign-up and booking process B: 1.6. Traveling with children or carrying things	4	17	9	30
A: 1.2. Sign-up and booking process B: 1.7. Insufficient infrastructure	4	10	16	30
A: 1.3. Membership cost B: 1.4. Spontaneity of accessing bike or dock	12	11	7	30
A: 1.3. Membership cost B: 1.5. Proximity of docking station	12	11	7	30
A: 1.3. Membership cost B: 1.6. Traveling with children or carrying things	10	16	4	30
A: 1.3. Membership cost B: 1.7. Insufficient infrastructure	10	15	5	30
A: 1.4. Spontaneity of accessing bike or dock B: 1.5. Proximity of docking station	12	14	4	30
A: 1.4. Spontaneity of accessing bike or dock B: 1.6. Traveling with children or carrying things	12	14	4	30
A: 1.4. Spontaneity of accessing bike or dock B: 1.7. Insufficient infrastructure	12	15	3	30
A: 1.5. Proximity of docking station - B: 1.6. Traveling with children or carrying things	13	12	5	30
A: 1.5. Proximity of docking station - B: 1.7. Insufficient infrastructure	12	13	5	30
A: 1.6. Traveling with children or carrying things B: 1.7. Insufficient infrastructure	10	16	4	30
A: 2.1. Driver behaviour B: 2.2. Separate infrastructure	6	18	6	30
A: 2.1. Driver behaviour B: 2.3. Confidence and experience	13	11	6	30
A: 2.1. Driver behaviour B: 2.4. Harassment	10	6	14	30
A: 2.1. Driver behaviour B: 2.5. Safe environment and personal safety	10	14	6	30
Which of these characteristics is more important from your point of view? A: 2.1. DRIVER BEHAVIOUR - B: 2.6. TRAFFIC SAFETY	10	13	7	30
A: 2.2. Separate infrastructure - B: 2.3. Confidence and experience	14	8	8	30
A: 2.2. Separate infrastructure B: 2.4. Harassment	14	11	5	30
A: 2.2. Separate infrastructure B: 2.5. Safe environment and personal safety	4	11	15	30
A: 2.2. Separate infrastructure B: 2.6. Traffic safety	12	14	4	30
A: 2.3. Confidence and experience - B: 2.4. Harassment	7	10	13	30
A: 2.3. Confidence and experience - B: 2.5. Safe environment and personal safety -	7	15	8	30
A: 2.3. Confidence and experience B: 2.6. Traffic safety	6	9	15	30
A: 2.4. Harassment - B: 2.5. Safe environment and personal safety	12	6	12	30
A: 2.4. Harassment - B: 2.6. Traffic safety	12	8	10	30
A: 2.5. Safe environment and personal safety - B: 2.6. Traffic safety	12	8	10	30
A: 3.1. Peer influence B: 3.2. Negative perceptions (socio-cultural constraints)	12	13	5	30
A: 3.1. Peer influence (subjective norm) B: 3.3. Family responsibilities	9	14	7	30
A: 3.2. Negative perceptions (socio-cultural constraints) B: 3.3. Family responsibilities	8	16	6	30
A: 4.1. Weather B: 4.2. Topography	7	5	18	30
Total	396	490	314	1200

Table 80. Summary statistic: UC-IV - WOMEN RECRUITMENT IN RAILWAYS AND FREIGHT/CSR PROTOCOLS SURVEY

Question	A	B	Of equal importance	Total
Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view for fairness of conditions?				
A: 1.1. Job segregation B: 1.2. Policy and legal	9	12	9	30
A: 1.1. Job segregation B: 1.3. Demand factors	10	8	12	30
A: 1.2. Policy and legal B: 1.3. Demand factors	12	9	9	30
Which of these job characteristics is more important from your point of view?				
A: 2.1. Terms and conditions B: 2.2. Hr policies	14	10	6	30
A: 2.1. Terms and conditions B: 2.3. Female facilities	13	12	5	30
A: 2.1. Terms and conditions B: 2.4. Safety and security	12	9	9	30
A: 2.1. Terms and conditions B: 2.5. Training provision	11	10	9	30
A: 2.2. Hr policies B: 2.4. Safety and security	7	14	9	30
A: 2.2. Hr policies B: 2.5. Training provision	7	11	12	30
A: 2.2. Hr policies B: 2.3. Female facilities	8	15	7	30
B: 2.3. Female facilities B: 2.4. Safety and security	9	15	6	30
B: 2.3. Female facilities B: 2.4. Safety and security	15	9	6	30
B: 2.4. Safety and security B: 2.5. Training provision	13	8	9	30
Which of these personal characteristics is more important from your point of view?				
A: 3.1. Caring and parenting responsibilities B: 3.2. Economic deprivation	17	0	6	30
A: 3.1. Caring and parenting responsibilities– B: 3.3. Access to resources	13	9	8	30
A: 3.2. Economic deprivation B: 3.3. Access to resources		21	9	30
A: 4.1. Health status and wellbeing B: 4.2. Adaptability	13	11	6	30
4.1. Health status and wellbeing B: 4.3. Demographic	15	10	5	30
4.1. Health status and wellbeing B: 4.4. Skills	14	7	9	30
4.1. Health status and wellbeing B: 4.5. Educational level and attainment	13	8	9	30
A: 4.2. Adaptability B: 4.3. Demographic	11	14	5	30
A: 4.2. Adaptability- B: 4.4. Skills	4	17	9	30
A: 4.2. Adaptability B: 4.5. Educational level and attainment	4	9	17	30
A: 4.3. Demographic B: 4.4. Skills	3	24	3	30
A: 4.3. Demographic B: 4.5. Educational level and attainment	12	12	6	30
A: 4.4. Skills B: 4.5. Educational level and attainment	24	3	3	30
Which of these characteristics in your point of view affects more an employee's needs for fairness?				
A: 1. Socio-economic conditions B: 2. Job characteristics	3	18	9	30
A: 1. Socio-economic conditions B: 3. Personal circumstances	12	14	4	30
A: 1. Socio-economic conditions B: 4. Individual characteristics	12	9	9	30
A: 2. Job B: 3. Personal circumstances characteristics:	18	8	4	30
A: 2. Job characteristics B: 4. Individual characteristics	13	11	6	30
A: 3. Personal circumstances B: 4. Individual characteristics	13	8	9	30
Total	354	355	244	960

